

D1.18 Summary Progress Report Year 5

WP1 Coordination

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GENERAL INFORMATION

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1 Glossary

AH: Animal Health
ASM: Annual Scientific Meeting
AWP: Annual Work Plan
CaM: Communication workshop and Media training
CPD: Continuing Professional Development
CT: Coordination Team
ESAB: External Scientific Advisory Board
FS: Food Safety
JIP: Joint Integrative Projects
JRP: Joint Research Project
MS: Member State
OHEJP: One Health European Joint Programme
PH: Public Health
PMC: Programme Managers Committee
PMT: Project Management Team
POC: Programme Owners Committee
REA: Research Executive Agency
SPR: Summary Progress Report
SS: Summer School
SSB: Scientific Steering Board
ST: Support Team
STM: Short Term Mission
WS: Workshop

2 Publishable summary

2.1 Summary of the context and overall objectives of the project

2.1.1 What is the problem/issue being addressed?

The One Health EJP is a policy driven research network addressing issues related to needs identified in the food safety area.

- Need to strengthen the links between human health, animal health and environmental aspects: One Health approach
- Need to further integrate surveillance and response capacities, preventive approaches, detection systems as well as preparedness and response to disease outbreaks
- Need of collaboration in Joint Research and Joint Integrative Projects, as well as Training and Education activities throughout a consortium of national public mission organisations
- Need to foster interaction between European, national authorities and stakeholders
- Need to update policy makers on these achievements and, built on this knowledge, to take appropriate action

2.1.2 Why is it important for society?

The integrated health approach, known as 'One Health', is based on strengthening collaboration between human health, animal health and environmental management. It focuses on developing surveillance and response capacities, strengthening early-warning and detection systems; reinforcing the capacities of working together of public health and veterinary authorities as regards prevention, preparedness and response to disease outbreaks of infectious diseases; evaluating the social and economic impact of diseases; promoting inter-sector collaboration for public health and animal health; research on the conditions under which infectious diseases emerge and spread. Thus coordination between the different health systems, which are generally run separately, must enable economies of scale by encouraging synergies, and guarantee improved health security. Particular attention is paid to the communication of risks at all levels of action.

2.1.3 What are the overall objectives?

The overall objective of the One Health EJP is to develop a European network of research institutes, mainly with reference laboratory functions. The One Health EJP integrates public health, medical, veterinary and food scientists in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats in order to improve the prevention and control in the three domains, whilst taking into account the public health concerns of consumers and other stakeholders throughout the food chain.

Therefore, the following objectives are undertaken through the commitment of a highly interactive and experienced administrative framework encompassing scientific direction, financial management and communication of the respective beneficiaries and of the coordination team.

- 1. To bring together the major representatives of the European scientific communities in the field of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats dealing with national mandates of reference and performing official research programmes in these three domains.**

After the enlargement process in 2020 that successfully added six new beneficiaries to the One Health EJP consortium, no further requests to join the EJP were received. The EJP consortium is now brought to 44 members from 22 countries out of which 20 EU Member States and 2 non-EU countries, namely Norway and the UK. Three new EU Member States are now involved: Finland, Latvia and Lithuania.

- 2. To implement scientific integrative collaborative projects related to the prevention and control of foodborne zoonoses.**

The joint integrative projects are the core activity of the One Health EJP since they bring together One Health experts from all over Europe to propose improved surveillance programmes in all sectors (public health, animal health and food safety), to support the harmonization and validation of laboratory procedures, to propose better risk analysis, to share data and to set up alert tools, and to propose innovative intervention methodologies. Three JIP of the 2nd round continue their activity by the end of 2022, while the additional integrative project – JIP COVRIN to harmonize detection and characterization procedures of SRS-CoV-2 and to perform risk assessment will be active until March 2023.

- 3. To stimulate scientific excellence by co-funding dedicated Joint Research Projects, that will have the potential to enhance the scientific evidence base useful in the preparation of tools for surveillance and reference activities at the national and European levels in the field of foodborne zoonosis, AMR and emerging threats.**

Although the JRP are classic research projects with the aim to increase knowledge in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, AMR and emerging threats, these collaborations also add to

key components of the prevent-detect-response cycle. For instance, suggestions to improve surveillance programmes, laboratory procedures that can be taken up by other laboratories in other sectors, databases or repositories are developed in these JRP and support the preparedness of the collaborating partners. In 2021, the last five JRP of the first round have been finalized, thus leaving the 13 JRP of the second that are ongoing.

4. To foster the harmonization and standardization of the reference methods and tests by bringing together scientific and technical expertise in the field of foodborne zoonoses, delivering standards and materials of reference such as biological archives including collections of strains and DNA libraries.

Since the harmonization and alignment of protocols is a general objective of the One Health EJP, these activities are embedded in both the JRP and the JIP. As for the latter, the projects OH-Harmony-CAP and CARE are focussing on laboratory procedures and on reference materials and data bases, respectively. In this way, this main One Health EJP objective is specifically promoted and dedicated activities were set up.

5. To exchange and communicate with all National, European and International relevant stakeholders, and in particular the European Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

Close contacts with both ECDC and EFSA are maintained throughout the lifespan of the One Health EJP. During the revision of the Strategic Research Agenda in 2018, both organisations have shared their needs, which led to the launch of JRP and JIP in the second call that will address at least some of these. In 2020, new stakeholders joined the EJP's Stakeholder Committee, thus allowing a close discussion on the domains that are of interest to them as well. Now, in the later stages of the One Health EJP, dissemination efforts are set up to feed back the results and outcomes of the projects to these international stakeholders, as well as to the national and regional ones.

6. To promote and develop food safety research resources in the European Union by training, education and communication.

The research findings of JRP, JIP and PhD are continuously presented to the scientific community by designed yearly scientific meetings and workshops, beside the proper publications by the scientists. Also training courses and short-term missions, staff exchanges and targeted training are organized to improve researchers' skills in new techniques.

2.2 Work performed during the reporting period (M49-M57) and main results achieved

2.2.1 WP1

The Coordination Team (CT), consisting of the Coordinator, Scientific Coordinator and Support Team, continues with the management of the One Health EJP by having weekly conference calls for the day-to-day management of the project. Regular videoconferences with Project Management Team (PMT) were organised (21 January, 8 February, 4 April, 5 May and 10 June), as well as one videoconference with SSB (24 March). The second annual SSB meeting is planned as a face-to-face meeting hosted by BIOR in Riga on 28 September 2022. The CT has started the preparation of the joint PMC-POC meeting to take place on 21-22 November 2022 as a physical meeting in Stockholm, where specific attention will be brought on dissemination of outcomes towards high level scientists of EU stakeholders, namely the Chief Scientists of ECDC and EFSA, the POC members representing the national Stakeholders and some international Stakeholders such as WHO, WOH and FAO.

The Support Team has managed finances and the financial report of year 4 as well as the fourth amendment to the Grant Agreement. The Coordination Team together with the Project Management

Team has prepared the periodic report and submitted it to REA on 22 March 2022. In addition, the CT managed the finalisation of the request for a no-costs extension of the OHEJP.

An initial review meeting was held on May 17-18, 2022, at which the reviewers gave a positive review of OHEJP's scientific accomplishments.

As for the follow-up of possible ethical issues, the Ethics Advisors evaluated an additional integrative project, JIP COVRIN, started in 2021 and focusing on SARS-COV-2. The ethics report (D1.26) was delivered as planned.

The Communication Team successfully continues to create a strong impact by developing relationships between the One Health EJP and the identified audiences. This is done by producing content for a strong, cohesive brand, and developing a wide range of dissemination materials to highlight our outcomes and demonstrate impact.

2.2.2 WP2

In WP2, relevant scientific developments were monitored by screening the output of OHEJP projects as well as relevant information from external sources. A gap analysis of the priority topics selected in the second internal call has been conducted to identify gaps in One Health research and/or integrative areas. Also, an expert elicitation has been conducted to update the priority research topics. WP2 has also worked closely with WP7 towards the elaboration of the OHEJP Strategic Research and Innovative Agenda.

In addition, the repository of EU projects/initiatives has been regularly updated on the OHEJP website. Strategic interactions with a number of related EU projects and initiatives were established. During this period, a deliverable (2.9) was produced including the main goals and activities performed in WP2 task 2.2. This deliverable includes the revision of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives that overlap in scope with OHEJP projects. Besides, all the interactions that have been made between WP2 and other projects/initiatives, as well as interactions between OHEJP projects and other EU projects/initiatives, have been detailed.

2.2.3 WP3

The major task of WP3 is the monitoring of ongoing Joint Research Projects (JRP). All the first call projects have been finalized in June 2021, meaning that from January 2022 onwards, only second call JRP needed follow-up.

As all Work Packages, WP3 was involved in the preparation of the One Health EJP Periodic Technical Report and in the JRP Periodic Report (D3.18) which was submitted in March 2022. WP3 prepared the planning for the upcoming reports (9M and Final Reports) and the 9M templates.

The fourth Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) took place in Orvieto, Italy, and was set up as a hybrid (combined in person - online) event from 11 to 13 May 2022. It was a successful edition, where about 300 participants from 22 countries took part. The abstract book (D3.19) was submitted in April 2022.

2.2.4 WP4

WP4 supports and monitors the Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs) and integrative activities. Four JIPs have been in progress in Y5: CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, MATRIX and COVRIN. CARE has conducted cross-sectoral proficiency tests (PTs), set up a biobank with well-characterized reference materials, which in the end will be available for everyone and works with data for risk assessments. OH-HARMONY-CAP has identified best practices for laboratory protocols for the detection and characterisation of foodborne pathogens and determinants for AMR. OH-HARMONY-CAP has created a survey to be used to assess the adaptability, capability, capacity, and interoperability of the surveillance for detection and characterisation of pathogens. MATRIX has continued with some of the outputs from the finalised JIPs ORION and COHESIVE on roadmaps for surveillance, best practices for

collection, sharing, analysis and interpretation of data and dashboards for collaboration and communication of One Health data. These three JIP projects will end in December this year. They had a common final meeting the 20th of September in Copenhagen, followed by separate project meetings. WP4 participated in the joint meeting.

JIP-06-COVRIN focuses on One Health aspects of SARS-CoV2 on identification of drivers for the spread and emergence of SARS-CoV2 by developing and harmonizing methods for detection and characterization of the virus. Models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2 are being developed. COVRIN will end in March 2023.

The two JIPs of the first call, ORION and COHESIVE were evaluated in Y5. The evaluators considered both projects to have achieved the aims of the project plans.

Among other activities, some can be mentioned; The WP4 Team organized a very well visited Thematic Integrative Meeting in February on the subject “Data sharing across sectors”. The OHEJP Simulation Exercise, SimEx is managed as a project within WP4 with a dedicated project group. Eleven countries have conducted the exercise at the national level. Reporting and internal evaluation of the exercise is ongoing. The progress of DMP management proceeds and when the OHEJP finishes all DMPs will be available on Zenodo.

2.2.5 WP5

In Y5, activities of WP5 are taking full advantage of the well-consolidated connections with the Key EU Stakeholders, ECDC and EFSA, as well as with other European (EEA, EMA) and global (FAO, WHO-Euro, WOA) stakeholders. The ninth Stakeholder Committee meeting was held in connection to ASM 2022 as a hybrid in person/online meeting, and saw participation from ECDC, EFSA, EEA, FAO, and WOA. The tenth will take place in November 2022 in conjunction with the joint POC/PMT meeting.

Stakeholders’ needs were collected by the regular scanning of stakeholders’ documents activity, an activity continuously adjusted to keep track of evolving stakeholders’ priorities, as well as by direct contacts with organisations’ representatives.

The dissemination activities of WP5 were further developed to disseminate new scientific data and results to the different stakeholder groups in a targeted manner. These included targeted reports to Key EU stakeholders, dissemination workshops (mainly targeted at national stakeholders), direct contact, and other ways of targeted dissemination.

The One Health Outcome Inventory (OHOI) was improved and updated to support interaction and collaboration between consortium members and stakeholders. Solutions are being explored regarding its long-term sustainability.

Additional efforts were put to create links with interested parties not included in the Stakeholders Committee at the European and global level. WP5 highlighted the impact of the OHEJP at science and policy, but also impact that OHEJP-developed solutions can have at the environmental, economic, industrial, and societal level.

WP5 was active in disseminating its results in conferences and meetings at the European and international level, and OHEJP representative from WP5 Pikka Jokelainen was part of science-to-policy panel discussions at ONE2022.

2.2.6 WP6

The scientific research being carried out in the doctoral programme has progressed and planned outputs have continued to be produced. WP6 monitors the progress of the PhD projects through the submission of project deliverables and publications produced by the 17 PhD projects (WP6 and WP7). In total, in M49-54, 18 deliverables were achieved, and two publications were produced. Further

details of the progress of each PhD project are discussed in more detail in the individual PhD reports section. The deliverable D6.22: 4th periodic report on PhDs was submitted in M53.

Two Short Term Missions (STMs) have taken place that were funded to take place in 2021 but were postponed. Six additional STMs have also taken place in 2022. Reports for these have been received, and most of the case studies have now been created. An extended call for STMs to take place in 2022 was opened. There were 5 applications, of which four were recommended for funding. Award letters have been sent out to the applicants. The deliverable D6.14: Report on short term missions, 2021 was submitted in M54.

The Continuing Professional Development (CPD) module for 2022 is planned for the 2nd – 4th November 2022 to be held at the Statens Serum Institut (SSI), Copenhagen, hosted by SSI and DTU-Food, Denmark.

The ASM Satellite workshop 2022 was held online in April 2022. The workshop was hosted by the University of Surrey and the National University of Ireland, with the theme: mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications. The ASM 2022 deliverable report D6.16 will be submitted in M60 as planned.

The University of Surrey is proposing to hold the ‘Final’ summer school in December 2022, with the theme of Sustainability, and the budget/proposal will be submitted by the end of September 2022.

2.2.7 WP7

WP7 focuses on ensuring that alignment, harmonisation and integration initiatives taken during the EJP as well as the building-up of interactions with stakeholders and the main outputs, tools and outcomes will be sustained beyond the end of the One Health EJP. A key document to be delivered by WP7 at the end of the EJP is the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). WP7 has worked in collaboration with other WPs to define a preliminary outline of the SRIA (D7.2). Thereafter, the various chapters have been developed by contributors within the consortium. Two modules have been established, an AMR module and a One Health module, to elaborate in depth two principal sections of the SRIA. In order to meet the stakeholder needs and expectations, a SWOT analysis was conducted, this was followed by a stakeholder mapping (in collaboration with WP5). In order to ensure the legacy of outcomes of the One Health EJP, a list of key outcomes derived from JIP and JRP projects has been presented following the structure of the integrative strategy matrix. A link to access the tools in the outcomes is provided when available (D7.1).

2.3 Progress beyond the state of the art, expected results until the end of the project and potential impacts

Consistent with the “Prevent-Detect-Respond” concept, integrative activities will feed the approach of evidence based risk assessment and therefore risk management by the competent authorities.

Intensive collaboration between the most relevant partners in Europe in the field of foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance contribute to help to reduce unnecessarily duplication of work on these topics.

It is of importance to efficiently organize knowledge dissemination to the appropriate stakeholders (ECDC, EFSA, DG AGRI, DG Santé, the national authorities and beyond); these tasks were and will be taken forward by WP2 (Strategic Research Agenda), WP5 (Science to Policy) and WP6 (Education & Training)

The EJP aims at enhancing harmonization, alignment and integration of activities in these domains, but this process may not be finalised at the end of the programme. To make sure that the integrative activities will last beyond the lifespan of the One Health EJP, a specific WP (WP7) is dedicated to create a significant long-term capacity building and alignment among all EJP partners.

3 WP1 - Coordination and Management

3.1 Work carried out to date

3.1.1 Task 1.1: Management of EC contractual obligations

Regarding contractual procedures, the One Health EJP Support Team (ST) has ensured a monitoring of the deliverables and milestones, which has allowed the submission of the deliverables due in the period as well as the notification of the milestones achieved. The WP1 deliverables (Summary Progress Report Y5 - D1.18, Annual Work Plan Y6 - D1.19 and Ethical review report for year 4 – D1.26) have been prepared by the Coordination Team in order to report to the REA. The ST has also prepared the fourth amendment to the Grant Agreement with a main purpose to extend the duration of the One Health EJP from M60 to M69, due to COVID-19 situation, considered as a Force Majeure. The fourth Amendment to the Grant Agreement (AMD-773830-55) was approved by the European Commission on 18 March 2022. In the framework of the external review procedure, a review meeting has been organised by the REA on 17 and 18 May, giving occasion to the PMT to present the activities of all the WPs and to respond to the questions of the reviewers. The review report was received on 20 June 2022 and was carefully reviewed by the PMT.

3.1.2 Task 1.2: Project management

The CT provided effective management support to ensure the quality of the work both in terms of results and timing and to manage the relationships between partners and to ensure an effective internal communication. The CT has frequently organised videoconferences to monitor the project's progress and to ensure the timely implementation of the AWP year 5. When any important issue has arisen, the Coordination team has liaised with the Research Executive Agency (REA) to inform the Project Officers (PO) in the first place and request a delay in the submission of deliverables or a change of content of Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement whenever needed and relevant. The CT and PMT held regular videoconferences to monitor the progress of the activities per work package (WP). The PMT reviewed, commented and provided relevant guidance and input on important WP documents, and validated the deliverables, which have been prepared and submitted during this period.

3.1.2.1 Preparation of the Amendment to the Consortium Agreement

The ST is currently managing the 2nd amendment to the Consortium Agreement to update:

- The financial provisions by adjusting the resulting cofunding rate for cofunded activities, in accordance with the reality of costs declared by the consortium members over the first four years. Indeed initially the cofunding rate was set to 44% but actual expenses declared after four years of implementation show that it is rather 43%. The final cofunding rate for cofunded activities will be known at the end of the OHEJP when all costs will have been reported.
- Annex 1 “Background included”, to specify the access rights per participant for each of the 2nd round projects and possibly the PhDs.
- Annex 6 “CA detailed budget per partner and per activity” to reflect the EU contribution each partner is expected to receive until the end of the project in September 2023.

3.1.2.2 Implementation of the dissemination and legacy strategy

The efforts to implement an effective dissemination and legacy strategy have been intensified from January 2022 and will be pursued until the end of the project in September 2023. The One Health EJP collaborators involved in the remaining research projects, integrative activities and PhD, together with the Project Management Team and their collaborators are focusing on finalizing the scientific activities and on optimally disseminating all outcomes to both broad and specific audiences.

The objective of the dissemination activities is to publicise the outcomes of the research and integrative efforts, and to facilitate their uptake by other researchers, diagnostic and reference laboratories, risk assessors, risk managers and policy makers, at national, EU and international levels. As such, these deliverables of the One Health EJP will be sustained and the One Health EJP will have gained impact. Please note that all deliverables are openly accessible on the One Health EJP website in the '[One Health Outcome Inventory](#)'.

To this end, the CT and PMT have further detailed the planning to streamline this important period of the One Health EJP project, as well as the planning of three related strategic meetings (PMC-POC meeting in November 2022, bilateral discussions with key targeted stakeholders for the uptake of main outcomes of the OHEJP, One Health EJP Stakeholders Conference in spring 2023 and the Policy event at the end of the project in September 2023). A specific PMT TC (5 May 2022) allowed to clarify the scope of each of the dissemination/legacy meetings to avoid the overlapping and to maximise the impact of each of these strategic sequences.

3.1.3 Task 1.3: Organisation of EJP management and governance meetings

All consortium governance bodies (Coordination Team, Project Management Team, Scientific Steering Board, Programme Managers Committee) have actively cooperated in supporting the efficient implementation of the One Health EJP activities.

The Scientific Steering Board (SSB) holds two meetings per year. The first 2022 SSB meeting was held online on 24 March and allowed to achieve the following objectives:

- Presentation of the case studies, from a selection of three completed projects (JRP ARDIG, JIP COHESIVE and PhD LINRES), by their respective Project Leaders with focus on outcomes and expected impact.
- Review of the periodic technical and financial report of year 4 (2021);
- Detailed update on the financial situation, including the potential budget trajectory until the end of the project;
- Presentation on the progress of the scientific activities (JRPs, JIPs and Training & Education activities) and on the implementation of the SimEX;
- Discussion on the sustainability of the OHEJP, notably within the future EU Partnerships.

The second 2022 SSB meeting was hosted by BIOR in Riga on 28 September 2022 in Riga. At this meeting, the Consortium continued an effective process of dissemination of the outcomes of the EJP One Health and to demonstrate its impact at the national levels.

In addition, the meeting allowed to validate the OHEJP Annual Workplan Y6 and the Summary Progress Report Y5 and to present the first conclusions of SimEx.

Furthermore, an online meeting with the External Scientific Advisory Board (ESAB) was held on 3 June 2022 and discussed the progress One Health EJP made since the last ESAB meeting in June 2021.

Similar to last year, the PMT agreed to organize a joint meeting of the Programme Manager Committee (PMC), the Governing Board of the OHEJP and the Programme Owner Committee (POC), composed of the Beneficiaries' line Ministries Representatives. It will be hosted by the Public Health Agency of Sweden and held as a physical meeting on 21-22 November 2022 in Solna. The scope note of the meeting is available online ([link](#)), as well as the extended agenda of the meeting ([link](#)).

3.1.4 Task 1.4: Communication tools

The Communications Team have strengthened the One Health EJP brand and communications outputs for key One Health EJP events held in 2022, including the ASM 2022, ASM Satellite Workshop 2022, and will provide communications support for the next CPD module to be held in November 2022. The

Communications Team have supported all OHEJP events using the following activities: developing the promotional social media campaigns, posting information on the website, providing videoconference links and logos to local event organisers. The Communications Team provides an extensive list of support tools, before, during and after each event that provides delegates with a branded and professional experience.

The Communications Team have worked to improve the dissemination of outcomes, including the overarching One Health EJP deliverables, Publications, WP6 outcomes, Project outputs and WP5 activities etc. Communication with WP3 and 4 has been further developed, which has improved the ability to collect information from the One Health EJP projects and support the Project Leaders in disseminating their outcomes, including through the creation of Project Impact Brochures. These are interactive brochures designed to appeal to a wide audience, with brochures for METSTAVA, IMPART and TOX-Detect already available, and LISTADAPT and FULLFORCE brochures available soon. We aim to create Project Impact Brochures for all OHEJP JIPs and JRPs. The Communications Team have also supported other OHEJP events, including the WP5 Dissemination Workshop Series, the MATRIX Webinar Series 2022, the COVRIN SARS-COV2 in Wildlife Workshops, the SimEx training workshops & conduction exercises, OHEJP side events at the ONE2022 conference, by creating flyers, social media posts and providing information on our website to disseminate the event details to relevant audiences.

The previous expansion of the website has enabled continued collation of key dissemination documents and tools, such as the Annual Report 2021, Project Impact Brochures, Science to Policy Translation Reports, Cogwheel Workshops Case Study, One Health Outcome Inventory and Data Management Plan. The website shares information about OHEJP events, outcomes and other Consortium news through the Latest News and One Health EJP blog webpages, which are written in a less formal way to appeal to wider audiences, including non-scientists. For example, the current blog campaign features the “OHEJP PhD life” posts that describe a day in the life of the OHEJP PhD students for readers to better understand their research work.

The website is the main information hub of the OHEJP and is being improved and redeveloped during the fifth year. The Communications Team is currently working with an external web developer to ensure that the security and stability of the website are maintained. Website sustainability is a key focus since the site needs to exist two years after the end of the one Health EJP (in September 2023). This will involve future collaboration with the Med-Vet-Net Association to organise that management of the website will be transferred to their organisation once the One Health EJP ends, to ensure the legacy of our research remains available.

The One Health EJP social media channels have been an important information hub for our online audiences and have continued to grow in the fifth year, since we now have over 2700 followers on LinkedIn and over 4100 followers on Twitter. The Communications Team has focussed attention to supporting stakeholders spread their messages to support sustainability, sharing key one Health EJP news and information, and using WP5’s scanning documents to increase the number of social media posts.

The deliverable [D.1.16: Annual report on the internal and external newsletters produced during the fourth year](#) was completed and disseminated in M49. The deliverable [D.1.17: Annual report for stakeholder number 4](#) has been completed in M53 and widely disseminated to all OHEJP audiences, including the public. It details the key objectives of the OHEJP, and the progress made by WPs, JRPs, JIPs, PhD projects and other activities, including, but not limited to dissemination and communications.

The Communications Team took an active role in the DMP Committee to ensure that communication aspects of the data management plan were taken into consideration and information about One Health EJP is disseminated, when the “Dissemination Information Pack” was updated last year. The beneficial impacts of the updated DIP are evident in the fifth year, as Consortium members are better supported in understanding how to upload information to the OHEJP community on Zenodo (a sustainable open access repository) and apply the Publications Policy to their research outcomes.

Last year’s creation and dissemination of “An Overview Presentation for the One Health EJP” has provided a useful template for Consortium members to work with in Year 5 when they have presented the One Health EJP to internal or external audiences (e.g., at conferences or webinars) thus allowing communication of consistent messaging.

Consortium newsletters have been sent out on a quarterly basis in M51 and M54, the next is due in M57. These newsletters are targeted to Consortium members only and were disseminated to internal OHEJP mailing lists. These newsletters were also uploaded to the “Newsletters” page on the OHEJP website.

An external newsletter published in M54 used the re-designed style created last year that aims to improve engagement with external audiences through its branded design. The next external newsletter will be due at the end of the fifth year. These newsletters are targeted to those outside of the OHEJP consortium and those who have signed up to the OHEJP mailing list. The newsletter is sent to the external mailing lists, internal mailing lists, shared on social media and is uploaded to the OHEJP website on the “Newsletters” page.

A substantial role in dissemination of deliverables, outcomes and data has been undertaken by the Communications Team in the fifth year. The Communications team have worked closely with IMPART and TOX-Detect project leaders to create interactive PDF documents, described as Project Impact brochures, which highlight the key outcomes of each project. IMPART Project Brochure became available online in M50 (February 2022) and TOX-Detect in M53 (May 2022). Further Project Impact Brochures will be created for the other One Health EJP projects during Years 5 and 6. The Communications Team worked with JIP management team to produce the promotional document "Cogwheel Workshops Case Study" which has been uploaded to the Public Deliverables of our website and disseminated on social media in M57 (September 2022). Later this year, it will be shared in our upcoming newsletters.

The Communications Team members have presented at the governance and review meetings to update and demonstrate what the Communications Team have achieved and plan to achieve in the upcoming year, in addition to highlighting the impact and sustainability of the OHEJP outcomes beyond the end of the OHEJP.

3.1.5 Task 1.5 Ethics

The Ethical review report for Y4 (D1.26) was delivered as expected in M50.

3.1.6 Task 1.6 Declaration of Cofund

N/A

3.2 Deliverables and Milestones

3.2.1 Deliverables

Del. Ref.	Deliverable title	Submission
D1.16	Annual report on the internal and external newsletter produced during the fourth year	M49
D1.17	Complete version of annual report for stakeholders n°4	M53
D1.18	Summary progress report year 5	M57
D1.26	Ethical review report for Y4	M50
D1.30	Annual Work Plan Year 6	M57

3.2.2 Milestones

Mil. Ref.	Milestone title	Expected Delivery/ Achievement Month	Notification
MS10	SSB Meeting n°9	M57	SSB Meeting n°9 was organised by BIOR in Riga on 28 Sept. 2022
MS16	PMC/POC/ESAB	M57	Joint PMC/POC meeting will be FoHM in Stockholm from 21 to 22 Nov 2022 ESAB meeting was held online on 3 June 2022.

4 WP2 – Integrative strategic research agenda

4.1 Work carried out to date

4.1.1 Task 2.1: Development of the SRA

At the start of OHEJP, in January 2018, a provisional Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) has been delivered. In 2018, the SRA was updated and in the first month of 2019 the updated SRA was delivered (D2.7). The SRA is the product of a structured prioritisation process in which priority research and integrative topics have been identified. In this process both research and integrative needs of the EU member states participating in OHEJP as well as EU stakeholders (ECDC and EFSA) have been taken into account. The lists and descriptions of the priority topics have provided the basis for the internal calls for Joint Research Projects (WP3), Joint Integrative Projects (WP4) and PhD projects (WP6). In addition to the updated SRA, which was delivered as a confidential document (D2.7), a more concise, public version of the SRA was developed to be used for external dissemination purposes. This public SRA was delivered as an extra deliverable (D2.10). Furthermore, in task 2.1 relevant scientific developments, including the emergence of zoonotic threats and opportunities for scientific innovations are monitored. For this, the output from OHEJP projects (e.g. deliverables, scientific publications) is screened, as well as relevant information from external sources (e.g. conferences, scientific meetings, published papers, etc.). In 2021, a gap analysis of the priority topics selected in the second internal call for project proposals has been conducted to identify gaps in One Health research and/or integrative areas that have not been (sufficiently) covered by the OHEJP, as well as key outputs/unique selling points of OHEJP (e.g. scientific approaches and innovations, guidelines, databases developed, etc.) that would benefit future partnerships. Also, an experts elicitation has been conducted among the partner organizations, including partners that recently joined the OHEJP, to update the priority research topics. This information will be used as input for the development of the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA) in WP7.

4.1.2 Task 2.2: Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives

As mentioned above, during this period a new deliverable was produced (M49) including the main goals achieved regarding strategic links established and strategic developments. This deliverable was disseminated as publicly available. The main activities can be summarized as identification of relevant EU-projects and initiatives and strategic interactions between OHEJP projects and other EU projects and initiatives.

Regarding the first one, an online inventory has been periodically updated three times a year since the beginning of the OHEJP to facilitate the identification of potential strategic interactions within the OHEJP consortium. The repository (spreadsheet) is available to all OHEJP consortium through the OHEJP website (Intranet_Home_Groups_OHEJP Consortium Members_Documents). So, since 2018, a total of 60 EU projects and initiatives have been included in the repository, including an information sheet of each project and initiative also available by clicking the acronym on the spreadsheet. Moreover, although CORDIS has been the main database used to gather all these EU projects and initiatives, eight JPIAMR calls were also included in another spreadsheet together with their information sheets. The scientific scope of the identified EU projects/initiatives was also visualized in relation to the OHEJP matrix consisting of three domains (FBZ, AMR, ET), five themes (Analytical methods, Host-microbe interaction, Epidemiology, Risk assessment and socio-economic impact and Intervention). This classification helped the OHEJP project leaders to identify the EU projects/initiatives that could be of interest to establish interactions promoting scientific collaborations.

Regarding strategic interactions, during the lifetime of the OHEJP, WP2 has contacted several projects and initiatives (ELIXIR, ENOVAT, European Burden of Disease Network, GloPID-R SEC 2, HealthyLivestock, HIDALGO, IS_MIRRI21, JPI-AMR, PANGAIA, PhagoPROD, SPRINGBOARD and VetBioNet) in order to establish a fruitful collaboration or to identify possible synergies between them

and the OHEJP projects. For this, WP2 elaborated the list of candidate projects considering the EU project repository, selecting only projects that had not been contacted before by other OHEJP members. Besides, the duration of the project, as well as the scope, covering the majority of OHEJP project topics, were also taken into account for the selection of EU projects/initiatives. Besides, several actions have been taken to facilitate the interactions between the OHEJP JIP, JRP and PhD projects with relevant and related EU projects and initiatives. These activities include the repository of EU projects/initiatives, direct contact with project leaders, attendance to congresses/meetings, cogwheel workshops, etc. As a result of this active search for related EU projects and initiatives to avoid duplicity and strengthen collaboration between projects that are working with the same pathogens, technologies, platforms, etc., several interactions have been initiated during the lifetime of the OHEJP project. All the interactions between OHEJP projects and other EU projects and initiatives have resulted in synergetic collaborations with an important impact in all the projects. The outcomes of these interactions can be summarized as follows:

- a) Share of data, workflows and bioinformatics pipelines
- b) Share of products previously developed (standards, culture media)
- c) Collaboration to develop new methodology and protocols
- d) Expertise in organizing Proficiency Tests
- e) Compatibility of platforms developed
- f) Dissemination of OHEJP results
- g) Share of information on the use of NGS
- h) Submission of project proposals to JPI-AMR and JAMRAI calls
- i) Collaborative publications and workshops

In addition, WP2 has participated in several dissemination activities [e.g. CONNECT Network final meeting, questionnaires from “Open call for data on use of antimicrobials in animals” distributed by European Medicines Agency and Global Antimicrobial Resistance Platform for One Burden Estimates (GAP-ONE) and One Health Latinoamerica (OHLA)] to increase the OHEJP visibility and foster strategic interactions with related EU projects and initiatives.

Finally, WP2 has been in contact with WP4 to exchange information about some EU projects/initiatives for the selection of possible candidates for the organization of cogwheel workshops. This collaboration has been another way of identifying synergies, joint priorities, and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. Since the beginning of OHEJP, WP2 has collaborate with WP2 in order to select candidates for Cogwheels workshops (COMPARE, EFFORT, INNUENDO, IRIDA, INFACIT, MAGITICS, K-STaR, OASIS, TRIuMPH, IDx, SafeConsume, VEO, MOOD and ELIXIR).

4.2 Deliverables and Milestones

4.2.1 Deliverables

Del. Ref.	Deliverable title	Submission
D2.9	Report on strategic links established and strategic developments	M49

4.2.2 Milestones

Mil. Ref.	Milestone title	Expected Delivery/ Achievement Month	Notification
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MS24	List of strategic synergies with EU projects and strategic developments	M49	Achieved
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5 WP3 - Joint research projects

5.1 Work carried out to date

5.1.1 Task 3.1: Drawing up of guidelines for submission, selection and evaluation of JRP proposals as well as request of extension of accepted JRPs.

The activities related to this task and the corresponding deliverables have been finalised in 2019; no more new official guidelines are expected.

5.1.2 Task 3.2: Supervision of the JRP in the first round of projects.

The activities related to this task and the corresponding deliverable D3.18 were finalised in December 2021 since all the first round projects came to an end in 2021. These activities have been reported in the One Health EJP Periodic Technical Report Y4 and in deliverable D3.18, the JRP Periodic JRP Report Y4.

1.1.1 Task 3.3: Organisation of a second round of projects and their supervision.

The only JRP that are running in 2022 are those of the second call. WP3 prepared the planning of the June-September (9 Months Report) and the October-December (JRP and JIP, except COVRIN: Final Report; COVRIN: 12 Months Report) templates. WP3 also prepared the templates, in collaboration with WP4 and WP6. The team will collect the first version of the 9M reports and include the information in this SPR Y5 report.

The monitoring of projects of the second round is described further under “5.1.3.3”.

5.1.3 Detailed follow up of JRPs

5.1.3.1 Milestones and Deliverables of JRPs

Only 50% of the deliverables and 45% of the milestones are available. The delays are essentially due to the Covid-19 situation. All the second round projects have been granted an extension that will allow them to complete the tasks and finalize the deliverables according to the amended Annual Work Plan.

Deliverables

PROJECT	DELIVERABLES DUE FOR SEPTEMBER 2022	ACHIEVED DELIVERABLES	% OF ACHIEVED DELIVERABLES
JRP12-FARMED	4	1	25%
JRP13-WORLDCOM	2	2	100%
JRP14-FULL-FORCE	8	3	38%
JRP15-FED-AMR	22	11	50%
JRP16-TELE-Vir	5	4	80%
JRP17-IDEMBRU	20	5	25%
JRP18-MEmE	21	13	62%
JRP19-PARADISE	4	3	75%
JRP20-DISCOVeR	7	4	57%
JRP21-BIOPIGEE	9	5	56%
JRP22-TOXOSOURCES	No deliverables were due by M57	N/A	N/A
JRP23-ADONIS	12	8	67%
JRP24-BeONE	7	2	29%

PROJECT	DELIVERABLES DUE FOR SEPTEMBER 2022	ACHIEVED DELIVERABLES	% OF ACHIEVED DELIVERABLES
TOTAL	121	61	50%

Milestones

PROJECT	MILESTONES DUE FOR SEPTEMBER 2022	ACHIEVED MILESTONES	% OF ACHIEVED MILESTONES
JRP12-FARMED	10	3	30%
JRP13-WORLDCOM	9	4	44%
JRP14-FULL-FORCE	13	3	23%
JRP15-FED-AMR	31	12	39%
JRP16-TELE-Vir	7	5	71%
JRP17-IDEMBRU	34	11	32%
JRP18-MEmE	18	15	83%
JRP19-PARADISE	12	5	42%
JRP20-DISCoVeR	6	4	67%
JRP21-BIOPIGEE	12	9	75%
JRP22-TOXOSOURCES	No milestones were scheduled by M57	-	
JRP23-ADONIS	7	2	29%
JRP24-BeONE	15	5	33%
TOTAL	174	78	45%

5.1.3.2 Publications of JRP

Scientific Publications

In 2022, 24 manuscripts were published. In the table below are listed, per year, the round 1 and round 2 JRP publications. In total, 147 JRP manuscripts were published since the beginning of the project.

PROJECT	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	TOTAL
One Health EJP			1		1	2
JRP01-IMPART			5	2	1	8
JRP02-ARDIG		2	10	5		17
JRP03-RaDAR		1	1			2
JRP04-MAD-Vir		1	1			2
JRP05-TOX-detect		1	1	2	1	5
JRP06-NOVA	1	3	5	1		10
JRP07-LISTADAPT			2	4		6
JRP08-METASTAVA			4	2		6
JRP09-AIR-SAMPLE			5			5
JRP10-MOMIR-PPC			5	2		7
JRP11-MedVetKlebs	1	4	6		1	12
JRP12-FARMED				1		1
JRP13-WORLDCOM				1	7	8
JRP14-FULL-FORCE				1		1
JRP15-FED-AMR				1	1	2
JRP16-TELE-Vir			1	1	1	3
JRP17-IDEMBRU				1	1	2
JRP18-MEmE			7	4	4	15
JRP19-PARADISE			2	2	1	5
JRP20-DISCoVeR				1	2	3
JRP21-BIOPIGEE					1	1
JRP22-TOXOSOURCES			4	15	1	20
JRP23-ADONIS				2	1	3
JRP24-BeONE			1			1
TOTAL	2	12	61	48	24	147

2018 – 2 publications

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Analysis of consumer food purchase data used for outbreak investigations, a review. Møller FT, Mølbak K, Ethelberg S.

Eurosurveillance. 2018;23(24). doi:10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2018.23.24.1700503

https://zenodo.org/record/3747633#.XpCQ_sgzZM0

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella variicola* and Related Phylogroups by MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry.

Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondraso A, Brisse S.

Front Microbiol. 2018;9:3000. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660887#.XkEm5mhKiUk>

2019 – 12 publications

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Antimicrobial Usages and Antimicrobial Resistance in Commensal *Escherichia coli* From Veal Calves in France: Evolution During the Fattening Process.

Gay E, Bour M, Cazeau G, et al.

Front Microbiol. 2019;10:792. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2019.00792

https://zenodo.org/record/4249017#.YAqc_uhKjcc

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: The shufflon of IncI1 plasmids is rearranged constantly during different growth conditions.

Brouwer MSM, Jurburg SD, Harders F, et al.

Plasmid. 2019;102:51-55. doi:10.1016/j.plasmid.2019.03.003

<https://zenodo.org/record/3730621#.Xn3MyYhKi70>

JRP03-AMR3-RADAR: Attributable sources of community-acquired carriage of *Escherichia coli* containing β -lactam antibiotic resistance genes: a population-based modelling study. *The Lancet*

Mughini-Gras L, Dorado-García A, van Duijkeren E, et al.

Planetary Health. 2019;3(8):e357-e369. doi:10.1016/S2542-5196(19)30130-5

<https://zenodo.org/record/3621285#.Xjl8UGhKhPY>

JRP04-ET1-MADVIR: Field samplings of *Ixodes ricinus* ticks from a tick-borne encephalitis virus micro-focus in Northern Zealand, Denmark.

Petersen A, Rosenstjerne MW, Rasmussen M, et al.

Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases. 2019;10(5):1028-1032. doi:10.1016/j.ttbdis.2019.05.005

<https://zenodo.org/record/3634258#.Xjl8d2hKhPY>

JRP05-ET1-TOXDETECT: Point-of-Need DNA Testing for Detection of Foodborne Pathogenic Bacteria.

Vidic J, Vizzini P, Manzano M, et al.

Sensors. 2019;19(5):1100. doi:10.3390/s19051100

<https://zenodo.org/record/3935799#.X6Ud-GhKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: An outbreak of monophasic *Salmonella* Typhimurium associated with raw pork sausage and other pork products, Denmark 2018–19.

Helmuth IG, Espenhain L, Ethelberg S, et al.

Epidemiol Infect. 2019;147:e315. doi:10.1017/S0950268819002073

<https://zenodo.org/record/4249319#.X6UIWmhKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Non-Typhi, non-Paratyphi *Salmonella*-related hospitalisations in Spain: trends, clinical aspects, risk factors for worse prognosis and hospital costs.

Garrido-Esteba M, Latasa P, Ordóñez-León GY, Martínez-Avilés M, de la Torre A, García-Comas L.

Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis. 2019;38(2):337-346. doi:10.1007/s10096-018-3433-1

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244788#.X6LhGYhKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: *Salmonella* Surveillance Systems in Swine and Humans in Spain: A Review.

Martínez-Avilés M, Garrido-Esteba M, Álvarez J, de la Torre A.

Veterinary Sciences. 2019;6(1):20. doi:10.3390/vetsci6010020

<https://zenodo.org/record/3635293#.XjlyUGhKhPY>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Whole genome sequencing reveals resemblance between ESBL-producing and carbapenem resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates from Austrian rivers and clinical isolates from hospitals.

Lepuschitz S, Schill S, Stoeger A, et al.

Science of The Total Environment. 2019;662:227-235. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.179

<https://zenodo.org/record/4249232#.X6UhA2hKjcc>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Description of *Klebsiella africanensis* sp. nov., *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *tropicalensis* subsp. nov. and *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *variicola* subsp. nov.

Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Diallo TA, Criscuolo A, Brisse S.

Research in Microbiology. 2019;170(3):165-170. doi:10.1016/j.resmic.2019.02.003

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660879#.XkEmO2hKiUk>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Description of *Klebsiella spallanzanii* sp. nov. and of *Klebsiella pasteurii* sp. nov.

Merla C, Rodrigues C, Passet V, et al.

Front Microbiol. 2019;10:2360. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2019.02360

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660875#.XkEICGhKiUk>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Outbreak of Yersiniabactin-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit:

Wisgrill L, Lepuschitz S, Blaschitz M, et al.

The Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal. 2019;38(6):638-642.

doi:10.1097/INF.0000000000002258

<https://zenodo.org/record/3661013#.XkFq-OSWwj9>

2020 - 61 publications

One Health EJP: The One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), 2018–2022: An Exemplary One Health Initiative.

Brown, H. L.; Passey, J. L.; Getino, M.; Pursley, I.; Basu, P.; Horton, D. L.; La Ragione, R. M.

Journal of Medical Microbiology 2020, 69 (8), 1037–1039.

<https://doi.org/10.1099/jmm.0.001228>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5541709#.YVXFzPBy70>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART and JRP14-FULL-FORCE : Novel IncFII Plasmid Harboursing *Bla* NDM-4 in a Carbapenem-Resistant *Escherichia Coli* of Pig Origin, Italy.

Diaconu, E. L.; Carfora, V.; Alba, P.; Di Matteo, P.; Stravino, F.; Buccella, C.; Dell’Aira, E.; Onorati, R.; Sorbara, L.; Battisti, A.; Franco, A.

Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy 2020, 75 (12), 3475–3479.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa374>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4451840#.YAfRNhKg2w>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Spill-Over from Public Health? First Detection of an OXA-48-Producing *Escherichia Coli* in a German Pig Farm.

Irrgang, A.; Pauly, N.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Grobbel, M.; Kaesbohrer, A.; Hammerl, J. A.

Microorganisms 2020, 8 (6), 855.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8060855>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4447289#.YAWijthKg2w>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: First Detection of GES-5-Producing *Escherichia Coli* from Livestock—An Increasing Diversity of Carbapenemases Recognized from German Pig Production.

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Pauly, N.; Hammerl, J. A.; Grobbel, M.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Käsbohrer, A.; Bisenius, S.; Fuchs, J.; Horlacher, S.; Lingstädt, H.; Mauermann, U.; Mitro, S.; Müller, M.; Rohrmann, S.; Schiffmann, A. P.; Stührenberg, B.; Zimmermann, P.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Irrgang, A.

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JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance and Drug Usage in the Human and Livestock Sector and Foodborne Antimicrobial Resistance in Six European Countries.

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JPR09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: A multi-center proposal for a fast screening tool in biosecured chicken flocks. Foodborne Campylobacter

Jeffrey Hoorfar, Ivana Koláčková, Gro S. Johannessen, Giuliano Garofolo, Francesca Marotta, Kinga Wiczorek, Jacek Osek, Mona Torp, Bjørn Spilsgberg, Camilla Sekse, Natasia Rebekka Thornval, Renáta Karpíšková

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Calvez V, Grandmont C, Lochérbach E, Poignard C, Ribot M, Vauchelet N, eds. *ESAIM: ProcS.* 2020;67:261-284.

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Rebollada-Merino A, Ugarte-Ruiz M, Hernández M, et al.

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Santucci C, Bonelli P, Peruzzi A, et al.
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JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE: Species Detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* Complex by Novel Probe-Based Real-Time PCRs.
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Pathogens. 2020;9(10):791. doi:10.3390/pathogens9100791
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Belkessa S, Thomas-Lopez D, Houali K, Ghalmi F, Stensvold CR.
Microorganisms. 2020;9(1):54. doi:10.3390/microorganisms9010054
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JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Veterinary Students Have a Higher Risk of Contracting Cryptosporidiosis when Calves with High Fecal *Cryptosporidium* Loads Are Used for Fetotomy Exercises. Schaffner DW, ed. Thomas-Lopez D, Müller L, Vestergaard LS, et al.
Appl Environ Microbiol. 2020;86(19):e01250-20, /aem/86/19/AEM.01250-20.atom.
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<https://zenodo.org/record/4129990#.X6PX8WhKjcc>

JRP21-FBZSH9-BEONE: Prediction of antimicrobial resistance in clinical *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates

from whole-genome sequencing data.

Dahl LG, Joensen KG, Østerlund MT, Kiil K, Nielsen EM.

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JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: *Fluorescent Bead-Based Serological Detection of Toxoplasma Gondii Infection in Chickens*.

Fabian BT, Hedar F, Koethe M, et al.

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Klein S, Stern D, Seeber F.

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JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Isolation, Genotyping, and Mouse Virulence Characterization of *Toxoplasma Gondii* From Free Ranging Iberian Pigs.

Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Regidor-Cerrillo, J.; Vallejo, R.; Benavides, J.; Collantes-Fernández, E.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.

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2021 - 48 publications

In 2021, 47 manuscripts were published by the JRP (17 by the first round JRP and 30 by the second round JRP). The manuscripts are mentioned below (authors, title, DOI and repository link). A list of all the One Health EJP manuscripts published since 2018 is available on the One Health EJP website:

<https://onehealthjep.eu/publications/>.

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Co-Occurrence of the *Bla* VIM-1 and *Bla* SHV-12 Genes on an *IncHI2* Plasmid of an *Escherichia Coli* Isolate Recovered from German Livestock.

Pauly, N.; Hammerl, J. A.; Schwarz, S.; Grobbel, M.; Meemken, D.; Malorny, B.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Käsbohrer, A.; Irrgang, A.

Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy 2021, *76* (2), 531–533.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa436>

https://zenodo.org/record/4451874#.YgU9vt_MLFU

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Isolation Procedure for CP *E. Coli* from Caeca Samples under Review towards an Increased Sensitivity.

Pauly, N.; Klaar, Y.; Skladnikiewicz-Ziemer, T.; Juraschek, K.; Grobbel, M.; Hammerl, J. A.; Hemmers, L.; Käsbohrer, A.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Irrgang, A.

Microorganisms 2021, *9* (5), 1105.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9051105>
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JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Horsing Around: Escherichia Coli ST1250 of Equine Origin Harboring Epidemic IncHI1/ST9 Plasmid with Bla CTX-M-1 and an Operon for Short-Chain Fructooligosaccharide Metabolism.

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5.1.4 Details of the JRPs activity reported in 9M reports

5.1.4.1 JRP12-R2-AMRSH5-FARMED

5.1.4.1.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Unfortunately, the COVID-19 situation in Europe delayed the FARMED project, as many institutes have had restricted access to their laboratories for non-essential research work. The majority of the

FARMED project is based on wet laboratory work; therefore, the lockdowns or limited laboratories access has impacted this project. Despite this we have had some progress to the FARMED objectives.

FARMED aims to assess the feasibility of long-read sequencing to rapidly characterise the metagenome and resistome of samples, on-site, to provide investigators with the correct information to apply the most appropriate control measures.

This year has seen FARMED institutes test and develop lab-based DNA extraction methods. Three lab DNA extraction, commercially available methods have been selected and used by FARMED institutes on both 'simple' and 'complex' matrices, resulting in enough DNA for long read metagenomics (WP1). To aid comparisons, the same commercially available defined community has been used by all institutes. Further work is still required to optimise as well as automate the DNA sequence analysis methods, such that the analysis can be performed on 'basic' computers by non-bioinformaticians (WP2). Analysis has also included determining the relevant cut offs to ensure 'proper' interpretation of long-read metagenomics data.

Instruments capable of on-site DNA extractions have been trialled in the lab as well as field, for their suitability to produce DNA of sufficient quantity and quality for DNA sequencing. The release of the new version of the VolTRAX V2b was delayed by ONT and its availability was limited. However, two institutes have received it, one has already implemented the VolTRAX V2b for on-site metagenomics with some success. Preliminary analysis using on-site DNA extractions instruments has yielded DNA for single isolates suitable for long read sequencing as well as variable success for long-read metagenomics but current optimisation is underway to achieve the appropriate quality of metagenomic DNA (WP3).

5.1.4.1.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1 - Assess feasibility of Long-read metagenome sequencing on exemplar matrices. Investigate the use of Hi-C metagenomics.

WP1-T1-Assess feasibility /perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'defined' microbial community.

This task was finalized and reported in Y4-M12.

WP1-T2- Assess feasibility /perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'simple' sample matrices.

ISS decided to analyse sprout spent irrigation water, because it is one of the matrices mentioned in Reg. (EU) 209/2013, laying down microbiological criteria for testing the contamination of sprouts with Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*. Tests have been performed extracting DNA with Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit (Zymo Research) initially following the protocol and starting from 200 ul of sample, which did not produce appropriate yield (total 11 ng of DNA extracted). The use of a filtration step was excluded, due to the viscosity of the matrix. Concentration of different amount of water was then attempted and finally good results were obtained when concentrating 200 ml of water, obtaining total 1560 ng (52 ng/ul), sufficient for MinION sequencing. Samples (GMS and sprout spent irrigation water spiked with GMS) were sequenced with Native barcoding genomic kit, Mk1B flowcell in a single sequencing run lasting 21h 21m. Details of the sequencing results will be discussed in WP2-T1.

At UCM river water was used as 'simple' matrix. 800 ml of river water were filtered through a 0.22. µm pore and resuspended in 200 µl of PBS. DNA was extracted with Quick DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit (Zymo Research) with a few modifications of the manufacturers protocol from two different samples: a Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS) (Zymo Research) spiked in PBS and GMS spiked in river sample. DNA yields were enough for Oxford Nanopore Minlon sequencing (1320 ng GMS sample and 2760 ng for GMS+River water). Both samples were barcoded and sequenced in the same flowcell (R9.4.1) using the Native barcoding genomic DNA protocol in a 48 hours run. Sequencing run did not produce a high number of reads due to very low number of pores sequencing, most likely caused by the high amount of contaminants present in the river sample. Details of the sequencing results will be discussed in WP2-T1.

WP1-T3- Assess feasibility/perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'complex' sample matrices.

Sciensano performed shotgun metagenomics experiments using chicken faeces as 'complex' sample matrix. A Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS) from ZymoResearch was spiked either in PBS (PURE sample) or in chicken faeces (SPIKED sample). Chicken faeces were also analysed unspiked (BLANK sample) to have an idea of the natural microflora. DNA was extracted from the 3 samples (PURE, SPIKED and BLANK) using the Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit from ZymoResearch (selected in WP1-T1), and yielded enough (1.6 - 5.6 µg) of pure long fragment DNA (30 - 60 kb) was obtained, meeting the requirement for Nanopore sequencing with the ligation prep (min 1 µg). Therefore, the samples were sequenced with Nanopore (one sample per flowcell) as well as with Illumina (one sample per run) for comparison purpose. Except for the PURE sample for which a new DNA extraction was needed, the same samples were also used for multiplex Nanopore sequencing with 3 samples in one flowcell. All sequencing runs produced high amount of genomic data suitable for bioinformatics analysis (see WP2.T1). Nevertheless, it can be noticed that few bases (12.3%) were lost because not properly demultiplexed (unclassified or misclassified) by Guppy with the Nanopore multiplexed run.

In addition, Sciensano has investigated the use of metagenomics to characterize genetically modified microorganisms in food enzyme samples. By combining short- and long-read metagenomic sequencing, several *Bacillus* contaminations were detected in multiple food enzyme samples: *B. velezensis*, *B. licheniformis* and *B. amyloliquefaciens*; of which the latter two constitute unviable organisms that could not be cultivated. Furthermore, the three transgenic constructs could be fully characterized. Lastly, these contaminations were carrying a considerable load of antimicrobial resistance genes, representing a potential public health risk. These results are currently being written up for peer-review publication.

IZSAM spiked GMS into "bootsocks" which are socks worn on outside of shoe to collect faeces from the floor area. DNA was extracted by Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit from ZymoResearch from three samples: pure GMS, bootsocks spiked with GMS, and unspiked bootsocks as a blank. Good yield (> 1 µg DNA /50 µl) and DNA integrity (fragment length 25 Kb; DIN 8.3) were obtained for pure GMS. Higher length (50 Kb) was obtained for bootsocks, both spiked and unspiked, despite DNA recovery was lower. DNA from pure GMS and bootsocks were sequenced by MinION using ligation kit and Native barcoding exp 1-12 following the native barcoding genomic DNA protocol on a R9.4.1 flowcell in a single multiplex sequencing run for 72h. The critical point was the length of time to perform the high accuracy basecalling (more than 10 days). Details of the sequencing results will be discussed in WP2-T1.

At BfR, to test the feasibility of long-read metagenomics for pathogen detection and AMR-gene assignment, two artificial bacterial communities consisting of six or seven different bacteria, respectively, was constructed at the BfR. The constituent strains, *Bacillus subtilis* (n=1), *Salmonella enterica* (n=1 or n=2), *Escherichia coli* (n=1), *Vibrio cholera* (n=1) and *Staphylococcus epidermis* (n=1) exhibit different antimicrobial resistance (AMR) profiles. This community was inoculated onto a complex matrix resulting in final concentrations ranging from 10¹-10⁶ CFU/g.

Before inoculation, we investigated the suitability of different complex matrix samples such as pig and cow faeces as well as food products (edible insects and tahini) for the inoculation with the artificial bacterial community. For this purpose, DNA was extracted from matrices and applied for shallow short-read metagenomics sequencing. The resulting data was analysed bioinformatically using kma and kraken2 for the detection of AMR genes and the taxonomic profile of the matrices. To avoid interference of the matrix signals with the signals from the inoculated artificial community, a matrix with a minimum of sequencing reads from species and AMR genes present in the artificial community was selected. While all the matrices contained sequencing reads for the respective species of the artificial community, the faeces samples contain very few reads (<0,02% reads/total reads) that are classified as species of interest. Thus, the pig faeces was selected for inoculation since it contains only one of the AMR genes (*tet(L)*) and was available in sufficient quantity.

Total DNA from the inoculated samples will be sequenced using the MinION. The analysis will reveal to what extent AMR genes and species can be linked with long-read technology and if strains from different *Salmonella* species can be separated. Due to the inoculation of different concentrations, the limit of detection for AMR association, species and strain identification will be investigated.

Based on further evaluation of the sequencing results from the different matrices, insect food products were chosen as an example for real-life samples. We selected three different insect food samples for sequencing with Illumina short-read and ONT long-read technology. From the selected samples, different *Salmonella enterica* and *Bacillus* strains could be isolated. A detailed comparison between the results from WGS of the isolates and metagenomics sequencing of the total samples is planned for both sequencing technologies. Therefore, the assignability of AMR genes to species and the differentiation of strains from the same species/genus will be investigated.

SSI have performed MinION sequencing (4 samples per flow cell) on 2 different clinical faecal samples, with and without spiked-in ZymoBIOMICS GMS, DNA extracted with GeneFind V3 with 2 different lysis methods based on either bead-beating or lysozyme. For sequencing, purification the 12 samples were pooled in batches of four and prepared for sequencing on R9.4.1 flow cells using Ligation Sequencing Kit 1D (SQK-LSK109, Oxford Nanopore Technologies) and Native Barcoding Kit 1D (EXP-NBD104, Oxford Nanopore Technologies). Data processing are described in WP2-T1. Preliminary data has shown that read lengths were longer in samples extracted by bead-beating compared to lysozyme (no statistical analysis yet). Ongoing analyses are focusing on quality scores, species identification and statistics of the different sample preparations.

WP1-T4- Perform Hi-C metagenomics

At the BfR an artificial community (MC, mock community) consisting of four different species with known ARG profile, as well as known genome and plasmid sequences was constructed from single isolates. A shotgun library and Hi-C libraries in duplicates with two different versions of the commercially available Proximo Hi-C (Microbe) Kit (Phase Genomics Inc, USA) were prepared and paired-end sequenced using the NexSeq 500 system (Illumina, USA). The resulting data were analyzed with two different pipelines – the commercially available ProxiMeta pipeline and our own developed pipeline called Hiccap. The latter relies on a mapping-based approach and uses only the Hi-C dataset together with a species and AMR database. In summary, with both pipelines it was possible to link most of the AMR genes specifically to the species of the artificial community. The sensitivity and specificity of the Hiccap analysis can be adjusted by using different threshold parameters such as the selection of references genomes in the species databases and the AMR gene coverage threshold. A deliverable that reports on the feasibility of the method with detailed results of the study is being drafted.

Because artificial communities are far from real samples concerning complexity, pathogen and AMR gene concentrations and contain high amounts of matrix signals, in the next step the method will be tested on samples from the EFFORT project. These samples are derived from an *in-vivo* experiment where the transmission of an AMR plasmid from a *Salmonella enterica* serovar Corvallis strain was investigated in the gut of chicken livestock. DNA from the collected feces samples from two different days of the experiment on which a transfer could be detected microbiologically were extracted and Hi-C and shotgun libraries were generated and sequenced using Illumina technology. The results are currently being analysed but are hampered by data transfer problems to the ProxiMeta platform of Phase Genomics Inc. due to large size of the data files and ftp server access restrictions at the BfR. In an extensive literature search for further open-source pipeline, one pipeline has been identified that will be tested for the available Hi-C datasets.

The BfR has prepared another mock community (JRP12-WP1-T3) that was shared with Sciensano and will be used for the inoculation into different matrices. The applicability of Hi-C will be compared in different laboratories with various approaches e.g., the combination of Hi-C data with long-read sequencing vs. short-read sequencing datasets and data analysis approaches. For better coordination

of the experiments, a meeting between Sciensano and BfR was organised by Sciensano and carried out in May 2022 in Brussels, Belgium.

Sciensano has received aliquots of a defined mock community made by BFR (end of May 2022). This mock community will serve as a reference to validate the Hi-C sequencing method within Sciensano and compare the results to those of BFR. Some further validation of the mock community concentrations is being performed by BFR, and once validated, Hi-C experiments will be started at Sciensano. Depending on the results, new samples will be selected for analysis, e.g., food/feed additive samples containing or spiked with genetically modified microorganisms.

WP2 - Bioinformatics tools to analyse the sequencing data and defining the characteristics within the sample.

WP2-T1- Development/adaptation of a pipeline that can predict species within sample/matrix

Sciensano analysed the sequencing data generated from the different experiments with the BLANK, PURE and SPIKED sample (see Task WP1-T3), using KMA and the Custom-2 parameters (see 12M-Report-Y4). For this, different databases were used:

- gmstd_db: a database containing only the genomes of the different bacterial strains present in the GMS and provided by ZymoResearch
- gmstdFP_db: the same database as gmstd_db but containing in addition 60 genomes belonging to closely related species that could potentially be detected as false positives.
- DTU_db: the database previously used for KMA analyses of the DMC samples. This database contains only complete reference genomes.
- newDTU_db: a new extended database provided by DTU and containing a mix of complete genomes and contig/scaffold sequences.

When analysing the PURE sample with the gmstd_db, all the species with relative abundance 1.5% or above could be correctly detected with high depth, template identity and template coverage. Using the 2 DTU databases, some species were less correctly detected (*Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and *Fusobacterium nucleatum*). Finally, few false positive identifications were obtained when analysing the PURE sample with the gmstd_db and newDTU_db. The depth, template identity and template coverage values generated by KMA for each true positive and false positive species were compared in order to define detection threshold for species identifications. As with the Custom-2 parameters a lot of data is retrieved by KMA, the determination of detection criteria with confidence level was needed for proper interpretation. Therefore, 9 different levels of detection were proposed by Sciensano to help for data analysis. Using these detection criteria, various results were obtained depending on the used databases: the newDTU_db allowed a more sensitive detection of low abundant species but more false positive results were also obtained. Moreover, the interpretation of the results was less straightforward with the newDTU_db in comparison with the former DTU_db. These differences come from the composition of the 2 databases (complete genomes for DTU_db vs. complete genome + contig/scaffold sequence for newDTU_db) and highlight the importance of having a curated database adapted to the aim of the analysis: listing as much species as possible or detecting key pathogens.

In the SPIKED sample, some species were detected with a lower level of confidence than in the PURE sample, showing a possible effect of the matrix, that needs to be investigated in more details.

Comparison with the data obtained with samples sequenced by Illumina and Nanopore triplex is ongoing. Preliminary results showed that the coverage is higher for Nanopore singleplex compared to Illumina, which has a coverage itself higher than that obtained with Nanopore triplex. An adaptation of the detection criteria (elaborated above) was proposed to compensate the decrease in coverage when multiplexing.

At ISS, a low number of reads was obtained: 5,942 reads from clean GMS and 6,946 reads from spiked water were obtained, for 58.8 Mb and 62.7 Mb totally sequenced, respectively (Read length N50 were 18,637 bp and 22,825 bp, respectively). The data were analysed on ARIES, a webserver developed at ISS for NGS data analysis. The reads were trimmed with Porechop with default parameters and then mapped with KMA tool against a precompiled database of bacterial sequences (<ftp://ftp.cbs.dtu.dk/public/CGE/databases/KmerFinder/20200420>). Despite the low number of reads, the results showed that the sequence obtained from the pure GMS sample contained all the expected species present in the original sample with relative abundance higher than 1.5%. In the sequence obtained from the water sample spiked with GMS, only the species present in the pure GMS sample with relative abundance higher than 6% could be retrieved.

The Porechop and KMA tools were made available through ARIES web platform, curated at ISS, counting about 200 users worldwide. The subscription for using ARIES is free, granting easy access to bioinformatics pipelines to users without large experience in bioinformatics analysis.

At IZSAM, the total throughput obtained after 72h sequencing was 18.7 Gb, after filtering 17.1 Gb. The majority of them were obtained by the pure GMS (11 Gb), while only 3.3 Gb by the spiked bootsock and 2.8 Gb the blank bootsock. Discrepancies on the number of reads and the N50 reflects these unbalanced results from the different barcodes according to the input DNA. Only pure GMS and spiked bootsocks were analysed through KMA using the proposed parameters. Apart from the species *Veillonella rogosae*, *Prevotella corporis*, *Methanobrevibacter smithii*, *Candida albicans* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* not present in the old database, all the other GMS species were identified in both samples.

At SSI, data was processed with a minimum quality score set to 9 and the resulting reads were demultiplexed and basecalled using Guppy (v.5.0.11) with config file: dna_r9.4.1_450bps_sup.cfg. To exclude human contamination the k-mer alignment tool (KMA) (Clausen, P.T.L.C., Aarestrup, F.M. & Lund, O. Rapid and precise alignment of raw reads against redundant databases with KMA. BMC Bioinformatics 19, 307 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-018-2336-6>) was used to map reads against the human reference genome (GRCh38). All reads that mapped to human reference genome were discarded.

Read length distribution was calculated from the dehumanized fastq files using NanoPlot (Wouter De Coster, Sven D'Hert, Darrin T Schultz, Marc Cruys, Christine Van Broeckhoven, NanoPack: visualizing and processing long-read sequencing data, Bioinformatics, Volume 34, Issue 15, 01 August 2018, Pages 2666–2669, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty149>). Using KMA the remaining reads were mapped directly against databases with bacteria, fungi, archaea, and viruses. Only organisms with a depth above 0.1 and constituting more than 0.01% of the total organisms found were included in the analysis and R-packages tidyverse and ggplot2 were used to analyse and visualize all results.

At UCM, due to a problem with the contaminants present in the river water sample, low number of reads were retrieved from the multiplexed sequencing run (54798 reads in total). Reads were demultiplexed using porechop (v0.2.4 –barcode threshold 60 –barcode_diff 1) and filtered with filtlong (v0.2.1 –min_length 500 –min_mean_q 80) to keep only reads with a minimum of 500 bp and a quality score higher than 7. In the end, we worked with 11764 reads from GMS sample and 8703 reads from GMS+River water sample. Reads were mapped using KMA tool against a bacteria database (bacteria_DTU_db). Due to the low number of reads, only species with a relative abundance in the GMS equal or higher than 0.01% were detected in the GMS sample, whereas in the spiked river sample only species with a relative abundance equal or higher than 1.5% were detected. In addition, the number of reads classified as species where considerably lower (more than 1 log difference) in the GMS+river water sample in comparison to GMS alone sample.

WP2-T2- Development/adaptation of a Resfinder-'like' pipeline for identification of AMR for long-read sequences

Using KMA and Resfinder as database, Sciensano was able to detect, for the PURE and SPIKED samples analysed with Nanopore singleplex, all the AMR genes except 2 of them belonging to low abundant species. Only for the most abundant species present at 14%, all the AMR genes could be linked to their carrying species. Comparison is on-going with the samples sequenced with Illumina and Nanopore triplex.

Also, for the genetically modified microorganisms in the food enzymes samples, the AMR genes could be linked to their host chromosome or plasmid.

WP2-T3- Benchmarking of tools with spiked samples in WP2

This task is delayed until a KMA method can be established.

WP2-T4- Test protocols on site

This task is delayed until an analysis workflow is established (WP3).

DTU has tested the on-site sequencing and data analyses pipeline in the field (as preliminary trials) in February and March 2022. Samples from soil and faeces, with an addition of single bacterial isolate from a hospital, were collected in fields. DNA extractions were done using Quick-DNA HMW MagBead Kit (D6060, Zymo Research) on BentoLab device for DNA extraction and library preparation (<https://bento.bio/devices/>) with external portable power supply. Libraries were prepared using two protocols: Rapid Sequencing Kit SQK-RAD004 on BentoLab, and VolTRAX V2B with VolTRAX Sequencing Kit VSK-VSK004. All raw outputs (Fast5) were basecalled using an in-house built GPU-based laptop with Guppy-basecaller pipeline and high accuracy basecalling option. All resulted Fastq files were fed into KMA (after previous KMA performance assessment in WP2-T1, T2 and T3 in previous reports) for bacterial taxa and AMR identifications. From the faecal sample, approximately 65000 reads were assigned to 275 bacterial species and 12 AMR genes. As a control, *Staphylococcus aureus* bacterium was added to the faecal sample (100 µl of 10⁸ cells/mL) and *S. aureus* species was one of the abundant bacterial taxa in the microbiome analyses from the tested faeces.

DTU is planning another field trip in a pig farm in Denmark in July/August for another on-site microbiome analyses using Oxford Nanopore sequencing.

WBVR is currently planning a demonstration of on-site sequencing at the AERES agricultural school dairy farm in the Netherlands. Nanopore sequencing is planned to be used in the analysis of high versus low cell count milk, to be used as a fast-screening method for mastitis diagnostics, in comparison with further methods.

WP3 - Implementation of on-site protocols for long-read metagenomic DNA sequencing

WP3-T1- Literature search & Harmonisation of on-site DNA isolation : COMPLETE

The literature report on DNA extraction was finalised and uploaded Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724557>.

WP3-T2- Investigation of on-site equipment for DNA extraction and sequencing (original title: Investigate the use of Voltrax)

Sciensano performed initial tests with the VolTRAX V2 for automated, on-site library preparation. However, after an initial control run with phage Lambda DNA, the voltrax device failed to create other libraries. Several tests with different batches of reagents were performed, but the issue could not be alleviated. An update to the VolTRAX V2 device, the VolTRAX V2b, has since become available, and has been recently received (end of May 2022). The new VolTRAX device has to be assessed. As an alternative for on-site library preparation, the rapid sequencing kit is being tested, as it is a fast protocol requiring relatively few specialised equipment. Furthermore, a field-version of the rapid kit

exists, containing lyophilized reagents that allow for storage at room temperature. Initial tests on the same DNA extract indicate that the rapid kit results in slightly lower sequencing yields when compared to the ligation sequencing kit. Additionally, the Bento lab has been acquired, for further testing.

APHA have been working with the PDQeX to extract DNA from pig and cattle faecal samples. Following several iterations of faecal DNA extraction, a methodology has been developed that gives consistent DNA concentrations, which included heating the samples to 40°C for 10 minutes prior to commencing the DNA extraction. However, as the concentration for one extraction does not yield enough DNA for the rapid barcoding kit, the sample had to be extracted four times and pooled. It was also found that the eluted DNA from PDQeX extractions was too 'dirty' to be used for nanopore sequencing as the flow cells were noted to lose sequencing pores and become unable to sequence the DNA samples. A clean up method was derived utilising 2 types of magnetic beads in a 1:1 ratio with the volume of eluted DNA following the precipitation of DNA to maximise the recovered yield. After magnetic bead clean up, DNA was suitably clean to be processed through a flow cell and produce DNA sequences that could be used to determine the bacterial species and AMR genes within the faecal samples. Following this procedure, we have been able to detect and associate several AMR genes with bacterial species and plasmids in both pig and cattle faecal samples. This is currently the topic of a research paper in draft. The next stage is to carry this methodology out on faecal samples on-site. APHA currently awaiting to receive the VolTRAX V2b to enable onsite library prep for long read sequencing.

WBVR also experimented with the use of the PDQeX machine and the use of a hydrophilic ionic liquid isolation protocol (Martyz et al, 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-50246-5>) for on-site sequencing of organisms in faeces and milk. The ionic liquid method proved only suitable for extraction of spiked DNA from milk when LAMP (loop-mediated isothermal amplification) was used as a read-out parameter, but DNA quantity was much too low for Nanopore sequencing. The DNA quantity of the PDQeX from milk was sufficient for sequencing.

WBVR has tested the VolTRAX V2 but issues were perceived in the robustness of the runs. Several sample preparatory runs, using high quality DNA from the Purelink commercial kit, failed due unknown circumstances. In August, the VolTRAX V2b upgrade was received which will be used to assess if this issue is still perceived.

WP3-T3- Assess DNA isolation methods for suitability, test on matrices (faeces, blood, dust, (environmental), milk)

Currently, Sciensano has performed initial tests with the Claremont Bio DNAexpress kit on pure ZymoResearch GMS, and on chicken faecal samples spiked with the GMS. The kit uses a bead-beating based lysis step followed by DNA purification on a silica column. DNA extracts obtained with the kit contained enough DNA for Nanopore sequencing. However, the DNA was heavily fragmented and highly impure. Further purification increased DNA purity and removed a significant part of the most degraded DNA. However, purity remained insufficient, resulting in rapid blocking of pores during subsequent nanopore sequencing. Inclusion of new purification and wash steps will be tested to address these issues.

Interestingly, when comparing sequencing data from the Claremont Bio DNAexpress method with the data from the Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit, the latter seems to introduce more bias against certain Gram positive bacterial species. However, the Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit provides significantly longer read sizes. Going forward, the impact of the biases and differences in read sizes between the methods on linking AMR to species will be assessed.

IZSAM compared DNA extraction of pure GMS, bootsocks spiked with GMS, and unspiked bootsocks using both Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit from ZymoResearch and the E.Z.N.A.® Stool DNA Kit (Omega Bio-tek). The last mentioned failed in producing sufficient DNA from bootsocks which are the main sample matrix tested at IZSAM, conversely it allowed rapid and reliable isolation of high-quality total DNA from stool samples: 5.4 µg and 3.4 µg in a total of 100 µl for stool samples with and without GMS, respectively, and a mean of fragment length 10 Kb.

APHA have been working with frozen (-80°C) faecal material from pigs and cattle, using the PDQeX extraction system, followed by MinION sequencing or illumine sequencing. MinION sequencing (rapid library prep) produced a greater percentage of the genome coverage and mean species identity for selected pathogens found within faecal sample. Interestingly however, the frequency of species identified was greater in illumina compared MinION nanopore. Also, MinION offered the opportunity to link AMR genes to bacterial species as well as plasmids previously isolated from the same faecal samples.

Sequencing of spiked milk samples from which DNA was extracted using the PDQeX machine was technically feasible using the Rapid sequencing kit. Downstream analysis is ongoing for detection of AMR-genes of the spiked isolates, but the species were identified from these samples as expected. Sequencing of clinical mastitis samples is planned in Q4 of 2022 at WVBR.

The EU monitoring for AMR makes use of faeces samples for detection of diverse species. At WBVR, 6 faecal samples from the EU monitoring were compared, two each from broiler chickens, veal calves and slaughter pigs. DNA was prepared using the Purelink isolation method and sequenced with the ligation protocol, although preparation of the same sample set using the PDQeX isolation and the VolTRAX V2b is still planned. While *E. coli* was detected in all 6 samples, selective culturing detected ESBL-producing *E. coli* in 3 samples, which were not detected using sequencing. *Campylobacter* spp. were detected by culturing in five of the sampled while this species was detected in four of the sequenced datasets. MRSA was detected by culturing in two samples, while *S. aureus* was detected by sequencing in three datasets. However, the *mecA* gene was not detected in these datasets. Further analysis of the AMR phenotypes will be performed when MIC data becomes available for the isolated bacteria.

WP3-T4- Test protocol on site

This task has not started for all partners as we still do not yet have a suitable on-site DNA extraction and sequencing workflow. DTU have started to conduct on-site DNA extraction and long read sequencing, using the Quick-DNA HMW MagBead Kit on BentoLab device (<https://bento.bio/devices/>) with external portable power supply. In DTU first trials, two faecal samples from pigs were mixed with known concentrations of *Staphylococcus aureus* as control in the field (in a farm). High molecular weight DNA was extracted entirely in the field using the mentioned kit and BentoLab device for all the needed steps in the DNA extraction (centrifugation and heating). The DNA yield was used for Oxford Nanopore rapid library preparation (SQK-RAD004) also using BentoLab device for all the required steps in the library preparation. Finally, the library was loaded into R9.4 flowcell and AMR and bacterial detection analyses were done 2 hours after the sequencing had started on special in-house built GPU-based laptop. The entire process was carried out over 7 hours period (4,5 hrs for sampling, DNA extraction, library preparation and library loading and approximately 2,5 hours initial sequencing and rapid analyses).

WP4 - Project management, coordination, and training workshop.

WP4-T1- Annual physical project meetings

The FARMED consortium has not yet been able to gather in person since the start of the project, as soon after, the COVID-19 pandemic started. DTU, SSI and APHA are currently organising a FARMED physical meeting at DTU, Denmark between from the 20th to the 22nd of September 2022.

WP4-T2- Teleconferences will be organised every 3 months, between partners

The FARMED consortium has held teleconferences to discuss project progress and share experiences and results.

- In December 2021 and January 2022, the parameters of the KMA analysis were discussed based on the experience of SSI (APHA, Sciensano, SSI).

- In January 2022, the experiment on the Hi-C sequencing were discussed amongst the involved partners (BfR, Sciensano).

WP4-T3- Training dissemination of developed protocols

DTU, SSI and APHA are organising FARMED physical meeting at DTU, Denmark between from the 20th to the 22nd of September 2022. However, due the COVID-19 pandemic and the travel restrictions imposed by institutes, the need for a wet lab workshop is no longer needed. Instead, this meeting will be used to provide updates and discuss finalising the project as well as institute experience on long read metagenomics.

WP4-T4- Annual reports

The Y3 2021 annual report was submitted to OHEJP in January 2022.

5.1.4.1.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

Impact of COVID-19 on FARMED consortium partners

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a major effect on many of the FARMED consortium, which had delayed progress of the project.

- For many months (up to 2 years), some countries were in lockdown or had restricted access to the laboratories to only undertake essential activities, including some scientist involved in COVID activities. For most, all research activities, including the OHEJP projects were considered as non-essential and could not be continued, i.e. no activity in the R&D labs was allowed. This particularly had a big impact and the majority of FARMED involves laboratory based method optimisation.
- The national lockdowns delayed recruitment of staff or students to deliver FARMED objectives, with many new staff / students not in post until summer 2020. For some staff they had to contribute to the COVID-19 related activities.
- Research activities were able to start in summer 2020, however, homework remained the rule, and social distancing needed to be assured, meaning only a limited number of people can work in the R&D labs. In winter 2020/21, COVID-19 cases were increasing and national lockdowns were re-introduced.
- There has been limited availability, in many countries, of various consumables (such as pipette tips) and scientific kits (such as WGS kits), due to the these items being diverted to COVID-19 testing activities. There have also been delays in receiving both hardware and consumables from Oxford Nanopore sequencing on which this project is dependent on, which has added to the delays for some institutes.

As such all the milestones and deliverable have been delayed, and will require additional time to complete.

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
12	D-JRP12-1.1	Report on an initial assessment of long-read	M53		M56	Delayed due to the optimisation of analysis methods.	8 (Method application)

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
		sequencing for metagenome (community and AMR) analysis (defined community, spiked and real simple and complex matrices) and comparison to current short-read standard.					
12	D-JRP12-1.2	Report on the feasibility of using Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.	M52		M58	Delayed as one institute has been delayed in their analysis for this report.	8 (Method application)
12	D-JRP12-3.2	Protocol for use of Voltrax on-site for extraction and library preparation from clinical, veterinary and environmental samples, suitable for long-read metagenome sequencing.	M56		M57	Additional time is needed for methods to be optimised for on-site long read metagenomics, by multiple institutes.	2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice
12	D-JRP12-WP3.5	Report on initial findings of on-site diagnostic tests and IT solutions for human clinical, veterinary and environmental samples for early	M60			Not due yet.	3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		warning of emerging resistant pathogens.					
12	D-JRP12-4.1	Annual communication to stakeholders and OH EJP coordinators	M48, M60			Y4 annual report was submitted in January 2022.	8 (Sharing and communication for application of methods)

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

5.1.4.1.3.1 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
A shotgun metagenomics approach to detect and characterize unauthorized genetically modified microorganisms in microbial fermentation products https://zenodo.org/record/5347021#.YS-ksY4zaM8 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochms.2021.10002 Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences	Yes, partial	No	Yes, (0 euros)

Additional output

- Poster presentation: Gand Mathieu* (Sciensano), Buytaers Florence* (Sciensano), Bloemen Bram (Sciensano), Saltykova Assia (Sciensano), Denayer Sarah (Sciensano), Verhaegen Bavo (Sciensano), Mattheus Wesley (Sciensano), Piérard Denis (UZBrussels), Bogaerts Bert (Sciensano), Marchal Kathleen (UGhent), **the FARMED consortium (One Health European Joint Programme)**, Roosens Nancy (Sciensano), Vanneste Kevin (Sciensano), De Keersmaecker Sigrid C.J. (Sciensano) (* equal contribution). Shotgun metagenomics as a ONE Health tool for better protecting human health. ONE Conference 2022 (organized by EFSA). Brussels, Belgium. 21-24/06/2022.
- Poster presentation: Indre Navickaite, Thomas Wilkes, Manal AbuOun (APHA). FARMED: Long-read metagenomic sequencing. One Health EJP Annual scientific meeting April 2022.
- Poster presentation: Josephine Grützke, Jens-Andre Hammerl, Jennie Fischer, Lee Julia Bartsch, Burkhard Malorny and Carlus Deneke (BfR). Application of proximity ligation to link antibiotic resistance genes and species using metagenomics. 32nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases. Lisbon, Portugal. April 23-26 2022.
- Oral Presentation: Bosco R. Matamoros, Carlos Serna, Gabriel Moyano, Emilia Wedel, Natalia Montero, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn. Metagenomic sequencing analysis of the effects of apramycin on the poultry gut microbiome. One Health EJP Annual scientific meeting April 2022.
- Poster presentation: Bosco R. Matamoros, Carlos Serna, Gabriel Moyano, Emilia Wedel, Mario Pulido-Vadillo, Natalia Montero, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn. Metagenomic analysis reveals that apramycin use restructures the resistome and favours interbacterial spread of *aac(3)-IV* gene.
- Oral Presentation: Saria Otani. Antimicrobial Resistance and Bacterial Pathogen detections in Microbiomes. Ministry of Food and Agriculture in Denmark. June 2022
- Poster presentation: Quillan Dijkstra, Arie Kant, Teresita de Jesus Bello Gonzalez, Frank Harders, Kees Veldman, Michael Brouwer (WBVR) Implementation of Multi-Locus Sequence Typing based on Nanopore Single Molecule Real-Time sequencing. KNVM Spring meeting The Netherlands, April 2022.

5.1.4.1.4 [Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations \(e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO\), networks, or national ministries](#)

Presentation of poster (see above) at conference organized or attended by EFSA.

Several members of the FARMED consortium are involved in other OHEJP projects. In particular the Full-Force JRP is relevant as the project is utilising long-read sequencing to characterise mobile genetic elements which are associated with driving AMR in commensal and pathogenic Enterobacteriaceae.

Valeria Michelacci (ISS), working at the European Union Reference Laboratory (EURL) for E. coli at ISS, is involved in the activities of the steering committee for the development of a joint EFSA-ECDC database for molecular typing data collection, which started working in 2011 on PFGE and MLVA data but is now moving to WGS data collection. The three pathogens object of the surveillance at present are *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* and Shiga toxin-producing E. coli, that's why these three EURLs are involved. Moreover, since 2017 EURL E. coli on a mandate of the European Commission is coordinating the activities of an Inter EURLs working group on Next Generation Sequencing, involving the following EURLs: E. coli, *Listeria*, *Staphylococcus* (CPS), *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, Parasites, Antimicrobial resistance, and foodborne viruses. The aim is to promote the use of NGS across the EURLs' networks of National Reference Laboratories, build NGS capacity within the EU and ensure liaison between the work of the EURLs and the work of EFSA and ECDC on the NGS mandate sent by the Commission. The working group is meeting twice a year (online since 2020).

Deliverables produced by now consist in guidelines for the different steps of NGS data production and analysis, information on reference NGS datasets, trainings modules and proficiency test schemes available for NGS. It has never dealt with metagenomics, yet, but it is among the interests of the Working Group for the future. The presence of Valeria Michelacci, among partners of FARMED, in this Working Group will ensure proper exchange of information about the outcomes of the projects and metagenomics-related documents eventually produced in the working group. EFSA and ECDC are observers of the activities of the group.

DTU is a EURL laboratory as well as being certified WHO laboratory.

Sciensano, as NRL-GMO and also part of the European ENGL (European Network of GMO Laboratories), has contacts with the competent authorities at national (FAVV/AFSCA) and EU level, regarding the notification of the presence of GMM in microbial fermentation products. Sciensano is also member of the ENGL working group on "Sequencing strategies for the traceability of GMOs - methods and related quality aspects" and of the ENGL working group on "Detection of genetically modified microorganisms in food and feed", where the use of metagenomics for the identification and characterization of GMM in food/feed is being discussed.

5.1.4.2 JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM

5.1.4.2.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The One Health EJP WorldCOM project aims to develop diagnostic tools linked with mobile referencing technology for detection of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in zoonotic pathogens. Resulting technologies will enable rapid on-site detection of AMR in pathogens from animal and human populations, facilitating early investigation of emerging resistances and development of machine-learning algorithms for AMR prediction. Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) and carbapenemase enzymes produced by Enterobacteriaceae confer resistance to beta-lactam antimicrobials presenting a major public health concern. Relevant biomarker genes associated with highly prevalent ESBLs (CTX-M) and carbapenemases (OXA, KPC and NDM) were selected as AMR targets for diagnostic assay development.

UoS submitted a manuscript summarising AMR LAMP assays and the detection of AMR markers from environmental water samples for peer-review. UoS has also developed an assay targeting *mcr-9*, which will be further validated. Additionally, approximately 200 ESBL *E. coli* isolates from human urinary tract infections were received and are currently being processed for whole genome sequencing. Additionally, two machine-learning models have been developed to provide automated detection for LAMP diagnostic tests: resulting in high test accuracy for the fluorescence-based data, and promising, preliminary results for the colorimetric data. A smartphone app has been developed to automatically analyse captured images of colorimetric LAMP assays to facilitate field testing. The smartphone app has been successfully validated using AMR markers from pig faecal samples, with imaging performed outdoors mimicking conditions for future use.

At NUIG, a manuscript reporting the differential detection of CTX-M ESBL gene variants, *bla*CTX-M-1 and *bla*CTX-M-15, from *E. coli* isolates and animal faecal samples using an internally controlled LEC-LAMP assay has been submitted for publication, and is currently under peer-review. The NUIG team also successfully developed a multiplex OXA-48/181 LEC-LAMP assay by combining the previously developed singleplex OXA-48 and OXA-181 LEC-LAMP assays. Analytical specificity of this multiplex assay was established using environmental isolates, with analytical sensitivity of this assay, demonstrating single-digit genome copy detection.

At FLI, a manuscript describing the whole genome sequences of the cephalosporin-resistant isolates from alpacas and their respective β -lactamase genes used in validating the LEC-LAMP assay was submitted for peer-reviewed publication in July 2022. β -Lactamase genes from *E. coli* strains isolated

from pigs have been sequenced to confirm assay specificity and swine faecal samples collected and characterized for further validation of the CTX-M-1/-15 LEC-LAMP assay.

At UCM, NGS data of AMR *E. coli* strains from different sources have been generated. These include 110 *E. coli* from humans, 144 from pigs and 136 from broilers in which ESBL genes were identified (*bla*_{CTX-M-14} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}). NGS data of 43 *E. coli* strains of environmental origin (rivers and wastewater treatment plants) were included, in which the presence of ESBL genes (*bla*_{CTX-M-55} and *bla*_{CMY-2}) and colistin resistance genes (*mcr-1.1*) were detected. Additionally, 10 *Citrobacter werkmanii* isolates carrying NDM-1 and CTX-M-15 genes, that have been isolated from hospital wastewater, were sequenced. This work was published in February 2022.

At UT three research papers were published based on whole genome sequenced *Campylobacter* spp. and *Vibrio vulnificus* originating from food and clinical samples.

At INSA a paper reporting a colistin resistance gene was published.

5.1.4.2.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP: 1 Generation of up to date sequence information for selected pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes

JRP13-WP1-T2- Targeted and whole genome de novo sequencing of phenotypically characterised isolates from various settings

At UCM, 10 *Citrobacter werkmanii* isolates were collected from hospital wastewater samples in Tamale (Ghana). All *C. werkmanii* isolates shared a common multidrug resistance profile, showing resistance to β -lactam and carbapenems. Resistance to carbapenems was a consequence of the carbapenemase gene *bla*_{NDM-1}. They also presented ESBL genes (*bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *bla*_{CMY} and *bla*_{OXA}). NGS data from these isolates will be included in the database shared among partners. This work has been recently published in mSystems and uploaded to Zenodo repository (DOI: 0.1128/msystems.01019-21 and <https://zenodo.org/record/6619655#.Yp89wexBy58>).

At the UT, 103 *Salmonella* sp. genomes were *de novo* sequenced (Illumina) and assembled and AMR genes annotated. Long read sequencing protocol using Oxford Nanopore technology has been developed and tested for closing draft genomes successfully (using *E. coli* and MRSA isolates), results were presented on ASM 2022. Two scientific publications about *de novo* WGS of *Campylobacter* spp. has been published and one publication, genome announcement, about clinical *Vibrio vulnificus*.

Meanwhile, UCM and UT are leading creating and sharing a database draft, with the support of UoS, to develop a resource of all isolates, their resistance profile and sequences to facilitate sharing of all relevant information. This draft includes a total of 685 isolates (*E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *A. baumannii* and *C. werkmanii*) with corresponding metadata provided by WorldCOM partners. 20.4 % of the isolates (n = 140) presented CTX-M genes (predominantly CTX-M-15). Regarding the presence of carbapenemases, 13.8% of the isolates (n = 95) carried KPC-3 gene (especially *K. pneumoniae*), and 4.5% (n = 31) NDM-1 or NDM-5 gene. Options for uploading this database to a web server that would be privately accessible to WorldCOM partners are currently being evaluated.

At the UoS, approximately 200 ESBL *E. coli* isolates from human urinary tract infections were received from NHS collaborators. The isolates are currently being cultured and glycerol stocks prepared for further phenotypic characterisation and whole genome sequencing.

At FLI, 143 *E. coli* strains, resistant to 3rd generation cephalosporins and assayed with the CTX-M-1/-15 specific LEC-LAMP assay developed at NUIG, were short-read whole genome sequenced and analyzed for their β -lactamase gene sequences. Three sequences did not allow allele distinction due to incomplete gene assembly. Two LEC-LAMP negative assays were identified as non-responsive *bla*_{CTX-M-27} alleles. 87 strains were identified as encoding *bla*_{CTX-M-1}. A further 51 strains with a CTX-M-15-positive LEC-LAMP signal were classified as containing *bla*_{CTX-M-15} and 5 as containing *bla*_{CTX-M-55} confirming that

the assay does not distinguish between the SNP variants CTX-M-15 and CTX-M-55. The large number of field isolates validates the assay as specific. We additionally short-read sequenced 22 *E. coli* strains with an ESBL-phenotype that had been isolated from alpacas. Among the encoded β -lactamases, 16 encoded a CTX-M-1, two a CTX-M-15, two a CTX-M-27, one a CTX-M-65 and two a CMY-2 allele. These will be tested with the LEC-LAMP assay to further validate its specificity. Additionally, nine ceftiofur-resistant isolates, identified as *Klebsiella* via MALDI-TOF were long-read sequenced to identify their β -lactamase genes and extend the assay beyond testing *E. coli*.

This task is ongoing.

WP2: Assay Development

JRP13-WP2-T1- Development and performance evaluation of singleplex isothermal amplification assays for selected AMR gene targets

At the UoS, a *mcr-9* LAMP assay was further developed and tested to confirm specificity. The assay was tested using a *mcr-9* positive *Enterobacter ludwigii* isolate as a positive control (kindly supplied by INSA) and *mcr-1* positive *E. coli* NCTC 13846 and *Salmonella enterica serovar* Typhimurium NCTC 13952 strains as negative controls. The assay was further validated by testing different AMR gene containing Gram-negative isolates. The result demonstrated an amplification with *mcr-9 E. ludwigii* isolate within 4 minutes, while no amplification was detected with other isolates. The assay is currently being further tested using spiked and un-spiked pig faecal samples.

At NUIG, the previously developed singleplex LEC-LAMP assays for detection of OXA variants, *bla*_{OXA-48} and *bla*_{OXA-181/232}, have been successfully demonstrated using portable instrumentation testing *E. coli* environmental isolates.

JRP13-WP2-T2- Evaluation and selection of sample preparation methods for use with laboratory on-site tests

At the UoS, a water sample preparation method has been finalised as a manuscript, approved by all co-authors and submitted for peer review.

At NUIG, a rapid chelex heat lysis based sample preparation method was developed and is detailed in the above mentioned manuscript which is currently under peer review.

JRP13-WP2-T3: Development and performance evaluation of multiplex assays for pathogens and resistance genes.

At NUIG, development of a multiplex OXA 48/181 LEC-LAMP assay has been completed by combining the previously developed singleplex OXA-48 and OXA-181 LEC-LAMP assays. Analytical specificity of this multiplex assay was established using environmental isolates provided by NUIG and UoS, with analytical sensitivity of this assay, demonstrating single-digit genome copy detection, established using probit analysis. This assay will be further combined with an internal amplification control assay.

At UoS, multiplex LAMP assays were developed to rapidly detect five AMR biomarkers. LAMP primers were designed to specifically target plasmid-mediated colistin resistance (*mcr-1*), KPC-mediated carbapenem resistance (KPC), oxacillin-hydrolysing β -lactamases (OXA-48 and OXA-23 genes) and Verona Integron-encoded Metallo- β -lactamase (VIM). The work has been submitted for publication (June 2022).

WP3: Development of Lateral Flow Diagnostics Detection and Mobile Communication system

JRP13-WP3-T1- Development of lateral flow diagnostics detection

The development of lateral flow diagnostics at the UoS is now redundant due to the excellent performance of both fluorescent and colorimetric detection assays that have been developed. Therefore, we have expanded on our AMR LAMP panel instead to include an additional plasmid mediated colistin resistance marker (*mcr-9*) due to the high prevalence in *Salmonella* spp. and in some

reported *E. coli* and *Klebsiella spp.* The assay has demonstrated promising performance and will be further validated using additional *mcr-9* positive isolates.

JRP13-WP3-T2- Development of mobile technology for communication on-site results

A smart app for the Android platform has been developed to automatically analyse captured images from colorimetric LAMP assays performed outside, process captured images and upload their results to a cloud-hosted database. This deliverable transfers the machine learning outputs of WP1-T3 (i.e., deliverable D-JRP13-1.2) as applied to a mobile smart app for this purpose. This code was written in Python using the 'Kivy' package to develop software for the Android platform and tested on a mobile Samsung S10 device. This code has been uploaded to an online repository for version control purposes.

Further validations for assessing the efficiency of the smart app for detecting outdoors LAMP images are currently ongoing. These include our validated singleplex AMR LAMP assays and *mcr-9* LAMP assay from spiked and un-spiked pig faecal samples. Our beta testing demonstrated successful detection of positive (yellow tubes) and negative (pink tubes) in laboratory and outdoors settings.

WP4: Evaluation of on-site tests and other tools developed

JRP13-WP4-T1: Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tests for detection of pathogens and resistance genes

At FLI, composite faecal samples from different age groups (sows, suckling pigs, weaners, early, middle, late finishers) nine conventional pig farms were collected with the help of the local pig health service. They were plated and counts of total *E. coli* and ceftiofur-resistant *E. coli* were determined to have both the total number and the relative proportion of resistant isolates. For each sample with growth on agar plates containing ceftiofur, colonies were isolated and checked for the identity of the β -lactamase gene. So far, alleles for CTX-M-1 and CTX-M-15 have been detected. DNA from the faecal material will now be isolated directly following the protocol developed by NUIG to analyse sensitivity and specificity of the LEC-LAMP assay.

At NUIG, proof-of-concept on-site animal faecal sample testing was performed using the internally controlled multiplex CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay in combination with a rapid DNA extraction protocol with a custom portable diagnostics workstation in a non-laboratory agricultural setting. The portable diagnostics workstation included a thermostatic fluorimeter, mini dry bath, mini vortex, portable power pack, laboratory accessories and a protector case. On-site sample analysis using the portable workstation was carried out with PCR-confirmed *E. coli* blaCTX-M positive porcine faecal samples. Details of this portable on-site testing are documented in the previously mentioned manuscript, submitted for peer-review. Further validation of the internally controlled multiplex CTX-M-1/15 LEC-LAMP assay in combination with rapid DNA extraction protocol and custom portable diagnostics workstation will be carried out from September to November, 2022, using additional bovine and porcine faecal samples. These bovine and porcine animal samples will be supplied from selected agricultural and veterinary sources from various location in Ireland.

At INSA, the protocol developed by NUIG to analyse the sensitivity and specificity of the LEC-LAMP assay is being tested and evaluated using clinical animal (aquaculture), environmental and human samples.

WP5: Project Management

JRP13-WP5-T1-Project Management

Regular virtual (ZOOM) consortium meetings were held during the year to date. WorldCOM consortium members attended the OHEJP ASM meeting, presenting the work of the consortium to colleagues and stakeholders at various fora. The consortium members who attended the meeting also met to review progress to date. The consortium also hosted a very successful virtual workshop during

ASM entitled "**One Health EJP ASM Satellite Workshop: Diagnostics workshop; mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications**" which was held on April 14th 2022.

The WorldCOM DMP received positive feedback from the DMP Committee team during March 2022. It was noted that the WorldCOM DMP was well developed, with a good understanding about how to use the template. Reviewer's individual comments for improvement were implemented in the online tool. The online DMP was updated again on 14th June 2022. The next update is due for 30th September 2022.

5.1.4.2.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
13	D-JRP13-1.2	Novel machine learning algorithms for the prediction and detection of AMR from genomic sequences.	M56			Deliverable document uploaded on WorldCOM section of OHEJP website and is part of the 1-page abstract made public on Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618173	2
13	D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP3.1	On-site testing using Smartphone App for collection of data and transmission of test results to reference laboratory	M50		M57	1-page abstract made public on Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618173 Deliverable document uploaded on WorldCOM section of OHEJP website.	1
13	D-JPR13-AMR2.1-WP4.1	Feasibility testing of on-site tests for pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes complete	M58		M60	Feasibility testing has been started and is ongoing, but is delayed due to difficulties in obtaining samples due to COVID-19;	
13	D-JRP13-AMR2.1-WP4.2	Novel algorithms for prediction of antimicrobial resistance	M60				1, 3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
13	D-JPR13-AMR2.1-WP4.3	Protocols and SOPs prepared and available for dissemination	M60		M60	Will be performed in parallel with feasibility testing	2

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-02	Transfer of relevant sequence information for development and training of novel machine learning algorithms.	M56	Yes		
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-07	Performance testing of lateral flow detection completed	M48	Yes		This milestone has been modified to assess the performance of AMR LAMP assays.
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-08	Smartphone App for curation of assay results developed	M48	Yes		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6618173
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-09	Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tests underway	M51		M60	Ongoing work

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-10	Feasibility testing of novel algorithm underway	M51		M60	Ongoing work
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-11	Project review meeting organised	M41	Yes		
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-12	Technical and financial reports prepared	M49		M60	To be performed in parallel with feasibility testing
13	M-JPR AMR2.1-13	Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tested underway	M51		M60	
13	M-JPR AMR2.1-14	Feasibility testing of novel algorithms underway	M55		M60	

5.1.4.2.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance dynamics of Escherichia coli in wastewater and river environments. Delgado-Blas JF, Ovejero CM, David S, Montero N, Calero-Caceres W, Garcillan-Barcia MP, de la Cruz F, Muniesa M, Aanensen DM, Gonzalez-Zorn B. Commun Biol. 2021 Apr 12;4(1):457. DOI: 10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x https://zenodo.org/record/5524433#.YcyB25HMJuR	YES		YES (2680 euros)
Genomic Screening of Antimicrobial Resistance Markers in UK and US Campylobacter Isolates Highlights Stability of Resistance over an 18-Year Period. van Vliet AHM, Thakur S, Prada JM, Mehat JW, La Ragione RM. Antimicrob Agents Chemother. 2022 May 17;66(5):e0168721. DOI: 10.1128/aac.01687-21 https://zenodo.org/record/6618202	YES		YES (2430 euros)
Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP): for mobile rapid detection of nucleic acid targets. Hassan, M.M., Grist, L.F., Poirier, A.C. & La Ragione, R.M. Journal of Medical Microbiology 2022 May 71(5):001522. DOI: 10.1099/jmm.0.001522. https://zenodo.org/record/6618240	YES		YES (no specific gold OA cost due to Publish & Read agreement between publisher/society and university)
Survey on shedding of selected pathogenic, zoonotic or antimicrobial resistant bacteria by South American camelids in Central Germany. González-Santamarina, B., Schnee, C., Köhler, H., Weber, M., Methner, U., Seyboldt, C., Berens, C. & Menge, C. Berliner und Münchener Tierärztliche Wochenschrift 2022, 135:1–16	YES		YES (1130.50 euros)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
DOI: 10.2376/1439-0299-2021-21 https://zenodo.org/record/6642390			
The Prevalence, Counts and MLST Genotypes of Campylobacter in Poultry Meat and Genomic Comparison with Clinical Isolates. Tedersoo T, Roasto M, Mäesaar M, Kisand V, Ivanova M, Meremäe K. Poult Sci. Published online 2022:101703. doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2022.101703 https://zenodo.org/record/6642459	YES		YES (1740 euros)
Antibiotic Resistance in Campylobacter spp. Isolated from Broiler Chicken Meat and Human Patients in Estonia. Tedersoo T, Roasto M, Mäesaar M, Häkkinen L, Kisand V, Ivanova M, Valli MH, Meremäe K. Microorganisms. 2022;10(5):1067. doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10051067 https://zenodo.org/record/6642526	YES		YES (1623 euros)
Dissemination Routes of Carbapenem and Pan-Aminoglycoside Resistance Mechanisms in Hospital and Urban Wastewater Canalizations of Ghana. Delgado-Blas JF, Valenzuela Agüi C, Marin Rodriguez C, Serna C, Montero N, Saba CKS, Gonzalez-Zorn B. mSystems. 2022 Feb 22;7(1):e0101921. doi: 10.1128/msystems.01019-21 https://zenodo.org/record/6619655#.YqBvbOxBy59	YES		YES (2830 euros)
Genomic Analysis of a <i>mcr-9.1</i> -Harbouring IncHI2-ST1 Plasmid from <i>Enterobacter ludwigii</i> isolated in Fish Farming. Manageiro V, Salgueiro V, Rosado T, Bandarra NM, Ferreira E, Smith T, Dias E, Caniça M. Antibiotics 2022, 11, 1232. https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11091232	YES		Yes (no cost to the WorldCOM project)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://zenodo.org/record/7096620#.YymkZ3bMJPY			

Additional output

Posters and presentations

- Rapid and culture-independent LAMP detection of key AMR markers from environmental water samples. Hassan, M.M., Vliet, A.H.M. van, Higgins, O., Burke, L., O'Connor, L., Morris, D., Smith, T. & La Ragione, R.M. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, online.
- Rapid real-time differential detection of OXA-48-like variants using loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification. Owen Higgins, Louise O'Connor, Marwa M. Hassan, Brian Gardner, Liam Burke, Dearbhaile Morris, Arnoud H. M. van Vliet, Roberto M. La Ragione and Terry Smith. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, online.
- Comparative genomic analysis of multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* from South American camelids in Central Germany. Bélen González Santamarina, Michael Weber, Christian Menge and Christian Berens. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, online.
- HYBRID ASSEMBLY OF NANOPORE AND ILLUMINA READS – solving fragmented *de novo* assembly of resistant bacterial genomes Peeter Laas, Age Brauer, Mado Remm, Tanel Tenson, Veljo Kisand · One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, online.
- Characterisation of OXA-48 plasmids in a diverse range of clinical and environmental Enterobacterales isolates from an urban location in Ireland. Mark Maguire, Carlos Serna Bernaldo, Natalia Montero Serra, Louise O'Connor, Niamh Cahill, Brigid Hooban, Kelly Fitzhenry, Aoife Joyce, Georgios Miliotis, Niall DeLappe, Genevieve Devane, Martin Cormican, Simone C Coughlan, Dearbháile Morris, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn and Liam P. Burke. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting 2022, Orvieto Italy and online.
- Genomic and resistance diversity of *Escherichia coli* from hospital inpatients and outpatients with urinary tract infection in Spain. Carlos Serna, Jose F. Delgado-Blas, Bosco R. Matamoros, Natalia Montero, Mario Pulido-Vadillo, F. Javier Fernandez-Favieres, Maria Garcia-Castillo, Rafael Cantón, Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn. 32nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases 2022. Lisbon, Portugal.
- Oral presentations (R. M. La Ragione) on the development and use of Rapid diagnostic – MEVMA 2021, OHEJP conference 2022, ESGVM 2022, ECVM 2022.
- Antimicrobial Resistance and One Health. Bruno González Zorn. 5th International Caparica Conference in Antibiotic Resistance 2022, 05th – 08th September 2022, Caparica, Portugal.

Conference Workshop

- One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting Satellite Diagnostic Workshop 2022: Mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications [<https://onehealthjep.eu/asm-satellite-workshop-2022/>].
- The workshop was hosted by the University of Surrey, led by Dr. Marwa M. Hassan (LEO) with Dr. Owen Higgins as deputy lead. The online workshop showcased the research that is currently undergoing in the field and illustrated a guidance to designing diagnostics for One Health applications. The workshop was very well attended with almost 100 registered participants and highly perceived with a satisfaction of 93% for the workshop in general and 91% for the hands-on practical component (about 25 participants).

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

We have developed One Health diagnostic techniques that can be utilised and implemented for testing on farm and from contaminated water sources. We have developed rapid and sensitive detection techniques that can detect key antimicrobial resistance markers to aid AMR screening, especially in remote areas. Additionally, we have developed a Smartapp algorithm to facilitate off-site detection, reporting of results and transfer to central cloud storage. The detection of AMR markers from contaminated water samples has been submitted for publication and is currently under review. We have also contributed to a Journal of Medical Microbiology LAMP profile to feature the diagnostic technology we use, design and its application. Additionally, we led the organisation of the 2022 One Health EJP ASM Satellite Diagnostic Workshop as part of the OHEJP ASM showcasing the research that is currently undergoing in the field of One Health diagnostics and providing guidance on designing diagnostics for One Health applications. The Smartapp detection of AMR markers from pig faeces samples will be also prepared as a manuscript for publication.

5.1.4.2.4.1 *Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries*

The WorldCOM project has been presented at national level in Ireland to the National Interdepartmental AMR Consultative Committee (with membership from government Departments of Health and Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine - DAFM). This committee are tasked with developing and implementing Ireland's 2nd National One Health Action plan on Antimicrobial Resistance 2021-2025 (iNAP2). Strategic Objective 5 of iNAP2 is to promote research and sustainable investment in new medicines, diagnostic tools, vaccines and other interventions. Completion of the WorldCOM project has been identified as a strategic action under this objective, and project updates are communicated during committee meetings. Recently, Prof. Dearbhaile Morris presented on WorldCOM and other relevant projects at the "Building One Health Action under iNAP2" meeting co-hosted by DAFM, the Department of Health and the EPA, Farmleigh House, Phoenix Park, Dublin, June 23rd 2022. Additionally, Prof. Bruno González Zorn presented different projects, including WorldCOM, at the summer course "One Health Response and Antibiotic Resistance: New Approaches, New PRAN in Spain", El Escorial, Madrid, July 20th 2022. This course was attended by members of the Ministries of Health and Agriculture and the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products (AEMPS) with the aim of applying One Health actions in the new National Plan against Resistance to Antibiotics (PRAN)

5.1.4.3 *JRP14-R2-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE*

5.1.4.3.1 *Summary of the work carried out in the Project*

The goal of the Full Force project is to supply 17 EU partners with a technological toolbox and hands-on training in Single-Molecule Real-Time (SMRT) sequencing, and to apply this knowledge on study cases and applications in metagenomics and AMR transmission models. Using this state-of-the-art technology, public health and veterinary labs will have the capacity to perform full-length sequencing, and gain detailed insight in mobile genetic elements (MGEs) which carry antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes within and across species.

In Y5, corresponding to the third year of the project, the main focus went to (i) updating the Full Force Plasmid Assembly (FFPA) pipeline to incorporate progress in long-read sequencing technology, (ii) progressing in the five study cases in WP2, (iii) launching our benchmarking study (T2.6), and (iv) modelling efforts. Right before the Covid-19 wave in the winter of 2022, we were able to organize a

hybrid meeting in meeting on November 22 in Brussels. Despite strong hindrance by the pandemic throughout the project, we are still confident that most goals of the Full Force project are still within reach, also thanks to a six-month extension which was applied for in May 2021.

- The main goal of the Full Force project is to enable consortium partners to reach a sufficient technical level in plasmid sequencing. However, as the technology of long-read sequencing is rapidly evolving, the WP1 partner (SSI) had to modify the FFPA to a version 2.0, which is currently being benchmarked against PacBio sequencing data. A re-evaluation of proficiency data, based on this new pipeline, is planned for Q3/4 2022.
- Although WP2 (five cases studies implementing long-read sequencing on existing datasets) has suffered some delays, substantial progress has been made. In all five study cases, phylogenetic analyses on short-read datasets has been concluded, and strains have been selected for detailed study by long-read technology. Especially Task 2.2, a cross-sectional analysis of IncK and IncZ-type plasmids which suffered delays due to long-term absence of the task leader at BfR, has been successfully initiated after transfer of the task lead to RIVM.
- In the context of WP4, a protocol for harmonized bacterial conjugation has been established. A subgroup has been formed by INRAE, Sciensano, SSI and APHA to test out this protocol on a reference set of plasmid donor/receptors, with promising preliminary results.
- The design and parameterisation of a transmission spread model of pAMR in the simulation framework SimInf has led to a first publication, and is currently being refined.

5.1.4.3.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WPO Project management

JRP14-WPO-T1-meetings and telcalls

The annual consortium meeting, planned during ECCMID 2022 (Lisbon) will be replaced by a physical / hybrid meeting at the end of the year. Regular teleconferences were held to discuss progress and planning of ongoing WPs.

JRP14-WPO-T2-reporting

To date, 5 new deliverables were uploaded to Zenodo during 2022, and 2 papers were submitted for review. The 9 month reports (Y5) was submitted in due time.

JRP14-WPO-T3- central data repository

FULL_FORCE is using a centralized data repository to upload sequence data and metadata, which are generated during WP1 and WP2. Originally, we planned to use the AMR data hub of the European COMPARE Consortium and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). However, we were not successful in reaching an agreement with ENA, who is still negotiating single-subcontractor model for hubs created during COMPARE. Therefore, we have decided to use a commercial cloud tool (OwnCloud) for temporal data storage during Full Force.

Currently, this cloud stores over 3.7 Tb of data ,which is exchanged among partners.

JRP14-WPO-T4-data management plan

The Full force Data Management Plan was constructed in the CDP software and uploaded to <https://apps.lisam.com/app/#Apps/CDP>. As important part of the DMP, a framework agreement on Material Transfer was drafted, circulated and signed among all participating institutions. This agreement covers all transfer of data and strains during Full Force. Recently (March 2022), the DMP was updated with most recent available information of the various case studies (WP2).

WP1 SMRT implementation

JRP14-WP1-T1-methodology for MGE sequencing

This task was completed during the first annual year of Full Force.

JRP14-WP1-T2-SMRT sequencing workshop

This task was completed during the first annual year of Full Force.

JRP14-WP1-T3-proficiency test for MGE sequencing

Each institution's proficiency in SMRT sequencing is being assessed afterwards using a proficiency test, organised and coordinated by SSI. Upon discussion during and after the workshop in October 2020, it was decided to include 5 *Escherichia coli* strains from BfR (GER) as reference strains, since they have been sequenced using Illumina, MinION and PacBIO technologies.

However, given the advancement in sequencing technology and our goal to have a sustainable, long-term solution for plasmid assembly at the end of the project, it was decided to rebuild the FFPA pipeline. Instead of Unicycler-based assemblies, we implemented Flye-based assemblies with neocat/racon based correction, and polishing with short read data.

FFPA v2.0 pipeline (Henrik Hasman, SSI, DK)

The FFPA v2.0 is currently being benchmarked against PacBio sequencing data. A re-evaluation of proficiency data, based on this new pipeline, is planned for Q3/4 2022.

WP2 Genome studies

In WP2, the acquired SMRT toolbox will be applied in the (re-)sequencing of AMR strains from various research and surveillance projects in WP2 including EU projects such as EFFORT, COMPARE-VEO, ENGAGE and ARDIG, as well as national and EU surveillance activities for which short read sequences are available. In Y4, the focus in WP2 was on **hypothesis generation based on short-read sequence data** for the five defined studies cases (T2.1-2.5). Short-read Illumina data will allow comparison of total plasmid content and phylogenetic relatedness of isolates and based on those results choose a subset of isolates for MinION runs.

JRP14-WP2-T1- MGE evolution in longitudinal sample sets (ARDIG, ABRES)

This task focuses on IncI1 plasmids and on the research question regarding the European diversity in the complete sequences, and whether these plasmids evolve either host-or country specific. Data on

Incl1 containing samples from more than 1,400 bacterial isolates from longitudinal and annual surveillances were collected. In short, spades was used for the assembly, Resfinder to predict ESBLs and Plasmidfinder to predict plasmid replicons. We used MLST (Github/TSeemann) with a custom template for Incl1 pMLST. Ragout was used with 7 previously published Incl1 plasmids as reference to select the plasmid contigs from the genomes, followed by Prokka, Roary and RAxML.

Example of phylogenetic analysis of Incl1 plasmids for NVI (Norway), leading to a selection of 24 strains for long-read sequencing, indicated in green. Reference strains are indicated in blue. Analysis performed by Mike Brouwer (WUR, NL).

Resulting cross-sectorial and pan-European conservation of plasmid lineages lead to a selection for long-read sequencing (M-JRP19-M12) based on the previously discussed criteria, being pMLST type 3, 7 or 12 with CTX-M-1, CTX-M-15 or CMY-2. Long-read sequencing results are expected to be submitted to Owncloud by Q3 of 2022.

JRP14-WP2-T2- MGE evolution in cross-sectional data sets (EFFORT, ENGAGE & National Surveillance)

After long-term absence of task leader Jens (BfR), the task is now transferred to Joost Hordijk and Marta Rozwandowicz (RIVM, NL). IncZ plasmids belong to the I-complex together with Incl1, Incl2, InclY, IncK1, IncK2 and IncB/O. The first IncZ plasmid was described in 1983. Later, seven additional distinct IncZ plasmid groups have been described. The most commonly used *in silico* plasmid typing scheme does not discriminate between the different plasmids within the IncK/B/O/Z group.

In this study 402 samples carrying IncK/B/O/Z replicons were collected and subjected to short-read whole genome sequencing. Samples originated from humans, poultry, pigs and dairy and veal cattle from 11 European countries. IncK/B/O/Z plasmids were further typed based on their RNAI sequence and categorized into existing plasmid incompatibility groups.

Diversity of IncZ plasmids in Europe. Courtesy of Marta Rozwandowicz (RIVM, NL).

This work revealed that IncZ is the most observed type within the IncK/B/O/Z plasmid group with a prevalence of 52%. IncZ plasmids carry a wide variety of genes conferring resistance to β -lactams, sulphonamides, aminoglycosides and colistin (*mcr-1*). The results indicate that human clinical samples have a significantly higher occurrence of IncZ plasmids compared to carriage samples from humans. Additionally, a phylogenetic analysis based on the RNAI sequence revealed existence of potential new clusters in addition to the previously described IncZ plasmid types.

Samples for long-read sequencing have been selected and communicated to the partners.

JRP14-WP2-T3- *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: the canary in the coalmine

PHAS (Alma Brolund) and RIVM performed analyses on a large dataset of clinical and environmental *K. pneumoniae* strains provided by the task participants (ST type, and carbapenemase gene content), and found wide variety in sequence types of which some are limited to either human, animal or environment (Figure). Likewise, clear association between certain sequence types and carbapenemase genes (e.g., OXA-181 and ST873) was found. More specific phylogenetic analyses were performed at RIVM (Antoni Hendrickx), leading to a final selection of strains for long-read sequencing (M-JRP19-M12) based on ST37. The results of these sequencing efforts are expected at the end of Q2 of 2022.

JRP14-WP2-T4- AMR in horses: commensals and pathogens

This task objective is to investigate the spread of ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae in horses in Europe. The focus will be on blaCTX-M-1 and blaSHV-12 genes. To date, isolates carrying blaCTX-M-1 predominate in horses. This is due to clonal dissemination as well as the spread of closely-related IncHI1 plasmids. The success of this plasmid gene combination might be due to the fact that the IncHI1 plasmid also carries the fos-operon, involved in the metabolism of fructo-oligosaccharides, which could give the plasmid a selective advantage in the gut of the horse. The combination IncHI1+ blaCTX-M-1 appears to be almost exclusively linked to horses. Less is known of the epidemiology of blaSHV-12, which is often associated with IncX3-plasmids.

The inventory of available isolates from horses, both commensals and clinical isolates, among participating partners is completed (n=264). All short-read sequences have been uploaded to

owncloud, raw reads are assembled and the plasmidome determined/filtered. The plasmidome is comprised out of 8 clusters.

Based on this information, a selection has been made for long-read sequencing (M-JRP19-M14), results of which are being processed.

JRP14-WP2-T5- MGEs in Salmonella Infants and Kentucky

Salmonella Infantis is typically most prevalent Salmonella serotype in broilers, and the 4th most prevalent serovar in humans. It is known for increasing drug resistance. In 2007, a first report of megaplasmid pESI (300 kb) was published, while follow-up studies showed that this IncP plasmid contains a *mer* operon, yersiniabactin, toxin-antitoxin systems and AMR genes. Currently it is being reported in Israel, Italy, Switzerland, US, and Hungary¹.

This task examines the European distribution and evolution of this plasmid, and is led by ISS and IZSLT, who previously published on the phylogeny of *S. Infantis*. During Full Force, data from their publication will be merged with pESI positive *Salmonella* Infantis strains from contributing partners, to study its diversity and evolution.

The number of available isolates are listed in the table on the right, and short reads were uploaded to Owncloud. Based on this information and subsequent phylogenetic analyses, a selection has been made for long-read sequencing. The results are currently being processed.

JRP14-WP2-T6- Evaluation of tools for MGE typing

The task 2.6 deliverable 6 (D6) is to investigate relevant publicly available and in-house developed tools for MGE typing. During a WP2 meeting, the agreement was to focus on plasmids since this is in line with the focus of the entire project. A questionnaire was sent to all participants of the FULL_FORCE consortium in M42 to get a knowledge of which tools are used at the different institutions.

In addition to the tools summarized in Table 1, three plasmid characterization tools were suggested by FULL-FORCE partners, namely Platon, rfpasmid and Plascad.

An NCBI search was performed in February 2022 (M50) to get an overview of available on line tools. The following two queries were entered:

Detection of ARGs:

```
((((software[Title]) OR (tool*[Title])) OR (program*[Title])) OR (type[Title])) OR (typing[Title])) AND
((((antimicrob*[Title]) OR (antibiotic*[Title])) OR (AMR[Title])) OR (ARG[Title])) OR (antimicrobial
resistance gene*[Title])) OR (antibiotic resistance gene*[Title])) OR (resistance gene*[Title])) AND
((((sequenc*[Title/Abstract]) OR (identif*[Title/Abstract])) OR (contig*[Title/Abstract])) OR
(assembl*[Title/Abstract])) OR (NGS[Title/Abstract])) OR (WGS[Title/Abstract])) OR
(HTS[Title/Abstract]))
```

Determination of plasmid replicontype:

```
((plasmid*[Title]) AND (((software[Title/Abstract]) OR (tool*[Title/Abstract])) OR
(program*[Title/Abstract])) AND (((((((predict*[Title/Abstract]) OR (sequenc*[Title/Abstract])) OR
(identif*[Title/Abstract])) OR (contig*[Title/Abstract])) OR (assembl*[Title/Abstract])) OR
(NGS[Title/Abstract])) OR (WGS[Title/Abstract])) OR (HTS[Title/Abstract])) AND
```

¹ Franco A, et al. PLoS One 2015; 10:e0144802. Aviv G, et al. Environ Microbiol 2014; 16:977–994 ; Hindermann D, et al. Front Microbiol 2017; 8:1322; Tate H, et al. Antimicrob Agents Chemother 2017; 61:e00488-17; Carfora V, et al. Front Microbiol 2018; 9:1880

(((((replicon[Title/Abstract]) OR (replicon type[Title/Abstract]))
OR (incompatibility group*[Title/Abstract])) OR (Inc[Title/Abstract]))

The results of the NCBI query was 1082 publications in total, and this list of publications will be manually curated. Tools will be excluded if they do not meet our inclusion criteria:

- can be run on the command line
- tools/databases is updated regularly
- identify AMR genes and/or plasmid replicons
- accepts fasta-file as input

The deadline for the benchmarking study was set in M58.

WP3 : Culture-Independent typing and metagenomics

JRP14-WP3-T1-MGE analyses in metagenomic datasets

This task has been completed in the first annual year of Full Force.

JRP14-WP3-T2-culture-independent methods for plasmid identification

This task has been completed in the second annual year of Full Force.

WP4 : Functional characterization of AMR mobile genetic elements (MGE)-carrying AMR genes and bacterial host associations

JRP14-WP4-T1-MGE and host selection

This task has been completed in the second annual year of Full Force.

JRP14-WP4-T2-In vitro characterization

Last year, a complete protocol of conjugation assays in liquid cultures has been drafted. This protocol has the objectives (i) to isolate the plasmid of interest in a plasmid-free recipient strain, (ii) to determine if the plasmid is self-transmissible or only mobilizable, and (iii) to determine the conjugation rate based on the Simonsen model and its derivatives (Simonsen et al., Huisman et al.). This protocol is derived from Huisman et al. that provides all tools to estimate conjugation rates and to simulate population dynamics in an R package and Shiny app (<https://ibz-shiny.ethz.ch/jhuisman/conjugator/>).

In Y5, we have been conducting many DRT and TRT experiments, trying to emulate the conditions described by SSI in three other laboratories (Sciensano, APHA and INRAE). The DRT was conducted using the donor ESBL strain, followed by a TRT experiment where we compared T1 from the DRT experiment, to the reference T1 strain. The conjugation rate was estimated for the ASM, SM and T_DR, meaning that the experiment likely did not exceed the critical time.

Having tried this experiment on several *E.coli* harbouring IncI1 plasmids, we can conclude that the setup is surprisingly robust. The main drawbacks to the approach are that i) It is very common to find you have exceeded the critical time and need to repeat the experiment and this can be extremely time consuming and ii) the conjugation estimates at 2hr and 4hr are often quite different.

Further validation of the technique, and publication are planned for Q3/4 of 2022.

JRP14-WP4-T3-Host association studies

This task has not yet been initiated at the time of writing due to departure of the task lead at DTU.

WP5 : modelling

The objectives of WP5 are to address: i) gaps in quantitative knowledge on the spread of pAMR which will be essential to direct future focused research, ii) insight in the uncertainty around the effect of measures reducing pAMR prevalence in the food production chains, and iii) identification of key elements in the production chains to mitigate the risk of human exposure.

Task 5.1 MODEL DESIGN for AMR TRANSMISSION (M25-M42)

This task has been completed in the first and second annual year of Full Force.

Task 5.2 EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT of HORIZONTAL and VERTICAL TRANSMITTED AMR (M25-M54)

The objective of this task will be on investigating the relative importance of exposure routes from the broiler in various transmission models.

Within flock transmission models. 1. SIS model with direct and indirect transmission, which are reduced as a bird ages. Only one phylotype is included. 2. SISIR model with three phylotypes with cross immunity after two infections.

Using these models, we assessed various interventions. We showed that intervention with complete clearance of bacteria between production rounds was the most effective for both models. However, a minor environmental contamination from the previous round can initiate an outbreak in the next round. An intervention by reduced shedding did not reduce the prevalence in SISIR model because the transmissibility is constant and reduction was not enough, while it was effective in SIS model where the transmissibility decreases exponentially during a round. Finally, consumption of chicken meat had minor estimated contribution of 0.1 to 0.2% of human prevalence (overall prevalence 4.68%).

Thorough cleaning and disinfection between production rounds in broiler farms can reduce ESBL-producing *E. coli*, but may be difficult in practice.

5.1.4.3.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP14-WP0.D6	Closure meeting report	M54		M60	Closure meeting planned in December	
14	D-JRP14-WP0.D7	Financial and activity report Y5	M54		M60	Will be published at the end of Y5	
14	D-JRP14-WP1.D8	Completion of final report of proficiency tests	M54		M60	Depends on validation FFPA v2.0	
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D8	Submission of long-read sequencing data of cross-sectional samples to ENA hub	M50	M50		Public; https://zenodo.org/record/6602217	5
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D9	Submission of long-read sequencing data of <i>S. Infantis</i> and <i>S. Kentucky</i> to ENA hub	M50	M50		Public; https://zenodo.org/record/6602367	5
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D10	Submission of long-read sequencing data of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> samples to ENA hub	M50		M54	Sequencing underway	
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D11	Submission of long-read sequencing data AMR horse samples to ENA hub	M50	M50		Public; https://zenodo.org/record/6602379	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP14-WP5.D3	A report on using ABC methodology for parameter inference of a SimInf model designed for pAMR.	M50		M60	Will be published at the end of Y5	

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
14	M-JRP14-M11	Final selection of cross-sectional samples for SMRT sequencing	M55	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M15	Analysis of proficiency test data by all partners	M52	No	M57	Depends on Validation FFPA v2.0
14	M-JRP14-M16	Individual reports of proficiency test sent to partners	M54	No	M60	Depends on Validation FFPA v2.0 and M15
14	M-JRP14-M22	Transfer frequency data of representative IncHI1-CTX-M1 plasmids	M52	No	-	Change of scope – no conjugations planned for IncHI plasmids so far. No impact on other tasks.

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
14	M-JRP14-M23	Data on conjugative transfer of pESI plasmid from <i>S. Infantis</i> to other <i>Salmonella</i> serovars and other microbial species	M52	No	-	Change of scope – no conjugations planned for pESI plasmids so far. No impact on other tasks.
14	M-JRP14-M24	Finalised hybrid assemblies of longitudinal samples	M50	No	M54	Expected in M54
14	M-JRP14-M25	Finalised hybrid assemblies of cross-sectional samples	M50	No	M54	Expected in M54
14	M-JRP14-M26	Finalised hybrid assemblies of <i>S. Infantis</i> and <i>S. Kentucky</i> isolates	M50	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M27	Finalised hybrid assemblies of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> isolates	M50	No	M53	Expected in M53
14	M-JRP14-M28	Finalised hybrid assemblies of AMR horse samples	M50	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M29	Transfer frequency data of <i>mcr</i> plasmids of different incompatibility groups	M52	No	-	Change of scope – no conjugations planned for <i>mcr</i> plasmids. No impact on other tasks.
14	M-JRP19-M30	Data on the role of short-chain fructooligosaccharide	M54	No	M57	Expected in M57

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
		metabolism in IncHI1 plasmid maintenance				
14	M-JRP19-M31	Data on plasmid-encoded fitness advantages of pESI to the host bacteria	M54	No	-	Change in scope: no fitness experiments planned due to departure of task leader in T4.3. . No impact on other tasks.

5.1.4.3.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Diaconu EL, Carfora V, Alba P, Di Matteo P, Stravino F, Buccella C, Dell'Aira E, Onorati R, Sorbara L, Battisti A, Franco A. Novel IncFII plasmid harbouring blaNDM-4 in a carbapenem-resistant Escherichia coli of pig origin, Italy. J Antimicrob Chemother. 2020 Dec 1;75(12):3475-3479. doi: 10.1093/jac/dkaa374. https://zenodo.org/record/4451840#.YZPKcWDMJM0	YES		YES (processing charges unknown)
Kirstahler P, Teudt F, Otani S, Aarestrup FM, Pamp SJ. A Peek into the Plasmidome of Global Sewage. mSystems. 2021 May 26:e0028321. doi: 10.1128/mSystems.00283-21 https://zenodo.org/record/5543288#.YZPKXmDMJM0	YES		YES (processing charges unknown)

Additional output

Two poster presentations featuring data of the Full Force project have been submitted/performed in Y5:

[Minori Furusawa. \(2022\). Transmission models of ESBL-producing *E. coli* in the broiler production chain. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6581036>. Presented at the society for Veterinary Epidemiology and Preventive Medicine \(SVEPM\) conference March 23-25 in Belfast.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6581036)

- M. Rozwandowicz et al. (2022). Occurrence and diversity of IncZ plasmids. Submitted for poster publication at the Plasmid Biology Conference

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

- The Full Force Plasmid Assembler (FFPA) is a software which can be readily implemented in public health and veterinary labs (as well as in clinical labs), and will provide standardization in plasmid assembly and interpretation in the context of plasmid outbreaks.
- The modelling efforts in WP5 suggested that thorough cleaning and disinfection between production rounds in broiler farms can reduce ESBL-producing *E. coli*.

5.1.4.3.4.1 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

- We plan to apply to the JPIAMR network call (2023-2024) which groups experts in sequencing, plasmid biology and bioinformatics, and aims to streamline procedures for plasmid sequencing and analysis. Therefore, we will extend the Full Force consortium to academic and hospital partners.
- The KENTUCKY PhD project (OHEJP, 2020-2022) has been successful in demonstrating the transfer of IncHI plasmids between Salmonella strains, with input from WP2 of Full Force.
- Potential collaborations with ECDC and EFSA are envisioned at the end of the Full Force project, for sustainable implementation of long-read sequencing technology in surveillance of AMR in Europe. Therefore, we aim to invite EFSA and ECDC experts to the final meeting of the consortium, planned at the end of 2022.

5.1.4.4 JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR

5.1.4.4.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

FED-AMR project aims at demonstrating the importance of extracellular free DNA (exDNA) as an environmental reservoir for ARGs. ARG concentrations, diversity, mobility, and bacterial biodiversity are being determined in an annual longitudinal study covering a crop's growing period. Different fertilisation and land management techniques as well as environmental compartments are being investigated.

Building on the existing structures of our project, we continued our efforts in WP1 to coordinate the scientific and administrative matters between the partners, including a hybrid meeting in Lisbon in April of 2022 organised by INSA, as well as periodic scientific online meetings and overall coordination of the project.

As part of WP2, we progressed with the harmonized statistical and bioinformatics analysis of the results obtained from the target enrichment and the 16S metagenomics data on the extracellular and total DNA samples. In addition, the bacterial isolates gathered by each involved project partner were

characterized by Whole Genome Sequence-based typing and antimicrobial susceptibility test were performed. Some of the WP2 results were communicated at several international conferences and at least two manuscripts are in progress.

Regarding WP3, after sampling campaigns and isolates characterization (phenotype, WGS), the most relevant zoonotic ribotypes of *Clostridioides difficile* were selected. Besides food producing animals carrying toxigenic and resistant *C. difficile* strains, the same was demonstrated for pets (dogs and cats). Currently WP3 is working in the genomic analysis of isolates from those ribotypes, collected from different sources (human, animal, food, environment) and countries (partners from the project), including in silico AMR and mobile genetic elements. The work carried out in WP3 during Y4 resulted in the following scientific outputs: one paper published in *Frontiers in Microbiology* in April 2022; two posters, one in the ASM OHEJP_2022 and the other in ECCMID_2022.

The sample analysis of antibiotics, elements and herbicides for all regions tested in WP4 has been finalized. Statistical analysis on these results is being performed, which will allow the publication of a manuscript. WP4 results will be integrated with those from other WPs. Additionally a manuscript is in progress describing results gathered in this WP.

For WP5, the project plan, milestones and deliverables were reassessed to ensure realistic progress over the remaining period giving the limited staff time allocated to the project and the complex nature of the work. This WP is currently optimising fermentation conditions *in vitro* to demonstrate suitable growth of *E. coli* J53 in the presence of faecal microbiota to ensure the successful detection of transformation events, as well as starting work with *C. difficile* to be able to compare horizontal gene transfer by conjugation to natural transformation. They are also investigating the use of AMR-encoding plasmids as another source for AMR resistance genes to mimic natural environmental conditions.

WP6 has focused on finalizing the protocol for a systematic review on factors influencing the prevalence of antibiotic resistance in the environment and on formulating and validating a mathematical model for the dynamics of microbial communities. The protocol was registered in a public repository (<https://osf.io/a8gv6/>) and submitted to Environmental International. We are working on incorporating their feedback. With respect to the task on modelling microbial communities, we have formulated a new model and validated it with in-silico data purposely developed. A major development is that Dr Brian Gardner has changed position, however, he has agreed to carry on working on the project on a part-time basis until December 2022 (4 hours per week).

5.1.4.4.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1 Project Management and Communication

WP1-T1 Scientific Management (M25-M60)

This task is ongoing for the whole project duration (M25 to M60).

WP1-T1-ST1.2 Webinar forum and Skype meetings for instant scientific interactions (M29-M60)

This subtask is ongoing to facilitate regular scientific exchange between the project partners. TCs are held where all WPs provide a short update about their status. Minutes of these meetings are registered and shared with the project partners for approval. A definitive version incorporating all suggestions received is distributed and published in the AGES website (<https://fed-amr.ages.at>). In addition, regular calls occur between members of one or two WPs, in order to discuss the progress of their tasks. Such meetings will continue for the duration of the project as necessary.

WP1-T1-ST1.3: Project Meetings (M25-M52)

Due to the COVID pandemic, the 2nd consortium meeting was postponed to April 2022 (Y5) in Lisbon. This meeting took place at INSA for two full days, on the 21st and 22nd of April 2022, in a face-to-face format (24 participants) and with the option of joining online by Teams. All 6 WPs made an update on the data already achieved, followed by discussion, namely with the aim of clarifying questions about

several scientific issues, reorienting the analysis of these data, and talking about respective publications. Each WP leader was responsible for organizing and coordinating the work during the time allocated to the respective WP, ensuring the involvement of all participants. In the end, the next steps were discussed in a general and WP-dedicated way, and particular attention was given to the outputs and the importance of leaving a legacy available and useful to the scientific community, stakeholders, policy makers and the population in general in the field of the project, overall, the AMR spread. This subtask is finished.

WP1-T2: Administrative Management (M25-M60)

The coordination of joint activities in the frame of the FED-AMR project are coordinated by AGES. Additionally, each partner has appointed an Administrative Representative who is in direct contact with the AGES Administrative Manager (AM). The administrative team at AGES and the Scientific Manager (SM) have defined a risk management strategy for the project. The overarching risk management strategy initiated in year 3 of the project was put in place by the AM and the SM, in consultation with the Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) to ensure that adverse situations are properly handled along the course of the project, which is being highlighted in the Data Management Plan. This task is ongoing.

WP1-T3: Data and Protocol Management (M25-M58)

In year 5, a new version of the Data and Protocol Management Plan will be delivered. This task is ongoing.

WP2: Field experiments: Determination of the naturally occurring ARG background load and microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments (M25-M60)

In WP2 we are trying to understand 1.) Which (clinically relevant) ARGs are present in a given compartment? 2.) How many and which ARGs are in the compartments? 3.) Which bacteria are present in the compartments? 4.) How many bacteria are present in the compartments? The subtasks below have until now partially answered to these questions, since the statistical analysis are not finished yet due to the large amount of results obtained derived from the sequencing (16S, gene enrichment, WGS).

WP2-T3- Assess microbial and ARG diversity with NGS in the selected test environments (metagenomics). Compare microbial and ARG diversity between ecosystems and over ecosystem boundaries. Characterization of cultivable environmental bacteria on complete nutrient and minimal media (M27-M54)

The WP2 « analysis team » has progressed with the statistical and bioinformatic analysis carried out with the results obtained from the 16S metagenomics, the target enrichment DNA samples and the whole genome sequencing-based analysis of the isolates. Preliminary outcomes have been presented at several international conferences. At present, the group continues to meet so that the analysis is integrated into the defined manuscripts, in accordance with the objectives. This task is **finished**.

WP2-T3-ST1- Shotgun sequencing and bioinformatic analyses of AMR genes and MGEs (M37-M58)

The FED-AMR partners agreed on the evaluation and comparison of ARGs using a novel methodology based on gene capture probes or gene enrichment (see task WP2-T2 and subtask WP2-T3.2). This methodology allowed us to analyse the AMR genes and MGEs, and dispense with both conventional shotgun metagenomics (this subtask) and qPCR (task WP2-T4) for the collected samples. So, this subtask does no longer exist in a methodological point of view, but the aim will persist, and results will come from WP2-T3.ST2.

WP2-T3-ST2- Gene enrichment with gene capture probes (M31-M48)

This subtask is **finished** regarding the lab work and with the main statistical analysis done, but the link between all WP2 variables and the correlation with other WPs needs to be completed. Results obtained from the gene enrichment assays are being statistically processed with several R packages by

the “analysis team”. These include evaluation of the ARGs diversity, among others, in each of the samples, DNA types (extracellular vs. total), compartments and countries.

The analysis of ARGs obtained via gene enrichment and sequencing started with samples obtained from Ireland, as this represents a more restricted set of samples which facilitates data exploration. A large diversity of AMR, stress resistance and virulence genes was encountered. Wastewater sludge samples had a greater diversity (higher Chao1 and Shannon indexes) of target genes than from wild deer faeces. Extracellular DNA from wastewater had a high diversity of ARGs, with aminoglycosides, beta-lactamase, multidrug resistance and tetracycline resistance comprising the main AMR types detected. By contrast, deer faeces ARGs were dominated by ARGs classified as „mutation or variant antibiotic target“. There was little variation in the diversity and abundance of AMR genes in wild deer faeces across the 7-month sampling period. In general, we encountered some irregularities with the AMR gene names, particularly regarding their classification into different AMR groups, which has necessitated a revision of the gene names and classification. For this reason, the bioinformatic and statistical analyses of the main set of gene enrichment data with all the compartments across all participating members will resume soon. In addition, correlation with WP4 results is being determined.

Regarding the characterization of cultivable bacteria by WGS-based typing, more than 300 clinically-relevant bacterial isolates belonging to the species *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *S. enterica*, *S. aureus*, *E. faecium* and *E. faecalis* were obtained after sample cultivation by the six participating countries. Also, nearly 200 environmental strains belonging to other bacterial species, mostly environmental were gathered by the partners. The clinically-relevant strains were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility and paired-end sequenced was carried out on Illumina devices at each institute. Afterwards, raw genome sequences (FASTQ) were forwarded to 2-AGES for genome assembly, species re-identification, species-specific assessment of the genetic relatedness by core genome MLST using publicly available schemes, extraction of the sequence types of the classical MLSTs, and extraction of ARGs and virulence genes using CARD and VFDB databases, respectively. Afterwards, the assemblies (FASTA) were forwarded to 33-NVI to extract the mobile genetic elements as well as re-extraction of ARGs and VGs. For this matter, the NVI performed in-house plasmid assembly, gene identification and annotation pipeline Ellipsis (<https://github.com/NorwegianVeterinaryInstitute/Ellipsis>) and PlasmidFinder.

cgMLST-based analysis showed intra-country clusters but no multicountry cluster was detected. However, several STs were detected in more than one country, especially among the *E. coli* isolates. In all countries, isolates retrieved from wastewater, pig manure and pigs were those carrying more ARGs, including extended-spectrum betalactamases, but also ARGs associated to antimicrobials used in animal husbandry such as aminoglycosides, tetracyclines or sulfonamides.

The analysis of associations between ARGs in the strains and the different compartments and countries is still ongoing. The identified mobile genetic elements (MGE) will provide more information about the possible dissemination via horizontal gene transfer of ARGs and VGs between clones of the same or different species, countries and compartments.

In silico analysis of 29 *Enterobacter cloacae* complex strains collected in Portugal (PT) from different water environmental compartments (influent, surface, sludge, and effluent from a stabilization pond; groundwater; irrigation canal; drinking water and river) allowed the characterization of the predominant ARG and mobile genetic elements (MGE). PT identified genes related with non-susceptibility to β -lactams (*bla*_{ACT-type}, including to carbapenems: *bla*_{FRI-8} and *bla*_{IMI-6}), quinolones (*oqxAB*-type), fosfomycin (*fosA2*-type), and macrolides (*mdfA*-type). PT also detected the virulence factor *iroN*, three plasmid replicon-types [IncFII(Yp), Col(MG828), Col(pHAD28)], as well as several insertion sequences, transposons and MITEs (miniature inverted-repeat transposable elements). All strains were considered pathogenic to humans with values ranging from 66.6% to 82.1%. Phylogenetic analysis identify two main clusters with closely related strains from different compartments. The strains were also phenotypically characterized showing that non-susceptibility to colistin was present in 93% of the strains; all strains were resistant to at least one carbapenem in 3 compartments (river

water, sludge, and effluent from a stabilization pond), 80% in the surface water and only 25% in strains isolated in effluent. These results were presented in the ECCMID 2022 and were part of an MSc thesis already defended in 2022 and will be part of a publication this year.

WP2-T5- Identify naturally transformable bacterial species in the tested compartments (NGS) (M42-M56)

This task is ongoing. To identify naturally transformable bacteria in the compartments tested, a query database containing bacterial species proven to be able to take up extracellular DNA under naturally occurring environmental conditions was generated. For this purpose, a literature search for naturally competent bacteria covering the years from 1994 to 2021 was performed using defined search strings and PubMed and SCOPUS as reference databases. Only hits describing the development of competence in bacteria under physiological conditions were eligible for entering the query database. The bacterial species names retrieved from literature were annotated and the appropriate phylogenetic levels were allocated according to the taxonomic classification system as laid down in SILVA 138.1. For the annotation and classification of 16S NGS data generated in the frame of the project the same version of SILVA was employed. The resulting collection of observed bacterial species in FED-AMR samples was used as the searched database. This search database was checked for the presence of bacteria sampled in the query database using the level “genus” as qualifier. The research questions were: 1. Are naturally transformable bacteria present in FED-AMR isolates? 2. If yes, in which compartments? 3. Which competent bacteria are to be found in these compartments?

The query database contained 171 entries (= bacterial species) with empirically obtained evidence for their natural transformability. The searched database contained the 16S sequence information of 488 samples and 5763 different bacterial species. Naturally transformable bacteria were identified in almost all samples (except for a sample from soil and from a farmer – both of exDNA as sample type), in all sample types and environmental compartments. The overall most prevalent taxons encountered in FED-AMR samples were Pseudomonads and Sphingomonads. Lactobacilli were found in a significantly lower number of samples but showed highly abundant genus-specific sequence reads. Samples from wildlife (exDNA), farmers (ex/total DNA) and crops (ex/total DNA) carried the lowest abundance of competent bacteria. The highest loads with competent bacteria could be observed in feed (exDNA), groundwater (total DNA) and field drainage (total DNA).

We can conclude that bacteria known to be able to take up extracellular DNA are present in all environmental compartments and may serve as receptor for ARG encoded on free exDNA.

The next steps are to perform a detailed statistical evaluation of the obtained results focusing on country-specific comparisons and a comparison with in silico alignment studies based upon comEC homologies.

WP2-T6- Assess clonal/lineage diversity in selected ARB species (M43-M52)

In the original task WP2-T6, phylogenetic trees using 16S amplicon sequencing and the shotgun sequencing data were planned. However, since the number of samples that the consortium analysed was significantly higher than the initially planned, the methodological approach was modified and no phylogenetic analysis will be done using the raw data (FASTQ). See deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6 for additional information.

In this task, we obtained the **16S shotgun sequencing (V1-V9) / the metagenomic results** for all partners. After cleaning up the data, all OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) with no reads, and correcting some errors we ended up with 573646 OTUs in 476 samples. We then proceeded to create a Phyloseq (R package) object using the available data in the literature (McMurdie & Holmes, 2013).

We divided the samples into 11 compartments: Crop – crops harvested in the agricultural fields; Feed – proceed feeds for animal consumption; Farmers – faeces samples from farmers; Pigs_Barn – faeces from farm pigs; Manure – faeces of pigs and other organic material used to fertilize the soil;

Wild_animals – faeces samples of wild animals like deal, hares, sheep and goat; Soil_Fs_Ms_Ctrl_Bline – soil samples from forests, meadows and agricultural fields before being cultivated or fertilized; Soil_field_noMan – soil samples from agricultural fields fertilized without the use of manure; Soil_field_Man – soil samples from agricultural fields fertilized with of manure; water_DRG – water samples from drainage, river and ground water; water_WTP – water samples from waste treatment plants.

Overall, water_DRG is the only compartment exclusively with samples that did not pass the quality control. If we separate the data sample type we will have 232 samples and 1725 genera for extracellular DNA samples and 223 samples and 1810 genera in total DNA samples. Phyla in extracellular and total DNA samples, are dominated by Proteobacteria and Firmicutes. Most of the Phyla are present in both extracellular and total DNA samples. Acidobacteriota, Chloflexi and Gemmatimonadota have higher reads in soil samples while Bacteroidota and Firmicutes have higher reads in farmers, pigs, manure and wild animals samples. Concerning alpha diversity, we explore the data with and without rarefaction (a procedure commonly used in microbial diversity analysis, but which may lead to loss of data. The compartments that are significantly different from each other in terms of alpha diversity were determined both in the extracellular and total DNA samples. Most of the compartments were significantly different. From a total of 55 possible comparisons between compartments, we have 42 agreements extracellular and total DNA samples when rarefaction was used and 45 agreements when rarefaction was not used. This suggest that there are some punctual differences concerning alpha diversity between the extracellular and total DNA. To perform ordination analysis we used CLR (centered log ratio) transformation that allowed us to use Aitchison distance. In both extracellular and total DNA samples PC1 will separate soil samples from everything else, PC2 and PC3 separate the other compartments. The first three principal components explain 41.6%, 8.9% and 4.0% of the data variability in extracellular DNA samples and 45.2%, 7.3% and 5.3% in total DNA samples. PC2 and PC3 will separate crops, feeds and water samples from farmers, pigs and manure, with wild animals samples bridging these two clusters. We used multiple differential abundance methods to help ensure robust biological interpretations and we choose ALCOM-BC, ALDEx2 and the Wilcoxon test with CLR transformation. For all analysis, the results suggest a similarity between the three soil compartments, with low percentages of differential expressed genes and reads. For the remaining compartments, the conclusions are not that clear and the dendrograms cluster them in different ways, depending on the methodology used. Finally, we will try to understand how OUT's passes between compartments and what OUT's are shared or are unique to the different compartments. In both extracellular and total DNA samples, the compartments are divided into two main groups that separate the soil samples from everything else, as in the ordination analysis. The remaining samples are further divided into two groups: one with the mammals, another with the crops, feeds and water_DRG. Water_WTP and manure seem not to cluster with any other compartment. Concerning the separation for the OUT's we see that there are separations, which are common to the extracellular and total DNA and others that are specific. In both types of samples, we note large OUT's clusters exclusive from soil, others that are exclusive from manure and others exclusive for water_WTP. Following the group order in the dedrogram for the OUT's in the total DNA samples, we have a first cluster shared by mammals and manure, another that is shared by mammals, water_WTP, manure and soil samples. These are followed by a cluster shared by every compartment. For other clusters it is difficult to assign a characteristic.

Overall, the data suggest: A) Separation between three groups: 1) soil; 2) crops, feeds and drinking water; 3) farmers, pigs, wild animals, manure and waste water. B) No significant difference was detected between soil in fields with and without manure. C) Differences were detected between extracellular and total DNA samples in: farmers, feeds and soil. D) Very few samples of water that also did not pass quality control.

WP2-T7- Isolate and assess quantity, diversity and stability of free extracellular ARG encoding DNA in the tested environments. Sequence comparisons (M34-M52)

DNA extractions and sequencing assays were already performed in Y4. The WP2 analysis team is still working on the statistical analysis. This task is dependent on sub-task 2.

The start and end of this task was delayed from M34 (year 3) and M50 (year 5), respectively.

WP3: Elucidating the role of *Clostridioides difficile* as an ARG transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries and its linkage between human and non-human zoonotic reservoirs.

WP3-T2- WGS and AMR characterization of human and non-human *C. difficile* isolates (M34-M53)

Based on the ribotypes (RT) obtained in task 3.1, available genomes and zoonotic importance (including predominant RTs found in the sampling campaigns in the HOALS from Portugal, Estonia and Ireland) four *C. difficile* RTs were selected to proceed with Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS)-based analysis for joint publications. The work was distributed as follows: RT033 for INSA, RT078/126 for SSI, RT049 for BfR and RT002 for FLI.

Partners shared WGS data (FASTQ files) through SSI and FLI cloud services, and/or genomic DNAs in M50-M52.

From M48 to M53, WP3 partners finalized characterization of *C. difficile* regarding AMR profiles and WGS, with identification of sequence types (STs) and antimicrobial resistance genes (ARG). Ribotyping was also performed.

WP3-T3- Evaluation of the extent of genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages (M41-M58)

The activities per partner in this task are described in more detail below. This task is ongoing.

At 36-INSA, the study was focused on RT033 diversity from different sources (human, cattle, pig, pets, manure, water, soil) and FLI, SSI, IP, BfR partners were involved. Comparative genomic analysis and phenotypes, including biofilm, sporulation germination and toxins production is being carried out. A scientific manuscript will be prepared and should be submitted during Y5. In addition, in order to explore alternative sources for community-acquired *C. difficile* infection and to give a further contribution for the evaluation of the genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages, we analysed samples from pets (dogs and cats). A total of 475 faecal samples were collected from pets. The overall prevalence of *C. difficile* varied between 18.6%-26%. Two of the most frequently identified ribotypes in pets, RT014/020 and RT106, are also highly prevalent in Portuguese patients with CDI, with RT106 showing an increase trend in human infections over the last years. Among pets isolates, we found resistance to antibiotics relevant for human use, including AMR to clindamycin (27.7%-37%), metronidazole (12.8%-28.6%) and moxifloxacin (8.6%-12.8%). Genetic overlap between strains was assessed through core genome SNP analysis. WGS analysis supports the possibility of clonal transmission between pets and humans (threshold of ≤ 2 SNV), suggesting these animals may act as a reservoir for toxigenic and antimicrobial-resistant human-associated strains of *C. difficile*. This study was presented in OHEJP ASM 2022 meeting as a poster (*Clostridioides difficile* in companion animals, a One Health concern?). For this study (*C. difficile* and pets), a scientific manuscript is being prepared to be submitted during Y5. An own sampling campaign of air samples in pig farms will be conducted during Y5, in order to complete the study of the environmental compartments (already performed for water, soil and manure).

10-FLI received from the project partners University of Tartu and National University of Ireland, Galway, samples from different compartments to isolate and analyse *C. difficile*. In summary, we received 57 samples, of which 5 were positive for *C. difficile*. In total, we obtained 73 isolates belonging to RT049 and AI-83. Among the four selected *C. difficile* RTs (RT033, RT078/126, RT049, RT002) we proceeded with RT002 WGS data analysis for a joint publication. FLI received RT002 WGS sequence data from SSI, IP, BfR and ready to sequence DNA from INSA. FLI provided WGS sequence data of RT033, RT078/126, RT049 to WP3 partners SSI, INSA and BfR. 39 RT033-cattle-isolate-sequences were sent to INSA. 31 RT078-respectively RT126-sequences were transmitted to the SSI, also mostly from

cattle-isolates. 18 RT049-sequences, largely FED-AMR-samples-isolates, were sent to the BfR. Here 4 more strains of RT049 will be sequenced. FLI and SSI provided server capacity to exchange WGS data. A procedure for quality control of the sequence reads before data sharing was proposed based on the partners comments by FLI. According to the partners experience this QC parameters could be more relaxed.

We prepared a mobile genetic element database for *C. difficile*. To search mobile genetic elements, we assembled a list from the literature that included transposons, plasmids and phages. We uploaded this list and the FASTA sequence data to the FLI cloud service accessible for all WP3 partners. Additionally, a compilation of publicly available databases and tools that can be used for *C. difficile* mobile genetic elements analysis was provided.

To investigate further sources of *C. difficile* and to contribute to the assessment of the genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* strains, we analysed samples of New World Camelids of 43 husbandries in Middle Germany. In seven farms, eight strains were found (RT 002/2, RT 015, RT 029, RT 078, RT AI-75). All strains were toxicogenic, potentially human-pathogenic and showed resistances against different antimicrobials. This study is planned to be presented as a poster at the German International Symposium on Zoonoses Research 2022 (<https://zoonosen.net/zoonoses-2022-international-symposium-zoonoses-research>). Further a scientific manuscript will be prepared with the aim to be submitted this year. At SSI we performed the analyses on ST11 (RT078/126).

First part was focused only on Danish isolates. Here, a total of 330 pig faecal samples collected from 14 different farms in 2020, were cultured for *C. difficile*. Thirty-three (10%) were *C. difficile* positive and among those 21 were ST11 originating from 6 farms. All isolates were whole genome sequenced and sequences were compared to 479 human ST11 isolates from 2020-2021 by core genome and whole genome MLST (cgMLST/wgMLST), while the presence of ARG were investigated by AMRfinder. Eighteen out of 21 veterinary isolates of ST11 displayed 0-2 allelic differences based on wgMLST – they were different from the human isolates indicating either direct transmission or a shared intermediate reservoir. The 18 pig isolates were part of three different human clusters (0- 2 cg- and wgMLST allelic differences) representing ca. 20% of human isolates, indicating that the veterinary clones are common among human *C. difficile* infections. ARG variant profile (aminoglycosides, beta-lactamases, fluoroquinolones and tetracycline) within each human/veterinary cluster, confirmed similarity and important potential of resistance (not confirmed by phenotype). The data was presented at ECCMID 2022 titled “Potential for the zoonotic spread of multi-resistant *Clostridioides difficile*”.

The second part of the study included partners from the FED-AMR project. We received ST11 WGS data from BFR, FLI, INSA, AGES and IP. The WGS comparison showed that most isolates clustered within the same country of origin. However, we also identified 11 international clusters counting 2 or 3 different countries, all within 0-2 cgMLST/wgMLST allele differences. This important finding indicates that these clones are able to spread across Europe possibly facilitated by veterinary or food sources. The international isolates contained ARG variants (aminoglycosides, beta-lactamases, fluoroquinolones and tetracycline) that aligns with the clustering and underlines the important multidrug resistant potential. Further studies in the upcoming months will focus on: 1) finalize the complete WGS data from all partners, 2) SNP analysis to compare/confirm cg/wgMLST findings and 3) a more detailed ARG analysis including associations with MGEs.

At 9-BfR in Y5, we have been focusing on comparative WGS analyses with special regard to RT049. Strains of this particular PCR-ribotype were mainly found in different compartments of the HOAL from Tartu, Estonia (partner 14-UT). From the 24 strains that were isolated in the Estonian soil and water samples provided to BfR, twelve belonged to RT049. All of them were positive for the classical toxin genes *tcdA* and *tcdB*. We performed WGS and subsequent cgMLST analysis on these isolates and compared them with the sequences that we received so far from partner 10-FLI, who was responsible for the isolation and characterization of *C. difficile* strains from manure and animal samples from the Estonian HOAL. The isolates from this HOAL showed less than four allelic differences, indicating a close

genetic relationship. This was true even for isolates from different sampling time points with up to nine months in between or from different compartments. Taking the epidemiological and temporal data into account, a long term persistence and the transmission of *C. difficile* RT049 between animal and the environment is very likely.

At the moment, we are sequencing the remaining RT049 strains from 36-INSA and plan to compare our sequence data with those from epidemiologically unrelated RT049 strains of different origins (human, animal, food) obtained by SSI and INSA. Further characterization will be conducted using resistance genes and virulence genes databases as well as the MGE database provided by 10-FLI.

A joint publication is planned to be submitted this year. The results will be presented at upcoming scientific conferences. Furthermore, we provided WGS data from seven RT078/126-ST11 strains to 13-SSI, one RT033 strain to 36-INSA and 18 RT002 strains to 13-SSI for inclusion in their phylogenetic analyses.

WP4-Determination of the selection pressures in the tested compartments of human, animal and environmental ecosystems (M25-M50)

All samples have been analyzed for antibiotics, herbicides and trace elements. WP4 is currently working on a harmonized statistical analysis in order to deliver a manuscript with the results obtained.

WP4-T2-Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in aqueous matrices (water) (M31-M50)

29 antibiotics are in the analytical scope of the LC-MSMS method used in WP4-T2, T3, T4 and T5: 4 tetracyclines, 7 sulphonamides, 10 fluoroquinolones, 7 macrolides and trimethoprim. 72 samples were analysed and in 10 samples antibiotics from 4 antimicrobial classes (macrolides, tetracyclines, fluoroquinolones and sulphonamides) were detected: azithromycin, oxytetracycline, enrofloxacin and sulfadimidine).

This task is finished.

WP4-T3- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in manure (M31-M50)

Results of 22 manure samples are currently available. Antibiotics from 2 antimicrobial classes (fluoroquinolones and tetracyclines) were detected in 12 samples (maximum values are 41 µg/kg marbofloxacin, 69 µg/kg enrofloxacin and ciprofloxacin; 124 µg/kg oxytetracycline; 768 µg/kg doxycycline). The concentrations of all five antibiotics exceeded the minimum selective concentrations. This indicated that under the given circumstances the detected antimicrobials were likely to select bacteria resistant to these compounds.

This task is finished.

WP4-T4- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in faeces (M35-M50)

24 samples were analysed. Antibiotics from 2 antimicrobial classes (fluoroquinolones and tetracyclines) were detected in 2 samples (maximum values are 265 µg/kg enrofloxacin; 1250 µg/kg oxytetracycline; 3440 µg/kg doxycycline). The concentrations of all 3 antibiotics exceeded the minimum selective concentrations. This indicated that under the given circumstances the detected antimicrobials were likely to select bacteria resistant to these compounds.

This task is finished.

WP4-T5- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in soil (M31-M50)

In this task, 118 samples were analysed. The tetracycline doxycycline was detected in 8 samples (6.8 %) in the range between 9 µg/kg and 20 µg/kg. The highest concentration could be detected at the minimum selective concentration.

This task is finished.

WP4-T6- Quantification of herbicides in agricultural soil (M31-M50)

The following substances were in the analytical scope of the LC-MSMS method: Glyphosate and its more stable degradation product AMPA (Aminomethylphosphonic acid), Glufosinate, 2,4-D (2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid), Metolachlor ESA the degradation product of Metolachlor, Bentazon and the degradation products of Metazachlor (Metazachlor ESA and Metazachlor OA).

The following samples were analysed:

114 soil samples: herbicides were detected in 66 samples (58 %) (maximum values are 200 µg/kg AMPA and 74 µg/kg glyphosate)

30 water samples: herbicides were detected in 26 samples (86.7 %) (maximum values are 4.3 µg/L AMPA and 0.7 µg/L Metolachlor ESA)

7 manure samples: herbicides were detected in 6 samples (maximum values are 91 µg/kg AMPA and 41 µg/kg glyphosate).

The observed glyphosate levels in the tested compartments were below the MICs and sub-inhibitory concentrations as analysed for Salmonella sp strains. It is likely that the observed glyphosate concentrations (wet weight) do not select for resistant bacteria or perturb bacterial populations.

This task is finished.

WP4-T7- Measurement of the concentration of trace elements in environmental samples gathered across participants countries (M31-M50)

The analyses by ICP-MS focused on the most relevant trace elements for co-selection (Cd, Cr, Cu, Co, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn). Additionally to these 8 key elements 19 more elements were in the analytical scope.

98 soil samples, 77 water samples 43 manure/faeces samples and 56 crop (including feed) samples were analysed. The concentrations of the 8 key elements were within the usual range for these compartments.

This task is finished.

WP5 : Identification of environmental conditions modulating transformation frequencies in soil microcosms and an in vitro porcine gut model (poGutMo) (laboratory studies) (M32-M60)

WP5 has in Y5 updated the whole WP and that included changing priorities to have a more focused approach. Some milestones and/or deliverables were deleted. Likewise, tasks names have been amended. A meeting was organised with WP5 colleagues to discuss the WP5 milestones and deliverables. It was agreed that the project was ambitious, given the allocated staff time and nature of the experimental studies. The project team also experienced some delays with the laboratory work due to COVID, setting up the gut model and all the associated tasks, including writing risk assessments for handling genetically modified organisms (GMOs) and performing troubleshooting experiments. Thus, it was agreed that the WP5 milestones and deliverables would be reviewed and updated to ensure practical feasibility. Moreover, conjugation would be established (alongside transformation) as an additional mechanism of AMR transfer, and to demonstrate the potential of the pig gut model for studying AMR transmission.

WP5-T1-ST2 : Optimisation of fermentation conditions to ensure suitable growth for *E. coli* J53 (M40-M57). [PRIOR name: JRP15-WP5-T1-ST2 Determine the optimal growth parameters for cultivating *E. coli* strains within the gut model (M40-M50).]

Previously, the pig gut microbiome communities were pooled, mixed and aliquoted as a source for faecal microbiome in the pig gut model, and the gut model conditions were standardised (so it represents the large intestine in terms of pH, temperature, etc., to allow for the optimal growth of the recipient strain, the faecal microbiome and subsequent fermentation).

We are currently optimising fermentation conditions *in vitro* to demonstrate suitable growth of *E. coli* J53 in the presence of faecal microbiota to ensure the successful detection of transformation events. We are going to test conditions such as co-culture, bacterial concentration, and faecal microbiota concentration. We are also investigating the use of AMR-encoding plasmids as another source for AMR resistance genes to mimic natural environmental conditions and will perform *in vitro* transformation experiments to confirm that the recipient strain uptakes the chosen plasmids in the pig gut media and conditions.

The task has been started and is still ongoing.

Start date delayed to M40. New end month: M57.

WP5-T1-ST3 Rates of transformation calculated by taking samples from the gut model and plating on agar plates supplemented with the appropriate antibiotics (M46-M50).

Start date delayed to M46. New end month: 50 (Year 4).

Once all conditions in D5.2 are optimised and we demonstrate transformation in the presence of gut microbiome we will determine the baseline rate of transformation in the final tested conditions.

The task has started and is finished.

WP5-T2: Demonstrating successful growth of Clostridial strains in pig gut media and conditions. [PRIOR name: JRP15-WP5-T2- Evaluate conditions that drive HGT and the emergence of AMR via transformation (M49-M56)]

Dr Aurore Poirier has just joined WP5 FED-AMR team one day a week to work on this task with support from Dr Marwa Hassan. We shall commence work on this task in June (M54). We have sourced the *C. difficile* strains, culture media and most reagents that are required.

Start date delayed to M54. New end month: M56.

WP5-T3- Effect of different environmental conditions on the expression of competence genes in *A. baylyi* determined using soil microcosms (M44-M56)

This task started in August 2022 (please replace by the appropriate M-number, thanks) and is being performed with *A. baylyi* as it is more suitable to show the effects on soil microcosms. RNA isolation from soil microcosms was established. RT-TaqMan qPCR systems for two competence genes and several *A. baylyi* housekeeping/reference genes have been designed and are available. Information on differential competence gene expression levels in relation to environmental stimuli (temperature shift, exposure to antibiotics, different nutrient levels) are expected to be available at the end of October 2022 in these pilot experiments.

This task is ongoing. New end month: M56.

WP6- Probabilistic and mechanistic models of the links between antimicrobial usage in animals, AMR in the environment, and the risks for public health.

In this task, we have now decided to carry out a systematic evidence map regarding environmental factors associated with AMR.

WP6-T1-ST1 Data Integration, Annotation and Association Analysis (afterwards: Systematic review: environmental factors associated with AMR) (M32-M60)

Start date delayed to M32.

As said in the previous report, due to challenges in obtaining the data required for setting up a machine learning model (in part related to COVID-19 restrictions), we have decided to carry out a systematic evidence map of the literature regarding environmental factors of AMR prevalence.

The proposed protocol for the systematic evidence map has been submitted to Environmental International and the protocol was registered in a public repository (<https://osf.io/a8gv6/>). We have incorporated the feedback from the Editor and it is now up for review. We have also including a new leading editor (Dr Inaki Deza-Cruz) as well as many co-authors, to help with the deliver. We have had two meetings with the editor that gave several suggestions. By M60 we expected the protocol and the screening to be completed.

This task is ongoing.

WP6-T2 Develop mechanistic models to address key questions regarding the spatio-temporal changes observed in microbiological communities (M34-M60)

WP6-T2.1 - Modelling microbial communities (M34-M60)

We are continuing to review the literature to keep updated with state-of-the-art techniques. We have developed and formulated a mathematical model for microbial communities. We have also tested different approaches to infer relevant parameters for published models and adapted some of these techniques to our model. In-silico data were developed and validated with our model. We are now further improving the model and start to use the model to address a few conceptual questions.

This task is ongoing.

Due to the departure of Dr Brian Gardner the scope of this task is now drastically reduced. However, he has agreed to carry on working on the project on a part-time basis until December 2022. We still aim to deliver a draft research paper by M60.

5.1.4.4.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR - WP1.6	Interim project report (T1.3.)	M47	M52		Public. Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057286	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR- WP2.4	Determination of naturally transformable bacteria in tested environmental compartments (T2.5)	M52		M56		
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR- WP2.6	16S metagenomics results: Microbial biodiversity and phylogenetic relationships of ARBs over ecosystem boundaries (T2.3, T2.6)	M52		M54	Public. Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057188	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.7	Quantity and stability of free extracellular DNA observed in environmental compartments tested so far (T2.7)	M52		M56		
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.8	Annual report for Y4 (WP2)	M49	M49		Public. Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057332	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.9	ARG dynamics in an agricultural testing area: Response of ARG concentrations according to different fertilisation techniques and crops over an annual growth period (WP2)	M54		M58		

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP3.2	Overview of genetic overlap between human and non-human <i>C. difficile</i> isolates (task 3.2 and task 3.3)	M50		M58		
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP3.3	Classification of pig farm compartments according to their role in the epidemiology of <i>C. difficile</i> (task 3.4).	M50		M58		
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.2	Quantitative results of antibiotics in water	M50	M50		Public. Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396025	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.3	Quantitative results of antibiotics in manure	M50	M50		Public. Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396070	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.4	Quantitative results of antibiotics in faeces	M50	M50		Public. Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396112	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.5	Quantitative results of antibiotics in soil	M50	M50		Public. Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396145	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.6	Quantitative results of herbicides in environmental samples	M50	M50		Public. Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6396160	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP4.7	Quantitative results of trace elements in environmental samples	M50	M53		Public. Uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057243	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.2	Optimal growth parameters for cultivating E. coli and transformation pilot experiments using AMR-encoding DNA are tested	M50		M57		
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.3	Optimal growth parameters for cultivating and demonstrating conjugation	M50		M57		

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		between the Clostridial strains are determined					
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.4	Transformation and Conjugation-mediated HGT efficiency rates are demonstrated in the pig gut model and the effect of a chosen antibiotic and/or TE maybe determined	M52		M59		
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.5	Conjugation-mediated HGT between the clostridial donor and recipient strains within the gut model determined	M52			This deliverable is redundant. It is duplicate of D-5.3.	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.6	Results from using chromosomal DNA derived from E. coli as ARG donor	M54			This deliverable has been changed and a justification has been sent to WP1 (D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.2)	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.7	Results from using lysate of E. coli as ARG donor	M51			This deliverable has been changed and a justification has been sent to WP1 (D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.2)	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP5.8	Results from pig gut model regarding HGT by transformation and conjugation in presence of selected antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals	M58			By delivering D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.4 we will get the same information that the one described in this deliverable. Results are being transferred between WPs. Therefore, it is not practical to report on this. Not enough time was allocated for such an ambitious deliverable, and it is not cost-effective to perform the analysis as described in the deliverable.	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.9	Results from pig gut model regarding HGT by transformation and conjugation in presence of selected antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals	M49			This deliverable has been changed and a justification has been sent to WP1. Results are being transferred between WPs. Therefore, it is not practical to report on this. Not enough time was allocated for such an ambitious deliverable, and it is	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
						not cost-effective to perform the analysis as described in the deliverable.	
15	D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.10	Results from pig gut model regarding HGT by transformation and conjugation in presence of selected antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals	M53			Results are being transferred between WPs. Therefore, it is not practical to report on this. Not enough time was allocated for such an ambitious deliverable, and it is not cost-effective to perform the analysis as described in the deliverable.	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.11	First results from soil microcosm experiments on effects of environmental conditions on transformation	M51		M58	Pilot experiments have been performed. RNA isolation from soil samples has been established. RT Taqman qPCR systems for competence and reference genes have been designed and are available. Delays were due to bottlenecks in availability of laboratory staff.	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP5.12	Results from pig gut model regarding HGT by transformation and conjugation in presence of selected antibiotics, herbicides and	M51			This deliverable has been changed and a justification has been sent to WP1. The content of this deliverable was duplicated.	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		heavy metals					
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP5.13	Results of the soil microcosm experiments regarding environmental effects on competence gene expression	M52		M58 October 2022	Please see "D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.11"	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP6.2	Findings presented at one international conference and one national conference.	M54	M54		We presented our results at two international conferences (ASM 2021 and One Conference 2022). See output section for more information. The deliverable document has not been drafted yet but the deliverable is finished.	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.4	Submission/publication of 1/2 paper(s) on how resilience of microbial communities depends on external environmental drivers and richness and diversity of the community.	M54		M60	This deliverable is ongoing. As already said, due to the departure of Dr. Brian Gardner the scope of this task is now drastically reduced. We now aim to one draft paper by the end of the project.	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.5	Main code for the mathematical modelling made available in public repository (e.g. GitHub) with associated documentation (which can be used as “Material and Method” section of the forthcoming publications).	M54	M57		<p>In the previous document this deliverable appeared as D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.3, not D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.5. Both deliverables are similar, 6.5 <u>now</u> is just an update on the code but the deliverable titles were switched.</p> <p>This deliverable relates to WP6 task 2, 'Modelling microbial communities', and describes prototype code written in Python, along with associated documentation, uploaded to the University of Surrey's online repository GitLab for version control purposes.</p>	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.6	Update of codes and documentations in public repository (e.g. GitHub).	M50			<p>As above, prototype code written in Python, along with associated documentation, uploaded to the University of Surrey's online repository GitLab for version control purposes. This deliverable is now duplicated because of the previous merging of the tasks. It is basically the same as D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.5</p>	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP6.7	Findings presented at one international conference and one	M54			<p>This deliverable is now duplicated and it is the same as D-JRP15-FEDAMR-</p>	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		national conference.				WP6.2.	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP6.8	Submission/publication of 1 paper on how temporal fluctuating systems affect the potential emergence of resistant strains	M54			The content would be essentially the same as the deliverable above. Please see comment on D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.4.	
15	D-JRP15-FEDAMR-WP6.9	Final update of codes and documentations in public repository (e.g. GitHub).	M54			This deliverable is now duplicated because of the previous merging of the tasks. It is basically the same as D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.5	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from WP 2021 (month)	Achieved Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
15	M-JRP15- p-AMR-19	Finalizing determination of transformable bacteria (T2.5)	M52	No	M56	This milestone is in progress and depends on the results of task 2.3 and therefore it has been delayed.
15	M-JRP15- p-AMR-21	Finalizing 16S metagenome analysis of obtained DNA isolates (T2.3)	M52	yes		This milestone is in progress due to the high amount of sequence data to be analysed.
15	M-JRP15- p-AMR-22	Finalizing assessment of clonal/lineage diversity of ARB (T2.6)	M52	yes		This milestone is in progress due to the high amount of sequence data to be analysed.
15	M-JRP15- p-AMR-23	Finalizing shot gun sequencing and bioinformatics and statistical analysis of NGS data (T2.3.1, T3.2.2, T2.3)	M53	yes		Statistical analysis ongoing. Target enrichment and 16S sequencing have already finished.
15	M-JRP15- p-AMR-24	Delivery of final annual report on WP2 + draft version of peer reviewed paper (WP2)	M54	Yes		
15	M-JRP15- p-AMR-26	Complete WGS on all included isolates	M46	yes		This milestone is in progress due to the high amount of sequence data to be analysed.
15	M-JRP15- p-AMR-27	Complete AMR profiles on all included isolates	M46	No	M59	This milestone is in progress since not all entries have completed the susceptibility tests.
15	M-JRP15- p-AMR-28	Genetic overlap-analysis human vs. non-human	M50	No	M60	
15	M-JRP15- p-AMR-29	Identification of transmission network as described above	M50	No	M60	

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from WP 2021 (month)	Achieved Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
15	M-JRP15-AMR-40	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M52	Yes		
15	M-JRP15-AMR-41	Antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals most likely to drive T through transformation applied to UoS.	M56	No	M57	
15	M-JRP15-AMR-42	DNA sent for whole-genome sequencing	M55	Yes		
15	M-JRP15-AMR-45	Deliver results from 1st round of gut model experiments WP6 leader for further modelling	M55		M55	
15	M-JRP15-AMR-46	Results from modelling in 6 communicated to inform parameters for use in 2nd round gut model experiments	M55		M55	Not feasible as explained above in the deliverables. Not feasible as explained above in the deliverables.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-43	Sub-strains of <i>E. coli</i> with appropriate antibiotic resistances and chromosomal DNA and plasmids prepared	M55	Yes		Rifampicin resistant <i>E. coli</i> strain has been generated and appropriate nucleic acid preparations have been made.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-44	Porcine gut model set up using faecal samples obtained through WP2, samples stored for trace element analysis (WP4) – experiments can start	M51	Yes		All samples are stored for trace element analysis
15	M-JRP15-AMR-47	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace	M50	Yes		All samples are stored for trace element analysis

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from (WP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
		ment analysis (WP4)				
15	M-JRP15-AMR-48	Deliver results from 1 st round of gut model experiments to WP6 leader for further modelling	M53			Duplicated. This milestone is not applicable as we need to collect enough samples to be financially feasible to sequence before we can deliver results to WP6. Additionally, sequencing has been delayed as we are troubleshooting.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-49	Results from modelling in 6 communicated to inform parameters for use in 2 nd round of gut model experiments	M46			Duplicated. This milestone is not applicable as depending on the previous milestone is no longer applicable.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-50	Deliver results from 2 nd round of gut model experiments to WP6 leader for further modelling	M50			Duplicated. This milestone is not applicable as we need to collect enough samples to be financially feasible to sequence before we can deliver results to WP6. Additionally, sequencing has been delayed as we are troubleshooting.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-51	Results from modelling in 6 communicated to inform parameters for use in 3 rd and final round of gut model experiments	M51			Duplicated. This milestone is not applicable as depending on the previous milestone is no longer applicable.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-52	Deliver results from soil microcosm experiments to WP6 leader for final modelling	M52			This will depend on results from soil microcosm experiments. Due to the departure of Dr Gardner we need to reassess feasibility of this milestone.

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from WP 2021 (month)	Achieved Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
15	M-JRP15-AMR-56	Literature review on situating ecological systems in a gut model approach.	M45	Yes		The review of the literature is an ongoing task to ensure we are updated with the state of art.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-57	Analysis of data produced from the 1 st round of gut model experiments. Formulation and implementation of the model to identify how natural fluctuations depend on the drivers. Results communicated to WP5 leader.	M46	No		Not feasible. Please see comments in the 5 deliverables.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-58	Analysis of data produced from the 2 nd round of gut model experiments. Formulation and implementation of the model to identify how natural fluctuations depend on the drivers. Results communicated to WP5 leader.	M50	No		Not feasible. Please see comments in the 5 deliverables.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-59	Application of the model to address specific questions and dissemination of findings in peer-reviewed publications and conferences.	M50	No		Partially achieved: the mathematical model has been presented in the OHEJP conference in Brian in continuing work on this milestone.
15	M-JRP15-AMR-60	Analysis of data produced from the 3 rd and final round of model experiments. Formulation and implementation of the	M56			No longer feasible. This milestone is not applicable as depending on the previous milestone is no longer applicable.

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from (WP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
		model to identify how natural fluctuations depend on drivers. Results communicated to 5 leader.				
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-61	Application of the model to address specific questions and dissemination of findings in peer-reviewed publications and conferences	M54			This is the same as milestone 59.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-62	Finding presented at one international conference and one national conference	M54	Yes		The mathematical model has been presented in OHEJP conferences.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-63	Submission/publication of 1 paper on how temporal fluctuating systems affect the potential urgency of resistant strains.	M54			This is actually a deliverable. Please see deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.4.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-64	Finishing annual report (WP2)	M48	No	M59	Since the FED-AMR project was extended December 2022, the WP2 annual report for Y5 will be delivered at the end of Y5.

5.1.4.4.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Draft Genome Sequence of a Multidrug-Resistant Escherichia coli Sequence Type 1193 Pandemic Clone Isolated from Wastewater in Austria DOI: 10.1128/MRA.00762-21 https://zenodo.org/record/5770120#.YeZ1rd8xl4F	YES	NO	1.050,00 \$ 929,38 €
Assessment of the Transmission Dynamics of Clostridioides difficile in a Farm Environment Reveals the Presence of a New Toxigenic Strain Connected to Swine Production. doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.858310 https://zenodo.org/record/6857162#.Yyh-SXZByUk	YES	NO	2950,00 \$ 2750,00 €
Whole Genome Sequencing-based characterization of antimicrobial resistance in clinically-relevant bacteria isolated at the human-animal-environment interface in Austria Journal. International Journal of Molecular Sciences. Manuscript ID : ijms-1921579 (Under review, submitted 1 September 2022)	YES	NO	1640 CHF 1683,1 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Airborne spores' dissemination of a swine associated Clostridioides difficile clone. Anaerobe (Under review, submitted 13th August 2022) Manuscript Number: ANAE22-159	YES	NO	3,080 \$

Additional output

WP1

Oral presentation

- Werner Ruppitsch. Dissemination workshop on preparedness 2022 organized by OHEJP-WP5 on the topic AMR movement over ecosystem boundaries.
- Werner Ruppitsch. “FED-AMR: The role of free extracellular DNA in dissemination of antimicrobial resistance over ecosystem boundaries along the food/feed chain (One Health EJP)”, One Conference, 21st-24th June, Brussels, Belgium.

WP2

Poster presentations

- D. Olivença; A. Cabal; T. Tenson; M. Hassan; V. Manageiro; E. Dias; T. Rosado; V. Kõiv; V. Kisand; G. Rab; J. Jeremejeva; K. Telling; K. Arbo; M. Chambers; R. Laragione; E. Voit; Z. Drahošová; M. Kořínková; M. Woegerbauer; W. Ruppitsch; M. Caniça; A. de Menezes 2022. “Microbial and antimicrobial resistance gene diversity in extracellular and total DNA across rural ecosystem barriers in Europe”; OHEJP ASM 2022, Orvieto, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6857015>
- A Cabal Rosel; N. Peischl, B. Daza, A Stöger, G Rab; K Rathhammer; F Allerberger; M Wögerbauer, W Ruppitsch. 2022. “Antimicrobial resistance and genetic relatedness of environmental bacteria across the animal-human-wildlife interface in Austria”; ECCMID 2022, Lisbon, Portugal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6641985>
- Manageiro, R Coelho, T Rosado, P Vieira, L Reis, R Matias, J Rodrigues, C Menezes, E Ferreira, A Sequeira, O Moreira, E Dias, M Caniça. 2022. Resistome, mobilome and virulome analysis of Enterobacter cloacae complex strains isolated from the water environment. ECCMID 2022, Lisbon, Portugal
- A de Menezes, M Caniça, S Ciutti, L Griffin, A Haigh, AC Rosel, W Ruppitsch. 2022. Antibiotic resistance and AMR gene seasonality patterns in fallow deer (Dama dama) with different levels of human interaction: a case study of Ireland. Annual Conference of the UK-Ireland Microbiological Society, Belfast, UK (Oral communication).

Master Thesis

- R Coelho. 2022. Caracterização da Resistência aos Antibióticos em estirpes isoladas de diferentes reservatórios ambientais. [Characterization of Antibiotic Resistance in Strains Isolated from Different Environmental Reservoirs]. Lisbon, Portugal

WP3

Poster presentation

- F. Alves; R. Castro; M. Pinto; M. Oliveira; C. Pomba; M. Oleastro 2022. “Clostridioides difficile in companion animals, a One Health concern?” One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, Orvieto, Italy.2022. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6641860>
- “Potential for the zoonotic spread of multi-resistant Clostridioides difficile “ ECCMID 2022 <https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.6641860.svg>
 - resulted in the following article in the Guardian: “Pigs can pass deadly superbugs to people, study reveals”. <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2022/apr/24/pigs-can-pass-deadly-superbugs-to-people-study-reveals>

- A. Scholtzek; P. Witt; G. Raatz; A. Bhatte; S. Maurischat 2022. "Prevalence of Clostridioides difficile in strawberries from Germany". One Conference 2022, Brussels, Belgium.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6856987>

WP4

Abstract

- WP4- Abstract entitled "Analysis of antimicrobials in environmental samples as a part of determination of selection pressures for antimicrobial resistance" accepted at Euroresidue IX conference. 23rd-25thMay 2022, Egmond aan Zee, The Netherlands.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4916158>

WP5

Poster presentation

- M. Hassan; M. Getino; J. Leng; M. Chambers; R. M. La Ragione. 2022. "Development of an in vitro pig gut model for evaluating factors driving antimicrobial resistance" ; OHEJP ASM 2022, Orvieto, Italy.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6642824>

WP6

WP6- Abstract in Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 (e-poster):

- B Gardner, M M Hassan, M Chambers, R M La Ragoine, G Lo Iacono, 2021. "Ecological modelling of microbial communities subject to perturbation", ASM 2021,
<https://zenodo.org/record/4915941#.YTsqS-dCR4E>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915941>

Poster presentation

- B Gardner, L C Gonzalez Villeta; J Leng; M M. Hassan; M Chambers; R M La Ragione; G Lo Iacono. 2022. "Mechanistic modelling of microbial communities with insights from an in vitro pig gut model", ASM 2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6856915>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6856915>
- B. Gardner; M. M. Hassan; M. Chambers; R. M. La Ragione; G. Lo Iacono 2022. "Modelling the dynamics and long-term stability of perturbed gut microbiota", One Conference 2022, Brussels, Belgium.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6860460>.

5.1.4.5 JRP16-R2-ET2.2-TELE-Vir

5.1.4.5.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

TELE-Vir is a 2.5 year (now 3.0 with an extension of six months) Joint Research Project of the One Health EJP that focusses on developing a fast point-of-evidence (poi) toolbox for identification and characterization of emerging virus threats for human and/or domestic and wildlife animals.

In the TELE-Vir project we are combining a suitable field-deployable point-of-care approach, and a direct upload of genomic, phenotypic and epidemiological data into a user-friendly bioinformatics toolkit for fast identification and characterization of new emerging virus threats. We developed by adapting existing point-of care methods a harmonized poi protocol for field analysis. The poi protocol requires a minimum of laboratory equipment and is designed to be compatible with MinION sequencing technology. Moreover, we are combining and integrating in the poi toolbox phenotypic and epidemiological data to aid risk assessment and management. The poi toolbox will be made

available publicly, and disseminated across interested national and international parties, for example shared with established networks. The poi toolbox will be tested in field studies to identify RNA and DNA viruses collected from different sample materials and the results are to be expected at the end of Y5.

The worldwide SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has had a great impact on the TELE-Vir project. There has been national lockdowns, laboratories have been closed or allocated for SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics. There has been a worldwide shortage of basic laboratory reagents and equipment, which has influenced the ability to perform basic laboratory experiments. However, the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has also a positive influence on the project, as we demonstrated that we can inactivate the SARS-CoV-2, besides other RNA viruses being non-infectious and can develop alternative methods for NA extraction (WP3), which is in line with the development of a field-based protocol for MinION sequencing using a minimum of laboratory equipment (the poi tool box). We also could develop the field base metagenomics protocol using SARS-CoV-2 as model virus.

We agreed on focusing on RNA viruses as the newly emerged SARS-CoV-2, but also on DNA viruses to apply our approach. WP2 supported this approach by: i) shaping the “surveillance-oriented” pipeline (from reads to quality control, mutations detection, consensus generation, classification, alignments, phylogenetics, geno-pheno screening, etc.) to handle sequence data of any virus, while providing further virus-specific utilities for viruses of interest, namely coronaviruses, influenza viruses and, most recently, monkeypox (MPXV); ii) developing and implementing a novel pathogen detection module, from reads and quality control to identification of both RNA and DNA viruses.

The pandemic has both given new opportunities in this area with overwhelming volumes of data and tools becoming available as well as challenges caused by data quality, and logistical constraints and restrictions. In this context, the TELE-Vir platform is being built to enhance the detection and surveillance of viral pathogens, by facilitating both sequencing data analysis and output navigation and interpretation.

Challenged by the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, the TELE-Vir consortium has shown impressive resourcefulness and adaptability. Deliverables and reports of the first two years were reached and submitted. The TELE-Vir consortium meets regularly to exchange, to discuss problems and to find solutions to guarantee the best possible progress and success of the project. Results are disseminated as scientific publications and presentation at workshops, webinars and conferences including OneHealth EJP conferences.

Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic has had also a positive impact on the TELE-Vir project and many of the experiences and problems encountered during the crisis have been used or translated to the development of the TELE-Vir poi-tool box, which will help in the future to control outbreaks of new emerging viruses at national, regional, European and even global levels.

5.1.4.5.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1: Coordination and data management

WP1-T1

WP1-T1-ST1.1

JRP16-WP1-T1- Coordination and project management

Project management and coordination of the project is proceeding according to the plan. The WP1 leaders organize regular meetings for the whole TELE-Vir consortium to guarantee the best outcome of the project. This is ongoing.

JRP16-WP1-T2- Data management

Data management plan (DMP) was submitted in the first year of the project (December 2020) and is updated during the project (ongoing)

JRP16-WP1-T3- Kick-off-meeting at IZSAM, Italy

The kick off meeting of the TELE-Vir project was held on January 21st – 22nd 2020 at the International Centre for Veterinary Training and Information "F. Gramenzi" (CIFIV) of Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise "G. Caporale" (Via G. Caporale, Teramo, Italy). All partners were present. This task is completed.

JRP16-WP1-T4-1st TELE-Vir meeting online, organized by SSI

The first meeting of the TELE-Vir project was held on January 25th 2021 as an online meeting. All partners were present. This task is completed.

JRP16-WP1-T5-2nd TELE-Vir meeting at SSI, DK

The final annual meeting took place on the 23-24th of June 2022 at SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark. This task is completed

JRP16-WP1-T6-Workshop in the use of the POI toolbox at SSI, DK

The workshop took place on the 23-24th of June 2022 at SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark in combination with the annual meeting. This task is completed

WP2: Development of a Bioinformatics tool-kit for POI data analysis

JRP16-WP2-T1- Survey and collection of databases for genotype-phenotype associations

At the kick-off meeting it was agreed that the first stage was selection of important phenotypic characteristics for the chosen model virus (influenza and coronaviruses), followed by assessment of the amount and quality of data available. During M25-M36, a literature review was performed to identify coronavirus phenotypes of relevance to tropism, emergence, and clinical disease, and any data available for their prediction based on genotype. A summary was circulated to partner institutes and associated virologists, together with a survey. The aims of the survey were two-fold: (1) to obtain the views of virologists (potential end users of the TELE-Vir toolkit) on coronavirus phenotype prediction and variant monitoring activities that they would like to see in a genomic surveillance toolkit; and (2) to obtain test datasets for further development of the toolkit.

During M37-M48, progress covered several fronts. The results of the coronavirus survey were reviewed and discussed in TELE-Vir internal meetings, and presented as a poster at the OHEJP ASM 2021. Additionally, a scoping review to identify relevant phenotypes and their feasibility of prediction was performed for influenza A virus. Finally, data linking genotypes (lineages and mutations) with phenotypic changes for both SARS-CoV-2 and influenza A virus were collected from available literature.

For SARS-CoV-2, genotype-phenotype data are expanding rapidly, and data collection will have to continue to keep the database up-to-date and relevant. A decision was reached by the WP2 team to investigate making use of curated online databases for this purpose. Suitable databases (such as <https://sars2.cvr.gla.ac.uk/cog-uk> and <https://github.com/nodrogluap/pokay/tree/master/data>) have been selected and used as proof-of-concept to test a novel bioinformatics tool for rapid screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes (see WP2-T3).

JRP16-WP2-T2- Development of bioinformatics modules for third-generation sequencing analysis and pathogen identification

In the context of pathogen detection and field genome sequencing, there are multiple advantages in either using online bioinformatics tools or running the platforms locally. As such, a Docker version of the online INSaFLU platform has been built and distributed publicly (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/docker>) in order to facilitate the local installation process. INSaFLU users, TELE-Vir partners and other

stakeholders (e.g., ECDC) were notified of this novel feature. INSaFLU has been successfully installed and run locally 'offline' on partner computer servers including at UoS.

As a response to COVID-19 pandemic, both the locally installed INSaFLU version and original website (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/>) were adapted to better accommodate the identification and genome-based analyses of the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2), as follows:

- a new module for rapid assignment of Human Betacoronavirus (BetaCoV), including the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2), has been developed and implemented, and the rationale behind the classification and outputs was documented (https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/data_analysis.html#influenza-type-and-sub-type-identification-and-human-betacoronavirus-classification-as-of-march-2020; check more details in the list of current INSaFLU genetic markers used for Influenza type and sub-type identification and Human Betacoronavirus classification);
- the publicly available SARS-CoV-2 reference genome sequence (NCBI accession number MN908947) was inserted as default in the INSaFLU reference database;
- multitasking configurations were changed, considerably speeding up the analyses, and the maximum upload file size was made more flexible;
- a new tab “Settings” was created making software parameterization more flexible and tailored to SARS-CoV-2 NGS analyses, with emphasis on including user-defined parameters for reads quality analysis, mapping and consensus generation.
- automatic masking of low coverage regions was incorporated in the platform, i.e., automatic generation of consensus sequences for incomplete locus, i.e., undefined nucleotides (“N”) are automatically introduced in low coverage regions at a user-selected coverage thresholds
- an automate pipeline for Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) data analysis was optimized and implemented in INSaFLU, from raw reads to quality analysis, reference-based generation/curation of consensus sequences, mutation annotation, gene/protein/genome alignments, phylogenetic tree, metadata visualization, etc (details about the pipeline, including software version, default settings, etc, can be found in: https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/data_analysis.html#). By automatically detecting the sequencing technologies (e.g., Illumina, or ONT) and subsequently allocating the technology-specific pipeline, the platform allows flexible data analysis and sample comparison regardless the technology used. This flexibility is particularly useful, for instance, in the context of genomic epidemiology consortia with centralized data analysis, but decentralized sequencing. Partner Sciensano shared ONT data on animal influenza A viruses, SARS-CoV-2, and locally implemented the INSaFLU pipeline, and, in a joined effort with partner INSA evaluated the assembly approach for animal DNA viruses (LSDV). Read data was also shared by partner SSI in order to evaluate the pipeline performance on ONT data.
- Automatic SARS-CoV-2 Pango lineages (<https://pangolin.cog-uk.io/>) assignment using Pangolin (<https://github.com/cov-lineages/pangolin>), as described by Rambaut and colleagues (Nat Microbiol; 5:1403-1407), was integrated in both the locally installable and website versions of the platform. Whenever a new Pangolin / Pangolearn version is released, a button “Update Pango lineage” is automatically made available, so that users can re-assign all samples in the project using the latest software/database versions.
- Direct links for consensus sequences analysis using Nextclade (<https://clades.nextstrain.org/>) were also included in the INSaFLU online, allowing an easy and rapid SARS-CoV-2 clade classification, mutation exploration and other analyses available at the Nextclade framework. Meanwhile, this functionality was further expanded to launch automate Nextclade exploration of seasonal influenza sequence data.

- A first version of the module for the rapid mapping-free influenza type and subtype/lineage identification, as well as Human Betacoronavirus (BetaCov) identification, using ONT read data was also released in both platform versions (locally installable and online).
- With the emergence of Omicron variant, the database for rapid assignment of Human Betacoronavirus (BetaCoV) was updated to enable a rapid and automated mapping-free detection of Omicron reads from both Illumina and ONT data.

These and other updates were documented and are available at full INSaFLU documentation webpage: (<https://insafllu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>) and Github (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/>)

One of the main goals of this task is also to upgrade the platform for automatic pathogen identification in order to support both human and veterinary clinical practice and disease outbreak investigations. After reviewing the current state-of-the-art of the field of bioinformatic pipelines for metagenomic virus diagnostics, a modular pipeline is being developed, incorporating the key steps of metagenomics taxonomic classification, namely: read quality control, host-depletion / viral enrichment, genome assembly, and reads/contig classification. Specifically, we are testing software (such as Centrifuge, Diamond, Kaiju, Kraken2, KrakenUniq, BLAST) and databases (such as NCBI, RVDB, UniProt, Virosaurus) commonly used in virological diagnostic laboratories on clinical metagenomics using datasets that have been well characterized by RT-PCR. This will allow us to benchmark the different workflows (i.e., test combinations of different components, reference databases and/or parameters) in order to finely explore how these different tools behave and, ultimately, to determine the best approach(es) to be implemented in the TELE-Vir toolbox. In parallel, work is ongoing to design, develop and implement user-friendly visual solutions for output reporting. In fact, independent of the workflow(s) that we ultimately choose to integrate into the platform, each classification run will culminate in user-oriented reports with a list of the most-likely suspected viruses, each accompanied by several robust and diagnostic-oriented metrics. We place particular emphasis on the usefulness and accessibility of end-user reports, as it is our intention that this toolbox will serve to strengthen output interpretation and decision-making on the part of users. Work is ongoing to fully implement this new diagnosis-oriented “pathogen detection” module into the INSaFLU- TELE-Vir platform, coupled with its inter-connectivity with the existing “surveillance-oriented” for an enhanced detection and monitoring of viral pathogens.

JRP16-WP2-T3- Development of bioinformatics modules for sequence curation and phenotypic association

The basis for a genotype-phenotype association module was developed, leading to the release of a bioinformatics tool for rapid screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/alg2pheno>; <https://pypi.org/project/alg2pheno/>). The module takes as input a nucleotide / protein alignment (as generated by the existing INSaFLU pipeline), and detects mutations in each of the sequences. It then rapidly screens these mutations against a database of known genotype-phenotype associations (such as, amino acid site changes already linked to: antiviral resistance, resistance to neutralizing antibodies, enhanced affinity to host-receptors antibodies or enhanced transmissibility), and generates a user-friendly overview of phenotypes predicted for each sequence. As a proof of principle, SARS-CoV-2 Spike alignments were screened using the `alg2pheno` tool against two databases: i) “COG-UK Antigenic mutations” (<https://sars2.cvr.gla.ac.uk/cog-uk/>; hosted by the COG-UK consortium), which currently includes >500 Spike amino acid replacements reported to confer antigenic change; 2) “Pokay” database (<https://github.com/nodrogluap/pokay>; hosted by University of Calgary, Canada), which is a literature-based compilation of hundreds of SARS-CoV-2 mutations potentially linked to multiple phenotypes. A pilot incorporation of the `alg2pheno` tool into the INSaFLU platform has already been implemented to automate the generation of user-friendly reports on repertoire of “relevant” mutations and their potential impact on phenotype. Working is ongoing to adapt this module to be compatible with other genotype-phenotype databases (such as, those relying in multiple reference sequences, e.g., influenza).

Additionally, we continue to investigate the feasibility of inferring biochemical and immunological properties, using existing models and machine learning approaches being tested at UoS. In this context (and in work aligned with JIP COVRIN), we have been exploring SARS-CoV-2 antigenic variation and its genetic determinants, using antigenic cartography analysis of published datasets as well as data received from partner SSI. Antigenic cartography offers a robust and reliable way to measure immunological properties using serological data and multidimensional scaling. The result is quantified antigenic distances between viruses, which can then be compared with genetic distances derived from sequence data. Proof of principle has previously been demonstrated for influenza virus where the antigenic effect of individual mutations has been inferred, allowing prediction of antigenic variation (phenotype) from genetic data (genotype). Antigenic distances between key SARS-CoV-2 variants are currently being measured using rabbit sera in collaboration with SSI, for comparison with genetic data.

JRP16-WP2-T4- Development of bioinformatics modules for genomic and metadata integration towards enhanced surveillance

Following the kick-off meeting, a strategic approach was agreed to achieve this task, including the upgrade of the existing platform with functionalities for detailed comparative genomics against genome sequences from known viruses and the development and integration of functionalities for surveillance-oriented phylogenetics and temporal/geographical data integration/analysis. The implementation of the novel functionalities will be focused on fitting the needs of labs working in different sectors (vet, PH, etc.) and that can be handled by users from multidisciplinary fields. In this context, INSaFLU was already upgraded to easily display metadata on phylogenetic trees (through user-defined node colouring and metadata blocks), thus facilitating integration of relevant epidemiological and/or clinical data and pathogen genomic data (https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/change_log.html). Other functionalities for better data navigation and interpretation were also implemented, namely the inclusion of novel interactive and dynamic “expand-and-collapse” panels for enhanced report of: 1) all detected mutations (including detailed information about genome position, nucleotide change, coverage evidence, frequency, impact at protein level, etc); ii) the mean depth of coverage and horizontal coverage per locus for all samples using interactive color-coded buttons; iii) mutations potentially linked to known phenotypes (pilot version). A pilot integration of Nextstrain tools (<https://nextstrain.org/>) was also performed, allowing the temporal and phylogeographical analysis involving consensus sequences generated in the platform as well as external sequences (e.g., sequences retrieved from GISAID). Working is ongoing to incorporate other tools (namely, ReporTree: <https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>) that enhance the rapid identification of pathogen genetic clusters and their linkage with surveillance (clinical /epidemiological) metadata. Still, further developments are ongoing, dependent on tasks 2 and

JRP16-WP2-T5-development of a user and surveillance oriented web-based interface

This task is in direct linkage with T2-T4 tasks, aiming at continuously optimizing the user interface so that it can provide final graphical outputs that can be easily interpreted by a broad audience, not only bioinformaticians, but also other scientists (e.g., virologists, epidemiologists) and decision makers with little computational background. Besides the advances described in T2-T4, we are investigating approaches to: i) synchronize local and web instances of the platform, allowing an easier integration and sharing of data, i.e., results of local analysis (“offline”) can be “communicated” to a centralized repository with web access; ii) facilitate data flow and sharing with external resources (GISAID/NCBI/ENA...).

WP3: Development of a protocol for POI MinION sequencing

JRP16-WP3-T1- Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment

The virucidal activity of MagNA Pure Lysis Binding (MPLB) buffer used at lower concentrations than recommended by producer was assessed against selected animal and human virus species. Depending

on the virus species MPLB-buffer was able to efficiently inactivate viruses at concentrations ranging from 15% to 30 %.

Reducing transmission risk during sample handling is paramount. Previous studies have shown virus inactivation abilities of the highly cytotoxic MagNA Pure Lysis Binding (MPLB) buffer used for nucleic acid extraction and purification (Rosenstierne et al. *Journal of clinical microbiology*. 2016 Oct;54(10):2521-9 ; Vinner and Fomsgaard, 2007. *Journal of virological methods*, 146(1-2), pp.401-404.). In this study, we show how 20 minutes of incubation in MPLB-buffer at room-temperature produce rapid inactivation of the SARS-CoV-2 using a modified published protocol by Rosenstierne et al (2016).

Two human SARS-CoV-2 isolates of 10^5 and 10^6 Tissue Culture Infectious Dose₅₀/ml were incubated 1:1 with MPLB-buffer or PBS (positive controls) for 20 minutes. The mixture was diluted to non-cytotoxic MPLB-buffer concentrations (determined empirically) and incubated on VeroE6 cells. Supernatant and cells were harvested at multiple time-points in biological duplicates with technical triplicates. We used reverse transcription quantitative-PCR (RT-qPCR) with a standard curve for quantification. To ensure inactivation, we serially passaged supernatant from a 144h culture and measured active replicating virus at the 24h time-point with a SARS-CoV-2 E-gene RT-qPCR

Results. MPLB-buffer incubated SARS-CoV-2 samples were non-infectious in the 10^{-4} MPLB-buffer dilution, except three samples indicated by median ct-value 39.8 (IQR=4.8) from the 10^5 TCID₅₀/ml stock. The control grew efficiently with median ct-values 11.8 (IQR=1.8) for cells and 16.1 (IQR=1.8) for supernatant. The sub-genomic RT-qPCR for the 24h time-point showed no evidence for virus replication, including the three exceptive samples.

We show that MPLB-buffer can reduce SARS-CoV-2 titers at least 2-log units. With this protocol, we can facilitate POI-diagnosis and promote field research without risk of infection. Therefore, we implemented this method into the first SOP.

WP3-T2- Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample NA purification

The use of MagNA Pure Lysis Binding (MPLB) buffer as a field-deployable method for viral NA extraction and purification has been proven useful for targeted diagnostics of EBOV using RT-qPCR (Rosenstierne et al. 2018. *Journal of visualized experiments: JoVE*, (136)). The same method has been tested successfully on grown SARS-CoV-2 isolates and human papilloma virus samples.

WP3-T3- Development and validation of a S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing (DNA & RNA)

Astroviruses – initial testing

The protocol was tested on a well-characterized porcine fecal sample obtained from one of the SPF pig farms in Sweden, which contained infection with several porcine astrovirus (PoAstV) species. The samples were slurried in PBS before DNase and filtration treatment. Very few of the sequenced reads (less than 0,3%) were from Astroviruses but several Astroviruses virus were detected by the method.

African swine fever – initial testing

Two different SOPs for MinION sequencing of African swine fever virus (ASFV) directly from positive samples were tested. After quality and quantity check of genomic DNA (gDNA) by Agilent tapestation and Qubit fluorometer, we used two different library preparation kits, Rapid Barcoding Kit 96 (SQK-RBK110.96) and a combination of Ligation Sequencing Kit (SQK-LSK110) and Native Barcoding Kit 24 (SQK-NBD112.24) for multiplexing samples. Rapid Barcoding Kit 96 (SQK-RBK110.96) is a PCR-free method that eliminate PCR bias and retains base modification information. This kit requires 50 ng of input DNA in a total volume of 9 ul per sample and takes less than 60 minutes. Ligation Sequencing Kit (SQK-LSK110) is optimized for throughput and long reads. The protocol includes DNA ends repair and dA-tailed using the NEBNext End Repair/dA-tailing module, and ligation of sequencing adapters onto

the prepared ends. For this kit the input DNA is 1 ug in a total volume of 47 ul per sample and the protocol takes about 2 hours. After priming the flowcell R9.4.1 (FLO-MIN106), we loaded the pool libraries and operated onto MinKNOW software to set-up the run parameters. We selected 24 hours as run time and Fast basecalling as Basecall model for both libraries. After starting run, we launch Fastq WIMP analysis on EPI2ME platform for taxonomic classification of the reads. The study is ongoing.

Metagenomic analysis of human clinical samples

The Shotgun Metagenomic approach allows to sequence comprehensively all microorganisms present in a given complex sample. Shotgun metagenomics also provides a means to study unculturable microorganisms that are otherwise difficult or impossible to analyze.

The SOP provides all the steps necessary to perform DNA and RNA extractions starting from biological specimens (whole blood, tissue, swab, urine, etc.), sequencing independent single primer amplification (SISPA) protocol, quantity control of input, library preparation, and eventually deep sequencing on the MinION platform.

Total Nucleic Acids (NA) extraction is performed by High Pure Viral Nucleic Acid kit (Roche). SISPA protocol is used to obtain cDNA by a random-tagged primer (FR26RV-N) consisting of six random nucleotides and a 20 nucleotides (nt) tag, synthesis of the second strand of cDNA will be achieved by 3'-5' Klenow Polymerase and PCR amplification step of ds cDNA is accomplished by a single primer (FR-20RV) complementary to the 20 nt tag.

We tested two different MinION library preparation kits: Rapid Barcoding Kit 96 (SQK-RBK110.96) and Ligation Sequencing Kit (SQK-LSK110).

We applied this protocol to analyze human samples received from Teramo hospital. In particular, we received two types of samples: a blood sample collected from patient with sepsis and multiple organs failure and a liquor collected from patient with meningoencephalitis. All the tests performed for direct detection of pathogens responsible for these symptoms were unsuccessful.

After priming and loading of the flowcell R9.4.1 (FLO-MIN106), we operated onto MinKNOW software to set-up the run parameters. We selected 24 hours as run time and Fast basecalling as Basecall model to obtain fastq files in real time. The study is ongoing.

Human papilloma virus (HPV) and SARS-CoV-2 – protocol developed for field studies performed in Y5

Initially a multiplexed approach was tested, where 4 and 12 individual samples were multiplexed using the Rapid Barcoding Kit (Oxford Nanopore Technology). The DNA concentrations of the samples were determined using a Qubit Fluorimeter (Life Technologies) and used to normalize the input material for sequencing libraries. Here, sample concentrations were standardized to contain 400 ng DNA (in 7.5 µl) when possible, incubated with 2.5 µl of the individual barcodes for 1 minute at 30°C and then 80°C, before 10 µl of multiplexed samples were incubated for another 5 minutes at room temperature with the rapid adaptor enzyme. Samples were included despite not meeting the library input recommendations (400 ng). The protocol suggestion of a bead purification step when multiplexing four or more samples was omitted for faster library preparation with field use in mind. The libraries were loaded and sequenced on R9.4.1 flowcells on the MK1C device (Oxford Nanopore Technology) with default settings, fast base calling enabled and a run length of 20 hours. DNase/RNase free water was included as a negative control.

For the final protocol a single sample approach using the Rapid sequencing Kit (SQK-RAD004) was tested and validated. This was done to reduce library preparation time and to simplify the field based protocol. The library was loaded on R9.4.1 flowcells and sequenced on the MinION device, with fast basecalling and a run length of up to 20 hours.

WP4-T5-Proof-of-concept

All TELE-Vir partners involved in WP4 have made an outline and presented it at the annual meeting in June in Copenhagen.

The field studies are ongoing M55-58. All results will be gathered at the end of M58 and be included into the 12 month report. However, here are the first examples for sample collection and POI tool kit application.

(INIA, Spain)

Here is a first example of sample collection needed for the field studies performed in Y5.

A first set of animal samples (birds and horses) from field clinical cases has been gathered. The samples were subjected to preliminary diagnosis of suspected flavivirus infection by PCR yielding a negative result, thus all remain undiagnosed.

On the other hand, some samples from two cats showing clinical signs and living with a SARS-CoV-2 infected person were collected and further diagnosed as positive for SARS-CoV-2 infection.

The samples are stored at -80°C and will be considered for testing in the proof-of-concept experiments.

A panel of oral swabs and feathers were collected from clinically affected red-legged partridges experimentally infected with different strains of WNV (taken from in vivo studies carried out within a national project at BSL-3 animal facilities of CISA-INIA-CSIC, Spain). Samples were processed immediately after their collection to mimic as much as possible the action in an emergency scenario in field conditions. Following the SOP produced in the WP3, fresh samples were treated with DNase, filtrated and inactivated with the MPLB-buffer, and were further stored at room temperature until further step. Two initial experiments running the whole TELE-Vir SOP have been performed testing one sample in each assay. Data analysis is ongoing.

(IZSLER, Italy)

A first set of 20 tracheal swabs were collected from turkeys showing respiratory signs referable to avian metapneumovirus (aMPV). These samples were not frozen and were tested for aMPV detection by RT-PCR, all of which tested positive. Samples were then analysed in pools of 5 animals (no. 5 samples) as a protocol for avian influenza analysis using the MinION Mk1B device for metagenomics virus detection. Two aliquots of all samples were analysed in parallel by two different protocols for whole transcriptome amplification (WTA) and whole genome amplification (WGA) using the rapid barcoding sequencing kit. Two aliquots of one negative sample were included as negative control in each protocol. Run summary report showed 265.45 Mb of estimated bases, 2,88 GB of data produced and 89.55K of reads generated. The analysis of fastq files is in progress.

5.1.4.5.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
16	D-JRP16-WP1.5	2nd TELE-Vir meeting (Copenhagen, SSI)	M54	M54		The 2nd TELE-Vir meeting will take place as planned see work plan- June 2022	
16	D-JRP16-WP1.6	Workshop in the use of the POI-toolbox (Copenhagen, SSI)	M54	M54		The workshop took place as planned see work plan- June 2022	
16	D-JRP16-WP2.1	Open-sourced bioinformatics platform that allows the user-friendly handling of high-throughput sequencing data (second and third generation) for detection and monitoring of viral emerging threats	M57		M59	All functionalities that are developed on behalf of TELE-Vir are continuously implemented and released in the publicly available platform. Additional modules are currently under benchmarking/testing and will be released soon. Due to the several circumstances (pandemic, difficulty in post-doc hiring, the extension of the project...), the “complete” platform is planned to be delivered on M59, providing an integrative star-to-end toolbox for both the detection and surveillance of viral pathogens.	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
16	D-JRP16-3.3	1st version of a poi S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing	M51		53	1 st version of the poi S.O.P – presented at the workshop hold in June 2022 – see WP1	
16	D-JRP#-WP3.3	Final version of a poi S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing	M54-60		53	We agreed that this will be final version of the SOP – same as the first version- as it worked well for the metagenomics detection of RNA-and DNA viruses. It might be modified or we will add steps after the field studies – M55-60	
16	D-JRP16-WP3.4	Report on the validation of MinION sequencing mimicking the field scenario in lab conditions	M59				

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
16	M-JRP16-03	Software modules for viral rapid detection and classification	M42		M59	A modular bioinformatic pipeline for metagenomic virus diagnostics was developed and is being benchmarked. Work is ongoing to fully implement this new “pathogen detection” module into the INSaFLU-TELE-Vir platform, coupled with its inter-connectivity with the existing “surveillance-oriented” toolbox for an enhanced detection and monitoring of viral pathogens. User-friendly visual solutions for output reporting are also being implemented.
16	M-JRP16-04	Software module for rapid screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes (e.g., antigenicity, tropism, anti-viral drug resistance)	M54	Yes		A bioinformatics tool for rapid screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes was developed and released as standalone tool (https://github.com/insapathogenomics/align2pheno ; https://pypi.org/project/align2pheno/) and also integrated (pilot version) in the platform.
16	M-JRP16-05	Advertisement of the poi-toolbox workshop finished	M52	Yes		We send out the advertisement for the workshop to all TELE-Vir partners
16	M-JRP16-06	Detailed plans and scheme for training of TELE-Vir and OHEJP participants in the POI protocol for MinION sequencing performed incl.	M52-54	Yes		Task completed – our plans could successfully be implemented at the workshop June 2022, SSI, Copenhagen

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
		training materials, manuals & lectures and personal				
16	M-JRP#-07	Detailed plans and scheme for training of TELE-Vir and OHEJP participants in the POI data analysis performed incl. training materials, manuals & lectures and personal	M52-54	Yes		Task completed – our plans could successfully be implemented at the workshop June 2022, SSI, Copenhagen
16	M-JRP#-08	Registration of participants for training in the POI-toolbox finished (max. 30 participants)	M52	Yes		24 TELE-Vir partners registered for the workshop
16	M-JRP#-09	Software module for locus- and genome-based comparative phylogenomics	M48		M57	Novel functionalities for better phylogenetic/metadata data navigation and interpretation were implemented. Work is ongoing to release a module for enhanced comparative genomics temporal and phylogeographical analysis

5.1.4.5.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
An alternative workflow for molecular detection of SARS-CoV-2 – escape from the NA extraction kit shortage, Copenhagen, Denmark, March 2020 https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.14.2000398 https://zenodo.org/record/4247188#.X6QLjWhKjcc	No		
Improvement of field deployable metagenomics virus detection by a simple pretreatment method DOI: doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.31.21268552	Yes	The manuscript is under review	
Phylogenomic characterization and signs of microevolution in the 2022 multi-country outbreak of monkeypox virus https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-022-01907-y	Yes		

Additional output

Posters

Assessing coronavirus risks: feasibility of predicting traits of clinical and epidemiological relevance from sequence data. C. Bogaardt, V. Borges, J. P. Gomes, J. Isidro, J. M. Prada, D. L. Horton. Poster presentation, OHEJP Copenhagen June 9-11th 2021

Pinheiro M, Pais RJ, Isidro J, Pinto M, Bogaardt C, Prada JM, Horton DL, Gomes JP, Borges V (2021) INSaFLU-TELE-Vir: an open web-based bioinformatics suite for influenza and SARS-CoV-2 genome-based surveillance. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 4:e68845. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.4.e68845>. Fast and easy field-deployable Sars-CoV-2 virus inactivation for downstream analysis. Anna S. Fomsgaard^{1,2}, Graham J. Belsham², Ria M. Lassaunière¹, Jannik Fonager¹, Katja Spiess¹ 1. Virus Research & Development Laboratory, Statens Serum Institute, Copenhagen, Denmark 2. Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark. Poster presentation at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Copenhagen, Denmark, 2021.

Vítor Borges, Miguel Pinheiro, Ricardo J. Pais, Joana Isidro, Miguel Pinto, Carlijn Bogaardt, Joaquin M. Prada, Daniel L. Horton, João Paulo Gomes. INSaFLU-TELE-Vir: an open web-based bioinformatics suite for genome-based surveillance of influenza, SARS-CoV-2 and other pathogens. ISIRV-WHO Virtual Conference, COVID-19, Influenza and RSV: Surveillance-Informed Prevention and Treatment, 19-21 October 2021 (**e-poster and recorded flash talk**)

A simple sample pretreatment method for metagenomics virus detection in the field. Anna S Fomsgaard^{1,2}, Morten Rasmussen¹, Katja Spiess¹, Anders Fomsgaar¹, Graham J Belsham², Jannik Fonager¹. 1. Virus Research & Development Laboratory, Statens Serum Institute, Copenhagen, Denmark 2. Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark. Poster presentation at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Orvieto, Italy, 2022.

Kaupke A., Kwit E., Bigoraj E., Radko L., Rzeżutka A. Assessment of virus inactivation efficiency for selected guanidinium thiocyanate/hydrochloride lysis buffers commonly used in PCR diagnostics." One health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Orvieto, Italy, 11-13 April 2022

LinkedIN – OneHealth- the workshop organized for all TELE-Vir partners in June 2022 has been published.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/h2020-one-health-ejp_ohejp-onehealth-strongertogether-activity-6969926954644869121-f4vq?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

We established successfully a protocol for field deployable detection of RNA- and DNA viruses and a bioinformatics module for third generation sequencing analysis and pathogen identification. All TELE-Vir partners from the different institutions were trained and participate in the ongoing field studies, using the TELE-Vir POI tool box. If this proves successful, the TELE-Vir partners can train in the future scientist/people, for example in countries with a lean-laboratory infrastructure or isolated ecosystems, to use the TELE-Vir point POI tool box. This could contribute to the control of potential new virus outbreaks.

5.1.4.5.5 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

As the national member of the ECDC EVD-LabNet (Anders Fomsgaard) we are sharing methods and results from our TELE-Vir methods in detection of emerging virus.

The Statens Serum Intitute (SSI) in CHP Denmark is a one health institute and thus all findings and methods and mutual surveillance testings are shared with Veterinary networks and ECDC.

The National Institute of Health (INSA) Dr Ricardo Jorge, Portugal, has presented the INSaFLU- TELE-Vir open web-based bioinformatics suite for virus genome-based surveillance on behalf of several international initiatives and networks, e.g., ECDC COVID-19 Laboratory Networks Influenza, WHO Europe Laboratory Workshop. INSA also maintains several cooperative actions at national and international levels to enhance the capacity building of other national and international laboratories (e.g., National Institute of Health from Guinea-Bissau) in pathogen genome-based surveillance.

5.1.4.6 JRP17-R2-ET2.2-IDEMBRU

5.1.4.6.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Project IDEMBRU aims to develop a toolkit for diagnostics, characterization and assessment of the zoonotic potential of newly discovered species and strains of worldwide present and dangerous bacteria from the genus *Brucella*. In the same time, the project examines the possibilities of the existence of new, unexplored wildlife and environmental reservoirs of classical *Brucella* species, which have been characterised worldwide as tools for bioterrorism. The toolkit will be able to assess the risks for new sources and newly discovered strains of *Brucella* species in order to greatly improve the public health protection from this highly contagious disease.

In the final year of the project, the consortium prioritized the tasks of genetic, phenotypic comparisons and characterisation of zoonotic potential of newly discovered species and isolated strains. Several partners continued sample collections from wildlife, environment and humans in order to assess the levels of contamination and provide scenarios to test the final toolkit within the One Health approach concept. In the same time, newly emerging *Brucella canis*, considered the classical type species but new in Western Europe, especially started fast spread in canine population, but among human owners as well. This created the major urgency to address the issue and dedicate the part of the project's activities towards studying *B. canis* zoonotic and risks for animal transmission and health.

To collect additional samples for WP1, the consortium organised sample collections with the wildlife protection networks and hunting organisations in each partner's country. To optimise the usage of wildlife samples, the existing sample collections from other research projects are exploited. Already more than 1500 samples have been processed and analysed at least by molecular or bacteriological methods. A panel of environmental strains of bacteria similar to *Brucella* (such as *Ochrobactrum* spp.) have been isolated, and genetic typing and phenotypic characterisation has been performed to validate the toolkit SOPs. Regarding the *B. canis* expansion, collection of canine samples from clinically suspicious animals as well as those epidemiologically related is still ongoing.

The Netherlands have recorded the first human case of *B. canis* infection in Europe. Within WP-2, the network with another One Health EJP project – COHESIVE has been established, regarding the evaluation of presence of *Brucella canis* in dogs and humans and to determine its pathogenic characteristics within WPs 3, 4 and 5. The professional exposure groups have been identified and WP-2 concentrated the sera testing on samples coming from individuals who are professionally more likely exposed to *Brucellae* – i.e. veterinary workers, vet school students, kennel owners even diagnostic laboratories staff. The members of two projects organised to prepare White Paper on *B. canis* regarding current epidemiological situation in Europe and recommendations to EU commission for

further necessary actions. Therefore, IDEMBRU project decided to focus a part of its work on *B. canis* as one of the evident emerging zoonoses from *Brucella* genus.

However, recently our project met with several risks that threaten to jeopardize the quality of the final toolbox. The project is based on the feed of results from one WP to another. So far, within WP-1 and WP-2, no atypical *Brucella* species/strains have been isolated, except several environmental bacteria similar to *Brucella* spp. This was resolved by the use of already isolated strains that partners were willing to share within the consortium. The problem of no isolation of new *Brucella* spp. from human samples was overcome by development of a new test for rough species (covering the new emerging threat *B. canis*). Therefore, these WPs started to provide the necessary materials and results to WP3, WP4, WP5. In the same time, we found it not acceptable to ignore the emerging European problem of *B. canis*. Recently, the project coordinator was asked by EFSA to prepare a short communication on the topic of *B. canis* epidemiology in Europe and current understanding of risks. Several partners were solicited and final results were presented at the last EREN meeting and the EREN *B. canis* briefing note was published on the EFSA website (link below).

On the other hand, during the last two and a half years of the project, besides the COVID pandemic, which greatly hampered the start of the project, the employment of new personnel and the sample collection, the consortium suffered tremendous changes of personnel. In total, five people left the project (retirement, maternity leave, change of job, etc.); nine new were recruited, while one partner can't find personnel. In the same time, many partners had to concentrate more than 50% of their time (Portugal, Italy, Germany, UK) on COVID testing during the whole course of the project. All these problems put tremendous pressure on the final toolkit, especially in the light of a new emerging threat such as *B. canis*.

Since the project saw many setbacks last year, the evaluation of DNA extraction methods from complex matrices (water, soil and faeces) was finalized only at the end of 2021. Additionally, the DNA extraction from canine faeces has been analysed as an important source of data. The harmonised whole genome sequencing protocols passed ring trials and are ready as part of the final toolkit. Last year the environmental bacteria *Ochrobactrum* spp. have been added to the *Brucella* genus since several species are considered opportunistic pathogens and both share more than 85% of genome. During our project, many isolated *Ochrobactrum* spp. strains, especially from environmental samples, which are morphologically similar to *Brucella* spp., have not been detected by molecular methods. Therefore, specific primers for *Ochrobactrum* spp. were constructed, in order to distinguish between the two genera. Furthermore, a microfluidics PCR plate was designed, so that the diagnostic and typing of *Brucella* and *Brucella*-like bacteria can be performed even from a few organisms on a large number of samples. The big advantage of the microfluidics system is that it can perform up to 96 primer pairs PCR on up to 96 samples at the time, and the total volume of the sample is one µl. The phenotyping by motility assays, antimicrobial resistance plates and MALDI-TOF SOPs are ready for validation and necessary data libraries will be completed until the end of the year. The SOPs for in vitro cell infections have been validated, and a pipeline for the pathogenicity classification established so that the first experiments in WP-5 can start as planned this year.

The regular monthly online meetings are held within the consortium, and WP communication.

5.1.4.6.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1 Recording the situation of brucellosis in emergent wild and environmental reservoirs (M37-M50)

WP1 takes place throughout the first, second, and first half of third year of the project. Task 2 and task 3 have been developed during 2021 and continued throughout 2022.

WP1-T2 Sampling and analytical strategy according to previous epidemiological information from the different partners (M37-M50)

Task 2 has been developed since November 2020 and will last until September 2022. At the time of this report, a total of 1900 samples from various hosts and from the three different biotopes (coastal regions, forest and fresh water) have been analysed. Table 1 summarizes the variety of samples obtained and processed to map existing atypical or emerging *Brucella* strains. Depending on the host species, collected samples included blood, and tissues such as brain, thymus, lung, muscles, parts of internal organs, and various lymph nodes.

Guidelines for sample analyses by complementary molecular and serological methods have been finished as well. Most of the tissue samples have been initially tested by molecular and then bacteriological diagnostic methods. Blood samples, when available, were tested using rose Bengal test (RBT), complement fixation test (CFT) and specific ELISAs, to characterise serological responses. All isolated strains (*Brucella* spp. or *Ochrobactrum* spp.) were characterized according to conventional molecular and microbiological methods. First results of these analyses, combined with epidemiological data were presented at the annual OH EJP Conference and at the international Brucellosis conference in Chicago (December 2021).

WP1-T3 Synthesis and analysis of data (M37-M50)

Data obtained in task 1 and task 2 are being integrated for further analyses to improve knowledge regarding emergent *Brucella* species infections.

Table 1. Existing collection of samples, hosts and Countries of origin.

Biotope	Host	No. samples	Origin
Coastal Region	Cetaceans	59	United Kingdom, France
	Pinnipeds	2	United Kingdom
	Fish	65	France
	Turtle	50	Italy
Forest	Foxes	660	Bulgaria, France, Germany, Portugal
	Hares	80	Portugal, France
	Jackals	42	Bulgaria
	Wild ruminants	262	Bulgaria, France, Germany, Portugal
	Wild boars	457	Bulgaria, France, Portugal
	Lagomorphs	100	France
Freshwater	Frog	7	Germany
Domestic animals	dogs	320	Italy, France, Portugal, United Kingdom

WP2 Recording the situation of brucellosis in humans

WP2-T1 Creation of a surveillance network dedicated to human brucellosis

A brucellosis laboratory surveillance network was developed in collaboration with Bruce-list and through Portuguese network of medical laboratories (hospitals and private laboratories). The epidemiological questionnaire was developed and distributed in order to obtain as many data as possible, and in the same time respect the personal data protection and privacies of each patient. Since 2020, several outbreaks of *Brucella canis* were recorded throughout European kennels. In collaboration with COHESIVE project, we decided to focus on patients who have professional exposure, primarily to *Brucella canis*, but also to other sources of atypical *Brucella* species (veterinary workers, veterinary students, kennel and shelter staff, fisherman...). From already existing sera bank and tissue collections, samples were obtained from same population as described above, in order to establish the strains collection and/or the biological samples from human populations suspected of *Brucella* infections. The campaign of sera collection from veterinarians, and veterinary technicians' volunteers as well as vet students has been planned for the beginning of the first part of 2022.

WP2-T2 Sampling and analytical strategy according to epidemiological information from the surveillance network

The human tissue samples in Portugal were processed by direct bacteriological and molecular diagnostic methods (isolation and real time PCR) in the biosafety level 3 facility. At this moment 44 human samples (21 blood, 13 cerebro-spinal fluids, 4 biopsies and 6 already isolated strains-confirmation analysis) were processed.

According to the agreement with COHESIVE project, we started to check already existing sera banks with targeted populations. We tested 400 sera belonging to the biobank of the National Institute of Health Dr Ricardo Jorge (previously no *Brucella* suspicions) using Rose-Bengal test. All serologically positive sera were tested by real time PCR for *Brucella* targeting IS711.

In the lights of newly identified strain *B. inopinata* –like BO3 isolated from a pet frog, which does not agglutinate with any of known mono specific sera (anti A, anti M, anti R), deliverables 2 and 3 have to be postponed. ANSES partner (also EURL for brucellosis) will produce the specific antigens for BO3 strain for diagnostic purposes. *B. inopinata* and *inopinata*-like strains are genetically atypical representatives of *Brucella* genus, with proven zoonotic potential. No reaction with known *Brucella* specific sera, demonstrates existence of strains/species that cannot be detected by current diagnostic tools, which still represents significant threat for public health. The production of a specific antigen will allow validation of existing banks on chosen (see above) human sera for the presence of specific antibodies for newly discovered atypical *Brucella* strains, probably even beyond BO3 strain.

In the same time, there is no approved test for humans for rough *Brucella* species (such as *B. ovis* and *B. canis*). This means that there are no tests (validated or in development), except direct bacteriological and molecular diagnostic tools, for newly emerging *B. canis* infections in humans. Therefore, we propose to use the existing *B. ovis* antigen for complement fixation (FC) test and try to validate it, on sera from confirmed human brucellosis cases, as well as dog owners from which *B. canis* or *B. suis* have been diagnosed.

We can perform all additional tests and shine more light on human brucellosis risks as well as public health protection strategies if we obtain additional eight months for the WP2-Del2, which will impact WP2-Del3 as well. This extension will also contribute greatly to the completeness of the final toolkit from human medicine side and improve the decision-making trees the toolkit will provide.

WP3 Genomic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

WP3 - Genomic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

WP3-T1 Optimisation of methods for generating molecular typing data from complex samples

- The optimization was focused on a number of complex matrices of particular significance to the current project, such as swabs and soil.
- Evaluation of methods for DNA extraction from soil has been performed at APHA. Comparison of DNA extraction methods has been undertaken using soil types relevant to the distinct ecosystems identified in IDEMBRU WP1 and biologically relevant concentrations of target organism DNA.
- Swabs are used for sampling animal and human tissues as well as environment. Evaluation of different types of swabs has been performed at ANSES. This work has identified optimal swab materials and recovery protocols. Optimisation of protocols for swabs has focused on both DNA extraction and culture of viable organisms. This work has now been published (Freddi et al., 2021 [<https://doi.org/10.1128/Spectrum.00728-21>]).

WP3-T2 Harmonisation and standardisation of protocols for whole genome sequencing

- This task aims to compare the performance of whole genome sequencing procedures undertaken in partner institutes. The task was finished with planned delays of six months in the beginning of the year.
- A relevant panel of *Brucella* spp. isolates was identified, and prepared. Prior to distribution (as heat-inactivated cultures) these strains are tested to confirm the identify and suitability of the material.
- Whole genome sequencing of the material shared was undertaken by partner institutes, using existing locally established protocols and finished with planned delays of six months.
- Results concerning the performance of library preparation and whole genome sequencing undertaken in partner institutes (e.g. quality metrics; number of reads etc.) have been collated, to assess comparability between partner institutes. Outliers in this relationship (i.e. those samples with the largest residuals in linear regression) were all *B. inopinata* BO1. Similarly, there was a highly significant positive association between the total number of reads and the average depth of coverage of the reference genome (linear regression $R^2 = 0.6636$: $P < 0.0001$).
- Previously observed high degree of genetic divergence of atypical *Brucella* strains (both relative to core *Brucella* spp. and amongst atypical strains) emphasises the need to select appropriate reference genomes for reference-based mapping and variant calling analyses. Additionally, this work has also identified a need for improved reference genomes for a number of recently described *Brucella* sp. strains.

WP3-T3 Identification of emerging *Brucella* species: adaptation of molecular tools

- This task aims to utilise conventional methods and whole genome sequencing to generate molecular typing data from emerging *Brucella* spp. isolates, to ensure that existing schemes remain applicable to the full diversity of the genus. The task was finished with planned delays of six months in the beginning of the year.
- Also under WP3, methods for generating long-read sequencing data using the Oxford Nanopore Minlon platform have been evaluated and optimized. Application of these protocols for generating long-read sequencing data have enabled complete, or nearly complete, genomes to be generated for a panel of atypical *Brucella* spp. isolates.
- Currently, the short and long read genome assemblies are being compared in order to complement each other.

WP3-T4 Integrative analysis of genomic and epidemiological data collected in WP1 and WP2

This task utilises results from other tasks within WP3.

WP4 Phenotypic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

WP4-T1 Phenotyping of novel emerging *Brucella* spp.

WP4-T1-ST1

A phenotyping scheme specifically for novel emerging *Brucella* spp. is currently under the validation steps by several project partners.

WP4-T1-ST2

Initial motility tests have been carried out. Suitable *Brucella* candidates are selected for electron microscopy studies. Electron microscopic investigations are still underway with previewed delays of three months.

WP4-T1-ST3

Unfortunately, production of the commercial test system for phenotyping *Brucella* has been discontinued. Therefore, the work was replaced with MALDI-TOF library analysis and library creation, currently underway with the planned delays of three months.

WP4-T2 Antimicrobial resistance testing of emerging *Brucella* spp.

WP4-T2-ST1

A micro dilution antibiotic test scheme has been validated on a novel emerging *Brucella*. A suitable antibiotic pattern has been selected for chloramphenicol, ciprofloxacin, doxycycline, gentamycin, levofloxacin, rifampicin, streptomycin, tetracyclin, as well as trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole combination. Based on these patterns, the antimicrobial test plates are being validated at each partner laboratory, which participates in this WP. Data are being merged together for better analyses in order to find unique patterns for atypical strains. In order to avoid bias and differences among institutions, the ELISA reader at 450 nm is used to compare with naked eye readouts.

WP4-T3 RNA sequencing of a representative panel of classical and novel *Brucella* spp.

WP4-T3-ST1

Evaluation of RNA seq kits for different *Brucella* species identification has been done. A suitable protocol has been developed. However, based on further work, this will also be adapted in the future, if necessary. Because of the encountered delays, results will be three months delayed.

WP4-T3-ST2

Optimization of the RNA-Seq protocol is still undergoing with estimated delays of three months.

WP4-T3-ST3

MALDI ToF MS spectra have been generated for clinical isolates from German partners. In addition strains from the in-house strain collection that had not yet been integrated into the existing peptide profile database have been analysed with MALDI ToF MS. Integration of these MALDI ToF MS spectra into the peptide profile database is underway. MALDI ToF MS spectra generation and subsequent integration will be continued when isolates from the other project partners are available.

WP4-T3-ST4

To identify active metabolic pathways in different *Brucella* spp. an integrative bioinformatics analysis of genomic, transcriptomic and metabolic data will be done. However, metabolic phenotyping of *Brucella* isolates cannot be carried out as planned since the Micronaut™ system is not available anymore. Therefore, a new metabolic phenotyping approach has been designed and is in the process of validation.

WP5 Zoonotic potential and virulence

WP5-T1-ST1 Creation of *Brucella* genomes database from publicly available and emerging isolates

Creation of the database was slightly delayed as emerging isolates are still mostly lacking. Combining sets of online available genomes and in-house sequenced strains gave a test-set of 30 genomes to be used to examine differences between zoonotic and non-zoonotic species and robustness of tools to assembly quality.

WP5-T1-ST2 Selection of bioinformatics tools for identification and comparison of virulence factors

A literature search revealed a diverse array of tools to identify virulence genes in bacterial assemblies, of which a subset was selected as possible candidates (VFAalyzer, PathoFact, BrucellaBase, PathogenFinder, and ABRicate), and only one widely used virulence gene database, namely VFDB (<http://www.mgc.ac.cn/VFs/main.htm>). However, because of the variabilities in the results and lack of sufficient data produced within WP-3 further assessment had to be taken only after finished

sequencing ring trial. Due to changes in personnel within WP lead institution as well as unplanned leaves, this task had to be delayed for additional three months.

WP5-T1-ST3 Creation of an automatic/semi-automatic pipeline for virulence assessment of novel isolates based on their genomes

We decided to make a pipeline on the basis of ABRicate. This package also includes the option to build a custom database. In this way we can add the genes that VFAnalyzer found extra and include 10 other potential *Brucella* spp. virulence genes selected in a recent paper on virulence factors in *B. melitensis* (Rabinowitz et al. 2021) to the core VFDB set. Due to delays during the building of the database and the necessity to build our own database for the pipeline, this task is additionally delayed by approximately two months and will thus most likely be completed in July 2022.

WP5-T2

WP5-T2-ST1 Assembly of macrophage cell lines collection derived from human and animals

It was decided to perform initial *in vitro* infections on dog macrophage cell line (DH82), a human monocyte cell line (THP1), bovine macrophages (BeVo), ovine (SV40) as well as human trophoblast cell line (HTR8-SVneo) and epithelial cells (HeLa). If necessary additional cell lines will be included.

WP5-T2-ST2 Development of *in vitro* infection protocol

For the optimization and development of an *in vitro* infection protocol HeLa cell lines had been used since most commonly available in all partners' collections. Five different *Brucella* species with different zoonotic potential were used in order to standardize the protocol and optimize parameters like MOI, time of incubation etc. Readout parameters include CFU count and PCR to quantify the infection rate. *Brucella* species will be exchanged from ANSES to WBVR for the next Subtask 5.3. The developed protocols will be shared by putting the SOPs on the SharePoint, so participating partners can use these protocols for the next milestone. In order to determine the zoonotic potential of newly discovered *Brucella* strains, it was decided to analyse following post infection (PI) time points:

1. Two hours PI, to quantify the number of bacteria attached and infected cells;
2. Six hours PI, to determine the amplification curve of intracellular bacteria
3. 24 hours PI, to continue the growth curve and analyse the cellular reaction and damages inflicted
4. 48 hours PI, to analyse the cell death and final numbers of bacteria.

Finalized protocols have been distributed and first tests performed. This task will be finished as planned without delays.

WP5-T2-ST3 Harmonization of analytical methods for investigation of pathogen – host-cell cross talk

The deadline of this project is in April 2022. *In vitro* protocols have now been created so the investigation of pathogen – host cell cross talk can started. Besides quantification of amplified bacteria, the RNA seq analysis will be performed on infected cells in WBVR while extracellular profiling will be performed for all experiments at ANSES.

WP6 Development of a toolkit for emerging Brucellosis infections

The review of existing toolkits for management of infectious diseases will be prepared for the September 2022.

The results and SOPs necessary for the toolkit will be analysed during the final annual workshop organised for the first week of October 2022.

WP7 Coordination, management and communication

WP7-T1 Management, integration and delivery of the project, coordination and effective reporting and communications between project partners

The project partners organize regular monthly meeting where the results, problems and further steps of each WP are discussed. WP leaders and deputies make sure that all milestones and deliverables have been met, and with the project coordinators prepare reports, scientific and public communications. When necessary, additional WP meetings are organized (this year 7 organised so far) where specific issues which need more research or confidentiality are discussed. Because of ongoing pandemic, all meeting are organized online.

In collaboration with COHESIVE project, two additional *B. canis* meetings were organized regarding the advancements on White Paper. Final version of the White paper is expected to be finished by the end of July 2022.

WP7-T2 A data management plan

Data management plan evolves with the needs of the project. Mainly the documents, databases are up to date.

WP7-T3 Milestones management

Necessary changes in order to deliver milestones on time as well as delays and problems in achieving them are reported in advance or during monthly meetings by work package leaders and/or deputies. Modifications to the project made possible by newly available materials and techniques are discussed among all partners, evaluated and, if considered appropriate, implemented in a coordinated manner. All possible changes are made with the emphasis on developments in perceived threats and newly published work appearing in the literature.

WP7-T4 Toolkit components communication

Since the work on final components of the toolkit has not started yet, this task will be performed accordingly in real time during Y5 – 2022. In the same time, advances on urgent matter of expansion of *B. canis* has been communicated in accordance with national and European stakeholders.

5.1.4.6.2.1 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
17	D-JRP17-WP1.Del2	Creation of animal and environmental samples collections (serum, tissues, strains, soil, water...) of emerging <i>Brucella</i> species and related reservoirs	M50	M48		Published on Zenodo OHEJP_JRP17_IDEMBRU_Data_management_datasheet Zenodo	1
17	D-JRP17-WP1.Del3	Development of a flowchart and related tools facilitating investigation and decision-making of emerging <i>Brucella</i> outbreaks	M50		M57	Due to delays described above as well as lack of newly isolated strains, it was decided to extend the work on this deliverable until the end of September 2022 (M56).	
17	D-JRP17-WP1.4 Del1	Phenotyping scheme to differentiate emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp. from classical species	M54		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this deliverable will be finished by M59	
17	D-JRP17-WP1.4 Del2	AMR testing protocol including proposals for ECOFFs for emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp.	M56		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this deliverable will be finished by M59	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
17	D-JRP17-WP2.Del1	Set-up of a human brucellosis network	M42	February 2021		Public: OHEJP JRP-17 IDEMBRU Work package 2 Deliverable 1 Zenodo Brucella canis workshop Zenodo	5
17	D-JRP17-WP2.Del2	Creation of human samples collections (serum, samples, strains) of emerging <i>Brucella</i> species and related environments	M50		M57	Due to delays described above as well as lack of newly isolated strains, it was decided to extend the work on this deliverable until the end of September 2022 (M56).	17
17	D-JRP17-WP2.Del3	Development of a biobank and tools facilitating investigation and decision-making of emerging <i>Brucella</i> outbreaks	M50		M57	Due to delays described above as well as lack of newly isolated strains, it was decided to extend the work on this deliverable until the end of September 2022 (M56).	17
17	D-JRP17-WP3.Del3	Molecular typing data from emerging <i>Brucella</i> isolates	M52				17
17	D-JRP17-WP2.Del4	Rapid detection assay(s) for atypical strains using clade specific markers	M52		M57	Due to delays described above as well as lack of newly isolated strains, it was decided to extend the work on this deliverable until the end of September 2022 (M56).	17
17	D-JRP17-WP3.Del1	Standard operating procedures for the extraction of <i>Brucella</i> DNA from complex matrices	M49		M50	Finished. Final scientific article is in preparation before publishing the deliverable on Zenodo.	17

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
17	D-JRP17-WP3.Del2	Harmonised whole genome sequencing and bioinformatic protocols	M48	M48		Finished. Final scientific article is in preparation before publishing the deliverable on Zenodo.	8
17	D-JRP17-WP5.Del1	Bioinformatics pipeline for detection and classification of <i>Brucella</i> virulence factors in context of zoonotic potential	M50		M54	Due to delays described above as well as lack of newly isolated strains, it was decided to extend the work on this deliverable until M54.	
17	D-JRP17-WP5.Del2	Development of a reliable macrophage based <i>in vitro</i> system for rapid assessment of zoonotic potential	M54	M54		Final report is being prepared.	
17	D-JRP17-WP5.Del3	<i>In vivo</i> infection model for emerging <i>Brucella</i> spp.	M54			Due to delays described above, this task can not be delivered with the time line restrains	
17	D-JRP17-WP5.Del4	Development of a decision-tree as a tool to support decision-making concerning zoonotic potential of <i>Brucella</i> species	M54		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this deliverable will be finished by M59	
17	D-JRP17-WP6.Del1	Review of toolkits for infectious diseases	M51		M54	Due to delays encountered in other WPs this deliverable had to be postponed	
17	D-JRP17-WP6.Del2	Collaborative toolkit for emerging <i>Brucella</i> species	M54		M60	Due to six months extension granted, this deliverable will be finished by M60	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		and related reservoirs					
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del5	Report of the 2nd annual workshop including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders	52		M55	Due to six months extension granted, this deliverable will be finished by M55	
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del6	Report of the last annual workshop including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders	M54		M57	Last annual workshop has been organised for the first week of M57.	
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del7	Implementation of a notification system including emerging and non-regulated <i>Brucella</i>	M54		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this deliverable will be finished by M59	

Milestones

JIP/ Code	JRP	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
17		M-JRP17-M19	Characterisation of serological responses and identification of isolated emerging <i>Brucella</i> species	M56		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17		M-JRP17-M20	Characterisation of serological responses and identification of isolated emerging <i>Brucella</i> species	M56		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17		M-JRP17-M24	Creation of an automatic/semi-automatic pipeline for virulence assessment of novel isolates based on their genomes	M56		M57	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M57
17		M-JRP17-M27	List of toolkits available from previous experience	M51	Yes		
17		M-JRP17-M28	Literature reviewing	M47	Yes		
17		M-JRP17-M29	Integrative analysis of the infection situation in the emerging reservoirs	M50		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17		M-JRP17-M30	Integrative analysis of the infection situation in the emerging reservoirs	M50		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17		M-JRP17-M31	Experimental determination of infection gates	M50	No		Due to encountered delays this milestone cannot be completed.
17		M-JRP17-M32	Implementation of 2nd annual workshop	M50	Yes		
17		M-JRP17-M33	Mailing list of people / institutes receiving notifications	M50	Yes		

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M49-M57

JIP/ Code	JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	17	M-JRP17-M34	Develop and apply PCRs on high resolving SNPS to DNA extracted from relevant samples	M52	Yes		
	17	M-JRP17-M35	Complete molecular typing of emerging <i>Brucella</i> isolates	M52		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
	17	M-JRP17-M36	Harmonization of analytical methods for investigation of pathogen – host-cell cross talk.	M52	Yes		
	17	M-JRP17-M37	Conference call of the steering committee regrouping WP leaders and deputy leaders	M53	Yes		
	17	M-JRP17-M38	Epidemiological analysis of emerging <i>Brucella</i> isolates	M54		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
	17	M-JRP17-M39	Biotyping of emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp. isolated within the project	M54		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
	17	M-JRP17-M40	Electron microscopy of selected isolates/strains	M50		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
	17	M-JRP17-M41	Phenotyping of emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp. isolated during the project using the BfR <i>Brucella</i> MICRONAUT™	M52	No		Due to discontinued production of MICRONAUT plates, this milestone cannot be completed and was replaced by creation of MALDI-TOF specific library.
	17	M-JRP17-M42	Antibiotic resistance of emerging <i>Brucella</i> spp. isolated during the project	M52		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
17	M-JRP17-M43	RNA sequences of a representative panel of classical and emerging <i>Brucella</i> sp.	M52		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17	M-JRP17-M44	Comparison of RNA sequences of selected clinical samples with 16S metagenomics to test viability of <i>Brucella</i> sp.	M52		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17	M-JRP17-M45	Formulation of <i>in vitro</i> infection parameters that will reflect zoonotic potential of a <i>Brucella</i> isolate.	M54	Yes		
17	M-JRP17-M46	Definition of the programme of the annual workshop	M49	Yes		
17	M-JRP17-M47	Comparison of antibiotic resistance patterns and ECOFFs determination of emerging and classical <i>Brucella</i> species	M50		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17	M-JRP17-M48	Harmonize <i>in silico</i> , <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> results	M50	No	M59	Since <i>in vivo</i> infections cannot be performed, <i>in silico</i> and <i>in vitro</i> results will be compared
17	M-JRP17-M49	Testing algorithms for WGS and proteome	M50	Yes		
17	M-JRP17-M50	Harmonised procedures from IDEMBRU WPs	M50	Yes		
17	M-JRP17-M51	Availability of reference database	M50			

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M49-M57

JIP/ Code	JRP	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
17		M-JRP17-M52	Organisation of accommodation and logistic aspects	M51		M56	Workshop organised for M57
17		M-JRP17-M56	Integration of emerging <i>Brucella</i> MALDI ToF MS spectra in the existing peptide profile databases	M54		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17		M-JRP17-M53	Description of infection pathodynamic using molecular and histological approaches in experimental animals	M52	No		Since in vivo infections cannot be performed, this milestone cannot be finished.
17		M-JRP17-M54	Finalize and benchmark the decision tree	M52		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17		M-JRP17-M55	Implementation of 3rd annual workshop	M53		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59
17		M-JRP17-M57	Identification of diagnostically relevant regulatory processes by bioinformatics analysis of metabolic data (BfR <i>Brucella</i> MICRONAUT™) and RNASeq data	M54		M59	Due to six months extension granted, this milestone will be finished by M59

5.1.4.6.3 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
The use of flocked swab with protective media increases the recovery of live Brucella spp. and DNA detection. Microbiol Spectr. 2021 Dec 22;9(3):e0072821. DOI : 10.1128/Spectrum.00728-21 . Epub 2021 Nov 17	Yes		
The Retrospective on Atypical Brucella Species Leads to Novel Definitions. Microorganisms. 2022 Apr 14;10(4):813. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms10040813 .	Yes		

Additional output

EFSA EREN note on *Brucella canis*: Emergence of canine brucellosis due to infection with *Brucella canis* in different European countries. PONSART C, DE MASSIS F, FERREIRA AC, KOETS A, LAHTI E, MC GIVEN J, SACCHINI F, WHATMORE AM, GIRAULT G, FREDDI L, FERREIRA VICENTE A AND DJOKIC V

EFSA EREN presentation on *Brucella canis*: Emergence of canine brucellosis due to infection with *Brucella canis* in different European countries. Ponsart C - 27th EMERGING RISKS EXCHANGE NETWORK MEETING (EREN), Vienna, 11-12 May 2022, <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2022-05/27th-emerging-risks-exchange-network-meeting-minutes.pdf>

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

OHEJP Roundtable of One Health EJP JRP on the 11th of April 2022 at OHEJPASM2022 presentation: Identification of emerging *Brucella* species: new threats for human and animals IDEMBRU. Ponsart C

Online guidelines for canine brucellosis (ANSES Website, French). [Présentation PowerPoint \(anses.fr\)](#)

Online seminar for French veterinary practitioners on *B. canis* awareness raising - <https://vimeo.com/733219390> . Ponsart C

Online seminar for French diagnostic laboratories on *B. canis* awareness raising and diagnostic specificities - <https://vimeo.com/732133799>

EU European Union Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis - 15th Workshop of the EU Brucellosis National Reference Laboratories Giulianova, Italy – September 14-15, 2022:

- Emerging *Brucella* species : update of the IDEMBRU project. Djokic V
- First *Brucella canis* human case in the NL. Koets A.

5.1.4.6.3.1 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

EFSA - EREN Note on *B. canis* emergence. The project started close collaboration with EREN and Emerging diseases offices of EFSA on *B. canis* threats for public health and economic welfare evaluation.

French Ministry of agriculture on *B. canis*. Through French National Referent Laboratory for brucellosis the project collaborates with the ministry on risks evaluation and disease management, through organisation of awareness raising seminars for veterinary professionals and departmental diagnostic laboratories, while aiding in management of identified kennels.

French Ministry of agriculture on *B. melitensis*. The developed protocols within IDEMBRU project, will be used to help evaluate the risks and manage occurrence of *B. melitensis* strain in cattle in French Alps. The strain that is known to be present in Alpine ibex sometimes infects dairy animals and is shown to be zoonotic. Further characterisation of this strain is necessary in order to explain the existence of this strain for last 30 years in Alps and risks for livestock species and public health.

French association of public veterinary diagnostic laboratories – ADILVA. Through ADILVA project obtained samples from wildlife across France. It is the network of diagnostic laboratories that are willing to help scientists identify new reservoirs and mitigate the spread of infectious diseases. So far, more than 600 samples have been collected from marine mammals, oceanic and freshwater fish, wild boar, rodents, lagomorphs, and several species of amphibians.

5.1.4.7 JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEmE

5.1.4.7.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

MEmE is an international multicentre collaborative project that aims to fill research gaps highlighted by international agencies for the detection and control of zoonotic parasites *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (Eg), causing alveolar echinococcosis (AE) and cystic echinococcosis (CE), respectively.

MEmE current achievements:

- Production of Standard Operating Procedures and sampling of different matrices from naturally or experimentally infected definitive and intermediate animal hosts.
- Validation of the parasitological (Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT) and molecular diagnostic (multiplex-PCRs and MC-RT-PCR assay) procedures to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.
- Development and validation of new tools: a) Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for the detection of Em in stool samples; b) Bayesian Analysis of three methods for diagnosis of CE in sheep; c) Microsatellite investigations of Eg cysts; d) Species detection of Eg by novel probe-based real-time PCRs; e) Validated method based on PCR-RFLP and multiplex PCR assay for the identification of Eg species; f) Identification of Eg G1/G3 by SNPs assays.
- Ongoing multicentre studies for the production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments (contamination of vegetables for human consumption by eggs of Em/Eg; prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces).
- Quantitative assessment on the impact of human CE in Europe by means of systematic review approach.
- Dissemination of project results at different levels (general public, scientific community, experts, health authorities and media).
- MEmE scientific papers published on peer-review journals:
- [Species and genotypes belonging to *Echinococcus granulosus* s.l. complex causing human cystic echinococcosis in Europe \(2000-2021\): a systematic review approach.](#) *Parasit Vectors*. 2022;15(1):109.
- [Insights into Human Cystic Echinococcosis in the Kurdistan Region, Iraq: Characteristics and Molecular Identification of Cysts.](#) *Pathogens*. 2022;11(4):408.
- [Chromosome-scale *Echinococcus granulosus* \(genotype G1\) genome reveals the Eg95 gene family and conservation of the EG95-vaccine molecule.](#) *Commun Biol*. 2022;5(1):199.
- [A Retrospective Cohort Study on Human Cystic Echinococcosis in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province \(Pakistan\) Based on 16 Years of Hospital Discharge Records.](#) *Pathogens*. 2022;11(2):194.
- [Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone.](#) *Pathogens*. 2021;10(10):1326.
- [New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030.](#) *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2021;15(5):e0009373.
- [Identification of *Echinococcus granulosus* genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs genotyping assays.](#) *Pathogens*. 2021;10(2):125.
- [Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs \(*Acinonyx jubatus*\) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed *Besnoitia* species.](#) *Parasit Vectors*. 2021;14(1):201.

- [Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the stool samples of naturally Infected red foxes.](#) *Animals (Basel)*. 2020;10(12):2381.
- [Cystic echinococcosis: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia \(Italy\).](#) *Pathogens*. 2020;9(6):907.
- [A validated method to identify *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* at species level.](#) *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*. 2020;85:104575.
- [Bayesian analysis of three methods for diagnosis of cystic echinococcosis in sheep.](#) *Pathogens*. 2020;9(10):796.
- [Species detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* complex by novel probe-based real-time PCRs.](#) *Pathogens*. 2020;9(10):791.
- [Microsatellite investigations of multiple *Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto* cysts in single hosts reveal different patterns of infection events between livestock and humans.](#) *Pathogens*. 2020;9(6):444.
- [Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis.](#) *The Lancet Global Health*. 2020;8(4):e470-e471.

5.1.4.7.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1. Sampling strategy

WP1-T1. SOPs for sampling in matrices

Task accomplished

WP1-T2. Matrices collection in the field from intermediate and definitive hosts

Task accomplished

WP1-T3. Matrices collection from experimental animal models

Task accomplished

WP2. Validation of parasitological and molecular assays

WP2-T1. Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT

Task updated and accomplished

Among the 603 red and arctic fox intestines collected by five partners (NVI, PIWET, FLI, ANSES and BIOR), 568 were independently analysed for each of the four segments of intestines resulting in 139 positive samples. The highest sensitivity was obtained for the combination of segments S4-S2 (99.3%), S4-S1 (97.1%) and S4-S3 (97.8%). The protocol of validation for SSCT was also applied to racoon dogs from Poland and Latvia in order to determine a potential combination of a pair of segments which may result in a high sensitivity of the method. Among 70 racoon dog intestines which were analysed, five were infected by Em. Data from racoon dogs will be combined with those from experimental results previously obtained in red foxes. Data from previous experimental infections of six racoon dogs at ANSES were combined with those from natural infections. The best combination of segments was obtained for S4-S2 with a sensitivity of 100% with confirmation that the distribution of worms is mainly in the posterior part as observed for foxes.

WP2-T2. Comparison of multiplex PCRs

Task accomplished

WP2-T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay

SOP for validation of Magnetic capture – real-time PCR assay. There was a delay with the milestone in this task and the lead on the task was transferred from SVA (SVA withdrew from MEmE in 2021) to NVI in M37. The methods (DNA extraction with automatic washing and manual washing protocols, as well as three real-time PCR protocols) and accompanying training video (for magnetic capture DNA extraction with manual washing) were published on Zenodo as project restricted technical notes in M42 (DOIs: 10.5281/zenodo.4897969; 10.5281/zenodo.4746190; 10.5281/zenodo.4746181; 10.5281/zenodo.4746141). If needed additional guidance, via digital meeting platforms, has been offered to the seven laboratories (BIOR, CVRL, INIAV, ISS, PIWET, SSI and VFL) that have registered for the training. So far, only one has requested this. The verification and ring test material has been distributed to all partners that have registered for participation in the ring test (FLI, INIAV, ISS, NVI, SSI and RIVM). So far only one of the partners has provided their ring test results whilst three others have requested a delay to reporting due to supply chain issues for the reagents used or request for additional training (ISS) in 2022. The ring test consists of a sample set of 10 faecal samples that have potentially been spiked with Em worm segments for each laboratory to analyse.

WP3. Development validation of new tools and production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments

WP3-T1. New molecular markers for Em and Eg s.l.: from rapid diagnostics to source attribution

WP3-T1-ST1: new mitochondrial markers.

Recent studies have revealed an unexpectedly high genetic diversity at mitochondrial genome level for Eg (*E. granulosus sensu stricto* and *E. canadensis* - genotypes G6/G7). However, these studies covered only part of the genetic diversity since many important endemic regions were missing (e.g. China and Russia). Moreover, for several species including Em, the mitogenomes data are scarce. In order to develop species/genotype specific diagnostic assays, additional mitogenomes data are required for all *Echinococcus* spp. using a larger worldwide panel of different Eg (*E. granulosus sensu stricto*) species and genotypes (n=300), and Em (n=200). Toehold Exchange Probes based diagnostic tool will be developed to provide a reliable and rapid identification of species/genotypes of Eg (*E. granulosus sensu lato*) and Em. The complete mitogenomes of 48 samples of the Eg genotypes G6/G7 from various countries of the world were sequenced. These sequences will be included to the total dataset of mitogenomes. Due data M58.

WP3-T1-ST2: New microsatellite markers

The screening of the Eg genome resulted in the identification of 15 new microsatellites targets, which were evaluated for their polymorphism, reproducibility, limit of detection, quality of the electrophoretic profiles and their specificity. The selected targets will be coupled with EgSca6 microsatellite previously described by MEmE (M'Rad et al., 2020) in order to obtain a panel with a high discriminatory power. The possibility to use these microsatellites for large phylogenetic studies was initiated for the validation of the clustering method. Eg DNA samples from North Africa (Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia) and Europe (France, Italy and Greece) were collected and testing of microsatellites polymorphism is ongoing. Currently a panel composed by six new targets and EgSca6 is currently under evaluation. After obtaining data on the genetic diversity from these targets the definitive panel will be determined and tested with Eg samples from different areas. Due data M58.

WP3- T1-ST3: NGS-based method

The very high variability of Eg (*E. granulosus sensu stricto*) at the mitogenome level provides a possibility to perform source attribution analysis. Using the mitogenome data together with microsatellite fingerprinting may constitute reliable means to track the source of infection. Previous studies have shown that samples collected from the same area can be distinguished from samples from other areas based on complete or near-complete mitogenome data. At first, a method will be developed to sequence 96 mitogenomes with a single sequencing run. For this, we have already developed primers that enable PCR-amplification of the entire mitogenome in a single PCR. We aim to

use 96 different barcodes and the PacBio's Single Molecule, Real-Time (SMRT) Sequencing in the Sequel System, which allows easy and cost effective generation of highly accurate long reads (>99% single-molecule read accuracy) for DNA amplicons, such as the complete mitochondrial genomes. However, this assay requires samples of good quality. As the quality of parasite samples varies and often important samples are of low quality, we started to develop primers for such samples that consists of several primer pairs. We have designed and tested 4 primer pairs, however, two of these produced low-quality results for a subset of G1 samples, most likely due to variation at the primer binding sites. We designed new primers and testing these is ongoing. Due data M58.

WP3-T2. New multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of *Eg s.l.* and *Em*

Task updated and accomplished

To detect species belonging to the *Eg* complex, two variants (EG1 and EG2) of a TaqMan[®] probe-based five-plex real-time qPCR assay were developed and validated. The first variant of these assays (EG1) can simultaneously detect and genotype *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1, G3), *E. equinus* (G4), *E. ortleppi* (G5), and the *E. canadensis* complex (G6 to G8 and G10). The second variant of the test (EG2) is capable of detecting and distinguishing *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1, G3), *E. ortleppi* (G5), the *E. canadensis* genotype G8, and the remaining two members of the *E. canadensis* cluster (G6 and G10). For simultaneous diagnosis and genotyping of *Eg* complex and *Em* infections, further two variants of a TaqMan[®] probe-based multiplex real-time qPCR were developed and validated (EGM1 and EGM2). EGM1 multiplex assay is able efficiently to distinguish between *E. granulosus s.s.*, *E. equinus*, *E. canadensis* (G6-10) and *E. multilocularis*. In the case of EGM2 multiplex assay the species *E. granulosus s.s.*, *E. canadensis* (G8), *E. multilocularis* and *E. canadensis* (G6-10) can be simultaneously detected and genotyped. Into each TaqMan[®] probe-based multiplex real-time qPCR assay an internal control was included.

WP3-T3. Detection of *Em/Eg* in complex samples: sequencing using Regions Specific Extraction (RSE) and NGS

First step was to establish a pipeline for nanopore mtDNA sequencing and to allow sufficient data generation and for testing data analysis tools. Work started using DNA from positive controls included from the MC-DNA *EmNok* surveillance method, as these were spiked faecal samples isolated using magnetic capture of mtDNA from *Em*. The processed samples contained lower number of targets compared with pure *Em*-controls. Having enough material to allow sequencing, in order to get nanopore protocols working, it calls for some modifications of the material. As an alternative enrichment step, Illustra TempliPhi, was considered as a means to generate more template DNA for nanopore sequencing. A few dilutions were carried out to accommodate for faint samples. In addition to the positive *Em* control from MC method, standard prepared DNA samples from *Taenia* spp. were also included as controls. Samples were cleaned and DNA was measured. Further, they were prepared according to the selected nanopore sequence kit and some runs on Minion flongle flowcell was attempted on the products. All runs failed to generate data, and experiments were suspended until replacement chemicals arrived. As an alternative approach which would help solve the potential issue of not having enough parasite DNA molecules available in the sample to allow for full characterisation, and learning from recent method development for Sars-Cov2, a similar approach to the nanopore Midnight protocol (Freed et al., 2020) which is in use for full characterisation of virus genomes. We are exploring a similar long PCR-tiling approach for *Echinococcus* spp. mtDNA characterisation, using a panel of primers generating eight overlapping segments. This protocol will be tested on positive samples (native parasites, and fish-DNA) and PCR-optimisation and testing suitable nanopore kit protocols (ligation vs. rapid) is ongoing. Due data M58.

WP3-T4. Proteomic study on biomarker discovery in exosomes from animal plasma

Task closed and remodulated

We encounter technical difficulties regarding the proteomic study (at ISS, Italy) from plasma of experimentally infected (and controlled) sheep in Portugal (at INIAV, Portugal). Because of COVID-19, we were late in obtaining ethics committee approval at INIAV. Afterwards, in November 2020 we made two attempts with parasite protoscoleces collected from sheep in Sardinia (IZSS, Italy) to infect foxes in Nancy, France (ANSES) where ethics committee approval was also obtained for foxes. Unfortunately, in January 2021 we did not obtain Eg worms from fox experimental model (neither at flotation of faecal samples nor at PCR examination). During February/August 2021, we mobilized the international community to provide Eg eggs from experimentally or naturally infected canids. We received positive feedback from Australia, Iraqi Kurdistan, Kazakhstan and China, willing to collect and subsequently provide eggs. National lockdowns and national restrictions due to COVID-19 affected such field-collaboration since all these participants have retired. These eggs would have been used to infect sheep (animals are still housed in Portugal) and collect plasma for proteomic analyses searching for biomarkers of infection. We also discussed to modify ethical clearance at INIAV and try to infect sheep with Eg protoscoleces, instead of Eg egg. Since intraperitoneal injection of protoscoleces does not mimic natural infection, this may affect molecular pathways and therefore proteomic analysis outcome. Even if we found another solution, there would be no time to implement it before the end of MEME because of the long time (at least 1 year) it takes for the parasite to develop in sheep.

We confirm that COVID19-pandemic has definitively discontinued task 4 of WP3. To replace this activity, a new subtask was inserted in WP3: "Contamination of berries for human consumption by Em/Eg" (WP3-T6-ST2).

WP3-T5. Assessment of newly developed molecular methods against the existing techniques

The different molecular methods developed in MEME (RFLP and qPCR for Eg; see MEME publications) will be compared with already available methods regarding limit of detection of each assay but also by evaluating sensitivity and specificity using DNA samples obtained from field samples but also from experimental infection. Furthermore, faecal samples obtained during SSCT will be used to be compared with results obtained by processing the available Em copro-qPCR. This evaluation will be realized using the same DNA samples in different laboratories. Due data M58.

WP3-T6. Contamination of vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg

WP3-T6-ST1 contamination of lettuces

A total of 1,034 lettuce samples but also 69 samples from other vegetables (parsley, spinach, chard) were collected during 2021-2022 from local markets and supermarkets with around 50/100 vegetables samples collected by each partner which realized the first washing step of the filtration method. Considering Em endemic areas, the proportion of Em positive lettuce samples was 1.1% (considering only one lettuce positive in a pool of two), while it was 2.2% for Eg considering all areas. Positive samples for Em were obtained from France (1/144), Switzerland (1/78), Germany (1/74), (Denmark (2/50), Latvia (1/62) and Pakistan (2/100). Regarding Eg, positive samples were obtained from Italy around Roma (1/80), Napoli (3/46) and Sardinia (4/105) but also in Pakistan (4/100) and Tunisia (9/75). Additionally, other Taenidae species were detected in 2.4% of the samples mainly *Hydatigera* sp. but also *T. hydatigena*, *T. multiceps*, *T. saginata*, *T. serialis* and *T. krabbei*. This is the largest epidemiological study ever conducted on contamination of vegetables by Em and Eg which will contribute to the understanding of foodborne transmission.

WP3-T6-ST2 new: contamination of berries

A new subtask on the detection of *Echinococcus* spp. eggs in strawberries and blueberries was inserted in MEME (WP3-T6-ST2). The filtration method was validated on strawberries with 95% probability of detection of three eggs in 200g sample (88% probability of detection for both two and one egg) and will be validated for blueberries in 2022. In 2022, 11 additional partners (including external partners Finland, and Tunisia) joined this research. From 20 to 30 samples per country were prepared with a

first washing step realized in each lab. In order to minimize bias, these frozen pellets were sent to ANSES where filtration and molecular detection methods were realized. Due data M58.

WP3-T6-ST3 new: dispersion of Em/Eg eggs in the soil

A new subtask on the dispersion of Em eggs on the ground was inserted in MEmE (WP3-T6-ST3). The aim of this study was to assess the dispersal of Em eggs, following the deposition of a fox faecal sample containing 10,000 eggs obtained by experimental infection (WP1-T3) in the centre of a 2 x 2m naive soil plot. Four months later, 400 soil samples homogeneously distributed (from the first 0-1 cm of soil; dispersed surface of 10x10cm) were analysed by flotation method to isolate and concentrate the eggs before DNA extraction (automatic machine with magnetic beads) and then detected by real time PCR. The flotation of the faecal sample not dispersed in the soil identified 378 eggs therefore estimating a dispersion in the soil of 87% of the 10,000 eggs. The DNA of the eggs was detected in 39.5% of the soil samples that were distributed in all directions. The dispersion of eggs have reached the maximum distance of 1/1.4 m. According to Ct values of real time PCR, the detection was mainly realized from one egg (92%) obtained after the flotation. Moreover, in the centre of the plot (12 squares of 10x10 cm), the soil was collected at two additional depth levels till 2-3 cm, resulting in the detection of eggs from three and four soil samples. These data will be useful to understand the dispersion of Em eggs especially in kitchen gardens.

WP3-T7. Prevalence of Em/Eg in dog (faecal samples) from selected geographical areas

Eight MEmE partners were involved in this task (one of them left the task because of COVID-19 pandemic). Until now 1,611 samples of dog faeces were collected, most of them together with filled questionnaires. DNA was extracted from 1,592 samples. Overall, 1,242 samples have already been examined in France, Italy, Poland, Latvia and Denmark using multiplex PCR (Trachsel et al., 2007) resulted in - 3 *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Poland) and 18 *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* (Italy, Estonia, Poland) positive samples. Moreover 27 *Taenia* spp. (*T. krabbei*, *T. serialis*, *T. hydatigena*, *T. pisiformis*, *T. taeniaformis*) and 3 *Mesocestoides* spp. positive samples were detected. Furthermore, samples from Italy, Poland and France were examined with the new qPCRs (Maksimov et al., 2021) for the identification *E. granulosus* species complex developed within MEmE framework: *E. granulosus s.s.* (G1-G3) was identified in 28 samples from Italy and Poland (out of 989 examined) while 623 samples for *E. equinus* (G4), 971 for *E. ortleppi* (G5), 846 for *E. canadensis* (G6-10) were examined without positive results. Additionally, 788 samples from France and Poland were examined using qPCR (Knapp et al., 2016) for *E. multilocularis* – 3 samples were identified as Em positive (Poland). In addition 381 faecal samples were examined microscopically using flotation – 12 of them were positive for Taeniidae eggs, one for *Toxocara* sp. Due data M58.

WP3-T8. Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires

Task replaced with “Quantitative assessment on the burden of human CE”

WP3-T8 new. Quantitative assessment on the burden of human CE

WP3-T8-ST1 new: Species and genotypes belonging to *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* complex causing human cystic echinococcosis in Europe (2000-2021): a systematic review

Task accomplished

This study aimed to fill a gap of knowledge by providing a quantitative measure of molecularly identified species and genotypes belonging to *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato (s.l.)* causing human cystic echinococcosis (CE) in Europe during the period 2000-2021. As these species and genotypes are characterized by genetic, animal host and geographical differences, studying the Eg complex is epidemiologically relevant. A systematic review (SR) was conducted on the basis of both scientific and grey literature considering primary studies between 2000 and 2021 in four databases. From a total of 1,643 scientific papers, 51 records were included in the SR. The main inclusion criterion for this study was the molecular confirmation of Eg at the genotype/species level as a causative agent of human CE

cases in selected European countries. Relevant data were obtained from 29 out of 39 eligible European countries. This SR identified 599 human molecularly confirmed echinococcal cysts: 460 (76.8%) identified as *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (s.s.), 130 (21.7%) as *E. canadensis* cluster (G6/7 and G10), 7 (1.2%) as *E. ortleppi* (G5), and 2 as *E. vogeli* (0.3%). Three geographical hotspots of human CE caused by different species of the Eg complex were identified: (1) *E. granulosus* s.s. in Southern and South-eastern Europe (European-Mediterranean and Balkan countries); (2) *E. canadensis* (G6/7) in Central and Eastern Europe; (3) *E. ortleppi* in Central and Western Europe. This SR also identified data gaps that prevented a better definition of the geographical distribution of the Eg species complex in Europe: western Balkan countries, part of Central Europe, and Baltic countries.

WP3-T8-ST2 new: Unveiling the burden of hidden pandemic cystic echinococcosis in Europe: a systematic review from the MEmE project

Task accomplished

The neglected zoonosis cystic echinococcosis (CE) affects worldwide poor pastoral and rural communities but also those of medium-high income countries, including European, where it should be managed as an orphan and rare disease. Even if human CE is a notifiable parasitic infectious disease in most European countries, in practice it is largely underreported by national health systems. To fill this gap, data on the burden of CE in Europe was extracted by means of systematic review approach from both scientific and grey literature, accounting for the period of publication 1997-2021. The utmost quantitative effect of the burden at country level was selected from different data sources to generate a descriptive model of human CE in Europe. This study identified 64,281 human CE cases from 40 European countries within the considered period. Bulgaria, Italy, Romania and Spain accounted for 67.5% of CE health burden. Mean annual incidence in Europe was 0.64/100,000 during 1997-2021 and 0.50/100,000 during 2017-19. An estimate of around 2,101 and 1,716 new cases per year are expected at European and EU level, respectively, according to the trend for the years 2017-19. Based on incidence rates and trends, the current epicentre of CE in Europe is represented by South-eastern European countries, while historical endemic European Mediterranean countries have seen a decrease in the burden over the time.

WP3-T8-ST3 new: Human source attribution of cerebral CE by molecular approach and its quantitative assessment in the literature”

This activity focuses on the first source attribution based on molecular methods of a rare case of cerebral CE in a child from Roman campagna. A literature search was also conducted on 6 databases with Boolean terms for the clinical and epidemiological quantification of cerebral CE at global level. No limitation of year of publication was envisaged. Inclusion criteria were: clinical reports including case reports, case series, clinical trials, retrospective and prospective cases of confirmed human cerebral CE. Exclusion criteria were: animal cases, AE cases and no confirmed cases of cerebral CE. The search identified 1,776 relevant articles which were selected by title and abstract. (Task ongoing).

WP4. Training, dissemination and proficiency testing schemes

WP4-T1. Trainings

This WP focuses on establishing the most effective methods for training scientists from institutions participating to MEmE in the parasitological and molecular identification of *Echinococcus* spp. Due to COVID-19 pandemic, no physical training was conducted until now. For this reason, NVI generated online training on “Magnetic capture of Em DNA from red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples: DNA extraction with manual washing steps”. A training movie showing each of the steps can be viewed on YouTube at: <https://www.youtube.com/embed/hdo3mE8oMKE?rel=0>. One of the partners (ISS) has requested physical training for the magnetic capture method at NVI and this has been planned for spring/summer 2022.

WP4-T2. Dissemination of project results

This task focuses on establishing the most effective methods for disseminating project results at different levels. Due to COVID-19 pandemic non-participation to physical events prevent the dissemination, while it was done during online events (“One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021”, “Annual meeting of the European Reference Laboratory for Parasites 2020”, “13th European Multicolloquium of Parasitology” and the “One Health EJP Final Annual Scientific Meeting 2022”) and publishing scientific papers for a wide scientific audience (see papers on Lancet Global Health and PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases).

WP4-T3. Organization of selected PTs from WP2 and WP3

Additional PTs on “Verification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* magnetic capture method in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces and proficiency test” and “Harmonization of Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using RSE and NGS” are planned and will be completed during the summer of 2022.

WP5. Scientific and administrative management

WP5-T1. Setup of the project

Task accomplished

WP5-T2. Administrative and scientific management

Activities are ongoing throughout the lifespan of MEmE to accomplish its administrative and scientific management. Interim online annual meeting of MEmE was conducted on 15 February 2022 (M50).

WP5-T3. Ethics management

Task accomplished

5.1.4.7.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
18	D-JRP18-WP1.1	SOPs for sampling in matrices shared within the Consortium	M28	M31		Public https://zenodo.org/record/4455196#.YAmIsxbSKgo	2
18	D-JRP18-WP1.2	Collection of samples in the field finalized	M36	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499866#.YTsvmc_OMzk	8
18	D-JRP18-WP1.3	Collection of samples from experimental animal model finalized	M48	M52		Public https://zenodo.org/record/6203493#.YhOPW5bjK70	8
18	D-JRP18-WP2.1	Validation of SSCT	M36	M48		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499551#.YTr8sM_OMzk	8
18	D-JRP18-WP2.2	Validation of multiplex PCRs	M44	M49		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499864#.YdwvolnSKgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP2.3	Validation of Magnetic Capture Real-time PCR assay	M44	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5500594#.YTusOaTOMzk	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.1	New molecular markers	M48		M58	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.2	New multiplex TaqMan qPCR	M48	M48		Public https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.YdwY6FnSKgo	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
18	D-JRP18-WP3.3	New NGS method for the detection in complex samples	M48		M58	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.5	Assessment of newly developed methods against the existing	M54		M58		8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.6	Contamination of vegetables by Em/Eg	M48		M58	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.7	Prevalence of Em/Eg in dog from selected geographical areas	M48		M58	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.8	Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires	M48			<u>Task replaced with "Quantitative assessment of the burden of human CE". Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19 crisis</u>	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.8	Quantitative assessment of the burden of human CE	M48		M58	ST1 and ST2 finished. ST3 ongoing	8
18	D-JRP18-WP4.1	Analysis and evaluation of training activities	M48		M58	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19	8
18	D-JRP18-WP4.3	Final report of PT SSCT	M48	M49		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5816663#.YdQlv1njLmE	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.1	Data Management Plan (DMP)	M30	M45	M58	Public M45: https://zenodo.org/record/5415292#.YTITD9_OOgo Update M58	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.2	Periodic technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M36	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5413157#.YTH66d_OOgo	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
18	D-JRP18-WP5.3	Periodic technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M48	M49		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5833427#.YdwWF1nSKgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.5	Kick-off annual meeting in Malzéville (France) by ANSES	M27	M28		Public https://zenodo.org/record/4455256#.YAmKvxbSKgo	8
18	D-JRP22-WP5.6	Interim annual online meeting	M49	M50		Public https://zenodo.org/record/6631959#.YqNbbuxBygo	8

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
18	M-JRP18-01	Tasks and responsibility allocation	M25	Yes		Kick off meeting in France used for the allocation of the tasks and responsibilities
18	M-JRP18-02	Organization of Kick-off annual meeting by ANSES	M26	Yes		

JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
18	M-JRP18-03	Ethics approvals for the use of animal model	M28	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-04	SOP for validation of SSCT	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-05	SOP for validation of multiplex PCRs	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-06	SOP for Validation of Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay	M41	Yes		Distributed along with verification material and ring test in M46.
18	M-JRP18-07	Protocols for New molecular methods, NGS included	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-08	Protocol for proteomic analysis in animals plasma	M30	No		COVID19 disrupted this task. See WP3-T4. New task on the detection in berries was inserted (WP3-T6-ST2).
18	M-JRP18-09	Protocol for contamination of vegetables by Em/Eg	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-10	Protocol for prevalence of Em/Eg in dog	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-11	(Questionnaire scheme for potential human risk factors) Task replaced with literature search for "Quantitative assessment of the burden of human CE".	M30	Yes		

JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
18	M-JRP18-12	Interim evaluation of collection of samples in the filed	M32	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-13	Preparation of technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M35	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-15	Interim evaluation of collection of samples from experimental animal model	M42	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-16	Selection of new/old methods to be compared	M44	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-18	Preparation of technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M47	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-19	Diagnostic performance of Participants to PTs	M54	Ongoing	58	
18	M-JRP18-21	Organization of Final meeting by ISS	M56	Ongoing	58	Planned for November 2022

5.1.4.7.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Insights into Human Cystic Echinococcosis in the Kurdistan Region, Iraq: Characteristics and Molecular Identification of Cysts. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0817/11/4/408 https://zenodo.org/record/6521840#.YnPhktNBygo	YES		Yes, 1983.77 €
Species and genotypes belonging to <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> complex causing human cystic echinococcosis in Europe (2000-2021): a systematic review approach. https://parasitesandvectors.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13071-022-05197-8 https://zenodo.org/record/6521887#.YnPkVtNBygo	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge; invited by editor)
Chromosome-scale <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> (genotype G1) genome reveals the Eg95 gene family and conservation of the EG95-vaccine molecule. https://www.nature.com/articles/s42003-022-03125-1 https://zenodo.org/record/6521878#.YnPjSdNBygo	YES		Yes, 0 €
A Retrospective Cohort Study on Human Cystic Echinococcosis in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province (Pakistan) Based on 16 Years of Hospital Discharge Records. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0817/11/2/194 https://zenodo.org/record/6091472#.Ygu6UJbSKgo	YES		Yes, 1983.77 €
Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0817/10/10/1326 https://zenodo.org/record/5646982#.Ydr55ybSizk	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge)
New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009373 https://zenodo.org/record/4771738#.YKTFCqHOOgp	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge; invited editorial)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Cystic echinococcosis: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia (Italy). https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9110907 https://zenodo.org/record/4159681	YES		Yes, 1.389 €
Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs (<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed <i>Besnoitia</i> species. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3 https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YTDH7t_OOgo	YES		Yes, 2.190 €
Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for detection of <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> in the stool samples of naturally infected red foxes. https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10122381 https://zenodo.org/record/4384600	YES		Yes, 1.481 €
Species detection within the <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> complex by novel probe based Real-Time PCRs. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100791 https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.X6PY3WhKjcc	YES		Yes, 1.258,81 €
A validated method to identify <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> at species level. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104575 https://zenodo.org/record/4066416#.X6UQMWhKjcc	YES		Yes, 2.300 €
Identification of <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs Genotyping Assays. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020125 https://zenodo.org/record/4471215#.YGLkiq8zZM0	YES		Yes, 696,38 €
Bayesian analysis to evaluate three diagnostic methods for cystic echinococcosis in sheep. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100796 https://zenodo.org/record/4061823#.X6PZl2hKjcc	YES		Yes, 1.389,79 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto</i> cysts in single hosts reveal different patterns of infection events between livestock and humans. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9060444 https://zenodo.org/record/3894117#.XvyQ6ygzZM0	YES		Yes, 654,56 €
Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis. https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30066-8 https://zenodo.org/record/3730559#.Xn3FalhKi70	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge; invited comment)

Additional output

Presentation of MEmE project at:

- “Do we really know the burden of human cystic echinococcosis in Europe?: a systematic review approach from MEmE project”, 32nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID), April 22-26, 2022 Lisbon, Portugal.
- “The burden of human cystic echinococcosis in Europe (2000-2021): a systematic review approach from meme project”. OHEJP final meeting, April 11-13, 2022. Orvieto, Italy.
- Several presentations on MEmE project as a whole and on project specific tasks. 15th International Congress on Parasitology, ICOPA. August, 20-26, 2022. Copenhagen, Denmark.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Expected achievements of MEmE are:

- Validation of the parasitological and molecular diagnostic procedures to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.
- Development and validation of new molecular tools to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.
- Production of data relevant for epidemiological and risk assessments on the contamination of vegetables and berries by parasite eggs and on the prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces in selected endemic countries.
- Dissemination of project results at different levels.
- Creating a strong parasitic Em/Eg network in Europe with contacts at the national and international level.

5.1.4.7.5 [Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations \(e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO\), networks, or national ministries](#)

Ongoing and planned collaborations with the following entities:

- The other parasitology-JRPs: PARADISE and TOXOSOURCES.
- The European Reference Laboratory for Parasites (EURLP).
- The WHO Collaborating Centre WHO Collaborating Centre for the Epidemiology, Detection and Control of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis (in humans and animals).
- PERITAS project (molecular ePIdemiological studiEs on pathways of tRansmission and long lasTing cApacity building to prevent cyStic echinococcosis infection). 2018-2021. Funded by the EC under EULAC-Health.
- ECHINO-SAFE-MED project (New sustainable tools and innovative actions to control cystic ECHINOCoccosis in sheep farms in the MEDiterranean area: improvement of diagnosis and SAFETy in response to climatic changes). PRIMA, Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area.

5.1.4.8 JRP19-R2-ET1.1-PARADISE

5.1.4.8.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The PARADISE project aims at delivering informative genotyping schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for both *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*, which are important pathogens of humans and other animals. This will contribute to better investigations of outbreak and to generation of prevalence data to inform risk assessment.

The most relevant progresses for the research-orientated activities are summarized below:

- WP2: The NGS sequencing effort has been completed, with production of >100 *C. parvum* whole genomes sequences (WGS) from humans and ruminants, and of >40 *G. duodenalis* assemblage B WGS, mostly from humans. Currently, comparative genomics studies of this large collection of European WGS are in progress, and aim at a better description of the population structure, virulence and evolution for both parasites. For metagenomics studies, reference material from *Cryptosporidium parvum*, *Toxoplasma gondii* and *Giardia duodenalis* has been used to spike plant DNA (mixed salad) at different concentrations, to mimic natural contamination and to explore the limit of detection of the two NGS platforms (amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics). Spiked samples were correctly identified using species-specific qPCR. The amplicon-based platform only identified *T. gondii* whereas the shotgun approach revealed problems of specificity in the detection for the three parasites.
- WP3: The validation of the new novel multi-locus sequence typing (MLST) schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* has been completed, with hundreds of isolates tested by PCR and sequencing. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) describing the two MLSTs were prepared and distributed to all partners. An inter-laboratory comparison was organized in May 2022 between all partners to assess the robustness and reproducibility of the SOP. Extracted DNA of five samples per pathogen were distributed among 14 different laboratories from 11 European countries. Prior to shipment, two virtual technical training workshops were performed for each SOP separately.
- WP4: The libraries of nanobodies were screened for candidates specifically binding to *G. duodenalis* cysts or *C. parvum* oocysts. The procedure retrieved 10 promising candidates for *G. duodenalis*. Testing of specificity to assemblage A and B in immunofluorescence assays revealed assemblage-dependent binding pattern, and identified two candidates binding to the cyst wall of both assemblages. For aptamers, ANSES is evaluating the binding properties and affinity of ten putative binders for *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis*, and of five putative binders for both. In parallel, new SELEX protocol was set up with modifications for the single strand DNA generation step. Up to date, three rounds were achieved showing higher purity of the aptamers. ISS evaluated the binding properties of 20 candidate aptamers for *G. duodenalis* cysts. Immunofluorescence and enzyme-linked oligonucleotide assays revealed poor affinity of the aptamers to *G. duodenalis* cysts. Binding affinity test by flow cytometry is ongoing. For DNA fishing, the capture system designed for *Cryptosporidium* (based on 18S rDNA and gp60 genes) was thoroughly characterised to determine the sensitivity of both probe sets. An interlaboratory study was performed (SVA and RIVM) to compare the use and application of protocols. Finally, probes were used in an outbreak and surveillance setting.

5.1.4.8.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1-Coordination and impact

WP-1-T1- Management, coordination and communication

In Y5, regular meetings between WP and Task leaders allowed to track the project's activities, plan experiments and discuss new strategies. The Final meeting will be held in Uppsala (local organizer, SVA) on June 22-23. On March 2022, one partner (OKI) decided to leave the project; this decision was communicated to ISS (project coordinator) and to OHEJP (Sciensano and ANSES).

WP2-NGS-based genomics and metagenomics

WP2-T1- NGS-based genome study of selected isolates of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*

In Y5, after generating the largest collection of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* WGS at the European level, in-depth comparative genomics studies are being conducted to improve our understanding of the population structure, virulence and evolution for both parasites. Publications are planned for the end of Y5.

WP2-T2- In silico analyses of metagenomes for detection of foodborne parasites (protozoa and helminths)

In Y5, the focus has been on the refinement of the analytical workflows for detection of parasite sequences in metagenomics data. Signature sequences, already available for *C. parvum*, were identified for *G. duodenalis* and *T. gondii*. These will be used to mine additional metagenomics dataset before the end of the project.

WP2-T3- Experimental amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics for detection of foodborne parasites

In Y5, the main objective was to compare the limit of detection of two platforms on a matrix (mixed salad) spiked with three parasites at three different concentrations. The results revealed difficulties in detecting low number of parasites in large metagenomics datasets essentially composed by eukaryotic sequences. Alternative detection strategies are being explored.

WP3-Design, implementation and validation of multi-locus typing schemes

WP3-T1- In silico selection of informative loci from comparative genomics data

This task has been completed.

WP3-T2- Development of MLST schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*

IN Y5, the new novel multi-locus sequence typing (MLST) schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* have been robustly tested and validated on hundreds of field isolates from across Europe. The discriminatory power has been evaluated and, for *C. parvum*, compared to that obtained using loci containing Variable Number of Tandem Repeats (VNTRs).

WP3-T3-Interlaboratory comparison of typing schemes

In Y5, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) describing the new MLSTs were prepared and distributed to all partners, and two virtual technical training workshops were organized. The inter-laboratory comparisons were organized in May 2022 to assess the robustness and reproducibility of the SOP. Extracted DNA of five samples per pathogen were distributed among 14 different laboratories from 11 European countries.

WP4-Parasite enrichment strategies

WP4-T1- Development of pre-DNA extraction enrichment strategies

In Y5, screening of produced libraries for nanobodies specifically binding to *G. duodenalis* cysts or *C. parvum* oocysts retrieved 10 promising candidates for *Giardia* only. Testing of specificity to assemblage A and B in immunofluorescence assays revealed assemblage-dependent binding pattern, and identified two candidates binding to the cyst wall of both assemblages. The binding properties and affinity of a number of putative binders for *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis* are being evaluated and, in parallel, new SELEX protocol is being used for further screening.

WP4-T2- Development of post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies

In Y5, we thoroughly characterised the probes that were developed to detect *Cryptosporidium* using the *18s rRNA* gene and *gp60* gene. We determined the sensitivity of both probe sets and performed an interlaboratory study to compare the use and application of protocols. Finally, we applied both probes in an outbreak and surveillance setting.

5.1.4.8.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP1.2	Report of Annual meeting	M46	M57	M57	Public 10.5281/zenodo.7064005	8, meeting report
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP1.3	Report of Final meeting	M54	M57	M57	Public 10.5281/zenodo.7064023	8, meeting report
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.2	Report on the FBPs detected in metagenomics datasets by <i>in silico</i> analysis	M52		M58	We are performing additional analysis on matrices that were not yet considered and have repeated another panel of spikes	
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.3	SOPs for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> MLST schemes	M50		M57	Public 10.5281/zenodo.7064263	2

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-9	Submission of genome sequences of <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> to public repository	M50	No	M56	A few additional genome sequencing experiment are in progress, and the entire batch of data will then be submitted to a public repository
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-11	Highly affine nanobodies selected	M45	No	M56	Selection did work for <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> but not for <i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i> , and additional experiments are ongoing (RfI)
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-14	Annual meeting (WP1)	M42	Yes	M46	The Annual meeting has been held, virtually, on the 26th October 2021.
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-15	Technical Workshop on enrichment strategies (WP4)	M54	No		Organization of the technical workshop not possible due to the Covid-19 pandemics. Possibility to produce a video tutorial and/or to organize a dedicated session during the last project meeting (June 2022, M54)
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-16	Final set of markers for MLST of <i>C. parvum</i> available	M45	Yes		
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-17	Final set of markers for MLST of <i>G. duodenalis</i> available	M45	Yes		

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-18	Technical Workshop for training on MLST (WP3)	M48	No		Organization of the technical workshop not possible due to the Covid-19 pandemics. Possibility to produce a video tutorial and/or to organize a dedicated session during the last project meeting (June 2022, M54)
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-19	Validation of marker for typability and resolution accomplished	M48	Yes	M54	Results of the interlaboratory test have been discussed at the final meeting (Uppsala, 22-23 June) and by direct contacts with the Consortium partners
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-20	Magnetic bead coupled nanobodies suitable for the enrichment of (oo)cysts available	M52	No	M56	Experiments ongoing to overcome difficulties in the selection of nanobodies showing affinity to <i>Cryptosporidium</i> oocysts.
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-21	Magnetic bead coupled aptamers suitable for the enrichment of (oo)cysts available	M52	No	M56	Aptamers with the desired binding properties against <i>Cryptosporidium</i> and <i>Giardia</i> (oo)cysts have not been identified yet.
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-22	Hybridization probes tested for robustness and sensitivity available	M52	No	M56	Validation almost completed by SVA and RIVM. The possibility of further testing by other partners will be discussed at the final meeting

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JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
19	M-JRP19-PARADISE-23	Final meeting (WP1)	M54	Yes	M57	The final meeting has been held in Uppsala on June 22-23

5.1.4.8.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Molecular Characterization of <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> in Children and Adults Sampled in Algeria https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010054 https://zenodo.org/record/4422456#.YArbG-hKjcc	YES		YES 2730.00 \$ = 2437.96 €
Veterinary Students Have a Higher Risk of Contracting Cryptosporidiosis when Calves with High Fecal Cryptosporidium Loads Are Used for Fetotomy Exercises 10.1128/AEM.01250-20 https://zenodo.org/record/4129990#.X6PX8WhKjcc	YES		YES 1475.33 €
Parasitic Intestinal Protists of Zoonotic Relevance Detected in Pigs by Metabarcoding and Real-Time PCR. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-2607/9/6/1189 https://zenodo.org/record/4898752#.YTnBA50zaUk	Yes		YES Free of cost
Mining public metagenomes for environmental surveillance of parasites: a proof of principle. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.622356 https://zenodo.org/record/5494583	YES		YES 1580.00 \$ = 2176.47 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Amplicon-based next-generation sequencing of eukaryotic nuclear ribosomal genes (metabarcoding) for the detection of single-celled parasites in human faecal samples. doi: 10.1016/j.parepi.2022.e00242.	YES		YES 1580 €
An outbreak of cryptosporidiosis associated with drinking water in north-eastern Italy, August 2019: microbiological and environmental investigations. doi: 10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2022.27.35.2200038. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7043272	YES		YES Free of cost

Additional output

Presentation of results WP2-T1 at the 13th International Meeting on Microbial Epidemiological Markers (IMMEM XIII), Bath, 14-17 September 202: “*Genomic epidemiology of Cryptosporidium parvum in Europe*”. By Davise Sasser (external collaborator, University of Pavia).

Presentation of the project’s highlights at the ICOPA Conference, Copenhagen, 21-26 August 2022: “PARADISE: PARAsite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation”. By Martha Betson, UoS.

Presentation of results WP2-T1 at the ICOPA Conference, Copenhagen, 21-26 August 2022: “*A large-scale comparative genomics study of human and ruminant strains of Cryptosporidium parvum from Europe*”. By Marco Lalle, ISS.

Presentation of results WP3-T1 at the ICOPA Conference, Copenhagen, 21-26 August 2022: “*Development of a multi-locus sequence typing scheme for Cryptosporidium parvum*”. By Umer Chaudhry, UoS.

Presentation of results WP2-T1 at the ECCMID Conference, Lisbon, 23-26 April 2022: “*Genomic epidemiology of Cryptosporidium parvum in Europe*”. By Greta Bellinzona (external collaborator, University of Pavia). https://markterfolg.de/ESCMID/Final_Programme_2022/#page=1

Presentation of results WP2-T1 at the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting, Orvieto, 11-13 April 2022: “*Large scale comparative genomics of the zoonotic pathogen Cryptosporidium parvum in Europe*”. By Simone M. Cacciò, ISS.

Presentation of results WP4-T2 at the Veterinary Parasitology Workshop, Wageningen University, May 18, 2022: “*Capture probe based detection method for Cryptosporidium spp. and it’s use to determine prevalence of zoonotic Cryptosporidium spp. in dairy calves*”. By Kees van der Ark, RIVM.

Presentation of results WP2-T3 at the Veterinary Parasitology Workshop, Wageningen University, May 18, 2022: “*Looking for Cryptosporidium in the (metagenomics) hay stack*”. By Frits Franssen, RIVM.

Application of tool developed in WP4-T2 for the detection of Cryptosporidium in the National Livestock Surveillance in the Netherlands. Public report by RIVM (in Dutch) expected in Q4 2022.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

A major outcome of the project is the generation of a large number of whole genome data for both *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis*. Exploitation of these data will provide an unprecedented opportunity to study the biology of these parasites and to shed light on the mechanisms that have influenced their evolution, virulence, host adaptation, and population genetic structure. Remarkably, the OHEJP will be at the forefront of genomic research for these two pathogens.

5.1.4.8.4.1 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

- Complementarities with the OHEJP research project “**Toxosources**”. Specifically, collaboration on bioinformatics approaches for genome comparison and development of new typing schemes. Further interactions foreseen in relation to new methodologies for enrichment and detection of parasites in specific food matrices (ready-to-eat salads).
- Complementarities with the OHEJP integrative project “**Harmony-CAP**”, in which *Cryptosporidium* has been selected as a model organism for evaluation of the current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols.
- Link with the objectives of the **European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites** in terms of new typing schemes for FBP that, in perspective, may become official, validated methods.

- Link with the objectives of the **Inter-EURL working group on Whole Genome Sequencing** in terms of building capacities at the EU level and foster the application of this technology. Training activities and implementation of bioinformatics pipelines.
- Complementarities with the **EFSA-funded research project “IMPACT”** for the definition of optimized protocols for the molecular detection and characterization of FBPs on selected food matrices.
- Complementarities with the National project **Microfoodrisk** (funded by the Italian Ministry of Health), in terms of research on emerging food safety risks from microbial hazards (including parasites) deriving from anthropogenic pressures in agricultural settings. Common use of metagenomics approaches, which may help to address some of the challenges identified by PARADISE.

5.1.4.9 JRP20-R2-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR

5.1.4.9.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

This DiSCoVeR project brings together experts from different disciplines (microbiology, bioinformatics and epidemiology) and sectors (veterinary science, food safety, public health and environmental health) from 19 institutions in 13 European countries into a unique consortium to address the challenges of source attribution in an interdisciplinary manner. As there is no gold standard for source attribution, we take a comprehensive approach applying several different methodologies and models in a comparative fashion.

In the first year, we mapped the existing knowledge gaps and recommend new studies and/or methods that are needed to fill them. We then mapped existing data by creating data inventories for all DiSCoVeR target pathogens. Now new data were included in the inventories after May 2022 in order to leave enough time for data analysis. This means that not all expected data were available for the project, as some partners met delays in collecting new data from non-livestock and non-food sources due to COVID-19. Still, we have managed to collect comprehensive datasets including data from a broad range of reservoirs and sources, including those that are not traditionally part of existing monitoring and surveillance activities, e.g. pets (incl. reptiles), wildlife, and environmental sources.

Work is focused on cataloguing, evaluating and advancing existing methods for source attribution of the three pathogens (*Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, and STEC) and AMR. For *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, several partners have or are in the process of developing WGS-based attribution models. Preliminary results indicate that the outputs are very much in line with previous subtyping approaches (phenotypic and MLST based), although the WGS-based models appear to have a higher predicting accuracy due to the increased discriminatory power. Conventional subtyping approaches are also being applied. A systematic literature review and meta-analysis of case-control studies of sporadic *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* infections has been completed, and so has an analysis of EU *Salmonella* outbreak data. Although the nuances and the level of attribution of these types of studies are different from the subtyping approaches, the results are comparable and dissimilarities can to a large extent be explained. Multi-country Comparative Exposure Assessments (CEA) of all target pathogens and AMR in pets have been completed. The output is the relative exposure of humans to pathogenic and antimicrobial resistant bacteria due to in-/direct contact with cats or dogs.

A mapping of the currently existing control programmes of the target pathogens and AMR in humans, animals and the environment at the EU and national level is also completed. This task was addressed by i) a scientific literature review, ii) a review of grey literature, and iii) a survey aimed at relevant national experts.

An online stakeholder workshop was held on January 22, 2021, where around 20 participants from EFSA, ECDC, EURLs, other relevant EJP projects joined in a discussion on how DiSCoVeR results could support the work of the stakeholders and vice versa. In November 2022, we plan to have a follow-up

workshop presenting project outcomes and discuss how the key findings including the attribution estimates can be translated into policy.

On the project management side, we have since the project start had one face-to-face meeting and eight web meeting for all partners, and 14 web meetings for the project management team. We have created a share site for partners to share documents and data. For sharing of genomic sequences, we have set up a secure space on the data platform sciencedata.dk. Finally, all partners have signed a Material Transfer Agreement.

5.1.4.9.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1: Project coordination and administration (M25-60)

WP1-T1- Project management (M25-60) - ongoing

Since the start of the project, we have had one face-to-face kick-off meeting hosted by DTU on February 10-12, 2020, and eight web meetings for all partners and 14 web meetings for the project management team (PMT) consisting of all work package leaders, their deputies and task leaders. In addition, the individual WPs hold monthly or biweekly meetings to follow progress and present and discuss results.

A share-site hosted by DTU has been set up, where project partners share documents and data, including minutes of meetings and the data inventories.

Partners have agreed on a Material Transfer Agreement (MTA), which has being signed by all partners.

WP1-T2- Mapping of existing knowledge gaps (M25-28) - completed

For the mapping of existing knowledge gaps, a systematic literature search by means of a rapid review was performed. Based on predefined search queries, publications relevant for source attribution of the bacterial species *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC/STEC and for antimicrobial resistant (AMR) bacteria (*Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *E. coli*) were identified in the two databases Scopus and Web of Science. Each identified publication was tagged according to categories like the organisms and sources they considered or the methods they employed. Using the data of the tagged publications, knowledge maps were created, which show the number of publications found for each method-source combination for each of the above-mentioned foodborne pathogens and AMR. The methodology and results of this mapping together with suggestions how to fill the identified knowledge gaps assembled in a report and submitted as deliverable D-JRP FBZ-1-WP1.1 to the project coordinator. The results were also presented at the OHEJP ASM in Copenhagen June 9-11, 2021. A summary is uploaded at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/5825542#.YdcJyWjMKUk>

WP1-T3- Data Management Plan (DMP) (M25-60) - ongoing

The first draft of the DMP was prepared in Nov 2020, but its development is a continuing process. Considering the structure of the new DMP tool, we plan to upload information about our selected datasets, whenever we have a 'finalised' dataset ready for data analysis. Next update was done in M49, where almost all WGS data were uploaded to sciencedata.dk.

The plan is to make the data open access through ENA by creating a so-called umbrella project. However, this requires some organising, as some sequences that are included in DiSCoVeR are already at ENA, whereas others are not, meaning that the partners need to upload these. We are currently completing pathogen-specific lists with all sequence data used in DiSCoVeR including ENA accession numbers. These lists need to be updated as partners upload 'new' sequences to ENA. First when we have a final list of accession numbers, can we ask for the creation of an umbrella project, which we can then open to the public.

WP2: Data: Coordination of data collection (M25-M50)

WP2-T1- Mapping of existing data/database est. (M25-36) - completed

A data inventory form in Excel was adapted to each pathogen subgroup. The purpose of the inventory was to get a quick overview of strains and sequences available in order to pinpoint areas with limited data availability to i) direct further sampling, and ii) identify for which pathogens and models we can expect to have sufficient data for source attribution. The data inventories have been filled-in by partners and hazard-specific web meetings have been organized to present the data available and agree on further sampling of mainly non-animal food reservoirs and/or isolate characterization (mainly sequencing) and transmission to the other WPs for source attribution analysis. A short description and the hazard-specific data sheets have been uploaded to Zenodo as D-JRPFZ-1-WP2.6 along with the data inventory files (Excel), which holds all the data collected and used in the project, except for the actual sequence data as explained above.

The data inventories provided the basis for selection of appropriate datasets for source attribution for the focus hazard and attribution approaches (see WP4 description for the source attribution approaches selected for each organism). Also, for each of the hazards, a publication describing the collected data and resulting dataset is being prepared.

For sharing WGS data among participants, we created a space on the data platform sciencedata.dk and made a plan for uploading data. A meeting to demonstrate the sciencedata platform was held May 27, 2021. The majority of the sequence data have been uploaded, but due to delays in sample collection, a few are still pending.

For *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* sequences, partners are either uploading i) raw sequence data, which are then run through the FoodQC pipeline at DTU, or ii) assembled sequences, which should then adhere to a set of agreed quality criteria, which are uploaded to the share-site. For STEC, a pipeline was developed as part of the projects, which all partners contributing with STEC sequences have been using.

WP2-T2- Data collection: Salmonella (M25-48) - completed

Overall, nine countries (Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Ireland, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Spain and UK) delivered data about *Salmonella* serovars in their collections. Six institutes showed data from animals, food and environment, five concerning humans.

Overall, the most numerous *Salmonella* serovars are *S. Typhimurium* (>20280 isolates/> 800 sequences), Enteritidis (>18560 isolates/> 800 sequences), monophasic variant of *S. Typhimurium* (>16500 isolates/> 300 sequences) and *S. Infantis* (>2560 isolates/ 120 sequences). Those serovars occur in all main sources. SE and ST were found as a top 1 and 2 in humans and animals. In food, *S. Infantis* and *S. Typhimurium* are dominant. The environment is represented by the least number of isolates of different *Salmonella* serovars (>300 isolates/ 0 sequences). Some countries declared ongoing sampling or being ready to sequence selected isolates if needed.

For WGS-based source attribution, focus is on the following serovars: Typhimurium, monophasic Typhimurium, Enteritidis, Infantis, Derby, and Newport. For these serovars it was possible for a handful of countries to contribute with 25+ sequences per source per serovar and country during the past 5-10 years.

For a multi-country attribution model based on phenotypic information only, available subtyping data for *Salmonella* were submitted from several partners and formatted for source attribution analyses in WP4.

WP2-T3- Data collection: *Campylobacter* (M25-48) - completed

Nine countries contributed with *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* data. Of data representing sources, most were from animals (n=1417) followed by food (n=557) and environment (n=142). All of these, except for 117 isolates, were also available as sequences.

All the sequences have been processed through the FoodQC pipeline and made available for the partners through the sciencedata.dk platform for further analysis. Bioinformatics extracted from the sequences include quality parameters, SNP, 7-loci MLST, cgMLST, wgMLST, Kmer and AMR genes. For results of the modelling work, see WP4.

WP2-T4- Data collection: *STEC* (M25-50) - completed

An isolate inventory was created and filled in by 16 partners from 11 countries. Isolates include in the inventory is distributed as follows: Humans = 5107, Livestock = 1433, wild animals = 91, environment = 29, fruit/vegetables = 8, other animals incl. pets and zoo animals = 22.

Of these, more than 3000 human STEC isolates with WGS data will be available for the project. For the animal, food and environmental STEC isolates almost 1000 isolates with WGS data will be available. ISS has developed a WGS pipeline, which most partners have been running using the Galaxy platform, and sequences are uploaded to sciencedata.dk.

The need for further sampling of other sources than food-producing animals has been highlighted throughout the project, but due to COVID-19 some sampling was cancelled meaning that we did not obtain all the data from non-food sources as initially expected. Still, the data we did manage to collect represent one of the most comprehensive datasets for STEC available!

WP2-T5- Data collection: AMR (M25-48) - completed

Overall, eight countries (Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal and Spain) contributed with data on ESBL-*E. coli* for a total of 10,241 isolates retrieved between 2009 and 2021. Most of the isolates originates from livestock (n=8892, 87%) with the remaining sources being less represented (human: n=713, 7%; environment: n=474, 5%; wild animals: n=110, 1%; pets: n=36, 0,4%; zoo animals: n=9, 0,1%; and fruit/vegetables: n=7, 0,1%). The majority of the isolates (~93%) had information on their AMR phenotypes (mostly based on MIC testing), and in a large proportion of the dataset the presence of ESBL genes was assessed using molecular methods (mostly PCR-testing). Approximately half of the isolates (51%) carried at least one blaCTX-M gene, 10% a blaTEM gene and 8% a blaSHV gene.

In addition, information about resistance genes will be available from the WGS data of *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and STEC and are currently being generated.

WP3: Methods: Assessment/improvement (M25-54)

In this WP, monthly web meetings were held to discuss progress and preliminary results. These were terminated in May 2022, as activities progressively moved to WP4.

Deliverable (D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.2) on evaluation of SA methods was completed and the report uploaded to Zenodo. In the report, the so-called TRACE framework was applied to evaluate the various models identified through a scoping review.

WP3-T1- Assessing and developing source attribution methods based on microbial subtyping (M25-54) – ongoing

and

WP3-T2- Assessing and developing source attribution methods based on phylogenetic data (M25-54) - ongoing

As it turned out, there is a considerably overlap between the objectives and activities of T1 and T2, and we have consequently merged the two task, which will therefore be reported collectively.

5.1.4.9.2.1 Models based on WGS data

A Danish dataset of *Campylobacter* sequences collected from humans, animals incl. pets, foods and environments from 2015-2017 has been used for model development. Data were processed through different bioinformatics pipelines to obtain 7-loci MLST, cgMLST, wgMLST, SNPs and Kmer data. All these genomic output data have been explored in different source attribution models using machine learning (ML) to identify any host-associated genetic (groups of) markers. The different models were assessed with regard to accuracy and number of human cases that they would be able to predict. A MSc student at DTU contributing to the development of the above-mentioned bioinformatics and machine-learning approaches for *Campylobacter*, handed in her thesis in June 2021. The best method was applied to more recent data from Denmark (2019-2020) and is currently being used to analyse the full *Campylobacter* dataset. A network approach using both cgMLST and SNP based data has also been applied, which has resulted in a publication. Based on the clusters identified by this method, a Bayesian model is currently being applied.

A comparison of source attribution methods is ongoing using a sample of 280 *Campylobacter* isolates from human cases and animal/environmental sources in the Netherlands using STRUCTURE, BEAST and a Random Forest methods on core-genome SNPs, gene presence absence data and cgMLST data. The three methods show slightly different attribution estimates, with the Random Forest method showing a noticeable lower attribution to the environment using both genetic sources, cgMLST representing the core genome and gene presence absence representing the accessory genome. Although there is no golden standard, the output of each method was compared with the majority vote. In this dataset, it seems that STRUCTURE based on cgMLST data slightly outperforms the other methods as it most often agrees with the majority vote. More analyses will be done to confirm this finding.

Similar modelling as described for *Campylobacter* is also being performed for *Salmonella* sequences i.e. applying cgMLST in STRUCTURE and different ML-models. The results for the STRUCTURE analysis is reported in WP4 and the ML-modelling is ongoing.

On a selected dataset of 420 human UK and DK sequences of *S. Typhimurium* and monophasic variants of *S. Typhimurium*, a ML approach using random forest (RF) to perform source attribution was applied. 482 animal sequences from nine primary source categories were used for model training and testing. The cgMLST profiles (3002 core genomes) and accessory genome (1230 genomes incl. plasmids, phages) of all 902 sequences were retrieved and used as model inputs (features) after imputing missing data. The same dataset were also analysed using a Bayesian model with MLST profiles and the so-called AB-SA model using accessory genes present/absence as input.

Deliverable D-JRPFBZ-1-WP3.1 "Describe novel approaches for source attribution using microbial subtyping" summarises the different WGS-based approaches developed.

5.1.4.9.2.2 Models based on phenotypic data

For *Salmonella*, the Dutch frequency-matching model based on serovars only was applied to all the available data. Attributions were performed overall, per country and year for the top-5 serotypes that were common to all four countries, namely Enteritidis, Typhimurium, the monophasic variant of Typhimurium, Infantis and Stanley. A 'moving sum' of the source isolates over the years was used so that the attribution of human cases caused by a specific serotype in a given year was based on the source isolates of that specific year and the year before. The results are briefly described under WP4. An ongoing activity is to apply the Bayesian approach (Hald-model) to the same dataset.

For *Campylobacter*, the plan is to apply the 7-loci MLST data in a multi-country model using the Bayesian approach, although we are struggling to find spare hands to do this task, so the results will most likely not be ready for the Deliverable D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.2.

For STEC, the Bayesian approach is currently being applied using the distribution of O-serogroup and virulence genes as input data for a multi-country model.

Also for ESBL *E. coli*, a multi-country Bayesian model is currently being developed using the distribution of AMR gene coding for beta-lactam as input.

WP3-T3- Evaluation of microbial subtyping source attribution by infectious disease modelling (M25-54) - completed

In this task, a method for evaluating the quality of source attribution based on subtyping was developed. Three evolving bacterial metapopulations were simulated including active migration between the metapopulations over time using the BactMeta software (<https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty093>) with variable migration rates between 2 of the populations (A and B). Samples were drawn from these at variable sampling fractions according to a Dirichlet distribution to generate synthetic human case data where the sampling fractions represent the attribution fractions that a source attribution model estimates. The synthetic data was submitted to the asymmetric island model (<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1000203>) to predict the sampling fractions. The association between the migration rates between A and B and sum of the error between the observed and expected attribution fractions was estimated by linear regression and summarized in parallel Tukey boxplots. The results indicated that the predictions of the asymmetric island model had median error of approximately 2% and largely were not impacted by migration between metapopulations. However, where resultant degree of overlap between the metapopulations due to migration was considered, an increasing error was detected with increasing overlap between the populations. For each 1% increase in overlap, the error in the prediction increased by 4.5% ($P < 0.001$). This indicates that this model performed well in spite of potential unobservable migration of bacteria between animals population, but there may be a limit to its utility, if the pathogens in the animal populations become too uniform. This work is presented as an R package to make it possible for others to test other candidate source attribution models here: <https://github.com/trosendal/sourceSim>.

WP3-T4- Assessing and developing approaches for source attribution of antimicrobial resistance based on metagenomics (M25-54) - ongoing

A paper ([Duarte et al., 2021](#)) describing the metagenomics-based source attribution methodology was recently published by one of the partners (but related to another EU financed project). We were unfortunately not able to obtain relevant metagenomic data from the general human population to test the model adequacy in the source-attribution of AMR for non-occupationally exposed humans. Data from the Dutch population exist, but we were not allowed to use the data in the project.

Between February and May 2022, a Master student explored in detail the outcome of the study by Duarte et al. during an internship at DTU. Genomic antimicrobial resistance signatures for each reservoir, previously identified with a SIMPER analysis, were investigated including 1) the distribution of abundance of 15 signatures by reservoir; 2) Principal Component Analysis using the 15 signatures, to investigate sample clustering according to reservoir and how each genomic signature explained data variance; 3) All-Subsets Regression for each reservoir, to determine the best combination of variables (antimicrobial resistance genomic determinants) for an outcome (a reservoir category) - in this case, all 15 signatures were included in the best variable combinations. The results of these three steps confirmed that the 15 previously identified reservoir-specific resistome signatures largely contributed to distinguish between four animal reservoirs (broilers, pigs, calves and turkeys).

Next, the outcome of the previously performed SIMPER analysis was compared with a non-linear method, a random forest model, which allows attributing single resistomes to one of the four reservoirs. The same data from the study of Duarte et al. were used, including 479 samples of

resistomes of four animal reservoirs, spanning relative abundance of 390 genes. Data were split into 80% training and 20% test, the model tuned with 300 trees, with 5 times 10-fold cross-validation. The model had an accuracy of 0.97 (MCC), and most incorrect attributions were between broilers and turkeys.

The model performance was assessed in three different ways: 1) testing with shuffled outcomes – as expected, the performance of the model markedly decreased and the MCC value was negative, indicating that the original model was learning from the data; 2) testing with the 15 worst variables from the model (variables with the least predictive importance). Since there were 127 genes that the model considered as zero important, 15 random genes among those were selected to test the model. The model performance markedly decreased, indicating that feature importance was not random; 3) testing with 2 testing sets, one with the 15 SIMPER-determined resistome signatures, and another with the 15 most important features according to the random forest model. Although some overlap was observed between the two sets of 15 AMR determinants, that overlap was not total, indicating that different sets of reservoir-specific resistome signatures may be determined depending on the method applied. However, the results showed that model performance (MCC) achieved with resistome signatures, either those determined by SIMPER or by Random Forest, was always higher than that achieved with other sets of randomly selected AMR determinants.

The next step will be to investigate the specific importance of selected resistome signatures by simulating their reservoir-specific relative abundance in a random forest model. The intended outcome of this task is a methodology to determine and validate reservoir-specific resistome signatures to be used in AMR source-attribution.

Also in relation to this task, INIAV and DTU were granted a STM addressing the use of metagenomics for source tracking in aquaculture. The STM was conducted in February 2022, during which INIAV explored the use of the random forest approach to attribute the source of AMR found in aquaculture (sediment) samples to different aquatic environments.

WP3-T5- Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on case-control study results (M25-48) - completed

A systematic literature review of recently published (2011-2021) case-control studies of sporadic *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* infections has been conducted. The merging of the this new systematic review with previous reviews followed by an overall meta-analysis using Bayesian evidence synthesis methods is also done and results summarised under WP4.

A methodological paper “A statistical modelling approach for source attribution meta-analysis of sporadic infections with foodborne pathogens”, outlining the approach used in WP4 to combine attribution estimates from different sources, has been published.

WP3-T6- Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on data from reported outbreak investigations (M25-48) - completed

Milestone in M33 (M-JRPFZ-1-06): Methods for source attribution based on outbreak data evaluated was met. Outbreak data for this task was requested from EFSA, which released the data in M40. Modelling for *Salmonella* is completed and results are summarised in WP4.

WP3-T7- Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on Risk-assessment (M25-45) - completed

A review of existing comparative exposure assessment (CEA) models was completed in M38 (M-JRPFZ-1-18).

For the CEA approach, data for all DiSCoVeR partner countries are incomplete or non-existent. A comparative exposure assessment, to be “comparative” needs to include different sources or to be performed in different regions/countries, which would also be in line with the spirit of OHEJP projects. It was therefore decided that a reasonable approach would be to perform an exposure assessment for

a specific source for which we expected to find only few typing data, i.e. pets like dogs and cats. The pet-CEA were performed for all three target pathogens and AMR in different countries that have the necessary data. The resulting exposure estimates were compared between the countries, and it was investigated whether possible differences are also reflected in the attribution estimates obtained by the other methods. The models are including available data on national pathogen prevalences in dogs and cats received from partners. Results are summarised in WP4.

WP4. Results – Quantifying the contribution of various sources of foodborne zoonoses and AMR (M30-56)

In WP4, data collected in WP2 and the methods assessed/developed in WP3 are used to quantify the contributions of the main sources of the three target pathogens and AMR. Results are presented per pathogen, attribution method, type of data and, when/if applicable, geographical region/country. The results of applied methods for each pathogen are compared in the light of data availability and robustness, underlying uncertainties, the point in the food production chain where source attribution takes place, and the usefulness of different methods to answer different One Health questions.

A plan for which models to apply for each pathogens was agreed upon at a meeting on February 15, 2021. At the same meeting, persons/groups responsible for data management and modelling, respectively, for each pathogen-model combination were identified.

As an activity of interest for all tasks within WP4 and in collaboration with WP2 and WP3, we worked together to define a minimum set of (meta)data to be collected to perform source attribution in a meaningful way. A document was prepared and shared with all partners. This document was integrated in the milestone M-JRP FBZ-1-07 (Format for results presentation (standard structure) for all pathogens and AMR).

WP4-T1- Salmonella source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches (M30-54) - ongoing

The specific activities of this task are structured as follows:

1) Attributions based on **microbial subtyping**, which include frequency-based models based on phenotypic subtyping data and machine-learning approaches based on WGS data.

The frequency-based models are based on serotyping data and target four countries (the Netherlands, Portugal, Czech Republic and Denmark, as examples of respectively Western, Southern, Eastern and Northern Europe). Only for these countries were serotyping data from both human and source isolates covering the whole 10-year study period (from 2010 to 2019) available for the project. Overall, 14,009 non-outbreaks and non-travel-related human salmonellosis cases (i.e. the sporadic and domestic cases) from the four countries together over the whole 10-year time period were mainly attributed to pigs (26.5%, 95%CI 19.4-33.6%), followed by layers (22.2%, 95%CI 15.6-28.7%), broilers (14.6%, 95%CI 6.8-22.3%), cattle (12.9%, 95%CI 8.9-16.9%), vegetables (11.4%, 95%CI 2.4-20.3%), seafood (6.8%, 95%CI 4.1-9.4%), turkeys (2.5%, 95%CI 1.3-3.6%), the environment (1.8%, 95%CI 1.0-2.6%), sheep and goats (0.8%, 95%CI 0.5-1.2%), while the other sources accounted together for only 0.6% of cases. Due to the much larger number of cases from the Netherlands and Denmark, the aforementioned ranking of sources was mainly determined by the attributions of these two countries. Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

The population-genetic model, STRUCTURE, was applied to cgMLST data. Data for six serovars were included in the analyses: 1) Enteritidis, 2) Typhimurium, 3) Typhimurium monophasic variant, 4) Infantis, 5) Derby and 6) Newport. A separate model for each serovar was built. Analyses were first performed overall and then stratified by the country, where the human cases occurred. This latter analysis included England and Wales, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Denmark, although not all these countries had sequence data available for all six serovars. The source with the highest attributable percentage for each serovar was found as follows: *S. Enteritidis*: Laying hens/eggs (>50% of cases), *S.*

Typhimurium: Pigs/pork (>60%), *S. Infantis*: Broilers (>60%), *S. Derby*: Pigs/pork and cattle/beef (around 60%), and *S. Newport*: Ruminants (>60%). Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

Different approaches were applied on a selected dataset of UK and DK sequences of *S. Typhimurium* and monophasic variants of *S. Typhimurium*: 1) a ML approach using random forest (RF) and cgMLST as input data, 2) ML regression approach using accessory genes as input, and 3) a Bayesian model using MLST as input. Although the input data were quite different, the results pointed in the same direction suggesting that the major source of human *S. Typhimurium* infections in UK and DK is pig meat (≈66% of cases). A publication is being prepared.

2) Analysis of **Salmonella outbreak data** based on national data reported to EFSA's outbreak database from 2015-2019. In total, data from 1,508 *Salmonella* outbreaks reported across 34 countries were provided. Of these 1,040 (69%) were caused by simple foods and 468 (31%) by 'unknown' sources. The most important source of human salmonellosis in EU was eggs, followed by pork. Regional, temporal and serotype-associated differences in the relative contributions of the different sources were observed with eggs being the dominant source in Eastern and Southern EU, pork gained more importance in Northern and Western EU. Salmonellosis outbreaks appeared also to have increased during the study period, particularly for *S. Enteritidis* outbreak in Eastern Europe. Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

3) **Meta-analysis of case control data** to update previous systematic reviews. A systematic review of articles published between 2011 and 2021 was performed using a standardized process to review literature and select relevant articles using the key-terms: Salmonella (salmonellosis), Case-control, Sporadic and Risk Factors. From 1464 identified references, four articles were deemed fit for data-extraction and were included in this review. Information on the frequency of mentioning and estimated odds ratios was collected. The extracted data were merged with data from a previous review and meta-analysis was conducted. The main transmission pathway of sporadic salmonellosis was estimated to be food preparation, accounting for 14.5% (95%CI 13.3%–15.5%) of cases, closely followed by food consumption (13.2%, 95%CI 12.0%–14.5%) and water consumption (14.6% 95%CI 13.2-16.1%). The overall 'food- and waterborne transmission route' accounted for about 53% of cases. Of the other (non-food or waterborne) transmission routes, contact with animals accounted for 14.7% (95%CI 13.6-16.3%), followed by the environment (5.7%, 95%CI 4.8-6.6%). Foreign travel (7.7%, 95%CI 6.6-8.7%) and predisposition (11.7%, 95%CI 10.4-13.2%) were also important, while occupational exposure accounted for 7.6% (95%CI 5.3-10.5%) of cases. Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

4) **Exposure assessment** (pets only, but all target pathogens). The goal of this analysis was to estimate the relative exposure of humans to pathogenic and antimicrobial resistant bacteria due to (in)direct contact with cats or dogs, as compared between countries, using two approaches. The General Exposure Indicator, which is the ratio of the number of dogs or cats and the number of humans in a country, gives a relative, bacterium a-specific, quantitative exposure estimate which proves to show clear variation and differences between countries. The Bacterium Exposure Indicator is the ratio of the number of bacterium-specific infected dogs or cats and the number of humans in a country, and this gives a relative, bacterium-specific, quantitative exposure estimate. The uncertainty introduced by the dog/cat prevalence data, and its availability, implies that only a limited number of differences between countries could be found for the Bacterium Exposure Indicator. Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1.

WP4-T2- Campylobacter source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches (M30-54) - ongoing

Like in the previous task, specific activities have been defined:

1) Attribution based on **microbial subtyping**, which include the machine-learning approaches and population genetic models (STRUCTURE) based on WGS data.

The models assessed or developed in WP3 (machine-learning approaches, network analysis, and STRUCTURE based on WGS data, and Bayesian approach based on 7-loci MLST) are currently being applied to all available data. Results are expected to be ready within a month and will be described in D-JRPFBZ-1-WP4.1.

2) **Meta-analysis of case-control data** to update systematic reviews (please see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1). A systematic review of articles published between 2011 and 2021 was performed using a standardized process to review literature and select relevant articles using the key-terms: *Campylobacter* (campylobacteriosis), Case-control, Sporadic and Risk Factors. From 620 identified references, five articles were deemed fit for data-extraction and were included in this review. Information on the frequency of mentioning and estimated odds ratios was collected. The extracted data were merged with data from a previous review and a meta-analysis was conducted. The main transmission pathway was estimated to be food consumption, accounting for 22.9% (95%CI 22.2%–23.6%) of cases, followed by food preparation (16.0%, 95%CI 15.5%–16.6%) and water consumption (9.7% 95%CI 8.9-10.5%). The overall ‘food- and waterborne transmission route’ accounted for about 53% of cases. Of the other (non-food or waterborne) transmission routes, the environment accounted for 15.1% (95%CI 14.4-15.9%), followed by contact with animals (8.9%, 95%CI 8.5-9.4%). Foreign travel (11.9%, 95%CI 10.9-12.9%) and predisposition (7.8%, 95%CI 7.3-8.4%) were also important, while occupational exposure and person-to-person transmission accounted for a minor proportion of cases (3.6%). Results are described in more detail in D-JRPFBZ-1-WP4.1.

3) **Exposure assessment** (pets only). (Please, see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1)

Analysis of **outbreak data** is not included because the scarcity of documented *Campylobacter* outbreaks would make such an analysis not very useful.

WP4-T3- VTEC source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches (M30-56) - ongoing

Specific activities include:

1) Attribution based on **microbial subtyping**, which include frequency-based models based on phenotypic data (ongoing) (O-serogroups, virulence genes, etc.), machine-learning approaches based on WGS data (if data allows – about to start), and population genetic models (about to start).

2) **Exposure assessment** (pets only). (Please, see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1)

Meta-analysis of case-control studies and **analysis of outbreak data** is not included, because there are already recent work available through a piece of WHO work led by one of the partners.

WP4-T4- AMR source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated (M30-56) – ongoing

Specific activities include:

1) Attributions based on **microbial subtyping**, more specifically frequency-based models of ESBL based on the distribution of AMR determinants. The database including ESBL data for source attribution using the frequency-based models is completed and analyses are ongoing.

2) Attribution based on a ML approach comparing the resistomes in human and various sources based on available metagenomic data. As mentioned under WP3, we were not able to get hold of the required metagenomics data from the general population. This analysis will, therefore, not be completed.

3) A multidirectional dynamic risk model for ESBL-*E. coli* (EC) transmission between broiler flocks, broiler farmers, and the open community has been developed and was parameterized for the Netherlands. This model was used to describe the transmission of ESBL-EC within and between populations including modelling of the flock-to-human transmission via food consumption due to contamination at the slaughterhouse and/or during food preparation. The colonization of the open community could primarily be attributed to the open community itself (62%), followed by vegetable

consumption (29.5%), and contact with farmers (8.5%). What-if analysis to explore the effect of interventions directed at different points in the food production chain on the ESBL-EC prevalence in the open community indicated that interventions aimed at reducing the spread of ESBL-EC at primary production level, i.e. within broiler flocks, were most effective. These results are reported in a manuscript that is under review (Eduardo de Freitas Costa et al. Multidirectional dynamic model for the spread of extended-spectrum- β -lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli* in the Netherlands).

WP5: Conclusions and policy translation (M32-60)

WP5-T1- Technical expert evaluation (M41-57) - ongoing

It is considered as part of this task to turn the deliverable (D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.2) into a document/report for decision makers/risk managers for an overview of the advantages, limitation, and data requirements for the various attribution models.

WP5-T2- Translating source attribution estimates into options for control policies (M33-58) - ongoing

An online stakeholder workshop was held on January 22, 2021. Around 20 participants from EFSA, ECDC, EURLs, other relevant EJP projects, as well as DiSCoVeR WP-leads joined the meeting.

A Master student enrolled at DTU has in collaboration with ISS addressed the deliverable D-JRPFZ-1-WP5.1: Map of the current existing control programme and intervention strategies to mitigate the risk of transmission of *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC, and antimicrobial resistance to human at the EU and national level. This task was addressed by i) a scientific literature review (completed), ii) a review of grey literature (completed), and iii) a survey aimed at relevant national experts (completed, being reviewed). The survey was distributed through the OHEJP network and EFSA's zoonosis network. DG SANTE and EFSA have been informed about the survey and provided their endorsement as well as their help to distribute the survey. The MSc student handed in her thesis in June 2021 and an abstract was selected for oral presentation at the OHEJP ASM on June 9-11, 2021, in Copenhagen.

A summary of the literature review and the overall results of the survey was submitted as deliverable D-JRPFZ-1-WP5.1 in M48.

WP5-T3- Final recommendations in a OH frame (M49-60) – ongoing

Discussions to complete this task has been initiated. A roadmap/diagram linking the DiSCoVeR project outcomes (the science) with risk assessment and risk management at the EU level has been drafted and is likely to form the basis for the further work in this task. In November, we will hold final stakeholder workshop, where we will get input from relevant risk managers on the main project outcomes, and how they can be used for policy making.

5.1.4.9.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.1	Describe novel approaches for source attribution using microbial subtyping	M49	M51		https://zenodo.org/record/6365186#.Yq4ONHZByUk doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6365186	2
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.2	Report on the critical and quantitative evaluation of existing and novel source attribution methods	M51	M51		https://zenodo.org/record/6365057#.Yq4ONHZByUk doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6365057	2
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.1	Salmonella source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method	M54	M55		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7058181	2
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.2	Campylobacter source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated	M54	M56		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7058216	2
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP4.3	VTEC source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for	M56		M59		2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		each applied method and integrated					
20	D-JRPFbz-1-WP4.4	AMR source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated	M56		M58		2
20	D-JRPFbz-1-WP5.2	Document: Transmission pathways of Salmonella, Campylobacter, VTEC, and antimicrobial resistance from animals, food, and environment to humans: One-Health characterisation of the source and components and options to inform control policies.	M57		M60		2

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
20	M-JRP20-13	Framework for using phylogenetic data for source attribution	M51	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-16	Results from evaluation of microbial subtyping methods using artificial data	M54	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-22	Completion of data collection	M42	Yes		
20	M-JRPFZ-1-23	Completion of dataset for all species	M50	Yes		
20	M-JRPFZ-1-24	Third annual project meeting hosted by ISS	M57			Planned for November 16-18
20	M-JRPFZ-1-25	Stakeholder Workshop	M57			Planned for November 16-18

5.1.4.9.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>V. Lopez-Chavarrias, M. Ugarte-Ruiz, M. C. B. Asensio, A. Olarra, M. Garcia, J.L. Saez, C. De Frutos, T. Serrano, I. Perez, M.A. Moreno, L. Domínguez, J. Alvarez</p> <p>Monitoring of Antimicrobial Resistance to Aminoglycosides and Macrolides in <i>Campylobacter coli</i> and <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> from healthy livestock in Spain (2002-2018)</p> <p>doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.689262 https://zenodo.org/record/5109549#.YUyIfLgzZM0</p>	Yes		Yes
<p>Lapo Mughini-Gras, Elisa Benincà, Scott A. McDonald, Aarieke de Jong, Jurgen Chardon, Eric Evers, Axel A. Bonačić Marinović (2022). A statistical modelling approach for source attribution meta-analysis of sporadic infection with foodborne pathogens.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12937 https://zenodo.org/record/6365098#.Ynkcy-hBxwQ</p>	Yes		Yes
<p>Pinedo, L. C., Mughini-Gras, L., Franz, E., Hald, T., & Pires, S. M. (2022). Sources and trends of human salmonellosis in Europe, 2015–2019: An analysis of outbreak data. <i>International Journal of Food</i></p>	Yes		Yes

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Microbiology, 379, 109850. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2022.109850			

Additional output

Abstracts from the ASM One Health EJP 2021 and 2022

- Sara Perestrelo, Guido Correia Carreira, Lars Valentin, Jennie Fischer, Yvonne Pfeifer, Guido Werner, Judith Schmiedel, Linda Falgenhauer, Annemarie Käsbohrer. "Source Attribution of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* in Germany" Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP 2021, 9-11 June, Denmark and online.
- Guido Correia Carreira, Annemarie Käsbohrer. "Mapping knowledge gaps of source attribution methods and sources for zoonoses and resistant bacteria using a rapid review approach". Oral presentation held at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Rebekka Sørensen, Tine Hald, Gaia Scavia, Michele Luca D'errico. "MAPPING THE CURRENT EXISTING HAZARDS' CONTROL PROGRAM AND STRATEGIES IN THE VARIOUS SECTORS AND TRACTS OF THE ANIMAL-ENVIRONMENTFOOD-HUMAN CHAIN IN EU". Oral presentation held at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Mónica Oleastro, Maria Leonor Lemos, Alexandra Nunes, Paulo Martins da Costa. "A PRELIMINARY STUDY OF *CAMPYLOBACTER* SPP. IN DOGS IN PORTUGAL – A ONE HEALTH PERSPECTIVE". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Ana Amaro, Célia Leão, Patrícia Themudo, Lurdes Clemente. "EMERGENCE OF MULTIDRUG RESISTANT *SALMONELLA* *INFANTIS* ST32 IN THE POULTRY INDUSTRY, PORTUGAL 2016-2020". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Leonor Silveira, Sofia Ribeiro, Iúri Lopes, Mariana Fontes, Rita Castro, Frederico Lemos, Angela Pista. "Prevalence and characterization of *Salmonella* spp. and pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in food-producing animals in Portugal". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Angela Pista, Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Rita Batista, Anabela Coelho, Rosália Furtado, Teresa Lopes, Isabel Moura, Margarida Saraiva, Carla Maia, Cristina Belo-Correia, Iuri Lopes, Leonor Silveira. "Prevalence and characterization of pathogenic *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. in wild animals in mainland Portugal". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Angela Pista, Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Iuri Lopes, Leonor Silveira. Phenotypic and Genotypic Characterization of *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. in Pets, Portugal 2019-2020 – A ONE HEALTH Perspective. Poster resented at ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, 11-13 April, Orvieto, Italy and online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645672>.
- Michele Luca D'Errico, Rebekka Aarlund Sørenses, Tine Hald, Gaia Scavia. Mapping control programmes to mitigate the risk of human exposure to *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *STEC* and antimicrobial resistance through animals, food and the environment: an experts' survey. Oral Communication at ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, 11-13 April, Orvieto, Italy and online.
- Ornella Moro, Sara Pires, Camilla Sekse, Rosangela Tozzoli, Gaia Scavia, Lapo Mughini-Gras. Exploring Shiga Toxin-producing *E. coli* sources in European countries through classical attribution methods. Poster resented at ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022, 11-13 April, Orvieto, Italy and online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645672>.

- GS. Johannessen, JK. Antony-Samy, CA. Bøe, EZ. Fiskebeck, K. Lagesen, K. Madslie, J. Våge, M. Økland, C. Sekse. Occurrence of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* in wild ruminants in Norway. Presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online. (Not yet uploaded to Zenodo).

Other abstracts

- Sara Perestrelo, Guido Correia Carreira, Lars Valentin, Jennie Fischer, Yvonne Pfeifer, Guido Werner, Judith Schmiedel, Linda Falgenhauer, Annemarie Käsbohrer. "To which extend do humans and animals share the same reservoirs of ESBL producing *Escherichia coli*?" Poster presentation at the Junior Scientific Zoonosis Meeting 2021, 3-4 June, online.
- Célia Leão, Ana Amaro, Patrícia Themudo, Lurdes Clemente. Insights into pESI like megaplasmid of *Salmonella* *Infantis* ST32 spreading in the poultry industry. Poster presentation at the MICROBIOTEC 2021, 23-26 November.
- Angela Pista, Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Iúri Lopes, Rita Castro, Leonor Silveira. Detection and characterization of Enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. in cats and dogs from a Lisbon area kennel - A ONE HEALTH perspective. Poster presentation at the XVII Congresso Internacional Veterinário 2021, 22-23 October, Santa Maria da Feira, Portugal.
- Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Iuri Lopes, Leonor Silveira, Angela Pista. Colistin Resistance Genes in *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. Isolates from Pets, Wild and Food-producing Animals in Portugal, 2019-2021. Poster presentation at the 32nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases 2022, 23-26 April, Lisbon, Portugal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645500>.
- Lopez-Chavarrias, Vicente, Wieczorek, Kinga, Osek, Jacek, Dieguez Roda, Bernabe, Torre Fuentes, Laura, Ugarte-Ruiz, Maria, Moreno, Miguel Angel, Dominguez, Lucas, & Alvarez, Julio. (2022). Epidemiological comparison of *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates from Poland and Spain combining MLST and antimicrobial resistance whole genome analyses. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6637353>
- Lopez-Chavarrias, Vicente, Dieguez Roda, Bernabe, Torre Fuentes, Laura, Ugarte-Ruiz, Maria, Saez, Jose Luis, Moreno, Miguel Angel, Dominguez, Lucas, & Alvarez, Julio. (2022, August 7). Mapping antimicrobial resistance markers for aminoglycosides and macrolides in *Campylobacter* in Spanish livestock. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6637724>
- Skarżyńska M, Zajac M, Lalak A, Kwit R, Pasim P, Skrzypiec E, Wojdat D, Koza W, Mikos-Wojewoda E, Skóra M, Wasyl D. Characterisation of *Salmonella* Typhimurium from domestic pigeons (*Columba livia domestica*). International Symposium *Salmonella* and *Salmonellosis* (IS), June 20-22, Saint-Malo.
- M. Zajac, M. Skarżyńska, A. Śmiałowska-Węglińska, R. Kwit, K. Tłuścik, A. Bomba, E. Skrzypiec, D. Wojdat, W. Koza, A. Lalak, A. Giza, E. Iwan, D. Wasyl. The phylogeny structure and molecular characterization of monophasic *Salmonella* Typhimurium from unhuman sources in Poland. International Symposium *Salmonella* and *Salmonellosis* (IS), June 20-22, Saint-Malo.
- Bonifait L., Baugé L., Thépault A., Payne A., Kérouanton A., Denis M., Rivoal K., Pozet F., Cesbron N., Nicollet P., Gibout O., Chenoufi N., Lequeux T., Zonderland J.-L., Chemaly M. 2022. Detection and characterization of *Salmonella* spp. in wildlife in France. Poster presentation at the International Symposium *Salmonella* and *Salmonellosis* (IS), June 20-22, Saint-Malo.

Scientific reports

- Eric Evers (RIVM, The Netherlands), Annemarie Käsbohrer (BfR, Germany). "Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on risk assessment", OHEJP DiSCoVeR WP3-T7, milestone M-JRPFZ-1-18, 10 February 2021.

- Mayu Horie. “Application of Machine Learning in source attribution of foodborne bacteria”, special MSc student project report, Utrecht University and RIVM, The Netherlands.

Master theses

- Bækken, M.S. Occurrence of Shiga-toxin producing Escherichia coli in minced meat and meat from pork in Norway (In Norwegian). MSc Thesis, May 2021, Norwegian Veterinary Institute in collaboration with the Norwegian University of Life Sciences (<https://nmbu.braze.unit.no/nmbu-xmlui/handle/11250/2826335?locale-attribute=en>).
- Brinch, M. L. [Development of a WGS-based source attribution model for Campylobacter](#). MSc Thesis, June 2021, National Food Institute, Research group for Genomic Epidemiology, Technical University of Denmark.
- Sørensen, R. A. Mapping the currently existing hazards’ control programmes and strategies in the various sectors and tracts of the animal-environment-food-human chain in EU/EFTA/EEA. MSc Thesis, June 2021, National Food Institute, Research group for Genomic Epidemiology, Technical University of Denmark.
- Wang, B. Development of a WGS-based source attribution model for Salmonella. MSc Thesis, September 2021, National Food Institute, Research group for Genomic Epidemiology, Technical University of Denmark.

Related publications

- Wainaina, L.; Merlotti, A.; Remondini, D.; Henri, C.; Hald, T.; Njage, P.M.K. Source Attribution of Human Campylobacteriosis Using Whole-Genome Sequencing Data and Network Analysis. Pathogens 2022, 11, 645. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11060645>

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

We expect by the end of the project to have identified and filled important knowledge, methodological and data gaps for source attribution of zoonotic pathogens and AMR determinants through systematic collection and analysis of existing and new data and by applying existing, modified and novel approaches.

Besides scientific publications describing the developed methods, we will also produce publications that in detail document the project’s datasets that we have collected. This will, hopefully, be useful for other researchers that will find it interesting to explore our data and models. In particular, we believe that the multi-country dataset compiled on STEC isolates and sequences from humans and different animal and food sources is unique and could provide novel insights to the epidemiology of STEC in EU MS. In addition, we plan to make models available, primarily as R-scripts. Each script will link to the exact dataset used in the model.

Finally, in an overall report, we will make recommendations on how source attribution estimates can be translated to policy action to support the surveillance, control and prevention of foodborne infections in EU. The report will be aimed at stakeholders such as ECDC and EFSA, and farmer and consumer organisations.

5.1.4.9.5 [Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations \(e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO\), networks, or national ministries](#)

We plan to have follow up stakeholder workshop in November, when we are also meeting for the final project meeting. EFSA, ECDC and the relevant EURLs will be invited to presented for and discuss the DiSCoVeR results and how they may contribute to their work.

5.1.4.10 JRP21-R2-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE

5.1.4.10.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The OHEJP BIOPIGEE project aims to identify effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to control hepatitis E virus (HEV) and *Salmonella* occurrence in European pig farming. These two pathogens represent important zoonotic organisms that are difficult to detect and control on a pig farm. To achieve this, nineteen partner institutes from 12 countries are carrying out together comprehensive literature reviews, field and experimental studies, expert surveys and risk modelling (organised in Workpackages, WP). The collated information will be disseminated to stakeholders (farmers, veterinarians, advisors) in illustrations, a support tool and workshops. BIOPIGEE has been successfully running since January 1st 2020 and the progress in 2022 so far has been as follows:

WP1: Three quarterly meetings of the WP leaders were held. An exchange of findings with the HealthyLivestock project is ongoing. The data management plan has been updated following advice from the DMP group. The publication plan for the project has been modified and is continuously managed. Deliverables are continuously collected, checked and distributed. Some tasks are still affected by the pandemic and consequences for links between Tasks/WPs have been coordinated. The BIOPIGEE final meeting is planned for taking place in person on 6-7th October 2022 in Italy.

WP2: The analyses of the biosecurity questionnaire and HEV/*Salmonella* laboratory results have been carried out. The results on *Salmonella* were shared with WP4 and WP5 for further use. Results for the risk factor analysis on HEV are in a group internal review process. Publications are being drafted from the analyses. The results from the slaughterhouse literature review, sampling visits and questionnaire survey are also being organised for a publication. Longitudinal field studies and repeated observations on specific biosecurity measures and *Salmonella* and HEV occurrence have been carried out in three countries and are partly still ongoing. Data are getting analysed and results prepared for publication. HEV samples from partner countries have been sequenced and have been uploaded to HEVnet for analysis.

WP3: The comparison of methods for testing the effect of disinfectants has been finalized for using reference strains, additional data are being produced using wildtype strains. A panel on wildtype strains has been selected. Disinfectant efficacy testing is completed. The study of HEV stability in relation to disinfection approaches has been executed.

WP4: The baseline QMRA for HEV and *Salmonella* has been completed and is currently being adapted for running with multiple biosecurity intervention measures. The network model has been merged for a full farm-to-consumption analysis. However, resource, data and logistic issues inhibited a fully functional connection of the models developed by different countries. Collaboration with T4.4 is ongoing to ensure the outputs from T4.2 models will be appropriate to act as inputs to the T4.4 economic model. Data for the economic analysis has been collected and biosecurity measures to include are selected in communication with tasks in WP2 and WP5. Costs for the selected biosecurity measures are identified within T4.4. T4.4 uses the output from T4.2 to calculate savings in human cases by using monetary values from cost-of-illness analyses carried out in T4.4. The calculations for the cost-benefit-analysis are still ongoing.

WP5: The BIOPIGEE catalogue has been filled with results from WP2 and WP5 on effective and prioritised biosecurity measures to control HEV and *Salmonella*. A literature review and meta-analysis to identify effective measures against HEV, *Salmonella* and pathogenic *E. coli* in primary production was finalised and results are getting prepared for publication. Another manuscript on biosecurity measures prioritised by experts has been prepared and submitted to a journal. A benchmark system which enables a farmer to compare own with best biosecurity practice and with a cohort of pig farms for controlling *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus occurrence in the individual pig production stages has been and is still being developed based on T2.2, T5.2 and T5.4 outcome and in consultation with T4.4.

WP6: For the dissemination of project outcomes, farm information material is being developed and websites are being listed. A slaughterhouse guidance document is being prepared and intended to publish. Two support tools, one for primary production (based on T5.5 benchmark check list) and another on modelling the whole production chain (based on WP4) are getting prepared. Finally, two virtual workshops are being organised for September to present and discuss findings on effective biosecurity measures in primary production and at slaughter.

5.1.4.10.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1 Project coordination and integration of results (M25-60)

WP1-T1 Project management and meeting organisation (M25-60)

The BIOPIGEE final meeting is being planned jointly by BfR and IZSAM and is scheduled to take place in person on 6-7th October 2022 in Giulianova, Italy. In total 33 project members intend to attend and three project external guests from EFSA are invited (status end of August 2022). Three quarterly meetings of the WP leaders have been arranged and held to discuss current issues and links. Participant inquiries, especially on project extension and budget issues were collected, forwarded to the board and answered. A collaboration with the HealthyLivestock project is ongoing and project outcomes have been exchanged and discussed, e.g. in workshop events. Project documents have been continuously managed in a file sharing system which allows Office documents to be edited together online in a web browser (uploaded to a server administered by BfR). Some tasks are still being affected by the pandemic (farm visits, lab work, workshops) and changes in the schedule and organisation of tasks and consequences for links between Tasks/WPs have been coordinated. The Gantt Chart and the list of due dates for deliverables and milestones have been modified accordingly.

WP1-T2 Development of data management plan (M25-60)

The data management plan was revised according to comments by the OHEJP WP4 DMP group at the beginning of 2022 and is continuously updated both in a shared document in the project group and in the Lisam CDP tool. Currently, a total of 29 data sets or methodologies from all tasks are described (status 5th September 2022).

WP1-T3 Provision of project deliverables and reports (M25-60)

The publication plan for the project, compiled in a shared document, has been modified to inform and exchange information about the status of publications (intended, in work, submitted, accepted, published) for WP2-5 and is continuously managed. Deliverables are continuously collected, checked and distributed (uploaded to the private web-group, to Zenodo and forwarded to OHEJP WP3/CommsTeam). A first draft of the 9M report has been submitted to OHEJP WP3 in June 2022 and updated until September 2022.

WP2: Biosecurity effectiveness studies (M25-56)

WP2-T2- Application of the biosecurity protocol (M27-M48)

Analysis of the biosecurity questionnaire and HEV/*Salmonella* laboratory results has continued. Descriptive analysis of the data has been carried out, with particular focus on presenting differences in biosecurity measures between farm types and participating countries/ regions. Multivariable risk factor analysis and principal component analysis have been completed to identify the most effective biosecurity measures in controlling *Salmonella* on European pig farms. These results have been shared with WP4 and WP5, so that cost-benefit analysis can be applied to the identified measures and the benchmark system can include the measures. To assess the potential effect of bias on the task 2 results, a number of sensitivity analyses were completed, which confirmed the suitability of the multivariable risk factor model. Similar analyses have been completed for HEV with results for the risk factor analysis being reported internally for review. Publications are being drafted from these analyses.

WP2-T3 Slaughterhouse biosecurity practices (M37-M48)

The results from the slaughterhouse literature review, sampling visits and questionnaire survey that were collected from this study are being organised for a publication.

WP2-T4 Field studies (M25-M54)

In the UK, two longitudinal studies have been completed to investigate the epidemiology of HEV, in particular with regards to the mixing of pigs and potential environmental reservoirs. The first trial was a two-stage breeder-finisher unit, and the second trial was a weaner-finisher unit, and both were visited four times to collect samples from a cohort of pigs, from entry onto the farm through to slaughter. Of the 376 faecal samples collected over four visits, 27.4% (103/376) samples were positive for HEV ribonucleic acid (RNA). None of the 26 faecal samples collected from farrowing sows were positive for HEV, and only 2.6% of suckler pig faecal samples were positive (2/78). There was a peak in the presence of HEV in pigs of weaner age (54.0%, 54/100), declining towards slaughter age. Pigs on this farm were mixed at weaning and remained in consistent groups throughout the rest of their fattening period. Of the 24 blood samples collected from finisher pigs, 79.2% (19/24) were positive for HEV antibodies, and 84.2% (16/19) of those collected from sows were HEV positive. HEV RNA was also detected in 54% of environmental samples collected across the four visits (44/81), ranging from 10% at visit 1 to 90% of samples positive from visit 3.

In the Netherlands, two longitudinal field studies are currently underway investigating the transmission rate of HEV between consecutive batches of finisher pigs in the same pens, and between pens within compartments. A secondary aim is to investigate whether PRRS pre- or co-infection influences the latent period, or the duration of infectious period of HEV in a pen of finisher pigs. Every pen is faecal sampled once a week, and serum samples are collected at the beginning and end of every batch to identify contingent HEV infection prior to the fattening stage, and seroconversion during the fattening phase. Between batches, pens are sampled post cleaning and disinfection. On May 15th, one farm has been followed up for 12 weeks and the other farm for 17 weeks. In the first farm, all pens are HEV negative, although boot socks of the first batch were positive in the last week prior to slaughter, demonstrating that HEV is still present on the farm and transmission is possible. On the other farm, all pens have become positive, and the moment of infection in a pen was dependent on the compartment the pen is in, and presence of a positive adjacent pen. No statistical analyses have been performed yet and the oral fluid samples will be tested for PRRS shortly. Data collection is ongoing.

In Italy, ten farms were recruited for a study which aims to determine the effectiveness of cleaning and disinfection procedures on farms against *Salmonella* and HEV. Enterobacteriaceae were also enumerated to have an indication of residual faecal contamination. The study did not investigate individual cleaning regimens or disinfectant products. Sampling occurred on four farms from April 2022. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the recent African Swine Fever outbreak in Italy it was not possible to recruit finisher farms as initially proposed, and therefore farrow-to-wean and weaning farms were recruited instead. Each farm was visited before and after cleaning and disinfection. All samples collected from the four farms were negative for *Salmonella* and HEV; Enterobacteriaceae colony count ranged from negative to 105 cfu/cm² (mL).

WP2-T5 Analysis of hepatitis E prevalence and subtypes (M37-M56)

A protocol was designed for selecting and sequencing HEV isolates and uploading them onto the HEVnet portal, along with relevant metadata from Task 2.2. Data sharing agreements were designed and reviewed, to allow the data to be uploaded to HEVnet. The process of selecting representative isolates from HEV positive farms for sequencing was completed and the sequences upload to allow ongoing sequence analysis and comparison to the biosecurity data.

WP3: Impact of disinfection on persistence of pathogens in biofilm (M25-56)

WP3-T1 Comparison of methods for testing the effect of disinfectants (M25-46)

This task has been finalized for using reference strains. Additional data are being produced using wildtype strains.

WP3-T2 Effect of disinfectants on biofilm-associated wild type Salmonella (M25-56)

The panel on wildtype strains has been selected and shared with all partners. Disinfectant efficacy testing is still ongoing.

WP3-T2-ST2 Assessing the effect of disinfectants (M37-56)

The panel on wildtype strains has been selected and shared with all partners. Disinfectant efficacy testing is finalized. The efficacy of two disinfectants (Glutaraldehyde and Peracetic acid) at various concentrations were studied. The assessments were performed using three different biofilm models on wild-type strains selected in the previous sub-task.

Deliverable 3.19 is submitted.

Poster will be presented at Eurobiofilms 2022 (31.8.22-3.9.22, Mallorca, Spain) and a manuscript has been planned.

WP3-T3 Study of HEV stability in relation to disinfection approaches (M25-56)

A pilot study on HEV stability in relation to disinfectants has been executed

WP3-T3-ST3

On two different pig farms, environmental samples (291) were collected after the cleaning procedure. Samples were analysed for the presence of HEV and *Salmonella* in order to study if HEV may be more stable in *Salmonella* biofilms. Using electrostatic dust collectors, floors, walls, feed bowls and drink nipples were sampled. The wipes were processed in PBS and DNA and RNA were isolated using the pathogens kit of Zymo research. Isolates were tested for HEV and *Salmonella* by real-time PCR. In 171 out of the 291 samples, *Salmonella* DNA was detected (Ct between 29 and 38). In 15 out of the 291 samples, HEV RNA was detected of which 10 positives were in *Salmonella* positive samples and 5 positives in *Salmonella* negative samples. It was concluded that there was no significant correlation between the presence of *Salmonella* and HEV. An in-vitro study on *Salmonella* biofilms combined with an experimental HEV infection will not be conducted as this will have no added value.

WP4: Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures (M25-56)

WP4-T2 Stochastic simulations on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures (M33-56)

The baseline QMRA for HEV and *Salmonella* has been completed, subject to a final validation step. Work is now progressing on running the models for multiple biosecurity intervention measures. Some measures are being parametrised using prior data from published literature and some using the results of the longitudinal studies conducted in WP2. Unfortunately, due to data and resource issues it has not been possible to run the models for multiple countries, but this would be feasible in the future if sufficient data become available. We are also working in collaboration with our colleagues developing the economic model in WP4-T4, to ensure the outputs will be appropriate to act as inputs to their model. For each measure, the output metric of probability of human illness will be calculated. This will then be compared against the baseline run to determine the effectiveness of the measure, as well as between biosecurity measures to see which the model predicts to be most effective. These outputs will then act as inputs to the economic model.

WP4-T3 Merge of models into one QMRA (M34-56)

The outputs of the French network model developed by ANSES have been provided as inputs to the QMRA. This allows for a full farm-to-consumption analysis to be done for these input data. Unfortunately, due to resource, data and logistic issues it was not possible to fully connect the models developed by different countries into one fully functional model. In particular, it proved problematic to obtain pig movement data and impossible to obtain permission to share that raw data with multiple

countries. As such, future use of the full model would rely on the individual institutes running their own sections.

WP4-T4 Economic model of biosecurity measures across Europe (M37-56)

Ongoing. Data for selected example countries for conducting the economic analysis by applying the concept of a Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) has been collected. Biosecurity measures for the analyses based on the results from WP2-T2 and WP5-T2 are selected in communication with BIOPIGEE team members from WP4-T2 and WP4-T3. The selected biosecurity measures will be individually evaluated by using the pathogen specific QMRAs. Unfortunately, due to technical and logistical issues, only one measure can be considered at a time. Costs for the selected biosecurity measures have been identified based on the initial definition of the measure in the original study, that evaluated the effect of the measure as well as consulting national guidelines and expert opinions. Additionally, cost-of-illness analysis were conducted for human salmonellosis cases as well as human HEV cases. At this stage, the CBA can only be conducted per individual measure and for the currently parametrized countries within the QMRAs.

WP5: Benchmark of biosecurity practice (M27-58)

The WP5 lead could not be replaced after the former WP-leader left BfR in 2021. Task leaders and main authors of manuscripts are organising remaining tasks.

WP5-T0 Definition of 'biosecurity measure' (M39-50)

The new subtask "Definition of a 'biosecurity measure'" was moved from WP1 to WP5. In this task project participants developed a common understanding of the term 'biosecurity measure' across WPs/Tasks based on applied inclusion/exclusion criteria from five BIOPIGEE task groups and a literature scoping review including four scientific databases. The developed definition was presented via a poster at the ONE-Health conference in 2022. A manuscript presenting and discussing the definition in detail has been submitted to the journal One Health and will be resubmitted after minor revisions soon.

WP5-T1 Data integration from WP2-4 in catalogue of biosecurity measures (M27-56)

The BIOPIGEE catalogue of identified biosecurity measures has been filled with findings on effective measures to control HEV and *Salmonella* occurrence at different production stages in primary production and at slaughter as well as on expert opinion from Task 2.2, T.2.3, T5.2, T5.4. Task T2.4 has filled in placeholders, as the studies are still ongoing (delayed after covid restrictions). There are 431 entries at this stage (status end of August 2022). Information is used by T4.4, T5.5 and T6.3. This task is lacking a leader. The project leader asked task leaders to add their results to the catalogue organised in a shared document.

WP5-T2 Literature review/meta-analysis (M27-50)

The literature review and meta-analysis to identify effective measures to control HEV, *Salmonella* and pathogenic *E. coli* in primary production has been finalised in a joint work between 6 partner countries/institutes. A keyword based search revealed 5130 hits listed across the literature databases Scopus, CAB Direct and NIH PubMed. Papers were reviewed through multiple rounds by 11 scientists (2 per paper), as well as an AI literature screening tool ASReview. Finally, 35 articles met the inclusion criteria (4 on HEV, 29 on *Salmonella*, 2 on pathogenic *E. coli*). From these articles, 14 observations on measures related to HEV, 145 related to *Salmonella* and three related to pathogenic *E. coli* control were extracted. Most measures addressed biosecurity categories like Cleaning & Disinfection (42), Mixing of pigs (35) and FeedWaterBedding (24). The results were transferred to the biosecurity catalogue (T5.1).

A manuscript is currently being drafted to present the study and its results intended to be published in a scientific journal.

WP5-T3 Machine learning approaches

The prediction of effectiveness of specific biosecurity measures with the help of machine learning approach and to inform the biosecurity catalogue appeared not anymore useful and was therefore cancelled. Instead, we used the ASReview tool in WP5-T2 to automate and complement part of the comprehensive and thereby labour- and staff intensive literature review on global biosecurity practice.

WP5-T4 Expert panel to add estimations on effectiveness/weights (M33-52)

A manuscript for the study on biosecurity measures prioritised by experts to control HEV and *Salmonella* in indoor and outdoor pig production has been prepared between authors from six countries and has been submitted to Porcine Health Management.

WP5-T5 Benchmark system for effectiveness of biosecurity (M51-58)

This task has started in M51. Task group meetings took place (1-2 per month). The list of participants, the objective and subtasks were clarified and organised. At first, effective biosecurity measures were collated, based on incoming data from the other tasks T2.2, T5.2, T5.4 (collected in the T5.1 catalogue). Only measure that meet the BIOPIGEE definition of biosecurity measures (clarified in the additional BIOPIGEE task T5.0) and which were proven to be effective based on former studies or study analyses in T2.2 were included in the benchmark list. The wording of the measures was prepared in agreement with reference information, task partners and in consultation with T4.4. The measures were grouped into categories which were used in WP2, 4 and 5 and ordered by prioritisation of experts (panel). A benchmark system has been developed which will address different production stages and pathogens. A traffic light system will be used and cut-offs are currently being studied in applying the benchmark checklist to farms from T2.2 with the help of the collected survey data.

WP6: Dissemination (M25-60)

WP6-T1 Assembly and development of biosecurity information (M25-M60)

WP6-T1-ST1- Identification of appropriate websites or other online channels

So far, 21 web sites in 6 countries have been identified for dissemination and are listed in a shared document. The link is accessible for the consortium via the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website. This task is carried out on an ongoing basis and the list is amended and updated throughout the project.

WP6-T1-ST2a Provision of information for farming schools and websites

Illustrations of most relevant examples for good biosecurity (pictures), which are planned to be used in this task, have been collected in WP2. Pictures from different partner countries' farms have been uploaded to an assembly at our website. Ideas about the content and presentation of this material have been exchanged with a German farming education centre on how to set up the material to address farming pupils. This task is ongoing.

WP6-T1-ST2b Provision of slaughterhouse protocol to slaughter industry/related associations

An online workshop on findings about effective biosecurity measures to control *Salmonella* (and HEV) at slaughter of pigs is planned for September 16th, 2022. Results will be discussed. A guidance document is in preparation together with the publication of the findings taking into account the feedback received from stakeholders during the above-mentioned workshop.

WP6-T2 A support tool for calculating cost effectiveness (M55-60)

This task builds on results from T4.4 and is ongoing.

There are currently two tools planned. One based on results from T4.4, to test cost-efficiency of biosecurity measures along the food chain and another one which addresses the benchmark of biosecurity practice in primary production.

WP6-T3 Organisation of a workshop-series (M25-58)

WP6-T3-ST1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

Ongoing. For the last workshops, stakeholder groups have been identified. These will be invited by 1) main contact persons at the partner institutes per country, by 2) the OHEJP CommsTeam, and by 3) Task 2.3 (slaughterhouse panel).

WP6-T3-ST5 Organisation of final Workshops

The first onsite workshop at the beginning of the project was replaced by national dissemination events where findings and feedback could be exchanged. The events are described in the deliverable <https://zenodo.org/record/6974588>. After one online workshop when project findings were discussed with the T5.4 expert panel in December 2021, another two virtual workshops are planned for the end of the project (in mid of September 2022; instead of one onsite workshop) to finally present and discuss findings on effective biosecurity measures in 1) primary production and 2) at slaughter, each targeting an individual and wide audience of stakeholders. The workshop for primary production will include outcome from T2.2 and T2.4 field studies, T4.4 economic modelling, T5.2 literature study and T5.4 expert survey. The second workshop will address literature information and a guidance document on effective slaughterhouse measures and sample results from slaughterhouses in CZ and IT (outcome from Task 2.3). Both workshops intend to discuss implementation of effective measures in respective operations.

5.1.4.10.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP1.13	Project report 2nd year submitted	M49	M49		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5930342	8
21	D-JRP21-WP2.12	Produce report on evidence gathered by field studies	M54	M54		Public, https://zenodo.org/record/6780124	8
21	D-JRP21-WP2.18	Report on correlation of biosecurity practice with HEV sequences to WP5 and 6, sequence analysis of hepatitis E to HEVnet	M57			Upload of HEV sequences to HEVnet and analysis of data is ongoing	5
21	D-JRP21-WP3.19	Information on the effect of different disinfectants on <i>Salmonella</i> in biofilm	M56	M56		Public, https://zenodo.org/record/7023490	2
21	D-JRP21-WP4.11	Model Output: Number of animal cases with and without biosecurity measures	M56	M56		Public, https://zenodo.org/record/6974303 the output of the French network model developed by ANSES has been provided for input to the QMRA.	7

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
21	D-JRP21-WP4.16	Economic calculation	M55		M57	Ongoing. Deliverable report is under internal revision (uploaded to private project webgroup)	7
21	D-JRP21-WP4.17	Model output: Number of human cases with and without biosecurity measures	M55		M57	Ongoing	7
21	D-JRP21-WP5.21	Benchmark system for effectiveness of biosecurity practice finished and forwarded to WP1 and WP6	M58			Ongoing	4
21	D-JRP21-WP6.26	Workshop 3 completed	M58			Two online workshops planned for dissemination of results on effective biosecurity measures in 1) primary production and 2) at slaughter in September 2022	8
21	D-JRP21-WP6.3	Workshop 1 completed		M56		Public, https://zenodo.org/record/6974588 National events were visited for dissemination and exchange of thoughts with stakeholders (instead of organising one international onsite workshop at the beginning of the project which was cancelled due to the pandemic situation).	8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
21	M-JRP21-15	Transmission model adaptation based on available data	M45	yes		Completed. The baseline QMRA models for <i>Salmonella</i> and HEV have been completed utilising relevant recent data.
21	M-JRP21-19	Completion of farm visits and lab work	M54	M56		completed (NL continues with visits which can complement BIOPIGEE results)
21	M-JRP21-20	Application of appropriate economic methods based on available data	M51	yes		Completed. Economic methods were selected for application. Working document is created, to be updated if methods have to be adjusted.
21	M-JRP21-21	Uploading of sequences to HEVnet	M54	M56		Completed
21	M-JRP21-22	Matching of different simulation model approaches to one	M55	yes		Completed. The different models developed in WP4 have been developed to ensure that the relevant outputs of one model can act as inputs to another.
21	M-JRP21-23	Relevant disinfectants are tested against <i>Salmonella</i> in biofilm	M56	yes		Completed
21	M-JRP21-24	Relevant disinfectants are tested against HEV in surface microlayers/biofilms	M56	yes		A pilot study on HEV stability in relation to disinfectants has been executed

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
21	M-JRP21-25	Finalized data integration from WP2-4 into catalogue of biosecurity measures	M56		M59	ongoing, depends on delayed tasks; existing content has been used for other tasks
21	M-JRP21-26	Finalized literature review/meta-analysis	M50	M53		finalised (was delayed because of change in staff), results are currently being written up in a manuscript by the task group
21	M-JRP21-27	Economic model for the assessments of profitability of biosecurity measures	M56		M57	ongoing, parameters for economic assessment identified and model to calculate the profitability set up. To finalize cost calculations for biosecurity measures and to carry out the cost-benefit-analysis
21	M-JRP21-28	Predicted effectiveness of specific biosecurity measures from machine learning approach incorporated in catalogue	M57			cancelled, appeared not anymore useful and necessary for informing the biosecurity catalogue because other tasks (literature review, field studies) fed already the catalogue . Instead, ASReview was used in T5.2 to partly automate and complement the comprehensive literature search. Thereby, the following T5.5 bechmark task was well informed.
21	M-JRP21-29	Expert panel ranked biosecurity practice	M51	yes		finalised, manuscript has been submitted

5.1.4.10.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Propagation du virus de l'hépatite E de la case à la filière: analyse de réseaux complexes et modélisation, JRP conference/paper https://zenodo.org/record/6091598	Yes	Yes	No
Complex network analysis to understand trading partnership in French swine production, PlosOne (revision in process) https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0266457 https://zenodo.org/record/6458445#.YnkdKehBxwQ	Yes	No	Yes

Several publications, intended as peer-reviewed articles, are planned:

- **submitted:** manuscript in T5.0 on the definition of biosecurity measures (working title “What is a biosecurity measure? A definition proposal for animal production and linked processing operations”), Journal One Health (currently minor revision); manuscript in T5.4 on the expert opinion about relevance of biosecurity measures (working title “Prioritization of pig farm biosecurity for control of *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus infections, results of a survey among European experts”)
- **in work:** manuscripts in T2.2 on “Protective biosecurity measures to reduce hepatitis E virus in European pig farms” and “Effectiveness of pig farm biosecurity measures for the control of *Salmonella*”, in T2.3 on effective biosecurity measures and their implementation to control *Salmonella* and HEV in slaughterhouses, in T5.2 on literature review/meta-analysis about biosecurity measures in pig farming to reduce occurrence of HEV/*Salmonella*/pathogenic *E. coli*
- **ideas/intended:** manuscripts dealing with results (data evaluation is still in work) e.g. from T2.4 on longitudinal studies about specific biosecurity measures in farms; from WP3 on test methods for disinfectants and biofilms/ for HEV stability, on the comparison of implemented biosecurity measures in farms (T2.2 survey outcome) and assessed relevance of biosecurity practices (T5.4 expert survey outcome) to control *Salmonella* and HEV in pig production.

Additional output

Posters

- Jones, H., Smith, R.P., Burow, E., on behalf of the BIOPIGEE consortium (2022). Effective biosecurity measures for the control of *Salmonella* in European pig farms. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online.
- Ianiro G., Pavoni E., Alborali G., Guadagno F., Delibato E., Treglia I., De Sabato L., Monini M., Ostanello F., Di Bartolo I. (2022). Molecular tracing of dissemination routes of *Salmonella* spp, Hepatitis E virus and other viruses as fecal indicators in pigs at slaughterhouse. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6646338>
- Ianiro G., Pavoni E., Aprea G., Romantini R., Alborali G., D’Angelantonio D., Garofolo G., Scattolini S., De Sabato L., Ostanello F., Di Bartolo I. (2022). Presence of *Salmonella* spp. And Hepatitis E virus in Italian pig farms. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6638970>
- Meester M., Tobias T., Meulenbroek C., Hakze-van der Honing R., van Oort S., Bouwknecht M., Stegeman A., van der Poel W.H.M. (2022). Prevalence of HEV in finishing pigs: cross-sectional exploration of farm specific patterns and evaluation of sampling. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6566927>
- Kozyra, I., Zajac, M., Żmudzki, J., Dors, A., Skrzypiec, E., Wasyl, D., Rzeżutka, A. (2022). Epidemiological significance of *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus (HEV) occurrence in fattening pigs in Poland. Poster at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6673709>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2021). Multi-levels Hepatitis E Virus Spread In Various Epidemiological Contexts: Combining Complex Network Analysis & Disease Transmission Model. Poster at the 8th International Conference on Infectious Disease Dynamics (Epidemics 8), online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5786494>
- Huber, N., Zoche-Golob, V., Sassu, E. L., Prigge, C., Käsbohrer, A., Andraud, M., D’Angelantonio, D., Viltrop, A., Niine, T., Hammami, P., Żmudzki, J., Jones, H., Burow, E. (2022). What is a

biosecurity measure? A definition proposal for farms and linked processing operations. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.

- Smith, R., Jones, H., Burow, E. (2022). *Salmonella* presence on European pig farms. I3S International Symposium *Salmonella* & Salmonellosis 20.-22.06.222. Saint-Malo. <https://zenodo.org/record/7054296>
- Dors, A., Wasyl, D., Rzesutka, A., Karbowski, P., Szalkowski, W., Zmudzki, J. (2022). A survey on external biosecurity in selected commercial Polish pig farms. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Burow, E., Zoche-Golob, V., Tobias, T., Sassu, E. L., Galpó, E., Prigge, C., Smith, R. P., Sjölund, M. (2022). Expert opinion on biosecurity measures for controlling *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus in pig farming - findings of the OHEJP BIOPIGEE project. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online.
- Niine, T., Viltrop, A., Nurmoja, I., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). The best biosecurity practices in European abattoirs in regards to *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus. Poster at the ONE2022 21.-24.06.2022., Brussel/online. <https://zenodo.org/record/7032155>
- Jones, H., Smith, R. P., Burow, E. (2022). Effective biosecurity measures for the control of *Salmonella* in European pig farms. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Meester, M., Tobias, T., van der Poel, W. (2022). Biosecurity practices to reduce risk of hepatitis E virus in European pig farms. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Meester, M., Tobias, T., van der Poel, W. (2022). Sensitivity and specificity of pen-level sampling methods for hepatitis E virus detection in fattening pigs. Poster at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Wilkins, N. (2022). A farm-to-consumption quantitative microbiological risk assessment for hepatitis E in pigs. Presented at 16th International Symposium of Veterinary Epidemiology and Economics (ISVEE), 07.-12.08.2022, Halifax, CA.
- Osland, A.M, Oastler, C. Brook, E. Gosling, B. Arvand, M. Richter, A.M, Konrat, K. Asal, B. Vestby. L.K. (2022). Effect of Glutaraldehyde on biofilm-associated wild type *Salmonella*. Poster will be presented at Eurobiofilms 2022. 31.8.22-3.9.22, Mallorca, Spain
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Multi-levels hepatitis E virus spread in various epidemiological contexts: combining complex network analysis & disease transmission model. Poster at the Epidemics conference. <https://zenodo.org/record/5786494>

Oral presentations

- Niine, T., Viltrop, A., Nurmoja, I., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). Biosecurity measures in European slaughterhouses to prevent the contamination of pig carcasses with *Salmonella*. Konverentsi "terve loom ja tervislik toit 2022" artiklikogumik (Estonian conference), 157–160. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6355316>
- Viltrop, A. (2022). Biosecurity of *Salmonella* from Estonian pig farms perspective. Estonian Officials Veterinarian Training day.
- Burow, E. (presentation), Zoche-Golob, V. (abstract), Aprea, G., Sjölund, M., for the BIOPIGEE consortium (2022). Biosecurity measures reducing Hepatitis E Virus in pig herds – findings of the OHEJP project BIOPIGEE. Oral presentation at German conference 22. Fachtagung für

Fleisch- und Geflügelfleischhygiene, 1.-2. March 2022, Berlin,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6524126>

- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Spread of hepatitis E virus from pens to the national industry: complex network analysis and modelling. 54th Journées de la Recherche Porcine (JRP), 2nd February 2022, online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6091598>
- Hammami, P., Widgren, S., Grosbois, V., Apolloni, A., Rose, N., Andraud, M. (2022). Propagation du virus de l'hépatite E de la case à la filière : analyse de réseaux complexes et modélisation. Talk at the Junior Researcher Programme conference <https://zenodo.org/record/6091598>
- Burow, E., N. Huber, E. Galipó, R. Smith (2022). Effective and prioritised biosecurity practice to control *Salmonella* in pig farming - findings from the BIOPIGEE project. Oral presentation at HealthyLivestock conference, 16.06.2022, hybrid
- Burow, E., Schulze-Horsel, T., Harlizius, J., Rostalski, A., Smith, R., Zoche-Golob, V., Galipó, E., Waller, E., Jones, H., Sjölund, M., Käsbohrer, A. (2022). Biosicherheitsmaßnahmen zur Kontrolle von Salmonellen und Hepatitis E Viren in der europäischen Schweinehaltung - OHEJP Projekt BIOPIGEE. Biosecurity measures for controlling *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus in European pig farming - OHEJP project BIOPIGEE. DACH Epidemiologietagung 2022, 31.08.-02.09.2022, Oldenburg.
- Galipó, E., Zoche-Golob, V., Sassu E. L., Prigge, C., Sjölund, M., Tobias, T., Rzesutka, A., Smith, R., Burow, E. (2022). Pig farm biosecurity for control of *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus infections – a survey of European experts. Oral presentation at the OHEJP ASM 11-13.04.2022. Orvieto/online.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

In WP6, additional outcomes like support tool for e.g. farmers, information/education material for farming pupils, website information and two more workshops (in September 2022) for the exchange of ideas with stakeholders are planned. The organisation of the education material, website presentations and of the workshops has started.

5.1.4.10.4.1 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

BIOPIGEE is exchanging information on biosecurity and disease preventive measures on farm with the EU/global project **HealthyLivestock**. The key factors associated with disease prevention to be identified in HealthyLivestock and the key biosecurity measures associated with reduction of *Salmonella*/HEV prevalence to be identified in BIOPIGEE were compared in meetings and events. BIOPIGEE representants participated and presented project results in a hybrid event of HealthyLivestock on 23th June 2022, and HealthyLivestock is invited to a BIOPIGEE Workshop in September.

The collaboration with the **German Meat Industry Association** (Verband der Fleischwirtschaft e.V.) and the **Food Standards Agency in the UK** will be reactivated soon for the advertisement of the virtual workshop on slaughterhouse biosecurity measures in order to discuss findings on effective practices with the stakeholders. The same corresponds to **national collaborations with animal health services/veterinary services and practicing veterinarians**, for the online Workshop on biosecurity practices at primary production.

For a target group orientated preparation of dissemination material and tool (WP6), contacts were initiated between BfR and a **German public consultation service on biosecurity in pig farming** (Biosicherheitsberatung Schweinehaltung, Tiergesundheitsdienste der **Tierseuchenkasse Baden-Württemberg**). An additional contact was made with a **German training centre for farming apprenticeship** (Chamber of Agriculture North Rhine-Westphalia). A meeting with the training centre took place on January 2022. Ideas have been exchanged on how material and a tool can be designed to address the needs and interest of pig farmers. It was agreed to send draft material for feedback to the consultancy service and to keep them updated about new outcome from the project.

Data from a **biosecurity study** in Ireland has been assessed for its suitability to add to the task 2.2 dataset. A **data sharing agreement** is being produced between **APHA** and **Animal Health Ireland** to allow the data to be incorporated into a review of biosecurity measures applied on **European pig farms**.

5.1.4.11 JRP22-R2-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES

5.1.4.11.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

TOXOSOURCES is a Joint Research Project of the One Health EJP that focuses on *Toxoplasma gondii* at the interface between humans, animals, food, and the environment.

Toxoplasma gondii is a foodborne parasite that causes a high disease burden. The infection can be acquired by ingesting oocysts (environmental pathway) or tissue cysts (meatborne pathway). The relative contributions of the two pathways to the infection and disease in humans remain unknown, partly due to a lack of appropriate methods. Environmental contamination with *T. gondii* oocysts is understudied and likely underestimated due to the lack of suitable harmonised sampling approaches and detection methods.

TOXOSOURCES investigates the relative contributions of the different transmission routes and sources of *T. gondii* infection using multidisciplinary approaches. The project is developing new methods and yielding new knowledge, and it has both ambition and potential to advance science in the field.

The TOXOSOURCES consortium has collected data for a multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for *T. gondii*: a multicentre quantitative exposure survey was conducted, and systematic literature reviews yielded estimates of prevalence of the infection in a high number of animal host species as well as in fresh produce and the environment. After an extensive literature review to support the selection of a method to detect *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce, a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) was developed, implemented and validated, and is being applied in a multicentre pilot survey on ready-to-eat salads. The project has selected promising antigens for exploring serology for detecting *T. gondii* infections caused by oocysts, and an unprecedented effort of whole genome sequencing of *T. gondii* isolates was used to identify polymorphic marker regions for the establishment of a new typing method to detect within-genotype variation. The developed SOPs for these methods are being applied during the second half of the project. The project has organised ring trials as part of validation of the method to detect *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce, and to harmonise the current state-of-the-art genotyping method.

The outcomes of TOXOSOURCES will include quantitative and comparable estimates of the contribution of the main sources and transmission routes to *T. gondii* infections across Europe. The project fills several relevant data gaps. A major outcome already reached is the collection and whole genome sequencing of a large number of *T. gondii* isolates across Europe. Moreover, the consortium itself is a major achievement - exemplifying a successful cross-sectoral, international One Health collaboration, which is needed to address this zoonotic parasite.

The TOXOSOURCES Consortium comprises 21 One Health EJP partners and several external partners. The TOXOSOURCES Consortium has shown impressive resourcefulness and adaptability, and while timelines have needed adapting, all Milestones have been reached on time and all Deliverables and

reports have been submitted by their planned deadlines. Dissemination of outcomes has been active and included scientific publications and presentations at conferences, workshops and webinars, and several collaborations with other projects and networks have been established.

5.1.4.11.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

Progress made in TOXOSOURCES has throughout the project lifetime followed the planned timeline, and all Milestones and Deliverables have been reached by their deadlines.

Due to the COVID-19-pandemic there was a need to considerably adapt internal timelines, in particular those related to laboratory work due to lockdowns. TOXOSOURCES applied for a 6-month extension until the end of the year 2022, to ensure 1) that the project can fully achieve all the planned aims; 2) that all partners have the opportunity to benefit from implementation of the new methods and knowledge; 3) that the studies are able to cover all the aspects planned; 4) that the outputs scheduled for 2022 will be of high quality and we have time for their efficient dissemination; and as a result of all the previous points: 5) that TOXOSOURCES will have the impact it has the potential to have. The project also carefully revised the budgets of 2022 to ensure that outcomes will be reached.

The work is organized into 5 work packages (WPs) with tasks (T) and some subtasks (sT). The project spans over three Annual Periods (Y3-Y5, 2020-2022).

Key outputs are available via the project homepage: <https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-toxosources/> and via Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22TOXOSOURCES%22&sort=-publication_date.

Kick-off Meeting of TOXOSOURCES, February 2020, at Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark.

WP1 Coordination and impact

TOXOSOURCES-WP1 manages the project and is responsible for its progress, and integrates all the results of the project to achieve the common goals. TOXOSOURCES-WP1 ensures the project adheres to H2020 rules regarding e.g. ethics, IRP, dissemination and publication. Moreover, TOXOSOURCES-WP1 is responsible for the Data Management Plan of the project. TOXOSOURCES-WP1 coordinates the compiling of deliverables and reports and their timely submission, as well as the organization of project meetings and communication. Science-to-policy translation and efficient dissemination are emphasized to maximize the impact. Interest Group with representatives from e.g. industry will facilitate targeted dissemination to stakeholders.

The main focus of TOXOSOURCES-WP1 is ensuring project progress as planned, and organizing the Annual Meetings. TOXOSOURCES-WP1 integrates the results of the project to make them useful, in particular to contribute to developing interventions. These aims have been reached. All Milestones have been reached on time and all Deliverables and reports have been submitted by their deadlines.

The Annual Meeting of 2022 is planned to be organised in two parts to benefit from synergies with both ICOPA2022 and another relevant conference organised during the year. Dissemination has active and included scientific publications and presentations at conferences, workshops and webinars - including several invited presentations. TOXOSOURCES was invited to present its results at the Stakeholders Committee Meeting of One Health EJP on June 11, 2021, was highlighted in a Thematic Report focusing on environmental aspects addressed by One Health EJP projects, and presented also at ESAB and REA meetings. Several collaborations with other projects and networks have been established and strengthened. Of specific note is the collaboration with SafeConsume project, originally benefiting from Horizon Results Booster services.

The impact of the COVID-19 situation is followed closely, and challenges have been managed well by planning and resourcefulness, deputies and replacements. The effect of delays caused by the COVID-19-pandemic is evident, and there has been a need to considerably adapt internal timelines, in particular those related to laboratory work due to lockdowns. The project applied for a 6-month extension until the end of the year 2022; the extension request was solely due to the challenges caused by the COVID-19-pandemic.

WP1-T1- Management, coordination and communication

The Kick-off Meeting was held February 3–4, 2020, at SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark, with a possibility to participate remotely. Online meetings with the whole consortium have been held on October 20, 2020, on June 8, 2021 (Annual Meeting 2021, Part I), and on November 15, 2021 (Annual Meeting 2021, Part II). Two annual meetings are planned for 2022.

The established key structures for management of the project include monthly online meeting with TOXOSOURCES WP-Leaders and Co-Leaders, Consortium emails, use of the online group for sharing and storage of relevant documents, and WP-level online meetings.

Screenshot from an online meeting of TOXOSOURCES-WP-Leaders and WP-Deputy-Leaders.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is updated regularly, and the project leader participates in the work of the One Health EJP DMP Committee. Outcomes are made available following FAIR principle. Dissemination of the outcomes has been active, and included presentations to relevant audiences at conferences, workshops and webinars, and scientific publications.

The collaborations with the Interest Group and other collaborators have started by establishing key contacts. Invited by SafeConsume, TOXOSOURCES joined a Horizon Results Booster project group called “DISH - Towards healthy and safe diet” that includes SafeConsume, TOXOSOURCES, Stance4Health, EAT2beNICE and FOODSAFETY4EU. TOXOSOURCES suggested a OHEJP Cogwheel Workshop with SafeConsume, and it was organized on November 25, 2020. SafeConsume invited TOXOSOURCES to give a presentation and participate in round table at their International Conference June 27-28, 2022.

Challenged by the COVID-19-pandemic, the TOXOSOURCES Consortium has shown impressive resourcefulness and adaptability, and the careful risks-and-dependencies planning has proved useful. All Milestones, Deliverables and reports have been reached and submitted by their planned deadlines

throughout the timeline of the project. The consortium is highly motivated and the general atmosphere is positive and supportive.

WP1-T2- Integration of all results to contribute to developing interventions, dissemination

Efficient dissemination and science-to-policy activities at national, European and global levels include facilitating the use of the new knowledge, linking the providers and users of the knowledge, and advocating multidisciplinary approaches.

TOXOSOURCES was part of a Horizon Results Booster project group “DISH - Towards healthy and safe diet” that included SafeConsume, TOXOSOURCES, Stance4Health, EAT2beNICE and FOODSAFETY4EU. Module A was finished at the end of 2020, and module B services were launched in 2021. A factsheet and video about the DISH collaboration were produced, and made public in 2022. A lunch webinar was organised on April 6, 2022.

A page from factsheet produced for DISH collaboration.

TOXOSOURCES was invited to present its results at the Stakeholders Committee Meeting of One Health EJP on June 11, 2021, and was highlighted in a related Thematic Report focusing on environmental aspects addressed by One Health EJP projects. Moreover, TOXOSOURCES presented at ESAB meeting on May, 2022 and OHEJP Review meeting on May 17, 2022.

Outcomes of TOXOSOURCES are made available following FAIR principle. Dissemination of the outcomes has been active, and included presentations to relevant audiences at conferences, workshops and webinars, and scientific publications. Early-career colleagues involved in the work are particularly encouraged to present the results. Another special focus in the dissemination is integration of results from the different TOXOSOURCES-WPs.

WP2 Multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for *T. gondii* infections

TOXOSOURCES-WP2 aims to quantify the relative contribution of sources of *T. gondii* infection, including meat products, fresh produce and environmental pathways, in Europe by quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA). TOXOSOURCES-WP2 develops QMRA models for infection via tissue cysts (meat) and oocysts (environmental pathways), and applies the models in a multi-country study covering four European regions. Input data for the QMRA were collected with contributions and support by all partners and TOXOSOURCES-WP3. An overview of the prevalence of *T. gondii* infection in humans and animals used for human consumption as well as cats was obtained by review of available literature, including grey literature. Exposure data were collected in a harmonised way using a survey specifically designed for QMRA purposes and with focus on possible sources of *T. gondii* infection. Region- or country-specific products, dishes or eating habits were identified and the

associated key processing parameters collected by the partners. The literature review of human infections also covers risk factor studies, to compare QMRA outcomes and epidemiological data.

The work has progressed following the plans. All milestones have been reached on time, and Deliverables have been submitted on time. The data collected will likely be useful also for other initiatives and projects.

WP2-T1- QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections

The Consortium members involved in QMRA modelling met at RIVM, The Netherlands, to discuss plans in 2020. The development of the structure for the QMRA model for environmental transmission of *T. gondii* was finished, and expansion of both the meatborne and environmental QMRA models to include multiple countries was started. The work builds on previous work, in particular on an existing meatborne QMRA model, as well as on environmental QMRA model developed in a PhD project of Huifang Deng, which was successfully defended on December 08, 2020.

During Y4, the main focus was checking input data as preparation for running the QMRA model. In addition, sensitivity analyses (to identify the most influential input parameters) and scenario analyses (in case of large uncertainty regarding input parameters) that will be initiated were planned.

WP2-T2- Review of prevalence of *T. gondii* infection in animals

A list of European countries and a list of key animal species raised or hunted for human consumption in Europe were collated. These were used to develop a search strategy for data on prevalence of *T. gondii* in animals. Earlier experiences from systematic reviews performed by EFSA and in the Baltic-Nordic region were taken into account in the process.

The search, screening of retrieved records, and data extraction were finished in 2020, and the data were checked and cleaned. The process and general results were summarised in a Deliverable. Selected primary results were submitted as abstracts and selected for presentation at scientific events. The results are being prepared for scientific publication.

This task is an example of a task that has included collaboration with early-career colleagues, and cross-project collaboration with OHEJP PhD project.

Related to this task, TOXOSOURCES members are also participating in another review together with the OHEJP-ORION project, focusing on risk factors for *T. gondii* infections in animals. While that information is not directly needed for the QMRA, together with the prevalence estimates it will provide important input for planning interventions.

WP2-T3- Quantitative exposure survey

In 2020 a general questionnaire was developed by expanding an existing questionnaire and taking into account experiences from the Dutch National Food Consumption Survey, risk factor information from a prospective case-control study in the Netherlands, and applying categorisation of the EFSA FoodEx system, which enables comparison with existing surveys. The questions were adapted to the different countries by including region/country-specific products. Decisions on sample size (respondents per each country) were finalized.

In 2021, the questionnaires were distributed via a market research agency to collect harmonised data on food consumption and handling and exposure to oocysts from the countries included in the QMRA. The data were provided for the QMRA, and plans for making the data publically available in connection to their publication, so that they can be used for QMRA modelling of other foodborne pathogens, were initiated. The results were disseminated in 2022 e.g. at OHEJPASM2022 and ONE2022.

WP2-T4- Overview of processing parameters for relevant meat products

Information on food consumption in the different countries was collected from the EFSA FoodEx2 database. Information on region/country-specific relevant products was also collected from

consortium members. The list of products that need to be included in the exposure survey was harmonised across the countries. Product-specific processing parameters were discussed in the process of planning the survey questions, in particular regarding local products.

The data from the exposure survey inform which meat products are included in the QMRA model. Next, product-specific parameter values for freezing, salting and heating (e.g. time, temperature, concentration) were collated. The information were obtained using meat processing handbooks, communication with meat producers, or from package information in retail, and will be used as input data to the QMRA. Further discussions about the parameters included contacts with the industry.

WP2-T5- Review of prevalence and risk factors for human *T. gondii* infection

This task was among those most affected by COVID-19 pandemic due to involvement of several key consortium members in the COVID-19 response. Efficient replacements and synergy with TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T2 ensured that this task has also progressed well. The experiences from TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T2 work were incorporated into the planning of the systematic review protocol under this task. During 2021, the main focus was to finalize the searches, screening and main data extraction, analyse the results for their usefulness for the QMRA and prepare to deliver data for the QMRA modelling team. The data will be analysed by Bayesian hierarchical modelling to estimate the prevalence by country.

Results from the literature review on *T. gondii* source attribution (including risk factor analyses) for COST-action Euro-FBP were presented at OHEJPASM2020, emphasizing the continuation of the work in TOXOSOURCES. The screening and extraction protocol was aligned with that of a review done in collaboration with OHEJP-ORION project.

WP3 Multicentre survey to fill the key existing gap: role of fresh produce (i.e. Ready-to-Eat salads)

TOXOSOURCES-WP3 aims to fill the knowledge gap concerning the relevance of fresh produce contamination by *T. gondii* oocysts as an infection source for humans. TOXOSOURCES-WP3 selected the most reliable methods for the molecular detection of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce using a literature review, expert experiences, experimental evaluation and inter-laboratory comparison by ring trial. Harmonised detection is implemented among the partners. TOXOSOURCES-WP3 collected existing data on *T. gondii* oocyst prevalence in fresh produce and the environment, together with information on fresh produce (e.g. RTE production, trading and consumption) in Europe. The data were used to design a risk-based sampling strategy for a multicentre pilot survey to detect *T. gondii* in fresh produce, applying the defined SOP. The ongoing multicentre pilot study, spanning all four European regions, is the first of its kind and will deliver valuable input for the TOXOSOURCES-WP2 and future QMRAs.

The work has progressed according to plan. The ring trial timeline was adjusted to allow all interested laboratories to implement the method. The final sampling strategy was presented to the consortium at the Annual Meeting 2021, Part I. Milestones and Deliverables have all been achieved on time.

WP3-T1- Selection, evaluation and implementation of detection procedure for *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce

An extensive literature review and multi-attribute assessment of the different steps in molecular detection of *T. gondii* (DNA) (oocyst recovery, DNA extraction and DNA amplification) was performed and complemented by a survey of expert opinions, current practices and experiences, to select the most suitable molecular method for *T. gondii* oocyst detection in fresh produce. The Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.1 summarizes this process, which provided a good starting point for developing a standard operating procedure (SOP) for the multicentre survey of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce. The results were published as a scientific article in early 2021.

The comparative experimental work was completed in 2020, and instead of the planned physical technical workshops, video tutorials were produced. The work towards the SOP was reported in

Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.2 and presented to relevant audiences in 2021. The deliverable describing the organisation of the ring trial was submitted on time. The ring trial timeline was adjusted to allow all interested laboratories (larger number of laboratories than originally planned) to implement the method, and thus this task was adapted to continue some months longer than originally planned. The main work was finished on time and all the outcomes (Deliverables and in addition a scientific article) were delivered on time. Dissemination of the outcomes of the work continues until the end of the project.

WP3-T2- Design of a risk-based sampling strategy

An extensive review of peer-reviewed literature on the prevalence of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce was performed, as well as a review of the literature on *T. gondii* prevalence in the environment (soil and water) and bivalves. These were complemented by an online questionnaire to consortium partners to collate grey literature on the topic. A data summary on literature-based prevalence of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce was provided to TOXOSOURCES-WP2, and the results have been prepared for scientific publication, and the manuscript has been submitted. The key aspects of the work and results from grey literature search were reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.4. Moreover, selected primary results were presented at scientific events.

The design of a risk-based sampling strategy for the multicentre survey of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce was started by preparing an online questionnaire to gather relevant information on trade and consumption of ready-to-eat salads from local and international industry. In addition, a request for information was sent via the EFSA focal point and a simple survey on RTE salads sold locally at supermarkets across Europe was conducted. Data were combined to design a sampling plan, taking into account sample size calculations, feasibility and costs, and the sampling strategy for WP3-T3 was defined.

The milestone of finalizing the sampling strategy was reached on time. The final sampling strategy was presented to the consortium at the Annual Meeting 2021, Part I. The strategy is being applied in WP3-T3.

WP3-T3- Multicentre pilot survey on *T. gondii* in fresh produce in Europe

The sampling strategy and plan for the multicentre pilot survey was finalized on time. A multicentre pilot survey for the molecular detection of *T. gondii* in selected fresh produce in Europe is being performed based on outputs of WP3-T1 and WP3-T2. Samples are being collected, over one year, in countries representative of the four European regions according to the strategy developed in WP3-T2. Fresh produce samples are obtained from local supermarkets and analysed the SOP defined in WP3-T1. Some partners perform only the oocyst recovery step of the SOP, store frozen the processed samples and deliver them to partners that have implemented the full SOP for the molecular testing. This approach ensures faster processing of the perishable fresh produce thus increasing the overall number of tested samples. The number of samples analysed is following the plan.

WP4 Serology method based on novel antigens to discriminate *T. gondii* infections acquired from oocysts

TOXOSOURCES-WP4 aims to develop a source-attributing serological method. TOXOSOURCES-WP4 identifies novel oocyst/sporozyte-specific antigens of *T. gondii* that have source-attributing potential and explores serological methods able to discriminate between oocyst- versus tissue cyst-driven infections. Finally, the methodology is applied to estimate the proportion of oocyst-driven infections in humans and animals used for human consumption.

The bioinformatic selection of promising protein candidates was finalized in 2020, and although laboratory work was strongly affected by the COVID-19-related restrictions, the work progressed following the overall plans. The recombinant expression of proteins of interest is followed by assessing them using suitable sera.

A detailed workflow for protein screening and development of a serological test was formulated and followed, reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.1 and published in international scientific publication. Selected preliminary results were disseminated to scientific audiences at Toxomeeting and International Workshop on Environmental Toxoplasmosis.

WP4-T1- Identification and production of *T. gondii* stage-specific antigens for source attribution

The predicted proteome of the *T. gondii* oocyst/sporozoite was analysed bioinformatically to identify the best stage-specific and antigenically relevant protein candidates. A list of 96 proteins with source-attributing potential was defined. The main selection criteria were exclusive expression in oocysts, evidence of secretion, and a high score in linear epitope prediction.

The bioinformatic selection of promising protein candidates was finalized in 2020, and the work on the next steps continued in 2021 and continues further in 2022. The recombinant expression of proteins of interest is followed by assessing them using suitable sera. A selection of known stage-specific proteins are tested in parallel to the novel candidates.

WP4-T2- Development of a novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA to diagnose oocyst- and bradyzoite-driven *T. gondii* infections

Key sera have been characterized using a selection of widely employed serological tests, yielding interesting comparative data. The results obtained in the comparative study were presented in an international scientific meeting. The results are prepared for scientific publication.

The plan and experimental design for the development work were finalized in 2020 for the screening of the proteins using a step-by-step validation process. A detailed workflow for protein screening and development of a serological test was formulated and followed, reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.1 and published in international scientific publication. Candidate proteins were selected out of a panel of 15 initial candidates for further ELISA development.

Key aspects of the work done as well as key achievements of the process were reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.1.

WP4-T2-sT1 Standardization of a POI-based ELISA to diagnose oocyst- and/or bradyzoite driven *T. gondii* infections using reference pig sera

A suitable panel of sera from pigs experimentally infected with either oocysts or tissue cysts, first characterized using commercially available and routinely used serological tests for the selection of the best secondary antibody for the novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA, is then tested using the approaches developed. Appropriate control sera were selected for the protein screening and assay development. The development of a source attribution serological assay is in progress following different strategies.

WP4-T2-sT2 Validation of a novel stage-specific antigen based ELISA to diagnose oocysts-and/or bradyzoite-driven *T. gondii* infections using reference sera from several relevant host species including humans

A suitable panel of sera from sheep experimentally infected with oocysts was characterized using commercially available and routinely used serological tests and the best secondary antibody for the novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA was selected. International collaboration identified suitable sera from humans that would be useful for the work. The reference sera are then tested using the approaches developed.

WP4-T3- Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-derived *T. gondii* infections in animals and in humans

For using the POI-ELISA validated in WP4-T2, pilot studies are planned. The method will be offered to other Consortium partners for testing existing collections of positive sera.

WP4-T3-sT1 Inter-laboratory validation of the POI-based ELISA

POI-based ELISA will be adapted to the participating laboratories to obtain comparable results. Inter-laboratory reproducibility and analytical sensitivity will be evaluated using positive and negative reference sera (experimental *T. gondii* infection) identified in WP4-T2-sT1.

WP4-T3-sT2 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in domestic animals (pigs, small ruminants) and wildlife (wild-boar, wild ungulates) used for human consumption

To reveal differences in the relative prevalence of oocyst-driven infections between animal species, regions and management systems, positive sera from naturally infected animals from different European regions will be tested using the POI-based ELISA. The planning of this work has started.

WP4-T3-sT3 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in humans

Well-defined positive sera from *T. gondii*-infected humans available from different European regions will be tested using the POI-based ELISA by pilot studies, that may include, based on availability, sera from congenitally-infected children aged <13 months and from older children >2 years; sera from recently infected adults; as well as sera from any suspected *T. gondii* outbreaks in Europe. The planning of this work has started.

WP5 Novel *T. gondii* typing method to detect within-genotype variation

TOXOSOURCES-WP5 aims to identify highly polymorphic regions in genomes of very closely related *T. gondii* strains across Europe, which are made available by partners and collaborators. Preliminary NGS data on European clonal type II *T. gondii* isolates has revealed substantial variation between isolates and relative to reference strains. Using the panel of strains from various parts of Europe, regions in the genome with an optimal SNP density are identified and used to establish a novel typing method.

The work in year 2020 was successful in both retrieval of relevant isolates and their whole genome sequencing (WGS). The work progressed following the plans in 2021, with focus on disseminating the results by presentations to relevant audiences. In 2022, ring trials focusing on the current state-of-the-art-genotyping method were organised - increasing our understanding of the genetic variation of the parasite in Europe as well as of the method, and supporting obtaining comparable results.

WP5-T1- Retrieval of relevant *T. gondii* isolates or NGS-quality DNAs for NGS and NGS-MST

T. gondii isolates, WGS-quality DNAs or WGS-data on isolates were collected from across Europe. Isolates were expanded *in vitro*, and DNA was extracted for WGS. The focus was on *T. gondii* Type II isolates, while other isolates were included as well. This retrieval of key *T. gondii* isolates or DNAs was successful and the total number of isolates retrieved for the work is markedly higher than the original target. Isolates from northern and eastern European regions were first underrepresented on the list, but further efforts were successful in gathering more isolates from these regions.

During 2021, further isolates were collected to establish a panel for inter-laboratory comparison and pilot studies (WP5-T3). A request for contributions was sent out to networks including the NRL network. For particular regions, we included a larger number of isolates to show that resolution of typing is high enough to trace differences of local isolates.

All DNAs are also characterised based on polymorphism of fewer markers using existing standard techniques (PCR-RFLP and microsatellite (MS) typing).

WP5-T2- Novel, standardized high-throughput direct NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method

Based on sequence information obtained by WP5-T1 a novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST genotyping method is being established and validated to distinguish between closely related *T. gondii* strains. Timely dissemination is emphasized, and progress and results of this work have been presented to relevant audiences.

WP5-T2-sT1 Whole genome sequencing (WGS) of key *T. gondii* isolates and WGS-quality DNAs

A large number of whole genome sequences have been generated. The sequences of key *T. gondii* isolates were provided to TOXOSOURCES-WP5-T2-sT2.

WP5-T2-sT2 Establishment, validation and refinement of a novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method

Based on the sequences from WP5-T2-sT1, highly polymorphic marker regions (partially focusing on introns and/or particular gene regions of e.g. virulence associated genes) were identified and are being evaluated for suitability for the establishment of a new typing method. The higher number of sequences than originally planned has proven highly beneficial for the work.

For validation, the novel NGS-MLST results were compared with results of conventional techniques (PCR-RFLP, MS typing) (i). Similarities and differences in the capability of the novel NGS-MLST method and the PCR-RFLP- and MS-based techniques for the *T. gondii* differentiation are established. (ii) The analytical sensitivity will be determined using different sample matrices, spiked with different levels of parasites. Plans were made for this work.

A standardized workflow for the collection and preliminary analysis of NGS-MLST data on *T. gondii* is established. The Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5.1 summarized the key steps of the NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method and its establishment. This deliverable provides the base for its further validation by an Inter-laboratory comparison and its application by NGS-MLST pilot studies. Finally, the new technology will be distributed to interested partners, if possible by a workshop at FLI, prior to inter-laboratory comparison and pilot studies (WP5-T3).

WP5-T3- Inter-laboratory comparison and NGS-MLST pilot studies

The plans for this work were made. Using a panel of reference samples, an inter-laboratory comparison of the established novel NGS-MLST genotyping method can be performed. Then, the method will be available to be applied to "real/unknown" *T. gondii* positive samples from the field, i.e. samples from intermediate hosts (including humans), definitive hosts and environment by laboratories that implemented the method.

Plans are being made for pilot studies, based on availability of suitable isolates/DNA/samples. Aim is to conduct three studies, and apply the method to different types of samples.

WP5-T3-sT1 Inter-laboratory comparison on the novel NGS-MLST method

The plans for this work were made and a panel of reference samples was prepared. An inter-laboratory comparison of the established novel NGS-MLST genotyping method will be based on this defined set of samples sent out to participating laboratories across Europe, to confirm that typing results are in agreement between different laboratories and to obtain information about the robustness and applicability of the method.

Additionally, ring trials focusing on the current state-of-the-art-genotyping method were organised - increasing our understanding of the genetic variation of the parasite in Europe as well as of the method, and supporting obtaining comparable results.

5.1.4.11.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

No deliverables and milestones with deadline during the first 9 months of 2022. All Deliverables have been submitted on time, all milestones reached on time. The list is available in 12M report of 2021.

5.1.4.11.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Contamination of Soil, Water, Fresh Produce, and Bivalve Mollusks with <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Oocysts: A Systematic Review. https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms10030517 https://zenodo.org/record/6351110#.YnkeCehBxwQ	YES	NO	YES, [details to be added]
A real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction for the specific detection of <i>Hammondia hammondi</i> and its differentiation from <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04571-8 https://zenodo.org/record/4647866#.YGNbWK8zaUk	YES	NO	YES, 2190 €
Expanding the Known Repertoire of C-Type Lectin Receptors Binding to <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Oocysts Using a Modified High-Resolution Immunofluorescence Assay https://doi.org/10.1128/mSphere.01341-20 https://zenodo.org/record/4657064#.YGXUY68zaUk	YES	NO	YES, 2130 €
Experimental infection with <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> in broiler chickens (<i>Gallus domesticus</i>): seroconversion, tissue cyst distribution, and prophylaxis https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-020-06984-x https://zenodo.org/record/4647895#.YGNbDT9JGU Shareable link: https://rdcu.be/chKFi	YES OHEJP is not mentioned under 'Funding', as the main authors are from external partners,	NO	NO But as FAIR as possible: a "shareable link" is provided by the Springer Nature SharedIt content-sharing initiative: https://rdcu.be/chKFi "Authors of original research"

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
	<p>participating at their own funding.</p> <p>OHEJP is acknowledged under 'Acknowledgments', stating: "AG, RB and GS are part of the TOXOSOURCES consortium, supported by funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 773830: One Health European Joint Programme."</p>		<p>articles: // Can post shareable links to view-only versions of their peer-reviewed research paper anywhere, including via social channels, institutional repositories and authors' own websites as well as scholarly collaborative networks" The metadata are available via Zenodo, together with the shareable link.</p> <p>This publication could be placed under 'additional output' in final report, if better fit there.</p>
<p>Expression of in vivo biotinylated recombinant antigens SAG1 and SAG2A from <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> for improved seroepidemiological bead-based multiplex assays 10.1186/s12896-020-00646-7 https://zenodo.org/record/4129949#.X6Ldr4hKjcc</p>	<p>YES</p>	<p>NO</p>	<p>YES, 1.890 €</p>

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Fluorescent bead-based serological detection of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> infection in chickens https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04244-6 https://zenodo.org/record/3974390#.X6PV0WhKjcc	YES	NO	YES, 1990 €
Infection prevention and control practices of ambulatory veterinarians: A questionnaire study in Finland https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.464 https://zenodo.org/record/4647937#.YGNfea8zaUk	YES	NO	YES, 0 €
Isolation and genetic characterization of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> in Spanish sheep flocks https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04275-z https://zenodo.org/record/3974417#.X6PWsWhKjcc	YES	NO	YES, 1990 €
Molecular Methods for the Detection of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Oocysts in Fresh Produce: An Extensive Review https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010167 https://zenodo.org/record/4647840#.YGNQk68zaUk	YES	NO	YES, 738.89 €
Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs (<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed <i>Besnoitia</i> species https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3 https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YHg5Z-gzaUk	YES, both TOXOSOURCES and MEME	NO	YES, 2190 € Open Access funding enabled and organized by project DEAL.
Isolation, Genotyping, and Mouse Virulence Characterization of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> From Free	YES	NO	YES, ND (= no data on fee)

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Ranging Iberian Pigs. https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.604782 https://zenodo.org/record/5516873#.YUg5qOxxe70			
In vivo and in vitro models show unexpected degrees of virulence among <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> type II and III isolates from sheep. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00953-7 https://zenodo.org/record/5516897#.YnkflehBxwQ	YES	NO	YES, ND
Comparison of Direct and Indirect <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Detection and Genotyping in Game: Relationship and Challenges. https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9081663 https://zenodo.org/record/5516907#.YUg8qOxxe70	YES	NO	YES, ND
Zoonotic pathogens in wild muskoxen (<i>Ovibos moschatus</i>) and domestic sheep (<i>Ovis aries</i>) from Greenland https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.599 https://zenodo.org/record/5516925#.YUhCMexxe70	YES	NO	YES, 1600 €
A longitudinal study of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> seroconversion on four large Danish sow farms. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109460 https://zenodo.org/record/5516957#.YUhCDexxe70	YES	NO	YES, ND

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Veterinarians as a risk group for zoonoses: exposure, knowledge and protective practices in Finland https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2021.10.008 [zenodo link to add]	YES	NO	YES, 0 EUR
The disease burden of ocular toxoplasmosis in Denmark in 2019: Estimates based on laboratory testing of ocular samples and on publicly available register data https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parepi.2021.e00229 https://zenodo.org/record/5595613#.YXZegxpBy70	YES	NO	YES, 1580 €
Identification of Oocyst-Driven Toxoplasma gondii Infections in Humans and Animals through Stage-Specific Serology—Current Status and Future Perspectives https://zenodo.org/record/5821931#.YdXABWCZOUk https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9112346	YES	NO	YES, 1647 €
Development and validation of a time-resolved fluorescence immunoassay for the detection of anti-Toxoplasma gondii antibodies in goats https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109432 https://zenodo.org/record/5812135#.YdVYmmjMKUk	YES	NO	NO Reasoning: not directly from the work plan of TOXOSOURCES, but co-authored by TOXOSOURCES co-funded colleagues, and the work supports and contributes to TOXOSOURCES (synergies). The authors have considered that using TOXOSOURCES funding for open-access publishing fee of this papers

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
			is not applicable, and other funding supporting the work did not cover Open Access publishing fees.
Seroprevalence of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> in outdoor dogs and cats in Bangkok, Thailand https://doi.org/10.1017/S0031182021000421 https://zenodo.org/record/5812133#.YdVZOGjMKUk	YES	NO	NO Reasoning: not directly from the work plan of TOXOSOURCES, but co-authored by TOXOSOURCES co-funded colleagues, and the work supports and contributes to TOXOSOURCES (synergies). The authors have considered that using TOXOSOURCES funding for open-access publishing fee of this papers is not applicable, and other funding supporting the work did not cover Open Access publishing fees.
Molecular survey of <i>Besnoitia</i> spp. (Apicomplexa) in faeces from European wild mesocarnivores in Spain https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14206 https://zenodo.org/record/5812123#.YdVZXWjMKUk	YES	NO	NO Reasoning: not directly from the work plan of TOXOSOURCES, but co-authored by TOXOSOURCES co-funded colleagues, and the work supports and contributes to TOXOSOURCES (synergies). The authors have considered that using TOXOSOURCES funding for open-access publishing fee of this papers is not applicable, and other funding

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
			supporting the work did not cover Open Access publishing fees.
Changes in serum biomarkers of inflammation in bovine besnoitiosis https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04991-0 https://zenodo.org/record/5812119#.YdVZe2jMKUk	YES	NO	YES, 1555 €, covered from other funding
Identification of molecular biomarkers associated with disease progression in the testis of bulls infected with <i>Besnoitia besnoiti</i> https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00974-2 https://zenodo.org/record/5812116#.YdVZo2jMKUk	YES	NO	YES, 2245 €, covered from other funding

Additional output

TOXOSOURCES is active in disseminating its outputs, with presentations to relevant audiences.

Invited talk at Mandagsmøde, Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology & Prevention, SSI, March 2, 2020:

How and why to prevent *Toxoplasma gondii* infections

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Oral presentation at OHEJPASM2020, May 27-29, 2020:

Source attribution for *Toxoplasma gondii* infections in Europe

Marieke Opsteegh (1), Hannah Morgan (1), Huifang Deng (1), Gereon Schares (2), Sandra Stelzer (2) Sara Monteiro Pires (3), Helga Waap (5), Jacek Sroka (6), Heidi Enemark (7), Jelena Srbljanovic (8), Olgica Djurkovic-Djakovic (8), Chiara Trevisan (9), Agnetha Hofhuis (1), Lasse S. Vestergaard (4), Pikka Jokelainen (4), Joke van der Giessen (1), Euro-FBP (COST Action FA1408), TOXOSOURCES Consortium

RIVM, The Netherlands (1); FLI, Germany (2); DTU, Denmark (3); SSI, Denmark (4); INIAV, Portugal (5); PIWET, Poland (6); NVI, Norway (7); UoB, Serbia (8); ITG, Belgium (9)

Poster at OHEJPASM2020, May 27-29, 2020:

TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen (1), Marieke Opsteegh (2), Marco Lalle (3), Furio Spano (3), Gereon Schares (4), Sara Monteiro Pires (5), Anne Mayer-Scholl (6), Frank Seeber (7), Simone M. Cacciò (3), Joke van der Giessen (2), TOXOSOURCES Consortium (Joint Research Project of the One Health European Joint Programme)

SSI, Denmark (1); RIVM, The Netherlands (2); ISS, Italy (3); FLI, Germany (4); DTU Food, Denmark (5); BfR, Germany (6); RKI, Germany (7)

[10.5281/zenodo.3924467](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3924467)

Poster and talk at 3-Minute-Thesis competition at OHEJPASM2020, May 27-29, 2020:

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to sausage and dry ham, a quantitative risk assessment

Filip DAMEK¹, Bastien FREMAUX², Dominique AUBERT³, Marieke OPSTEEGH⁴, Sandra VUILLERMET¹, Pikka JOKELAINEN⁵, Joke VAN DER GIESSEN⁴, Pascal BOIREAU¹, Isabelle VILLENA³, Radu BLAGA¹

¹ UMR BIPAR, Ecole Nationale Vétérinaire d'Alfort, ANSES, France ² IFIP - Institut du Porc, France ³ National Reference Center on Toxoplasmosis, Toxoplasma Biological Resources Center, CHU Reims and EA7510, SFR CAP-Santé, University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, USC EpiToxo ANSES, France ⁴ National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, The Netherlands ⁵ Statens Serum Institut, Denmark

Short oral presentation at One Health EJP Cogwheel workshop with JPIAMR, April 28, 2020:

#TOXOSOURCES *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Poster and short oral presentation in a webinar 'Toxoplasma gondii e toxoplasmosis in una prorspettiva One Health' organized by Italian Society of Parasitology (SOIPA), June 30, 2020:

TOXOSOURCES – TOXOplasma gondii SOURCES quantified

P JOKELAINEN¹, M OPSTEEGH², M LALLE³, F SPANO³, G SCHARES⁴, S MONTEIRO PIRES⁵, A MAYER-SCHOLL⁶, F SEEBER⁷, S M CACCIÒ³, J VAN DER GIESSEN², TOXOSOURCES CONSORTIUM (JOINT RESEARCH PROJECT OF THE ONE HEALTH EUROPEAN JOINT PROGRAMME)

1 Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark, 2 National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, Bilthoven, The Netherlands, 3 Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Rome, Italy, 4 Friedrich Loeffler Institute, Insel Riems, Germany, 5 Technical University of Denmark, Kongens Lyngby, Denmark, 6 German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment, Berlin, Germany, 7 Robert Koch Institute, Berlin, Germany

Two lectures at One Health EJP Summer School August 17-28, 2020:

Parasites in the food chain: global One Health risks

Wildlife and Public Health

Joke van der Giessen, RIVM, The Netherlands

Oral presentation at PhDay, October 14, 2020:

Desarrollo de un nuevo ELISA para la detección de anticuerpos frente a *Toxoplasma gondii* en el ganado porcino

Nadia María López Ureña, UCM, Spain

Invited talk at International One Health Webinar Series of School of Public Health and Zoonoses, Guru Angad Dev Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, India, November 5, 2020:

Relative contributions of the different sources of *Toxoplasma gondii*, a globally important pathogen of major public health concern

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Oral presentation at International Pathology Day, November 11, 2020:

Endemic pathogens and international research projects during a pandemic: *Toxoplasma gondii* and international research project TOXOSOURCES as an example

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark and Martha Betson, UoS, UK

Roundtable, International Pathology Day, November 11, 2020:

Discussion topic: Why international knowledge sharing is a winner

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Oral presentation at ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, November 12, 2020:

Toxoplasma gondii in Spanish farm animals: opening new avenues from genotype to phenotype

Mercedes Fernández-Escobar, UCM, Spain

Short oral presentation at One Health EJP Cogwheel workshop with SafeConsume, November 25, 2020:

TOXOSOURCES - *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Short oral presentation at 15th Workshop of the National Reference Laboratories for Parasites, December 15, 2020:

#TOXOSOURCES *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Oral presentations at TOXO-21 webinar, 2021

by Rafael Calero-Bernal and Pikka Jokelainen

Oral presentations at ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, February 18, 2021:

Selection, validation and SOP development of a molecular detection method for identification of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in leafy-green vegetables

Iva Slana¹, Nadja Bier², Borbara Bartosova¹, Gianluca Marucci³, Anne Mayer-Scholl², Pikka Jokelainen⁴, Marco Lalle³

A comparative study of the most widely used serological tests in the diagnosis of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in small ruminants

López-Ureña, Nadia María¹; Calero-Bernal, Rafael¹; Pazmiño-Bonilla, Elvis Daniel¹; Vázquez-Calvo, Ángela ²; Sánchez-Sánchez, Roberto¹; Ortega-Mora, Luis Miguel¹; Álvarez-García, Gema¹

Invited oral presentation at RSU conference, virtually in Riga, Latvia, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen

Poster presentation at CSBSP conference, virtually in Vilnius, Lithuania, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen

Presentation at internal dissemination events 'OHEJP at SSI' 4.5.2021 and 3.11.2021

Pikka Jokelainen

OHEJPASM 2021, June 9-11, 2021

Two oral presentations and several posters, including:

Fernández-Escobar, M.; Maksimov P.; Joeres, M.; Álvarez-García, G.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Calero-Bernal, R. Lights and shades in genotyping: European *Toxoplasma gondii* needs a closer look using harmonised approaches. *Annual Scientific 2021 OneHealthEJP*. 9th-11th June 2021. Poster.

Joeres, M.; Maksimov, P.; Tuschy, M.; Bärwald, A.; Conraths, F.J.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Cacciò, S.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G. Unprecedented Whole Genome Sequencing effort reveals highly polymorphic regions in the genome of European *Toxoplasma gondii* strains. *Annual Scientific 2021 OneHealthEJP*. 9th-11th June 2021. Poster.

Maksimov, P.; Cacciò, S.; Joeres, M.; Conraths, F.J.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G. Development of a Next-Generation Sequencing-based typing method for *Toxoplasma gondii* for European needs. *Annual Scientific 2021 OneHealthEJP*. 9th-11th June 2021. Oral.

Poster presentation at conference ‘Responsible Use of Antibiotics in Animals’

Infection prevention and control practices among ambulatory livestock and equine veterinarians

Marie Verkola¹, Terhi Järvelä¹, Asko Järvinen², Pikka Jokelainen^{3,4}, Anna-Maija Virtala⁴, Paula M. Kinnunen⁴, Annamari Heikinheimo^{1,5}

Keynote presentation at ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, June 24, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen

Oral presentation at ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, June 24, 2021

Environmental contamination with *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts: a systematic review

López-Ureña, Nadia María^{1‡}; Chaudhry, Umer^{2‡}; Calero-Bernal, Rafael¹; Messina, Davide²; Evangelista, Francisco²; Betson, Martha²; Lalle, Marco³; Jokelainen, Pikka⁴; Ortega-Mora, Luis Miguel¹; Álvarez-García, Gema¹

Poster presentation at annual conference of the German Veterinary Medical Society, section “Parasitology and Parasitic Diseases”, 28th to 30th June 2021

Development of a next-generation sequencing-based typing method to detect within-genotype variation in *Toxoplasma gondii*

M. Joeres¹, P. Maksimov¹, M. Tuschy¹, A. Bärwald¹, F. J. Conraths¹, B. Koudela^{2,3}, R. Blaga⁴, S. Cacciò⁵, M. Fernández-Escobar⁶, R. Calero-Bernal⁶, L. M. Ortega-Mora⁶, P. Jokelainen⁷, G. Schares¹

Poster presentations at WAAVP, Dublin, Ireland, July 2021

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to dry sausage

Filip Dámek¹, Bastien Fremaux², Dominique Aubert³, Marieke Opsteegh⁴, Sandra Thoumire¹, Sandra Vuillermet¹, Pikka Jokelainen⁵, Joke van der Giessen⁴, Pascal Boireau⁶, Isabelle Villena³, Radu Blaga¹

Toxoplasma gondii prevalence in animals in Europe: a systematic review

Filip Dámek¹, Helga Waap², Marieke Opsteegh³, Pikka Jokelainen⁴, Delphine Le Roux¹, Gunita Deksnė⁵, Huifang Deng³, Gereon Schares⁶, Arno Swart³, Anna Lundén⁷, Gema Álvarez-García⁸, Martha Betson⁹, Rebecca Davidson¹⁰, Adriana Gyorke¹¹, Sanne Stokman³, Daniela Antolová¹², Zuzana Hurníková¹², Henk Wisselink¹³, Jacek Sroka¹⁴, Siv Klevar¹⁵, Rob van Spronsen³, Radu Blaga¹

Endoparasites of feral cats in Denmark

Stine Thorsø Nielsen¹, Ida Sofie Thuesen¹, Søren Saxmose Nielsen¹, Peter Sandøe¹, Pikka Jokelainen², Christen Rune Stensvold², Michelle Bitsch Hardy¹, Nikoline Johansson¹, Heidi Huus Petersen³, Stig Milan Tamsborg¹, Helena Mejer¹

International workshop on molecular methods for *T. gondii* during summer 2021
teachers and participation from TOXOSOURCES.

One Health session of Project Review Module of ECDC's EPIET and EUPHEM programmes, August 25, 2021

Project presentation, chairing, participation in round table.

Poster presentation Zoonoses 2021 – International Symposium on Zoonoses Research “From Disease Ecology to SARS-CoV-2; Berlin, October 13-15, 2021

Identification of oocyst-driven *Toxoplasma gondii* infections through stage-specific serology – concepts and challenges

Gema Álvarez García ¹; Rebecca Davidson ²; Siv Klevar ²; Pikka Jokelainen ³

Luis Miguel Ortega Mora ¹; Furio Spano ⁴; Frank Seeber ⁵

EMOP 12-16 October

Several presentations, including:

Pikka Jokelainen TOXOSOURCES: *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen (invited duo-talk with Karen Shapiro) Wildlife as sentinels and indicators for transmission of *Toxoplasma gondii*

Joke van der Giessen Risk ranking and evaluation of surveillance systems for foodborne parasites in Europe.

Joke van der Giessen Public Health impact of foodborne parasite in a One Health approach

Filip Dámek *Toxoplasma gondii* seroprevalence in European wildlife: a systematic review

Filip Dámek Tropism of *Toxoplasma gondii* in the tissues of experimentally infected pigs

Nadia María LÓPEZ UREÑA^{1†}, Umer CHAUDHRY^{2†}, Rafael CALERO BERNAL¹, Davide MESSINA², Francisco EVANGELISTA², Martha BETSON², Marco LALLE³, Pikka JOKELAINEN⁴, Luis Miguel ORTEGA MORA¹, Gema ÁLVAREZ GARCÍA¹

Environmental contamination with *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts: a systematic review

Nadia María LÓPEZ UREÑA^{1†}, Rafael CALERO BERNAL¹, Ángela VÁZQUEZ CALVO², Patricia VÁZQUEZ ARBAIZAR², Nuria GONZÁLEZ FERNÁNDEZ¹, Radu BLAGA³, Bretislav KOUDELA^{4,5}, Luis Miguel ORTEGA MORA¹, Gema ÁLVAREZ GARCÍA¹

Comparative study of the serological tests used for the diagnosis of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in domestic pigs

Maksimov, P.; Caccio, S.; Joeres, M.; Conraths, F.J.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G. Genome-wide single nucleotide

variation in *Toxoplasma gondii* type II isolates from Europe. *13th European Multicollloquium of Parasitology*. Belgrade, Serbia, October (12-16), 2021. Oral.

DISCONTTOOLS seminar 20 October 2021

Gereon Schares et al.: DISCONTTOOLS expert group on zoonotic toxoplasmosis: many gaps identified, new diagnostics developments and vaccines are necessary for effective intervention

V SIMBRATOX -Brazilian Symposium of Toxoplasmosis and II SINTOX -International Symposium of Toxoplasmosis. Universidade Federal Rural de Rio de Janeiro. November, 2021.

Calero-Bernal, R. Invited speech: Methodologies for the study of *Toxoplasma gondii* genetic population structure: future perspectives.

OHEJPASM2021, Italy

Several presentations

TOXOMEETING 2022, USA

Two oral presentations

The 2nd International Workshop on Environmental Toxoplasmosis 2022, USA

Invited talk and trainee talk

OHEJP research seminar at DTU-FOOD, June 15 2022

Presentation of parasitology projects, Pikka Jokelainen

ONE2022

Poster presentations

International Conference of SafeConsume 27-28 June 2022

Invited oral presentation and round table discussion about DISH

ICOPA2022

Several presentations

Examples of other activities:

#TOXOSOURCES has been used on social media:

<https://twitter.com/hashtag/toxosources?f=live>

Participation in WomenInScience tweet of OHEJP 11.2.2021

Pikka Jokelainen, Joke van der Giessen

Interviewed to Pathologist-journal

Pikka Jokelainen

Interview for article in Finnish Cat Association on feline toxoplasmosis

Pikka Jokelainen

Contribution to Danish zoonosis report 2022

Artistic collaboration:

Pikka Jokelainen

Anni Puolakka: From the Heart (2021)

Single channel video, duration 14:14

The work has been / will be shown at Jyväskylä Art Museum, Tampere Film Festival, Baltic Triennial (Vilnius), HAM gallery / Helsinki Art Museum

<http://annipuolakka.com/fromtheheart/>

TOXOSOURCES partner institutes have also mentioned TOXOSOURCES in their communications, e.g.:

<https://www.ssi.dk/aktuelt/nyhedsbreve/epi-nyt/2020/uge-4---2020>

https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/Forsch/EJP_OH2020.html

<https://www.sva.se/forskning/internationellt-samarbete/europeisk-samverkan-kring-livsmedelsburna-smittor/toxosources-ett-one-health-ejp-projekt/>

https://www.bfr.bund.de/en/toxoplasma_gondii_sources_quantified_ejp_toxosource_-249310.html

<https://www.iss.it/en/web/iss-en/-/news-1>

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

- SOPs (final versions will be made available in 2022)
- Data from exposure survey (will be made available in connection to publication in 2022)
- Whole genome sequences of high number of *T. gondii* strains from Europe (will be made available in connection to publications in 2022)
- Video and factsheet from DISH collaboration (made available in 2022)

5.1.4.11.5 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

TOXOSOURCES builds largely on previous work and is actively looking for collaborations and synergies.

- An example of building on previous work is the building on the work performed within **COST-Action Euro-FBP**.
- Another example of building on previous work is that the TOXOSOURCES-WP3 work builds on work done in **project IMPACT** (Standardising molecular detection methods to IMprove risk assessment capacity for foodborne protozoan Parasites, using *Cryptosporidium* in ready-to-eat salad as a model organism”; Partnering Grant Project Grant Agreement Number GP/EFSA/ENCO/2018/03 – GA03).
- TOXOSOURCES addresses several key gaps identified in **DISCONTTOOLS** work - <https://www.discontools.eu/database/110-toxoplasmosis.html> and collaborates in the updating of the database. In 2021, TOXOSOURCES contributed to a poster presentation at DISCONTTOOLS Seminar.
- TOXOSOURCES collaborates with **SafeConsume project** (<http://safeconsume.eu/>). Both projects are interested in the relevance of *Toxoplasma gondii* contamination in fresh produce, with different focus: SafeConsume focuses on consumer behaviour on safe handling of fresh produce at home, whereas TOXOSOURCES WP3 focuses on fresh produce from harvest to packaging. TOXOSOURCES suggested OHEJP Cogwheel Workshop with SafeConsume, and it was organized on November 25, 2020. SafeConsume invited TOXOSOURCES to join a Horizon Results Booster group. Via this collaboration, TOXOSOURCES also established links with projects **Stance4Health**, **EAT2beNICE**, and **FOODSAFETY4EU**. In 2021, the collaboration was named ‘DISH’ and it produced a factsheet and video that was made public in 2022. Lunch webinar was held in April 2022, and TOXOSOURCES was invited to present at SafeConsume International Conference in June 2022. Collaboration continues.
- Collaboration with **International network for environmental Toxoplasma studies (INETS)** is another important established collaboration. INETS is a global network that organizes e.g. workshops. TOXOSOURCES will be presented at INETS workshop 2022.
- Collaboration with international colleagues on workshop on molecular methods during summer 2021.
- TOXOSOURCES has links to several PhD projects. For example, work in WP2 builds on the PhD work by Dr. Huifang Deng ‘Source attribution of human toxoplasmosis, A quantitative microbiological risk assessment approach’. **One Health EJP PhD project ToxSauQMRA** (PhD candidate Filip Damek) is closely linked to TOXOSOURCES. At RKI a recently started PhD project (David Warschkau) aims at establishing an *in vitro* model of oocyst generation in intestinal organoids by which antigens identified in WP4 will be further analysed for function/localization.
- There are collaborations with **other One Health EJP projects**, including **MEME**, **PARADISE**, **OH-Harmony-CAP**, **MATRIX**, **COHESIVE** and **ORION**. Synergies and complementary approaches have been identified.
- To enable and encourage collaborations, the QMRA models will be made available via a repository (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/rakip/>)
- **European Reference Laboratory of Parasites** and network of **National Reference Laboratories** are well represented in the consortium, and used for e.g. distributing request for sample collaboration. TOXOSOURCES work was presented at the annual workshop of 2021.

- The German EFSA Focal Point encouraged TOXOSOURCES to reach out to the **Focal Point network** to distribute the link to the survey gathering information on production and trade of fresh produce in Europe (TOXOSOURCES-WP3). Consumption of fresh produce is one of the possible routes of *Toxoplasma gondii* transmission to humans, which has been little explored to date. Thus, one aspect of the project is to investigate the presence of *T. gondii* in ready-to-eat fresh produce. The data will be used to evaluate the possible role of fresh produce as a source of *T. gondii* infection (quantitative microbiological risk assessment), and to design a sampling strategy for a multi-centre study investigating selected fresh produce for presence of *T. gondii* oocysts. Action on this was taken in early 2021, and the EFSA-contact of OHEJP was informed via OHEJP-WP5.
- WP5 development work for genotyping approach is suggested to be mentioned in 2021 report of OIE Collaborating Centre 'Zoonoses in Europe', FLI.
- TOXOSOURCES collaborates with and builds on the results of several national and regional projects.

5.1.4.12 JRP23-R2-FBZSH5-ADONIS

5.1.4.12.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

Salmonellosis remains the second most common zoonosis in humans in the EU and failed recent years to decrease further, or even increased, in some EU MSs despite a significantly long-term decreasing trend in human cases since 2008. The ADONIS project investigates at different levels (primary production, epidemiology, and the pathogen) possible underlying drivers for the change in Salmonella epidemiology.

On the primary production level measures implemented in the frame of the national control programs (NCPs) and information generated through these measures was evaluated using data from member states where partners in WP2 were located. Audit reports of the NCPs were extensively analysed in order to rank the type of flaws identified and type of recommendations made. Then, data on detection of *Salmonella* in poultry farms from one MS was used to identify factors associated with positive results in routine samplings, suggesting that farm (location, production type), animal (age) and sampling (season, sampler)-associated factors are associated with increased chance of detection of *Salmonella*. The framework developed will be used to analyse data from another country in 2022.

On the epidemiology level

- A detailed statistical analysis for the Netherlands and Belgium revealed that the incidence of *S. Enteritidis*, which is the dominant serotype, decreased significantly in both countries until 2015, followed by an upward trend, which was particularly pronounced in the Netherlands. Potential *S. Enteritidis* outbreaks in both countries and the fraction of invasive infections in the Netherlands also increased after 2015. From this we concluded that SE incidence in both the Netherlands and Belgium stopped decreasing as from 2015 onwards, when an increasing trend started. The increased occurrence of potential outbreaks and invasive infections since 2015 might partially explain the observed reversal of the trend.
- We evaluated the performance of the surveillance programs in Belgium and the Netherlands (that could maybe explain the observed changes in epidemiology). Both surveillance systems are characterized by a relatively high population coverage which changed only marginally between the time-periods 2006-2012 and 2013-2020. The observed change in Salmonella epidemiology can therefore not (or only partially) be explained from a change in surveillance systems.
- An exposure assessment regarding *S. Enteritidis* contamination of eggs, based on data from especially Spain, revealed the absence of a correlation of total exposure (product of prevalence

and microbiological load) with clinical incidence, indicating that changes in exposure are unlikely to explain observed changes in the *S. Enteritidis* epidemiology.

- We performed an analysis on the impact of the COVID19 pandemic on the incidence of Salmonellosis in The Netherlands which decreased significantly after March 2020 by roughly half of the incidence in the years 2016-2019. We noticed higher fractions of invasive infections and increased relative proportion of serotype Typhimurium and decreased proportion of Enteritidis. This led to decreased contributions of laying hens and increased contributions of pigs and cattle as sources of human infections. The observed changes probably reflect a combination of reduced exposure to *Salmonella* due to restrictions on international travels and gatherings, closure of dine-in restaurants, catering and hospitality sectors at large, and changes in healthcare-seeking and diagnostic behaviours.
- We conducted a source attribution study for Salmonella in the EU based on outbreak data using EFSA data. Overall, the most important food source was eggs (48%) followed by pork (10%), and (other) meat products (9%). Outbreaks caused by *S. Enteritidis* and other less common serotypes were mostly attributed to eggs (58% and 20% resp.) whereas outbreaks caused by *S. Typhimurium* and its monophasic variant were mainly attributed to pork (37%). There was a significant increase in the number of outbreaks, by 5% on average per year (IRR: 1.05, 95% CI: 1.01-1.09), between 2015 and 2019, which was mainly caused by an increase in Eastern Europe related to *S. Enteritidis* (and eggs).

On the pathogen level the project made a start with the genomics part by constructing a sequence inventory and a shared database from which analysis will be performed in order to assess potential changes in the population biology of *S. Enteritidis* on EU scale. Preliminary results suggest a role of plasmid content. *S. Enteritidis* is a quite clonal serotype and all methods are being tested to better analyze the population structure of Salmonella in the EU which will involve a population-genetic description (diversity, clonality, etc) as well as a phylodynamic analysis to identify recent clones that emerged.

The vast majority of strains belong to ST11 with the same content of 13 SPI. Of several major clusters identified some predominated prior to 2015, while the others seem to be more epidemiologically successful later on.

Finally, a framework for the multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) has been made, the criteria for the assessment of the possible explaining determinants for the changing *Salmonella* epidemiology have been defined. Two surveys regarding the weighting of criteria according to their importance and for scoring the different possible drivers according to the (weighted) criteria has been completed by the panel of experts. The MCDA modelling with this data will be performed in 2022.

5.1.4.12.1.1 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1 Project management

WP1-T1

Given the still challenging situation due to the pandemic and issues with capacity the project ran into some delays. These are expected to be cached up with the granted budget neutral extension.

WP1-T2

Reporting obligations has been fulfilled during the whole project.

WP2: Salmonella controls at the primary production level.

WP2-T1 Comparative analysis of Salmonella controls and management levels at MSs level

This task is largely completed (see 12M report 2021). Regarding the survey, data has been collected from partners based on a questionnaire. Information from each country has been analysed and deliverable submitted. Under this task, the revision of audit reports has been performed.

The analysis of NCP data has been done in Spain and more data from France about *Salmonella* control for about 9 years are to be analysed as extra analysis to replace the work scheduled under subtask 1 in T2 which cannot be performed because of the avian influenza crisis. From the NL, the data are very difficult to obtain, however many set of data, fragmented, will be used. The modelling framework developed to analyse NCP data from Spain will be adapted for the analysis of data obtained through the NCP from France, and results will be available in the second half of 2022.

WP2-T2 Comparative analysis of Salmonella controls and management levels at farm level

Collection of data about NCP in Poland is on a good way to be fulfilled in the coming months.

WP2-T3 On farm surveys

Five visits were scheduled in France and UK since 2020 but the Covid crisis followed by the avian influenza crisis for 2 successive years make it impossible to achieve the visits. As an alternative, the use of historical data would allow to perform the sensitivity analysis instead of the field data that was expected from the visits. Moreover, the outcomes of the literature search performed by WVBR are in line with the importance of the sensitivity analysis because of the variability observed among sampling within the NCP, investigations, etc.

WP3: Surveillance, epidemiology and source attribution.

The work in this WP is largely completed (see 12M report 2021).

WP3-T1 Evaluation of surveillance systems

This task was finalized during this reporting period. The main conclusion of this work, while assessing the Salmonella surveillance systems in The Netherlands and Belgium, is that evaluations of surveillance systems (although time consuming and often difficult) in recurrent cycles is highly recommended in order to correctly interpret incidence over time and conduct comparisons between countries.

Part of this work has been published as: Nina Van Goethem, An Van Den Bossche, Pieter-Jan Ceysens, Adrien Lajot, Wim Coucke, Kris Vernelen, Nancy H. C. Roosens, Sigrid C. J. De Keersmaecker, Dieter Van Cauteren, Wesley Mattheus. Coverage of the national surveillance system for human Salmonella infections, Belgium, 2016-2020. PLOS ONE: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256820>

WP3-T2 Assessment of changes in the epidemiology of human S. Enteritidis infections.

This task was finalized during this reporting period. Detailed time-series / regression analysis showed that SE incidence in both the Netherlands and Belgium stopped decreasing as from 2015 onwards, when an increasing trend started. The increased occurrence of potential outbreaks and invasive infections since 2015 might partially explain the observed reversal of the trend. While these factors provide insights into the possible causes of the stagnating trend, attention should also be given to factors influencing SE epidemiology at primary (animal) production and pathogen genomic levels.

[A manuscript describing these analyses is under rebuttal with Eurosurveillance].

We also determined the main food sources and recent trends of salmonellosis outbreaks in Europe. Overall, eggs remain the primary source of reported salmonellosis outbreaks, which increased significantly in occurrence from 2015 to 2019, particularly outbreaks caused by *S. Enteritidis* in Eastern European countries. Regional, temporal and serotype-associated differences in the relative contributions of the different sources were also observed.

[A manuscript is accepted by Journal of Food Microbiology]

Finally, we performed an analysis on the impact of the COVID19 pandemic on the incidence of Salmonellosis in The Netherlands. We showed a strong decrease in notified cases, primarily among travel-related cases. On the other hand we noted increased proportion of cases among older adults and increased proportion of invasive infections, decreased proportion of trimethoprim resistance, and increased proportion of serovar Typhimurium monophasic variant vs. Enteritidis.

[a paper has been published: Mughini Gras et al 2021, Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human salmonellosis in the Netherlands; *Epidemiology & Infection*, DOI: 10.1017/S0950268821002557]

WP3-T3 assessment of human exposure to S. Enteritidis

This task was finalized during this reporting period. Due to lack of data this was only performed for Spain. We showed a poor correlation between the number of human S. Enteritidis and the pre-treatment S. Enteritidis cases. This indicates that changes in human exposure to S. Enteritidis through consumption of eggs, which is the most important source of human S. Enteritidis infections, cannot explain the stagnating S. Enteritidis trend. Furthermore, the significance of import of eggs played a minor role in Spain. It remains uncertain how generable these results are for other countries.

WP4: Salmonella genomics

WP4-T1 collection overview

Completed. All partners are involved in WP4, especially in the collection of sequences. An inventory was created to get an overview of the available strains and sequences at each partner institution. The inventories were collated and presented at a teleconference held on 17 February 2020, where a decision was made on the final selection of strains to be sequenced for the genomic analyses.

The need of a MTA for sharing the sequences in order to analyse them in different partner laboratories, has significantly delayed the completion of the sequence sharing.

Country	Institute	No_isolates	No_sequences
Austria	AGES	245	193
Belgium	SCIENSANO	84	67
Denmark	SSI	220	213
England	PHE	142	124
France	ANSES	198	177
France	IP	65	64
Italy	ISS	45	44
Italy	IZSLER	30	26
Netherlands	RIVM	231	227
Netherlands	WBVR	45	45
Poland	PIWET	217	214
Portugal	INIAV	39	39
Portugal	INSA	63	59
Spain	VISAVET	177	74
United Kingdom	APHA	58	48
Wales	PHE	3	3
Total	NA	1862	1617

WP4-T2 Population structure and comparative genomics

High quality WG sequences have been used to generate cgMLST profiles. The majority of the sequences belonged to ST11 and these will be used in further population structure analyses. The structure of the population has been assessed using a gene-based pangenome reconstruction approach (panaroo) and

a core-genome nucleotide variant calling approach (snippy). Detailed insight in the bacterial population structure has been obtained by specific scanning for antimicrobial resistance genes (resfinder) and point mutations (pointfinder) and their association with the plasmid (plasmidfinder) and prophage (phaster) content. Further planned analyses include identification of prophages, insertion sequences and transposons. The results of the analyses are being constantly uploaded on the server of SSI, and will be made available in a public link within the next month.

WP4-T3 Phylodynamics and phylogeography

This task will be performed and completed the second half of 2022.

WP4-T4 Mutant creation and Testing — including GWAS studies

GWAS and machine learning are planned for the second half of the year.

WP5: MCDA model to support priority setting

WP5-T1 Framework building

Completed.

WP5-T2 MCDA modelling

We obtained the expert elicitation results for the assessment of weights for the MCDA modelling. Regarding the weights determinants possibly explaining the stagnating downward trend of Salmonella incidence, experts ranked the importance of “weight of evidence” as most important, followed by “consistency of findings”, “effect size” and “plausibility”. Regarding the criteria for interventions to reverse the non-decreasing trend, experts ranked “public health impact” as most important, followed by “feasibility”, “cost-effectiveness” and “novelty/originality”.

The scoring of the potential determinants of the non-decreasing trend and of the interventions to reverse this trend has been performed by the panel of experts and the data has been analysed. The final modelling phase of the MCDA is therefore being performed and will be finalized in June 2022.

5.1.4.12.2 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
23	D-JRP23-WP1.3	Y4 report delivered	M51		60	Following project extension	
23	D-JRP23-WP1.4	Result dissemination plan developed	M54		60	Following project extension	
23	D-JRP26-WP2.2	MS's specific analysis of temporal trend of Salmonella in poultry flocks	M42	M52		10.5281/zenodo.6811500	
23	D-JRP26-WP2.3	Recommendations for improving Salmonella surveillance in poultry flocks	M50		M60	End of the project (incl. extension)	
23	D-JRP26-WP2.4	Recommendations for improving Salmonella surveillance in poultry flocks	M58		M60	End of the project (incl. extension)	
23	D-JRP#-3.1	Description of surveillance systems regarding their key elements	M50	M50		10.5281/zenodo.6226393	
23	D-JRP#-3.2	Description of basic epidemiological characteristics of human S.	M50	M50		10.5281/zenodo.7082442	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		Enteritidis cases and other relevant serovars					
23	D-JRP26-WP3.3	Report on the evaluation of the surveillance systems' attributes	M50	M50		10.5281/zenodo.6226393	
23	D-JRP#-3.4	Extended the report on epidemiological characteristics with results from the rarefaction analysis the refined source attribution models, but also with data on food consumption patterns	M50	M50		10.5281/zenodo.7082442	
23	D-JRP#-3.5	Report on human S. enteritidis exposure in different countries and time periods	M50	M50		10.5281/zenodo.7082418	
23	D-JRP23-WP4.2	List of genetic determinants associated with the change in Salmonella incidence in Europe	M51		M59	End of the project (incl. extension)	
23	D-JRP23 WP5.2	Experts elicitation results for the assessment of weights.	M50	M50		10.5281/zenodo.6325485	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
23	D-JRP23 WP5.3	Outcomes of the MCDA analysis.	M52	M56		10.5281/zenodo.6786081	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
23	M-JRP26-4	Farm survey planed and questionnaires developed	M30	YES	M36	
23	M-JRP26-7	Sequence collection to be shared amongst partners	M44	YES	M47	
23	M-JRP26-8	Phylogenetic trees describing the sequence collection (D-JRP#-WP4.1)	M44	NO	M60	The project extension allowed to perform additional analyses. In progress.
23	M-JRP23-16	Final meeting organised	M54	NO	M60	Planned at dec 1 and 2 in Pulawy, Poland

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JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
23	M-JRP23-17	Data finalized for manuscript on Phylodynamics and Phylogeography	M51	NO	M60	The project extension allowed to perform additional analyses. In progress.
23	M-JRP23-18	Data finalized for manuscript on phenotypes	M54	NO	M60	The project extension allowed to perform additional analyses. In progress.
23	M-JRP23-19	Publication of sequence collection on European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)	M54	NO	M60/61	The project extension allowed to perform additional analyses. In progress.

5.1.4.12.3 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Mughini Gras et al 2021, Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human salmonellosis in the Netherlands; <i>Epidemiology & Infection</i> , DOI: 10.1017/S0950268821002557	Yes	https://zenodo.org/record/6090653	Yes (2500 euros)
Nina Van Goethem, An Van Den Bossche, Pieter-Jan Ceyssens, Adrien Lajot, Wim Coucke, Kris Vernelen, Nancy H. C. Roosens, Sigrid C. J. De Keersmaecker, Dieter Van Cauteren, Wesley Mattheus. Coverage of the national surveillance system for human <i>Salmonella</i> infections, Belgium, 2016-2020. <i>PLOS ONE</i> : https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256820	Yes	https://zenodo.org/record/6090759	Yes
Samper-Cativiela C., Dieguez-Roda B., Trigo da Roza F., Ugarte-Ruiz M., Elnekave E., Lim S., Hernandez M., Abad D., Collado S., Saez J.L., de Frutos C., Agüero M., Moreno M.A., Escudero J.A., Alvarez J. Genomic characterization of multi drug resistant of <i>Salmonella</i> serovar Kentucky ST198 isolated in poultry flocks in Spain (2011-2017). <i>Microbial Genomics</i> 8(3) (doi: 10.1099/mgen.0.000773)	Yes	https://zenodo.org/record/7082555	Yes (1500 GBP)

Additional output

Kamińska et al. ADONIS in Poland – the phylogeny structure of a countrywide and temporal collection of Salmonella Enteritidis. Abstract I3S congress.

Oral presentation

Characterization of the emergence of multidrug-resistant Salmonella Kentucky ST198 in poultry flocks in Spain. Samper-Cativiela Clara 1,2, Diéguez-Roda Bernabé 3, Trigo da Roza Filipa 2,4, Ugarte-Ruiz María 1, Elnekave Ehud 5, Lim Seunghyun 6,7, Hernández Marta 8, Abad David 8, Collado Soledad 9, Saez José Luis 9, de Frutos Cristina 10, Agüero Montserrat 10, Moreno Miguel Á2, Escudero José Antonio 1,2,4, Álvarez Julio 1,2* 1 VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre, Complutense University of Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain 2 Department of Animal Health, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Complutense University of Madrid 28040 Madrid, Spain 3 TRAGSATEC, Tecnologías y Servicios Agrarios S.A, 28037 Madrid, Spain. 4 Molecular Basis of Adaptation, Department of Animal Health, Faculty of Veterinary, Complutense University of Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain. 5 Koret School of Veterinary Medicine, The Robert H. Smith Faculty of Agriculture, Food and Environment, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, 76100 Rehovot, Israel 6 Department of Veterinary Population Medicine, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Minnesota, Saint Paul, 55455 Minnesota, USA 7 Bioinformatics and Computational Biology Program, University of Minnesota, Rochester, 55455 Minnesota, USA 8 Molecular Biology and Microbiology Laboratory, Instituto Tecnológico Agrario de Castilla y León (ITACyL), Junta de Castilla y León, 47009 Valladolid, Spain 9 Subdirección General de Sanidad e Higiene Animal y Trazabilidad, Dirección General de la Producción Agraria, Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 28010 Madrid, Spain. 10 Laboratorio Central de Veterinaria, Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 28110 Madrid, Spain

Poster presentation

Putting Salmonella Enteritidis in Spain in context using Whole Genome Sequencing: understanding persistence of specific strains and antimicrobial resistance determinants across hosts and over time. Samper-Cativiela Clara 1,2, Diéguez-Roda Bernabé 3, Herrera-León Silvia4, Ugarte-Ruiz María 1, De Frutos Cristina 5, Agüero Monserrat 5, Sáez José Luis6, Moreno Miguel Ángel 1, 2, Álvarez Julio 1,2 1 VISAVET, Health Surveillance Centre, Universidad Complutense, Madrid, Spain 2 Departamento de Sanidad Animal, Facultad de Veterinaria, Universidad Complutense, Madrid, Spain. 3 TRAGSATEC, Tecnologías y Servicios Agrarios S.A, Madrid, Spain. 4Laboratorio de Referencia e Investigación en Enfermedades Bacterianas Transmitidas por Alimentos, Centro Nacional de Microbiología, Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Madrid, Spain 5 Laboratorio Central de Veterinaria (LCV Algete), Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, Madrid, Spain. 6 Subdirección General de Sanidad e Higiene Animal y Trazabilidad, Dirección General de la Producción Agraria, Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, Madrid, Spain

Poster presentation

Factors associated with increased Salmonella positivity in the frame of National Control Plans (NCPs) in poultry flocks. A case study of laying hen Spanish data. Álvarez Julio 1,2, Prieto María Esther 3, Collado Soledad 3, Saéz José Luis 3, Samper-Cativiela Clara 1,2 1VISAVET, Health Surveillance Centre, Universidad Complutense, Madrid, Spain. 2Departamento de Sanidad Animal, Facultad de Veterinaria, Universidad Complutense, Madrid, Spain.3Subdirección General de Sanidad e Higiene Animal y Trazabilidad, Dirección General de la Producción Agraria, Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, Madrid, Spain

OHEJP ASM, Orvieto, Italy

Poster presentation

Characterization of plasmid-mediated resistance in Salmonella Enteritidis. L. Torre-Fuentes¹ • S. Holtsmark Nielsen² • E. Kamińska³ • E. Njamkepo⁴ • L. Petrovska-Holmes⁵ • C. Samper Cativiela¹ • J. Álvarez^{1,6}

1. VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre, Universidad Complutense, Madrid, Spain • 2. Section for Foodborne Infections, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark • 3. Department of Omics Analyses, National Veterinary Research Institute, Puławy, Poland • 4. Unité des bactéries pathogènes entériques, Institut Pasteur, Université de Paris, Centre National de Référence des Escherichia coli, Shigella et Salmonella, Paris, France • 5. UK Animal and Plant Health Agency, Addlestone, Surrey, United Kingdom • 6. Departamento de Sanidad Animal, Facultad de Veterinaria, Universidad Complutense, Madrid, Spain.

Oral presentation I3S Salmonella congres June 2022

Temporal trends and epidemiological patterns of antimicrobial resistance in human Salmonella enterica isolates in the Netherlands, 2008 to 2019

Linda CHANAMÉ PINEDO (The Netherlands)

Oral presentation I3S Salmonella congres June 2022

Risk factors and within-patient evolution of persistent non-typhoidal Salmonella infections

Roan PIJNACKER (The Netherlands)

5.1.4.13 JRP24-R2-FBZSH9-BeONE

5.1.4.13.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

The BeONE project develops an integrated surveillance dashboard where molecular and epidemiological data for foodborne pathogens can be interactively analysed, visualised and interpreted by relevant experts across disciplines and sectors.

The construction of the BeONE dataset, which includes genomes and metadata representing isolates of the four foodborne pathogens *L. monocytogenes*, *S. enterica*, *E. coli* and *C. jejuni*, was finalised adding up to 4,438 isolates. The genome data of this final dataset was assembled and the quality assured resulting in a diverse (and representative) dataset applicable for testing cluster congruence, novel algorithms, metadata structures, the BeONE dashboard etc. in the various WPs. Based on this dataset the pipelines used for clustering by the 12 partners will soon be evaluated to assess the cluster congruence, and for this purpose the bioinformatics tool, ReportTree, was recently developed.

The finalised BeONE outbreak detection algorithm, which was previously tested on *Listeria*, will be applied to the remaining target pathogens, and the evaluation is still ongoing.

A BeONE data model was finalised to accommodate epidemiological metadata, quality assessed WGS metrics and cgMLST fingerprints. Minimal information requirements were defined to allow for phylogenetic analyses and subsequent outbreak detection, while the data model is open to hold additional, non-harmonized information for further exploration. The BeONE data model was integrated into a MongoDB database structure based on SSIs Bifrost system to facilitate automated, distributed database synchronization between partners. For data protection and fine-grained control over data exchange, a collection of tools for data filtering and encryption is provided. A BeONE database API allows synchronization between, and queries of, local and remote databases, respectively. The utilization of the EFSA DCF ontology for encoding BeONE epidemiological data allowed a tight co-development with the upcoming EFSA WGS data model which itself aims at cross-sector harmonization with the ECDC.

The plan for the BeONE Dashboard construction was changed due to delays on the Danish platform SOFI, to which BeONE was synchronised, as well as due to personnel changes (as no one could produce

the necessary code). Now, the dashboard is being developed without being dependent on a specific backend. In this way, the dashboard can be used with data generated by different platforms. The dashboard input format builds on the JSON format that can be extracted from the MongoDB (used in the previously described backend). Currently, the BeONE dashboard enables the user to load such JSON files, to select relevant data for visualisation, to view selected data in a table format, to select and filter entries, as well as to load a newick file for viewing phylogenetic trees. Features of the dashboard have been (and will be) continuously tested and biweekly technical meetings are being held, where new features are discussed in detail. Github is used for depositing the code developed, and here the people involved can comment on issues. Lastly, google forum is used to obtain feedback from testers and both written documentation and youtube tutorials have been made available as instruction material.

5.1.4.13.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1: Typing comparability and nomenclature

JRP24-WP1-T1 Establishment of state of the art

Status: Completed

As reported in the 12M report (Y4), this task was completed in collaboration with the ORION project (deliverable available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5155570>). In particular, the BeONE contributions were mainly focused on describing start-to-end workflows for routine genome-based surveillance of the four foodborne bacterial species under study (*Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli* and *Campylobacter jejuni*), with emphasis on identifying challenges and opportunities for harnessing WGS as a key tool for One Health Surveillance. The final output is an online handbook covering the main technical and practical aspects associated with the application of WGS for foodborne diseases surveillance. By following a simple and straightforward writing and structure, this document can be easily understandable by laboratory staff starting in the field, thus helping national and local labs to build capacity and competence on the use of NGS methods for surveillance purposes. The One Health Sequencing for Surveillance HandBook is available at <https://oh-sfs-handbook.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.

JRP24-WP1-T2 Dataset selection and curation

Sub-Task: WP1-T2-ST1 Dataset selection and collection

Status: Completed

This task had the objective of compiling a dataset (including sequencing reads and respective metadata) that captures the genomic diversity within the populations of the four foodborne pathogens (*L. monocytogenes*, *S. enterica*, *E. coli* and *C. jejuni*), including samples from human, food and veterinary sources and sets of epidemiologically verified outbreak isolates. In particular, this dataset is intended to be used for: i) cluster congruence analysis between the different partner's pipelines (WP1); ii) testing novel algorithms (combining genomic and epidemiological data) for outbreak detection (WP2); iii) testing metadata structures and the compliance and viability of the metadata combination from different sectors and regions (WP3); iv) testing both the dashboard and the database, and analysis of the backend (WP3/4); and v) testing the behaviour of the system to handle epi-data from different countries in a user-oriented manner (WP4). Therefore, it required a close collaboration with all the BeONE partners, which were requested to share anonymized data under the compliance of a signed Material Transfer Agreement (MTA). The MTA was circulated a priori for revision and final acceptance. This task also involved that everything was set up at NVI's server SAGA for data upload, storage and analysis. Data submission was performed following guidelines for data upload (account login, anonymization, and transfer of data), which included specific instructions to fill a metadata submission form elaborated using EFSA Data Collection Framework for Controlled Vocabularies in collaboration with WP3. A final step for read anonymization including rename of sequencing reads and shuffling

their order in the file was performed. Since the Y4 12M report, the BeONE dataset was enriched, now comprising a total of 4,438 isolates [*L. monocytogenes* (n=1,513), *S. enterica* (n=1,786), *E. coli* (n=400) and *C. jejuni* (n=739)]. The BeONE dataset is considered as complete, being open for usage within the frame of BeONE activities (and in compliance with the MTA). Before the end of the project, this dataset will be publicly released for usage by the general scientific community, always in compliance with the MTA. The WP1-T2-ST1 deliverable is available at ZENODO link ([10.5281/zenodo.5808832](https://zenodo.org/record/5808832)).

Sub-Task: WP1-T2-ST2 Quality check and assurance, and genome assembly

Status: Completed

This subtask was redefined and inserted within WP1-T3 activities. In particular, it involved quality control/filtering of the sequencing reads, confirmation of species identification (and contamination checking), genome assembly and in silico typing (i.e. the classification of microorganisms at intra-species level). In order to optimise this task, an additional effort was made (in collaboration with WP3) to refine the genome assembly process not only regarding the running time and resources' allocation, but also to decrease the amount of unnecessary temporary data generated by the assembler. The delay associated with this additional work was compensated by its increased assembly efficiency.

JRP24-WP1-T3 Clustering congruence and thresholds

Sub-Task: WP1-T3-ST1 Selection of WGS-based typing methods to be evaluated

Status: Completed

The selection of WGS-based typing methods to be evaluated started at the BeONE Kick Off Meeting where a survey was performed to assess which institutions would be available to participate in the analysis, i.e. include their routine pipeline for genomic surveillance and outbreak investigation of the four foodborne pathogens. All partners (12 institutions, because PHE has left the project) confirmed their availability to participate in this exercise and each partner will be responsible for their pipeline installation and running on SAGA (or locally), with full support of WP1/WP3 teams. Additional details regarding each of the pipelines, such as its nature (assembly-based or mapping-based), clustering method, cluster definition and output format were requested. This information was used to i) identify overlap between the different pipelines and establish a strategy to increase the efficiency of the analysis; and ii) develop the necessary bioinformatics strategies to deal with the output heterogeneity and obtain a desired typing data to pursue with the subsequent sub-task. Furthermore, information regarding the partner's availability to run the pipeline locally or on SAGA was assessed. This information was also crucial to determine the list of pipelines that require installation on SAGA, and estimate the computational and storage needs. After this assessment, additional resources were requested. In summary, the clustering congruence analysis (WP1-T3-ST2) will count on the participation of all the BeONE partners, and will include eight assembly-based pipelines and four SNP-based pipelines, among which there are widely used commercial and non-commercial software.

WP1-T3-ST2 Assessing clustering congruence between different methods at different hierarchical levels

Status: Ongoing

With the completion of WP1-T2 and WP1-T3-ST1, we were able to move forward with this task and the setup of the different pipelines is currently ongoing. For the "Cluster congruence" dataset collection, an assessment of the sequencing data available at ENA/SRA was performed. Moreover, isolate typing data from public databases, such as Enterobase or PubMLST, as well as from major scientific publications of the field was collected and used as a complement to the BeOne dataset in order to build a "Cluster congruence" dataset with a proper representativeness of the diversity within each species. The selected public dataset was curated following the same procedure as described for the BeONE dataset (see WP1-T2-ST2). As mentioned in the previous 12M report, meanwhile, we have already developed bioinformatics pipelines to automatize the clustering congruence analysis.

Specifically, we developed ReporTree (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>; <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-1404655/v1>), a bioinformatics tool that besides providing samples' clustering information at all possible genetic distances, using a wide variety of inputs (e.g., cgMLST allele matrix, SNP-core alignment, phylogenetic tree) and different clustering methods (hierarchical clustering or MSTree implemented in GrapeTree), also allows the comparison of this clustering information between the different genetic distances. ReporTree can integrate this genetic information with the available strain metadata (e.g. epidemiological, demographic, microbiological), providing surveillance-oriented reports. Moreover, we are developing an additional script that is able to: i) identify threshold levels of clustering stability for each method; ii) compare the congruence between methods and ultimately define threshold ranges showing clustering convergence. Following the FAIR principles, all these tools are publicly available in github:

<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>
<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ComparingPartitions>

WP1-T3-ST3 Correlating clustering congruence with existing nomenclature schemes

Status: Ongoing

The completion of this sub-task depends on the completion of WP1-T3-ST2. As described in this task, the developed scripts are adjusted to allow a rapid comparison of the clustering profiles obtained at different threshold levels and the strains grouping defined by existing nomenclatures.

WP2: Joining molecular and epidemiological methods

JRP24-WP2-T1: Conceptualization of epidemiological and biological factors impacting on fine resolution clustering and outbreak detection

Status: Completed

A conceptual model of the factors impacting fine resolution clustering and outbreak detection has been made and explained in detail in a draft manuscript which is now undergoing the last revision round with the co-authors. The abstract hereof was submitted as deliverable to Zenodo and the OHEJP online platform.

JRP24- WP2-T2: Integrating genomics with epidemiology

Status: Ongoing

Cluster detection based on WGS often assumes that the various isolates come from a common source and that the source is clonal in nature i.e. the population of the bacterial pathogen at the source is genetically homogeneous. Thus, all the isolates pertaining to a cluster can be traced back to a most recent common ancestor, which, in epidemiological terms, means that patients that share highly similar strains are likely to have contracted these from a common source. Challenges still remain regarding the epidemiological interpretation of WGS. A major point of uncertainty is the definition of clusters. To this end we have developed a multitier algorithm that incorporates concepts of evolutionary biology. For compatibility with the currently used molecular typing system – cgMLST, Hamming distance, and single-linkage hierarchical clustering (sl) – the first step follows this procedure. The use of single linkage combined with a variable number of missing loci for each isolate allows, however, for allelic distances within a cluster much exceeding the predefined threshold of allelic dissimilarities. Furthermore, the structural unit of DNA is not the gene but the nucleotide, which means that allelic distances may be in fact an underestimation of the dissimilarity among isolates. We thus use a second step involving SNP-calling, pairwise Hamming distances, and Gaussian mixture models to split potential multimodal distributions of pairwise dissimilarities, which are often indicative of multiple clusters. Additionally, in a third step we calculate the expected SNP distances between any two or n (multiple coalescent) isolates based on Kingman's coalescent model of shared ancestry. In a fourth step, the comparison of the distribution of observed dissimilarities with the expected one is expressed as the probability that the two or n selected isolates come from a common ancestor in a

given timespan. The summarised WP2-T2 deliverable (D2.2) (<https://zenodo.org/record/6375255#.YjmYpjXcCUI>). The testing of the algorithm is still ongoing and expected to be finalised by M50. A draft manuscript (D2.3) describing the algorithm and its testing is expected to be delivered by M58.

JRP24- WP2-T2-ST1 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates

Status: Ongoing

Progress has been made in this task by partner SSI (13) with identification of several clusters/outbreaks and evidence that a successful surveillance programme can be based on sampling a relatively small fraction (10%) of the cases (DOI: 10.3201/eid2603.190947). Testing of the developed algorithm is expected to be finalized by M58.

JRP24- WP2-T2-ST2 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the Shiga toxin producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC) isolates

Status: Ongoing

We have assembled the dataset of epidemiologically validated outbreak isolates with available WGS and detailed epidemiological metadata; this is expected to be used in testing the algorithm by M58.

JRP24- WP2-T2-ST3 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the *Salmonella enterica* isolates

Status: Ongoing

We have assembled several datasets, corresponding to outbreaks of various *Salmonella enterica* serovars: *Salmonella enterica* serovars Enteritidis, Thompson, Typhimurium, and Heidelberg, that will be used in the validation process.

JRP24- WP2-T2-ST4 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the *Listeria monocytogenes* isolates

Status: Completed

We have applied the above mentioned algorithm to a dataset of *Listeria monocytogenes* CC6, containing isolates epidemiologically validated as part of an outbreak in The Netherlands. In our example, the cluster defined with the broad threshold of ten alleles dissimilarity (often used in practice) is subsetted in the second step to a cluster corresponding to seven alleles and in a third step to one corresponding to four alleles difference. Additionally, our analyses indicate that inclusion of WG sequences from other sectors (i.e. food safety) is highly desirable if not mandatory for accurate cluster identification. The results will soon be available in the deliverable document at ZENODO.

JRP24- WP2-T3: Definition of guidelines for cluster investigation

Status: Ongoing

In developing the algorithm at WP2-T2 (D2.2) (<https://zenodo.org/record/6375255#.YjmYpjXcCUI>) we have used various data sources (e.g. cgMLST and SNP) and methods (e.g. hierarchical clustering, maximum likelihood), and have identified strengths and weaknesses of their usage in daily practice. A comparison of the respective methods as well as prospective improvements to cluster detection are being compiled into a document expected to be delivered by M58.

JRP24- WP3: Storage, management, and sharing for meta- and molecular data

JRP24- WP3-T1: Evaluate national level data sharing

Status: Completed (see 12M REPORT 2020)

JRP24- WP3-T2: Metadata acquisition and standardisation

Subtask: WP3-T2-ST1 Metadata acquisition

Status: Completed (see 9M REPORT 2021)

Subtask: WP3-T2-ST2 Standardization using ontologies

Status: Completed (see 12M REPORT 2021)

JRP24- WP3-T3: Database design and implementation

Subtask: WP3-T3-ST1 Determine and implement data structure for database

Status: Completed

Database structures have been established for WGS data. Mandatory fields narrow down to cgMLST profile allele hashes, species names, country of origin and year of sampling. Additionally, it is strongly advised to fill a number of optional data fields, including results from Quality Control, computational steps and epidata at a higher spatiotemporal resolution within the limits of an MTA. Database design regarding Epidata has also been finalized. The epidata structure is based on the EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) catalogues using preselected fields (see JRP24- WP3-T2-ST2). The metadata implementation allows to combine the hierarchical terms of the DCF catalogues in a tag-like fashion to improve their joint descriptive accuracy. Each hierarchical term is stored as a term lineage within the data model including hierarchical level information to improve automated filtering and annotation of phylogenetic models. The BeONE data model has been incorporated into the SSI Bifrost database structure to benefit from Bifrost's MongoDB metadata handlers. Nevertheless, the BeONE module is independent of other Bifrost's modules tailored to the requirements of SSI, e.g. WGS data computation. A documentation of the database setup is available at the BeONE API repository (https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone).

subtask: JRP24- WP3-T3-ST2 Implement API for import of data

Status: Completed

Due to personnel changes at SSI, where the API was to be developed as part of the Bifrost system, we redesigned the data import structure, as also mentioned in JRP24- WP4-T3. As a proof of concept, data from local partners will be transformed into JSON files following the data structure determined in JRP24- WP3-T3-ST1. Data will then be exported, symmetrically encrypted, sent to partners and then decrypted on their end to add it to their local database. In detail, the BeONE API repository (https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone) provides scripts to import from and export to the BeONE JSON format. These scripts serve as a bridge between the BeONE MongoDB and the BeONE dashboard until live database queries are established (see JRP24- WP3-T3-ST6).

Data in transit as well as in public databases may be encrypted in a field- and detail-specific manner to preserve privacy and to control the information exchange between partners. Bilateral data sharing agreements determine the level of detail that can be decrypted and used for epidemiological analyses. For epidata described by terms of the EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) catalogues, each hierarchical level is paired with a cryptographic key to allow a fine-grained control over shared information. Scripts for en-/decryption, keyring generation and field filtering are available and documented in the BeONE API repository. Data exchange between distributed BeONE MongoDBs is facilitated by recurring execution of synchronization scripts to allow surveillance with a minimum of lag time. An implementation of this system was presented to BeONE partners during the BeONE workshop held at the SSI in June 2022.

JRP24- WP3-T3-ST3 Data porting from an existing pipeline

Status: Completed (see 12M REPORT 2021)

JRP24- WP3-T3-ST4 Data porting from further pipelines

Status: Delayed

The BeONE data model was designed with compatibility to a number of different pipelines in mind. The highest congruency in harmonization was achieved with the EFSA WGS data model. Its development coincided with the finalization of the BeONE data model and yielded reciprocal refinement. As a second compatible example pipeline, the outputs of Bifrost will be ported into the BeONE system. Development of this latter bridge has started.

JRP24- WP3-T3-ST5 Expansion of the API for referencing/exporting of entries in other reference databases

Status: Cancelled

Due to both time and trouble with the ENA API we have chosen to cancel this task. It will be moved to sustainability.

JRP24- WP3-T3-ST6 Expansion of the API for queries from the dashboard WP4

Status: Delayed

We are still working on the plan for how these queries should be made. For small datasets, the frontend should allow manual selection of samples destined for immediate backend processing and visualization of results in the dashboard. For large datasets, phylogenetic distance matrices have to be updated and held available to the dashboard in regular intervals due to their computational expense. A preliminary BeONE API (<https://test.pypi.org/project/beoneapi/>) includes functions to synchronize databases and to retrieve quality-controlled cgMLST fingerprints for backend processing.

JRP24- WP3-T4: National data sharing pilot

Status: Completed

Along with the development of the BeONE data exchange system, the national data sharing pilot was preferred and slightly readjusted. In collaboration with FLI, isolates of *Salmonella enterica* serotype Dublin were exchanged between the BfR and the FLI, responsible for Food Safety and Animal Health respectively. Data was clustered using cgMLST based on ChewieSnake and SNP-Clustering and cluster congruency was determined. A publication on this work is planned. Additionally, German federal state public health agents were trained in the usage of a WGS surveillance platform that featured data collection in the BeONE data model format via the BfR pipelines AQUAMIS and ChewieSnake. In this workshop, held at the LGL Oberschleißheim in May 2022, the BeONE MongoDB was presented as an automated information exchange system while emphasizing the ease of data submission to superordinate agencies for surveillance on the national and European level.

WP4: Development of a user-oriented interface (dashboard) for analysis and sharing of epi and molecular data

JRP24- WP4-T1 Dashboard

A preliminary version of the BeONE Dashboard was developed in the first half of 2022. It builds on the work done in WP3 with developing a standardised JSON-based data format for hierarchical structuring of analysis results, and metadata related to samples.

We have decided on an approach where the dashboard is developed as a stand-alone application, which the user can download and install on his or her own computer. This standalone application supports Windows, MacOS, and Linux computers and all major web browsers in recent versions. The source code is published on GitHub on this url: <https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard>. The major advantages of this approach over developing the dashboard as an integrated part of a client/server web application are:

- Test users can easily be incorporated in the project for continuous testing and do not need access to a server platform. Instead they are only required to download and install the stand-

alone application which can be done without any special technical skills and even without administrator permissions. This makes testing much more efficient and potentially ensures a more stable and error-free application.

- Although the stand-alone application is still in an early development stage it can potentially already be used for real work since it does not depend on any future server-side code development. This means that we can begin to create value for end-users earlier.

When the server-side components of the BeONE software architecture begins to take shape, the code from the stand-alone application will be integrated with the server side code.

Subtask: WP4-T1-ST1 Core display components

By now, these core display components have been developed and are considered finished:

- Data Sources view: This component enables the user to load BeONE JSON data files into the dashboard.
- Field Editor: This component makes it possible to search for data within the loaded BeONE JSON files and pick interesting data for showing in the dashboard. All data in the JSON files can be picked this way allowing the user to determine the data of interest as it is not predefined by the dashboard. Furthermore, the Field Editor can impose basic filtering on the selected data fields for further narrowing down interesting parts of a data set.
- Table View: This component shows the selected data set in a tabular fashion and features selecting and deselecting individual samples. It also has a feature for selecting all samples in the current filtering (or all samples in the dataset if no filtering is applied).
- Tree View: A Newick file containing a phylogenetic tree with the same sample ID's as the JSON files is required for this component. If such a file is loaded into the dashboard, it will show the samples in a tree view. Selecting and deselecting individual samples can be done here as well as in the Table View, and the selection state is shared between the two components.

Further display components will be developed as the project moves forward. The most important one will be a map for showing the geographic locations of samples, either as specific geographic coordinates (latitude & longitude) or by highlighting the country or region from which the sample is known to originate.

JRP24- WP4-T1-ST2 Component integration

Along with developing the individual display components described above, effort has been put into making them interoperate with each other in such a way that future display components can easily integrate into the architectural framework. Most notably, this is about providing structures for sharing data and application states (for example selection state) between display components.

JRP24- WP4-T2 Back end analysis implementation

Status: delayed

As described in WP3-T3-ST6, we are still working on the exact plan for the backend development; this will proceed in the fall. We expect that some code from the Danish data sharing platform SOFI can be used for BeONE as well.

As the new dashboard is independent of the backend, this task has been reduced to calculating or recalculating a distance matrix and building a phylogenetic tree. This way each institute is more free to choose its own backend. The input to the dashboard is still built on JSON files (WP3) which are possible to extract from a MongoDB.

JRP24- WP4-T3 Cluster analysis and collaboration tool

Status: Ongoing

BeONE will be a collaboration tool by enabling sharing data in the before described JSON format and cluster analysis is compared in WP1 and WP2. The exact method used in the backend of the dashboard is still being discussed and most will be described in the final sustainability document.

JRP24- WP4-T4 Data sharing front end

Status: Delayed

As mentioned in WP3-T3-ST6, an exact plan is not in place yet. However, the current idea is to create a frontend where it is possible to see all samples shared between the institutes you have agreements with. From this list it will be possible to filter by sample id, country, date, species, serotype and sequence type. The distance matrix will then be calculated and a phylogenetic tree built on these samples and visualised in the dashboard.

WP5: Dissemination, Testing, Evaluation and Sustainability

JRP24- WP5-T1 Dissemination

Status: Ongoing

Detailed instruction manuals will be provided as new features are developed, and user instructions will be made available for data input and output, as well as guidelines for data interpretation, sharing etc. Much of this will be output provided by the respective WPs.

Available documentation for the BeONE dashboard:

Instructions are available at <https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard> for the installation of the dashboard as well as the following youtube tutorials:

- How to install the dashboard (Windows tutorial)
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eEaD9donwI0>
- How to load the dashboard again (Windows tutorial)
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QKynHd-Sx5c>
- How to filter data (Windows tutorial)
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6IsRdFSC0js>

Available documentation for the WP3 pipelines for analysis:

- BfR Gitlab: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone
- Metadata parsing: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/beone-metadata-parsing
- AQAMIS: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/AQUAMIS/-/tree/hb_json_schema

chewieSnake: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/chewieSnake/-/tree/jsonexport

JRP24- WP5-T2 Continuous Testing and Feedback

Status: Ongoing

Testing of the dashboard has been started, both in the biweekly technical meetings and using GitHub (<https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard>). We will shortly begin a more structured testing with tutorials and surveys. It will be further tested at the technical workshop in June 2022.

JRP24- WP5-T3 Final evaluation

Status: Delayed

The final evaluation is postponed to autumn 2022, as the project has been extended.

JRP24- WP5-T4 Sustainability

Status: Ongoing

Key requirements for sustainability of the dashboard and analysis system have been identified as good documentation of the system, and an open source organisation around the system to carry on the collaborative work after the project ends.

At the end of the project a sustainability document will be created, describing the possibilities.

WP6: Management

JRP24- WP6-T1 Management

Status: Ongoing

We have continued with the monthly meetings. Furthermore, we have started biweekly technical meetings to discuss such details more thoroughly, in the fall these will be changed to monthly meetings.

JRP24- WP6-T2 Communication

Status: Completed

JRP24- WP6-T2-ST1 Kickoff meeting

Status: Completed

JRP24- WP6-T2-ST2 2nd Annual Meeting

Status: Completed

JRP24- WP6-T2-ST3 3rd Annual Meeting

Status: Pending

The third annual meeting will be in November 2022.

JRP24- WP6-T2-ST4 Development hackathon

Status: Changed

We changed this to a technical workshop hosted at SSI the 27th-28th of June 2022. Representatives from each WP presented their work and BfR did their final handover as well as a workshop to test it (as BfR will not be an active partner for the extension of BeONE).

JRP24- WP6-T3 Data Management

Status: Ongoing

The shared data used for WP1-2 and for testing in WP5 is placed at the NVI server SAGA.

Other data has also been shared between institutes for different tasks.

5.1.4.13.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
24	D-BeONE.1.2	Finalized BeONE dataset	M48	M48		Currently shared within the BeOne project, but will be publicly released before the end of the project https://zenodo.org/record/5808833#.Yp3oDi_5RQI	
24	D-BeONE.1.3	Report with clustering congruence results	M54	-	M60	Due to COVID-19 pandemics and technical issues faced during WP1-T2, this task was delayed but is expected to be completed before the end of the project.	
24	D-BeONE.2.2	Final Outbreak detection algorithm	M48	M50		https://zenodo.org/record/6375255#.YjmYpjXcCU	
24	D-BeONE.2.3	Final Guidelines	M48		M58	Delayed due to personnel shortage	
24	D-BeONE.2.4	Draft manuscript on outbreak detection algorithm and guidelines	M48		M58	Delayed due to personnel shortage	
24	D-BeONE.4.1	Back-end analysis pipeline	M48		M58	change of plans for dashboard construction	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
24	D-BeONE.4.2	Web input system	M48		M58	change of plans for dashboard construction	

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
24	M-BeONE.1.3	Curated WGS dataset completed	M51	Yes		This dataset will be publicly released before the end of the project, complying with the FAIR principles.
24	M-BeONE.1.5	Clustering congruence analysis completed	M54	No	M60	
24	M-BeONE.2.3	Guideline proposal	M50	No	M58	Delayed due to personnel shortage
24	M-BeONE.3.3	Implementation of data structure	M52	yes		
24	M-BeONE.3.6	Implementation of API for import of data	M52	yes		
24	M-BeONE.3.8	Application of the selected ontology system(s)	M54	yes		

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
24	M-BeONE.3.9	Data porting from at least one further pipeline	M52	no	M60	Data porting from the SSI-Bifrost system and EFSA pipeline not yet implemented.
24	M-BeONE.3.10	Expansion of the API for export functionality	M54	no	-	cancelled due to changed structure of data collection (no raw data provided). No other tasks are affected.
24	M-BeONE.3.11	Expansion of the API for queries from the dashboard	M54	No	M60	Dashboard functionality not established yet
24	M-BeONE.4.3	Prototype dashboard	M53	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.4.6	Cluster analysis and collaboration tool ready for testing	M42	no	M58	Delayed since the way to construct the dashboard has been changed
24	M-BeONE.4.7	Import/Export front end for reference databases implemented	M48	no	M58	change of plans for dashboard construction
24	M-BeONE.4.8	Dashboard in workable condition for Final Evaluation workshop	M48	no	M58	change of plans for dashboard construction
24	M-BeONE.5.1	Simulated international outbreak at 3rd annual meeting	M54	No	M59	Delayed due to project extension
24	M-BeONE.6.2	3rd annual meeting	M54	No	M59	Delayed due to project extension

5.1.4.13.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Prediction of antimicrobial resistance in clinical <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> isolates from whole-genome sequencing data 10.1007/s10096-020-04043-y https://zenodo.org/record/4249355#.X6UnVWhKjcc	YES		3825

Additional output

Pre-print publications

- Mixão V, Pinto M, Gomes JP, Borges V (2022) ReporTree: a surveillance-oriented tool to strengthen the linkage between pathogen genetic clusters and epidemiological data. Research Square. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-1404655/v1

Poster presentations

- Mixão V, Pinto M, Gomes JP, Borges V. ReporTree: a surveillance-oriented tool to strengthen the linkage between pathogen genetic clusters and epidemiological data. 32nd ECCMID (23-26/04/2022). Lisboa, Portugal
- Borges V, Isidro J, et al. Genomic epidemiology of SARS-CoV-2 in Portugal: supporting evidence-informed public health decision-making. 32nd ECCMID (23-26/04/2022). Lisboa, Portugal

Tools

<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>

<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ComparingPartitions>

<https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard> for the installation of the dashboard as well as the following youtube tutorials:

- How to install the dashboard (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eEaD9donwI0>
- How to load the dashboard again (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QKynHd-Sx5c>
- How to filter data (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6IsRdFSCOjs>

Available documentation for the WP3 pipelines for analysis

- BfR Gitlab: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone
- Metadata parsing: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/beone-metadata-parsing
- AQAMIS: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/AQUAMIS/-/tree/hb_json_schema
- chewieSnake: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/chewieSnake/-/tree/jsonexport

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Tools

<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>

<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ComparingPartitions>

<https://github.com/ssi-dk/beone-dashboard> for the installation of the dashboard as well as the following youtube tutorials:

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- How to filter data (Windows tutorial): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6IsRdFSCOjs>

Available documentation for the WP3 pipelines for analysis

- BfR Gitlab: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/bfr_beone
- Metadata parsing: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/beone-metadata-parsing
- AQAMIS: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/AQUAMIS/-/tree/hb_json_schema
- chewieSnake: https://gitlab.com/bfr_bioinformatics/chewieSnake/-/tree/jsonexport

5.1.4.13.5 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

The BeOne data sharing format (WP3) has been developed to be in line with the EFSA WGS data model development, and also harmonized with the ECDC.

The overall intention is to make BeONE compatible with other platforms currently being developed.

Collaboration with the ORION project on establishing state of the art (WP1).

Collaboration with the COHESIVE project.

5.1.5 Task 3.4: Organisation of annual scientific meetings (ASM)

The fourth Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) was hosted by ISS and took place in Orvieto, Italy, and was set up as a hybrid (combined in person - online) event from 11 to 13 May 2022. It was a successful edition, where about 300 participants from 22 countries took part. Altogether 24 oral presentations and a high number of poster presentations were selected from submitted abstracts. The abstract book (D3.19) was submitted in April 2022. Scientific keynote talks were delivered by Prof. Tiago Correia from the NOVA University of Lisbon, Prof. Raina Plowright from the Montana State University and Dr. Vittorio Fattori from the Food and Agriculture Organization and covered timely and important One Health topics: the concept of syndemic, spill-over of pathogens, and the impact of climate changes on food safety, respectively. Invited talks related to the main pillars of the One Health EJP, foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats, were delivered by Dr. Elisabetta Suffredini, Dr. Jean-Yves Madec and Dr. Bruno Gonzales Zorn. Active social media could be followed by following the hashtag #OHEJPASM2022. Chairpersons of sessions included early career colleagues co-chairing with experienced chairpersons. A special session focused on sustainability was co-organised with MedVetNet Association, and Round table format was used to present selected outcomes and impact of JRPs, JIPs, and PhD projects. 3-min PhD competition was held as hybrid competition.

5.2 Deliverables and Milestones

5.2.1 Deliverables

Del. Ref.	Deliverable title	Submission
D3.18	4th periodic report onJRP	M51
D3.19	Abstract book for 4th Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM)	M54

5.2.2 Milestones

Mil. Ref.	Milestone title	Expected Delivery/ Achievement Month	Notification
MS43	Preparation of final evaluation reports	M57	New deadline following the project extension: M62
MS44	Fourth Annual Scientific Meeting	M53	Achieved in M52
MS45	Final report preparation	M53	New deadline following the project extension: M57
MS46	Final reports n°3	M57	New deadline following the project extension: M60

6 WP4 - Joint integrative projects

6.1 Work carried out to date

6.1.1 Task 4.1: Development of procedures and guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals, and for reporting and evaluation

N/A

6.1.2 Task 4.2: Supervision of JIPs

The WP4 Team provides a support function for the JIPs and is regularly in contact with the JIP Leaders. The structure with continuous follow-up meetings with all JIP Project Leaders (PLs) continues and works very well. The projects are reminded by the WP4 support team well in advance of expected deliverables and support is given how to upload the completed deliverables. All projects are also encouraged to follow the updated procedures for scientific publishing, dissemination, and communication. In collaboration with WP3, templates for reporting have been prepared, partly prefilled, and sent out to projects. Also, the recurring meetings between work packages 3, 4 and 6, continue. This helps to harmonize the work between the OHEJP work packages and to approach the different projects in a similar way. Whenever possible, the representatives from the WP4 Team participate in the project consortium meetings. In M51, the 4th periodic report on JIPs (D4.27) was submitted. In M53 the Report on evaluation of finalised JIPs, 1st round (D4.24) was submitted. The finalised projects, ORION and COHESIVE, were both evaluated by three external evaluators. More about this can be found in D4.24.

During the ASM 2022 there was a PLs Forum, where updates from the OHEJP project management team were provided and the PLs got an opportunity to reflect and discuss on different aspects. Outputs from the JIPs were presented at the OHEJP ASM 2022 and at different other occasions. A set of dissemination workshops led by MATRIX is ongoing. In September the three JIPs ending in Y5 had a common final meeting. WP4 management team participated in this meeting. Details of the JIPs activities can be found in the respective JIP 9M reports.

6.1.2.1 JIP03-R2-IA2.3-CARE

6.1.2.1.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

In the reporting period of year 5 (9M), CARE continued to update and adjust certain activities to meet the deliverables and milestones. The delays were due to unforeseen issues such as a hacker attack at DTU and legal aspects as to the biorepository. The three new partners, ISCIII in Spain, BIOR in Latvia, and RUOKA in Finland, which joined the CARE consortium in 2021, have been active and included in the CARE activities contributing to this report.

The quarterly meeting with all partners continued to include participation by representatives of OHEJP MATRIX and OH-HARMONY-CAP. The two lead organizations, DTU and SSI have participated in integrative activities organized by the OHEJP such as the ASM, thereby promoting and disseminating information about the OHEJP and related activities.

The work in WP1 has been focusing on the third EQA on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data, W1-T2-ST3 for which data are being analysed and reported. The report of the first pilot EQA, W1-T2-ST1, which was successfully executed, has been developed and intended to be published. The second pilot EQA, W1-T2-ST2, on typing/characterization based on WGS was delayed due to the hacker attack at DTU. The trial is however in full progress and individual results have been shared with the participating laboratories.

The work in WP2/ WP3 has been focusing on the extended analysis of the identified genomes for AMR, virulence and other typing regimes. Experts have revised the raw read files and the genome assemblies to assess the quality of the sequences submitted to ENA or NCBI GenBank. A sub-database for AMR (D2.2) has connected the relational Web database of the strains (D3.1.3) with the ResFinder database [EFSA_2021 \(2022-05-24\)](#) of the resistance genes. The Web catalogue interface is being developed to ensure visibility and accessibility of the reference materials. MALDI-ToF MS reference spectra are being produced for *Campylobacter*, *Yersinia* and *Salmonella* strains in order to set up and share reference libraries. A sustainable development plan for the CARE collection has been collectively drafted.

More than 50 individuals from various institutions provided feedback to the risk assessment survey on relevant (meta-)data in relation to quantitative microbial risk assessments conducted by WP4. Thus, feeding into the quantitative microbial risk assessment analysis on data originating from the last five years and provided by 19 OHEJP members or stakeholders including those from ORION and RADAR (D.4.1.2) (no link). The identified (meta-)data in relation to quantitative microbial risk assessments were shared with WP2 and WP3 and stakeholders to assist by increasing the accessibility of data but also to avoid duplication (D.4.1.3). Currently, efforts are made towards developing a user guide for accessing relevant data for risk assessment (D.4.2.1) and presented during the September final meeting) and R software suite package “rStain Select” to ease the process of selecting suitable reference strains based on exposure and risks. Thus, the User guide and R software will contribute to and support the developed strategy by EU authorities to raise the awareness of relevant reference material microbial risk assessment analysis (D.4.2.2). The latter issue of what kind of data is necessary for risk assessment has been discussed with EFSA and ECDC and will be taken into consideration.

In summary, the CARE project progresses more or less as planned reaching milestones and deliverables in time and addresses additional assignments from the OHEJP WP4 in a timely manner.

6.1.2.1.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WPO Coordination

WPO-T1 Over-all project coordination

DTU and SSI still constitute the management team and follow the established comprehensive management system to ensure that all deliverables and milestones for the vast majority are reached in the timeframe envisioned for the project and submitted using the designated OHEJP format. DTU still hosts the secretariat, which warrants the successful completion of the proposed work programme. Furthermore, the DTU CARE share-site for storage of all reports, deliverables, milestones, minutes and other documentation is still in function.

DTU and SSI organised the final meeting at SSI in collaboration with JIPs, MATRIX and OH-HARMONY-CAP (M.0.3). The meeting was held as an on-site meeting to allow all partners to be updated from the CARE management team, WP-lead and on the DMP plan. External stakeholders will be invited if deemed important. There will be allocated time for break-out sessions where the sustainability of the completed tasks will be further discussed. In addition, the completed work will be presented by presentations. The minutes of the meeting will be reported and shared in the share site (D.0.6).

CARE status meetings for the management team (DTU and SSI) have been conducted every second week. Furthermore, DTU and SSI organized and conducted work package (WP) lead virtual meetings every 14 days to inform, discuss and delegate news and tasks from the OHEJP management as part of Task: JIP IA 2.1-WPO-T1. In addition, WP-leads reported on the work undertaken in each WP as progress, deliverables, delays etc. Minutes of all meetings have been reported and shared on the CARE share site. The implemented review system to ensure high quality work is still in function.

The management team has organized and conducted joint partner virtual meetings every quarter, primarily to allow the 16 partners to provide feedback on progress and accomplishments. The

meetings also allowed for the dissemination of information not shared already by email. Minutes of these meetings are shared and saved on the share site.

The three projects CARE, MATRIX and OH-HARMONY-CAP are still participating in each other's meetings sharing knowledge and progress on the projects. In addition, the three projects are planning to host the third One Health CPD-module with the theme, Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests in 2nd - 4th November of 2022 at DTU and SSI. Twenty onsite participants, including both microbiologists and epidemiologists, and up to 100 online participants are expected to participate in the module. The module will discuss the role of diagnostics and related challenges from both the microbiological and epidemiological perspectives. Outbreak case studies based on real outbreaks will actively engage both epidemiologists and microbiologists, walking participants through the different roles that each group plays during an outbreak scenario. Epidemiologists will accompany microbiologists in the laboratory to gain a better understanding of various testing procedures (e.g. PCR, serotyping, whole genome sequencing) and microbiologists will join epidemiologists in conducting epidemiological analyses typical during an outbreak investigation. This structure will allow each group to improve their understanding of the perspectives of the other when dealing with an outbreak together, focusing on the effects of applying rapid and/or harmonised diagnostic tests. Furthermore, the thematic call for original publications, whether research, perspectives, or policy, in the domain of integrated One Health surveillance has been launched in the Journal Frontiers in Public Health. We hope that this call might collect some of the intermediate achievements of the JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX with a special focus on the integrative aspects of the projects' methods and strategies.

The final joint meeting between the three integrative projects, CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, and MATRIX has been jointly planned. Project leads and co-leads from the three projects have held bi-weekly meetings in 2022. The final joint meeting was held at SSI on September 20th – 22nd. For the joint meeting "Lessons learned and sustainability beyond 2022" (20th September) a save the date flyer was shared with the three consortia, OHEJP WP4, and the Communications team on May 10th including a registration link. The deadline was initially June 15th but late applicants will be enrolled ad hoc. Each JIP will present key elements and outputs from their respective projects and the meeting will include a panel discussion where EFSA and OHEJP WG4 will be present to discuss how to make best use of the project deliverables.

WP1 Develop of cross-sectional PT's (proficiency testing)

The overall aim of WP1 is to develop EQA/ PT schemes that can be used to assess the combined performance of the OH sector, i.e., the human, food/feed, and veterinary sectors. The WP is divided into three tasks, a mapping exercise, which is finalized (WP1-T1 Mapping of existing and proposals for new PT schemes), a part where three pilot PTs are organized and documented (WP1-T2 Pilot trials and documentation of outcome), and a third part, WP1-T3 Development of guidance document with suggestions for design of future cross-sectorial PT schemes. This part of the WP has not started yet. The work conducted in Y4 has been focusing on the planning and execution of pilot PTs:

- WP1-T2-ST1 Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens
- WP1-T2-ST2 Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS
- WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data

WP1-T2-ST1 Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens

The aim of this pilot PT is to increase the understanding of the cross-sectorial capabilities to detect and characterize food-borne pathogens in a matrix relevant to the sectors of food safety, veterinary medicine, and public health. A total of 15 laboratories (12 OHEJP partners and 3 clinical microbiological laboratories from one country) participated in the PT/EQA organized by SVA, FOHM and SLV in 2021. The participants of the PT/EQA were to detect and characterize the target pathogens to species level (*Campylobacter*), to serovar level (*Salmonella*) and to species and biotype level (*Yersinia*) according to

the methods routinely used by each laboratory. A short web-based questionnaire was included in the PT/EQA.

A report of the PT/EQA was finalized in month 53 and uploaded to Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/6575861#.YoyVBKhBxaQ>. A scientific publication of the PT/EQA is in progress.

WP1-T2-ST2 Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS

The second PT in WP1 aims at assessing the quality and comparability of WGS based on a set of WGS quality metrics and looks into the laboratories ability to detect and assign subtypes/attributes from WGS data from bacterial isolates e.g., sero- and sequence types, antimicrobial resistance genes, toxin subtypes etc. The aim is to assess both the individual and the collective performance of the partner participating laboratories.

In Y4, work has been done on developing and documenting the reference material that are used in the PT, i.e., pure strains and FASTQ sequence files from *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and *Escherichia coli*. An invitation to participate in the PT was sent to the CARE laboratories in September, and instructions and material for the PT was dispatched from DTU, Lyngby, Denmark, in October Y4. The participants have received six live stains, two strains of *E. coli*, two strains of *Salmonella*, and two strains of *Campylobacter*, and six pre-prepared DNA samples corresponding the live cultures. The participants are requested to perform WGS on DNA purified from the live cultures and the pre-purified samples and upload the reads in FASTQ format to a FTP site. The participants are also requested to upload specific details in relation to the test material and details in relation to their sequencing and analytical methods. It is mandatory to identify the overall Multi Locus Sequence Type (MLST) lineage of the cultures and it is also mandatory to identify antimicrobial resistance genes, including genes associated with resistance towards extended spectrum beta-lactam antimicrobials, and point mutations that are conferring antimicrobial resistance. The deadline for submission was postponed from 21 December 2021 to 4 March 2022 due to a hacker attack at Corporate IT at DTU. This delayed to submission of the participant data and the downstream analysis. Luckily no data at DTU was compromised and the IT informatics system was re-activated. The submitted reads and corresponding results have been evaluated and individual feedback provided to each of the participants.

WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data

The aim of this pilot is to develop proficiency testing schemes for the analysis of whole genome sequence (WGS) data to detect clusters as might be required during an outbreak response.

The pilot PT was executed in the partner laboratories from December 15, 2021 until end February 2022. The PT included WGS data from three distributions of 35, 27 and 31 samples of *Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella*, respectively. The participants were recruited among the CARE partners and, additionally, the Singapore Food Agency participated. The participants could sign up for all or selected parts of the PT. In total 20 institutions participated. The participants downloaded genome sequence data in FASTQ format from an FTP site for the analysis of the data using their current operational pipelines. The reporting contained general questions on the cluster analysis approach. The laboratories were asked to use their routine quality control (QC), and only include samples that passed QC for further analysis. For all samples, the sequence type (ST) should be reported and it should be indicated whether the sample was a part of a closely related cluster. For *Salmonella* or *Campylobacter* the serotype or species should also be reported respectively. Both allele and/or SNP based cluster analysis were used. The PT results were uploaded to a reporting platform hosted by APHA using a scheme developed for this project. The reported data included information on the applied type of bioinformatics tools and for each of the three distributions the laboratories indicated the number of SNP and or allele differences to selected predefined index strains defined. Individual feedback was provided to the participants on May 23 2022. The feedback included a document where the submitted

results were compared with the expected results from the PT provider. Currently the final report of the PT is being elaborated.

WP2 Creation of EUROpanelOH, a reference database of strains and genomes for effective quality control analysis in food safety and public health protection across sectors

The overall aim of WP2 is to propose and better characterize strains of seven bacterial pathogens that would be integrated in a panel of Reference Materials (RM) named CARE collection at the moment with aims to build EUROpanelOH by growing and extension to other initiatives, such as ENOVAT for animal pathogens with which contacts have been made (Dr. Overesch, WG2 leader).

From the inventory of 2960 strains finalized in WP2-T1, a first gap analysis was conducted by expert groups during WP2-T2 to select a subset of resources among those proposed by 12 partners of the CARE consortium. This gap analysis identified the WGS data as a prerequisite for success. The first part of the gap analysis was done owing to the recommendations issued by the need assessment document. The second part of the document (M2.2) has been postponed until the end of September 2022 when strains, genomes, and data will be included in the first release of the final database. See WP3 for details on the customization of the Biologics software.

One of the major purposes of CARE is to establish a trustable link between the phenotypes and the genotypes of the strains. Consensual methods and protocols have been applied to fill relevant gaps for the characterization of the strains by each provider or by the Biological Resource Centers (BRCs) that are hosting the RM of the CARE collection. Numerous meetings have been conducted.

WP2-T3 Production of additional RM to fill in gaps and/or improve characterization if needed

A total of 830 RMs have been included in WP2-T3 for data completion.

WP2-T3-ST1 WGS characterization

Sequencing of the strains for which WGS was not available has begun in summer 2021. WGS data, at least raw reads, have been uploaded in international sequence repositories under the following ENA study accession numbers: PRJEB46213, PRJEB49020, PRJEB49018, PRJEB49008, PRJEB49009, PRJEB48968, PRJEB48148, PRJEB48129, PRJEB47991, PRJEB49424, PRJNA799608.

A dedicated folder gathering all the genomes of the seven pathogens has been created at IP for enabling easy file exchange among partners. Whenever necessary, the genomes have been *de novo* assembled at INRAE. The gene content for AMR has been analyzed by Staramr which scans genome contigs against ResFinder, PlasmidFinder and PointFinder. A first release of the AMR database has been recently delivered (D2.2) based on scripts that connect the CARE collection with ResFinder. Other partner analytical services have been used: Kmer analysis for species identification, Multi Locus Sequence Typing for the seven pathogens, Seqsero for *Salmonella* serotyping, VirulenceFinder for *S. aureus* and an ISS pipeline dedicated to the analysis of the serotypes and the virulence of *E. coli*. The results of these WGS analyses have been compared with the characteristics of the strains reported in the original Excel files of the providers.

WP2-T3-ST2 MALDI-TOF characterization

MALDI-TOF Mass spectrometry is now commonly used for bacterial identification but needs representative databases for correct identification of pathogens such as *Salmonella*, *Yersinia*, and *Campylobacter* responsible for gastroenteritis worldwide. In order to enlarge the database of reference spectra already existing in the Bruker commercial database, and to pave the way for further studies, four partners (IP, ANSES, INRAE, VISAVET) have been working on producing reference spectra for *Salmonella* and *Yersinia*. The work on *Campylobacter* is pending due to the delayed transfer of strains from Spain that constitute most of the panel due to addressing Nagoya protocol restrictions.

WP2-T3-ST3 Completing metadata and phenotypic data

The updated lists of strains selected for the final database (see WP3) are checked by the three BRCs (CIRM at INRAE, CIP at IP and BVR at IZSLER) that received the RM from the providers. Follow up actions are being conducted with the partners in collaboration with WP3 for transferring the complete set of information in the customized Biolomics software.

WP3 Access and sustainability of well-defined microbial reference materials (RM)

WP3-T1 Development of an information system for making RM more widely accessible and visible

The CARE website was developed that enabled running basic and advanced searches to access the CARE catalogue. Information on the AMR phenotypes and AMR gene predicted from WGS data have been introduced in the CARE database. The website contains all the information for the user to deposit or order strains. The website is currently being reviewed by CARE's partners before being made available to the public.

WP3-T2 Ensure the long-term sustainability of RM collections

The sustainability plan has been drafted. Materials deposit agreements (MDA) are signed between RM providers and mBRCs when integrating strains into the CARE catalog. A training session attended by 12 CARE partners over two days in May 2022 was organised. Visits to two microbial BRCs were included. All documents were made available.

WP3-T3 Ensuring the long-term accessibility of the RM collection and its existence

The deposit of strains in the three microbiological resource centers is on-going that will ensure the long-term accessibility of the CARE RM collection.

WP4 Investigate, benchmark and improve the availability and the quality of the existing data relevant for risk assessment

WP4-T1 Data and metadata available for risk assessment

After connections were established with other projects and stakeholders during Y4, further connections were performed during Y5 in the perspective to establish the roadmap for sharing information on pathogens and AMR useful for exposure/risk assessment.

CARE WP4's objective and findings for the practices of data sharing for risk assessment have been presented to the JIP MATRIX and during the 4th OHEJP Thematic Integrative Meeting "Data sharing across disciplines".

WP4-T2 Metadata web platform

The resources provided by DTU incorporating surveillance data related to antimicrobial resistance and infectious disease data into a web platform (D.4.2.3) was redrawn from central DTU administration during 2021, thus, the task and deliverable were omitted and co-funding redrawn. The other partners of this task (ANSES and RIVM) have initiated to draft a user guide describing how to access the data available (D.4.2.1). The user guide will be available as an html book. It follows the classical steps of quantitative risk assessments. It considers the information gathered during the survey and related to other OHEJP projects (see D 4.1.2). In the same way, the two partners will propose in Y5 a guideline document to raise awareness by EU authorities of collecting relevant and high-quality data for risk-assessment (D.4.2.2). This document will be shared and presented to stakeholders. It will then be presented to the EFSA Microbial risk assessment network.

WP4-T3 Dissemination plan

The 4th OHEJP Thematic Integrative Meeting "Data sharing across disciplines" was a first realisation of the dissemination plan.

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The network European network of focal points, the EFSA MRA network will be used to disseminate the results after the final meeting of September 2022.

6.1.2.1.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	gJRP/JIP code	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
D.0.6	Minutes of the closing meeting - 2022	JIP03-CARE	58				
D.0.7	Minutes of all tele-conferences	JIP03-CARE	57				
D.1.2.1	WP1-T2-ST1: Report - Pilot Isolation/detection of pathogens	JIP03-CARE	54	53		D.1.2.1 EJP CARE Pilot isolation-detection of pathogens: https://zenodo.org/record/6575861#.YoyVBKhBxaQ	1,2
D.1.2.2	WP1-T2-ST2: Report - Pilot on typing/characterization including WGS	JIP03-CARE	54	58		Report writing is in progress. A draft report will be discussed at the final CARE meeting in Copenhagen in September 2022 and the report will be ready in early November.	
D.1.2.3	WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data	JIP03-CARE	54	58		Report writing is in progress. A draft report will be discussed at the final CARE meeting in Copenhagen in September 2022 and the report will be ready in early November.	

Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	gJRP/JIP code	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
D.1.3.1	Guidance document for cross sectorial proficiency testing	JIP03-CARE	60				
D.1.3.2	SOPs for specific WGS proficiency testing distributions	JIP03-CARE	60				
D.2.2	Sub-database for antimicrobial resistances	JIP03-CARE	48	54		Available in Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/6644884#.YqmXVXZByUk	
D.2.4	Genome assemblies and raw reads deposited at ENA	JIP03-CARE	58				
D.2.5	Spectral (MALDI-TOF) database of protein mass fingerprints	JIP03-CARE	58				
D.2.6	Well-characterized RM (strains and genomes)	JIP03-CARE	58				
D.3.1	Establish a searchable catalogue containing RM	JIP03-CARE	58				

Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	gJRP/JIP code	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
	connected to a broad range of external databases including databases of CARE partners						
D.3.1.3	Searchable online RMs catalogue	JIP03-CARE	46	53		Delay was due to the difficulties in gathering information on RMs. https://zenodo.org/record/6575874#.YoyW_KhBxaQ	
D.3.2.1	Deposit of all the reference strains within microbial collections considered as "reference collections"	JIP03-CARE	51	60		Additional delays are expected related to ABS compliance.	
D.3.3	Reference strains made accessible via the CARE single entry point portal	JIP03-CARE			See for D.3.1.3 and D.3.2.1	D.3.3 is superfluous with D3.1.3 (Searchable online RMs catalogue) and D3.2.1 (Deposit of RMs within mBRCs and collections considered as "reference collections")	
D.3.3.1	Signing of an MoU to ensure the sustainability of the CARE IS	JIP03-CARE	59			MoU is unnecessary. MDAs are signed over time between RM providers and mBRCs when integrating their strains into the CARE catalog.	

Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	gJRP/JIP code	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
D.3.4	Signing of an MoU to ensure the sustainability of the CARE IS	JIP03-CARE			See for D.3.3.1	Detailed in D.3.3.1	
D.4.1	Report on analyzed survey data regarding the quality and accessibility	JIP03-CARE			See for D.4.1.3	Renamed to D.4.1.3	
D.4.1.2	The establishment of connection of this CARE activity with the databases and initiatives already in place	JIP03-CARE	47	54		Available in Zenodo : https://zenodo.org/record/6644910#.YqmZv3ZByUk	
D.4.1.3	Report on analyzed survey data regarding the quality and accessibility	JIP03-CARE	42	47		Deliverable D.4.1.3. Report on the survey related to the availability and quality of data used for risk assessment Available in Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5882651#.Yek9yP7MKUk	
D.4.2.1	User Guide for accessing relevant data for risk-assessment	JIP03-CARE	54	57		Available in Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/6644910#.YqmZv3ZByUk	

Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	gJRP/JIP code	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
D.4.2.2	Implementation of developed strategy to raise awareness by EU authorities	JIP03-CARE	54	57		The deliverable is postponed for 2 months in order to include the last development and the internal review process of CARE	
D.4.2.3	Web based exchange platform including antimicrobial resistance surveillance data.	JIP03-CARE				D.4.3.2 omitted in Y5 AMR	
D.4.3	An executed dissemination plan	JIP03-CARE	54	57			

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
JIP03-CARE	M.0.3	Closing meeting - 2022	58	Yes		
JIP03-CARE	M.1.3	Review of previous tasks (1 & 2) for the production of a guidance document for proficiency testing and SOPs for specific distributions.	50	No	59	There is a draft report ready for discussion at the final CARE meeting in Copenhagen in September 2022. The M1.3 will be delivered hereafter.
JIP03-CARE	M.2.3	Exhaustive characterization of EUROpanelOH RM	58			
JIP03-CARE	M.3.2	Microbial collection management Training session done	49	Yes		Organisation of a training session attended by 12 CARE partners over two days in May 2022 which included visits to two microbial BRCs and a set of 15 conferences. All documents were made available.
JIP03-CARE	M.3.2.1	Training session done	52	Yes		
JIP03-CARE	M.3.3.1	Drafting MoU to be done and circulated among partners	47	Yes		A sustainability plan was drafted instead of a MoU
JIP03-CARE	M.3.3.2	Launching event of the CARE portal where stakeholders will be invited to sign the MoU	50	No		

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JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
JIP03-CARE	M.4.3	Dissemination plan	50	Yes (month 54)		The dissemination plan includes the strategy of dissemination to stakeholders.

6.1.2.1.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Guillier L, Palma F, Fritsch L. Taking account of genomics in quantitative microbial risk assessment: what methods? what issues? Current Opinion in Food Science 100922; 2022. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2022.100922	Yes	The manuscript will be deposited in HAL repository	

6.1.2.1.5 Additional output

- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, April 11-13, Orvieto, Italy Elina Lahti, Linnéa Blom, Hilde Riedel, Nadja Karamemedovic, Anna Heydecke, Aurora Garcia Fernandez, Claudia Lucarelli, Elisabetta Delibato, Ingegerd Sjögren, Isaac Ring, Jeppe Boel, Karl Lundin, Kees Veldman, Lucas Wijnands, Maria Ugarte Ruiz, Martine Denis, Mia Torpdahl, Renata Kwit, Rene Hendriksen, Cecilia Jernberg “A cross-sectional pilot proficiency test/external quality assessment on detection and characterisation of food-borne pathogens.
- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, April 11-13, Orvieto, Jeppe Boel, Sally Hallam, Małgorzata L. Marzęta, Paula Johnson, Mia Torpdahl, « Cross-sectorial one health proficiency test for cluster detection of Campylobacter, Salmonella, and Listeria monocytogenes based on whole genome sequencing”
- Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM, April 11-13 2022, Orvieto, Forum Shah, Maria-Beatrice Boniotti, Anne Brisabois, Olivier Chesneau, Dominique Clermont, Emmanuelle Helloin, Rene Hendriksen, Valeria Michelacci, Michel-Yves Mistou and the OH-EJP CARE consortium. The CARE collection, an open panel of microbiological reference materials dedicated to zoonotic and foodborne bacterial pathogens.

6.1.2.1.6 Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

Presentation of the OHEJP CARE project with a focus on the inventory of reference materials and database at the Anses internal reference meeting, Maisons-Alfort, 19th of May 2022 (A. Brisabois).

A large collection of well-characterised reference strains of food-borne pathogens (>2500 strains) will be available for scientists and laboratories to use.

Guidance on cross-sectorial proficiency tests/external quality assurance

6.1.2.1.7 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

In WP1 we have had interactions with the proficiency testing unit at the National Food Agency of Sweden, and included the NRL network for commenting on a draft document on how to organize one health proficiency test.

MIRRI is a pan-European research infrastructure for the preservation, systematic investigation, provision and valorisation of microbial resources and biodiversity. MIRRI has been recognized as a “Landmark” on the ESFRI roadmap 2021 and was acknowledged the ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) status in the Summer 2022. The three mBRCs (CIP_IP; CIRM_INRAE; BVR_IZSLER) which are repositories of the CARE collection are members of MIRRI. By virtue of this membership the CARE collection will be visible within the MIRRI catalogue.

Interaction with ECDC, EFSA (WP4).

6.1.2.2 JIP04-R2-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP

6.1.2.2.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

OH-HARMONY-CAP is a 3-year project that aims to: 1. Collect information on current capabilities, capacities, interoperability, and adaptability at both the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) and the primary diagnostic level, across Europe by developing an in-depth OHLabCap survey. 2. Examine current and best practices within the One Health sectors (public health, veterinary & food/environment testing labs) in 'Sampling & testing', 'Characterisation of isolates' and 'Data management & harmonised reporting' including the identification of current knowledge gaps and propose new studies and/or methods to fill them. 3. Produce recommendations on how to harmonise the methodology for the detection and typing of pathogens.

- M54-M60 will focus on dissemination, scientific reporting, publishing, participating in conferences, networking and, presentation of scientific results
- The 59 question OHLabCap was created in Y4 and received 122 responses which is being analysed by 32-FHI; Instead of three dimensions and 10 targets four dimensions (adaptability, capability, capacity, and interoperability) and 15 targets are used to quantify the data.
- An additional deliverable is included, led by 39-SLV, which is based on an anonymous survey of the food business operators HACCP-based control programmes.
- Surveys of laboratories were designed to collate information on current harmonised data reporting and management systems within the EU.
- Detection and typing methods of STEC and ETEC have been ranked and harmonized procedures for these pathogens have been proposed. A decision tree for *Cryptosporidium* spp. has been created. No need for a procedure for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*. Training sessions will be organized in Y5.
- Trainings on detection and typing of ETEC, STEC and *Cryptosporidium* spp. will be held ISS.
- A special issue in *Frontiers Public Health* "One Health Surveillance in Practice: Experiences of Integration among Human Health, Animal Health, Environmental Health, and Food Safety Sectors" has been launched together with JIPs MATRIX and CARE.
- OH-HARMONY-CAP is organising the third One Health CPD module together with JIPs CARE and MATRIX. The role of diagnostics and related challenges will be discussed from both the microbiological and epidemiological perspectives.

6.1.2.2.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WP1 Project coordination

JIP04-WP1-T1: Internal coordination

Progress: As part of the internal engagement, it has been important to effectively communicate the progress and status of the project to the OH-HARMONY-CAP participants. Therefore, from the start of the project, and throughout, we have communicated a common understanding of the roles and responsibilities, output specifics and expectation.

- Several emails to all participants with project overview, status, and decisions
- Frequent conference meetings between the project leaders of WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5
- One conference call with OH-HARMONY-CAP project group (WP leads and deputy leads)

- A final meeting with the three JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, MATRIX and CARE was held on September 20 – 22 at Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark. Project leads and deputy leads from CARE, MATRIX and OH-HARMONY-CAP have held meeting every other week. These meetings are part of WP5T1 and T2.

JIP04-WP1-T2: External coordination, outreach and engagement

Progress: As part of the external engagement and to, effectively, find synergies with other projects, disseminate our project, progress and results, OH-HARMONY-CAP has participated and presented

- ASM 2022: Three posters were presented from WP2, WP3, and WP4
- Presented at the Project Leaders Forum (PLF), April 12th ASM 2022
- A strong collaboration has been built with the management teams of JIPs MATRIX and CARE. Therefore, throughout the year, there have been several meetings between MATRIX, CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP.
- 13-SSI and 12-DTU are organising the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Module on Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests. The team will involve representatives of several Joint Integrative Projects and Joint Research Projects of the OHEJP. As such, there have been several meetings between OH-HARMONY-CAP and the project leaders from CARE and MATRIX. The CPD will be held on the 2-4 November 2022.
- Participated and contributed to [the One Health EJP side event](#) at ONE – Health, Environment, Society – Conference 2022, on the 22nd of June 2022 in Brussels

JIP04-WP1-T3: Data management

Progress: The list of data covered in OH-HARMONY-CAP DMP was specified during the first and second year of the project. DMP is a living document during the lifetime of the project. The final DMP will be published at the end of the project.

WP2 Development of the OHLabCap

WP months: M25-M54.

The aim of WP2 is to develop a benchmarking instrument “OHLabCap”, by surveying OneHealth laboratory interoperability, capacity and capability across EU. The focus is on the detection and typing of selected priority foodborne pathogens, AMR determinants, and priority parasites across each sector (AH, PH, and FS). The main deliverable will result in the establishment of an OHLabCap instrument that is generic, adjustable and sustainable at both an EU and National level.

JIP04-WP2-T1: Development and testing of the pilot survey

Task month: M25-M30. Task completed.

JIP04-WP2-T2: Scoring of Collected Data and Chosen Indicators

Task month: M31-M38. Task completed.

JIP04-WP2-T3: Development and testing of an adjusted survey

Task month: M37-M42. Task completed.

JIP04-WP2-T4: Scoring of collected data and chosen indicators

Task month: M43-M54 (ongoing)

Description of the task: JIP04-WP2-T4 will evaluate, assess, and score the collected data from the OHLabCap to prepare the One Health map of the levels of system capability/capacity/interoperability/adaptability for the national reference and primary diagnostic

laboratories in each of the EU/EEA countries and dissemination. The overall outcome will be an integrated One Health map of the levels of system capability/capacity/interoperability/adaptability for each of the chosen organisms for the NRLs and primary diagnostic laboratories in the EU/EEA countries. This tool will not include an evaluation of surveillance capacities and capabilities (EUEpiCap), which is included in MATRIX.

32-FHI is currently analysing the responses to the OHLabCap survey and the preliminary data were presented at the meeting in Dublin in November 2021. When designing the OHLabCap we used the EULabCap as a model which has three dimensions and 10 targets. However, the EULabCap is very broad and the OHLabCap focuses on fewer pathogens. Therefore, to quantify data from the OHLabCap survey we used four dimensions (adaptability, capability, capacity, and interoperability) and 15 targets.

JIP04-WP2-T5: Development of a survey targeting the food sectors self-control

Task month: M37-M51 (completed)

Task description: The primary aim of this task was to provide an overview of the current procedures for microbiological sampling and analyses within the Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP)-based programmes food business operators. Like the OHLabCap, the survey was focused on the analyses of microbiological samples for the following six priority bacteria: *Salmonella* spp., *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Campylobacter* spp., Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), *Shigella* spp. and *Yersinia* spp.; and five priority parasites: *Trichinella* spp., *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Echinococcus granulosus* (sensu lato), *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Toxoplasma gondii*.

Progress: Participating EU/EEA countries distributed an online questionnaire to food business operators' laboratories within their countries; and overall, responses from nine EU/EEA countries were received and feedback from 35 laboratories were considered for data analysis.

A need for further efforts to harmonise and standardise analytical protocols and further characterisation of foodborne pathogens is needed.

The preliminary results were presented at the OH-HARMONY-CAP Consortium Meeting in Dublin 2021 and at later in a report published in M51 (Deliverable, D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.5 <https://zenodo.org/record/6414920#.YpUf1YzP02w>). The results of the survey were presented in a poster at the One Health Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 in Orvieto, Italy.

WP3 One Health Laboratory Interoperability Guidance

WP months: M25-M57 (ongoing)

The overall aim of this WP is to examine current and best practices within the One Health sectors (public health, veterinary & food/environment testing labs) in 'Sampling & testing', 'Characterisation of isolates' and 'Data management & harmonised reporting' including the identification of current knowledge gaps and propose new studies and/or methods to fill them. With the aim of providing guidance for the development of a more efficient and harmonised system the following issues are being addressed:

Sampling and testing

- current and best practices in designing statistically based sampling plans
- the most appropriate sampling methods
- currently available testing (detection) methods
- how these are applied
- the latest technologies/technological developments

Strain characterisation

- current routine strain characterisation in Europe
- gaps in strain characterisation that are inhibiting food safety regulation/policy in the EU
- recommendations on what typing methods, AMR and virulence gene testing, etc. should be undertaken as part of a future harmonised approach to strain characterisation
- recommendations on how this harmonised strategy should be implemented

Data management

- current used data management systems in Europe
- a harmonised data management system for the future
- recommendations on how this system should be implemented (hardware, software, motivating MSs, etc.)

For the purposes of this work, four target pathogens were selected including:

- Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC)
- Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC)
- *Cryptosporidium*
- AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

JIP04-WP3-T1: Sampling and Testing

Task month M24-M36. Task completed.

JIP4-WP3-T2: Characterisation

Task month M37-M48. Task completed.

JIP4-WP3-T3: Data Management

Task start month: M46-M57 (concluded).

Progress: The report 'Data management & harmonised reporting of Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp. in Europe was drafted. This includes analysis of the responses to the questionnaire (sub-task WP3.T1.S1) to establish current data management practices with individual MSs and how this data is communicated to EFSA and ECDC. Moreover, a second questionnaire was undertaken to obtain specific information on hardware and software used to store, manage and analyse data and communicate the results to relevant stakeholders and to regional, national or European agencies. The next step will include the participation of relevant experts to develop the concept of a harmonised data reporting and management system within the EU. The delivery date was extended from M54 to M57.

Further, 33-NVI submitted an abstract on the work on Typing and Characterization methods of Shiga toxin producing *E. coli*, described in deliverable D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.3.2

WP4 Harmonisation of Protocols

WP months: M25-M50.

The aim of WP4 is to produce recommendations on how to harmonise the methodology for the detection and typing of the model pathogens. The identified candidates are Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC), enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) and *Cryptosporidium* and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*. The strategy and the approaches adopted in the framework of WP4 activities may be

transferred to other pathogens, enabling harmonisation of methodologies in use in the EU/EEA laboratories.

JIP4-WP4-T1: Collection of the Laboratory Protocols for Model Organisms

Task start month: M25-M33. Task completed.

JIP4-WP4-T2: Evaluation of the Collected Laboratory Protocols

Task month: M31-M39. Task completed.

JIP4-WP4-T3: Ranking and choice of laboratory protocols

Task months: M39-M54 (ongoing)

Task Leader: 34-PIWet. Deputy Task leader: 1-ANSES

Task description: The aim of this task consists in choosing and proposing harmonised protocols. To do so, experts participating in WP4 have been enrolled for the ranking of the procedures collected and preliminarily evaluated in JIP4-WP4-T2. The major outcome and impact of this task will be the proposal for harmonised procedures for the model microorganisms evaluated in this WP, namely Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*.

Progress JIP4-WP4-T3 takes place in Y4 as scheduled and continued in Y5, as agreed and updated in the annual work plan Y4 and Y5.

The three subtasks WP4 T1-T3 have been carried out, as described in the 12 M report, and finalized with different outcomes: 1) proposal of harmonised procedures for STEC and ETEC 2) decision tree for *Cryptosporidium* spp. and 3) no need to issue a unique procedure for AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*). The whole process conducted in WP4 has been included in a final report, which will be published in M54 (D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.4.3. A technical report of Harmonised protocols including; 1) detection of selected pathogens, and 2) characterisation (e.g. virulence genes asset) and typing of pathogens.). The report will be the outputs of WP4-T3, which will be applied in the training sessions organized in Y5 in WP5-T3.

WP5 Training sessions on harmonised protocols

WP months: M40-M60 (ongoing)

The aim of this WP is to increase the EU capacity to deal with foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats across the One Health interface by organising trainings.

JIP4-WP5-T1 Facilitation and communication of the OHLabCap and T2 Joint workshop between CARE, OH-HARMONY-CAP, and MATRIX

Task months: M40-M57 (concluded)

Task descriptions: A workshop for communication and discussion of the outcome of the OHLabCAP survey. A joint meeting between the three joint integrative projects, CARE (IA2.1), OH-HARMONY-CAP (IA2.2), and MATRIX (IA2.3).

Progress: The meetings were held at 13-SSI on September 20 – 22, 2022. For the joint meeting “Lessons learned and sustainability beyond 2022” (20th September) a save the date flyer was shared with the three consortia, EJP WP4, and communications team on May 10th including a registration link. Each JIP presented key elements and outputs from their respective project. A panel discussion with a representative from EFSA and OHEJP were present.

JIP4-WP5-T3: Practical workshops (S1) and e-learning activities (S2)

Task months: M40-M57 (concluded)

Task description: The aim of this task consists of the organization of practical workshops and e-learning activities on detection and characterisation of *E. coli* (STEC), Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium* and AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*.

The trainees will be primarily members from the OH-HARMONY-CAP Consortium; nonetheless, the invitation may be extended to other networks in case of availability of places. The trainings will be free of charge, but the participants must sustain their travel expenses (travel, accommodation and allowance). An invitation letter and an application form to participate in three trainings have been sent. A registration link was included in the invitation letter with a deadline of August 10, 2022.

JIP4-WP5-T3-S1

The proposed timetable for the training on ETEC/STEC and *Cryptosporidium* will be held at ISS: First round 3rd-5th of October 2022; second round 23rd-25th of November 2022

A training on AMR in *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* spp. to be held at SSI on the 26th -28th of October 2022 was planned. However, no one has registered even though we have extended the deadline and sent out reminders. The workshop has been cancelled.

JIP4-WP5-T3-S2

The protocols for the e-learning contents are now being selected and will be based on the protocols of the practical workshops. The realization of the videos is planned in the next three months.

6.1.2.2.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA.2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP.4.3	A technical report of Harmonised protocols including; 1) detection of selected pathogens, and 2) characterisation (e.g. virulence genes asset) and typing of pathogens.	57	57		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038212	2, 4, 6
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.4	Integrated OneHealth Instrument	54	57	59	Delayed	2, 4, 6
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.5	Technical report: overview of the sampling and analyses that are performed on behalf of our food business operators HACCP-based self-control programs	50	51		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6414920	2, 4, 6

JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 3.3	A harmonised food safety data management system for Europe	57	56		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6899935	2,4,6
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 5.1	Workshop	57	57		The workshop was held on September 20 th	2,4,6
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 5.2	Workshop	57	57		The workshop was held on September 21 st	2,4,6
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 5.3	Training programs for the application of the harmonised protocols	54-60				
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 5.4	E-learning modules on the application of the harmonised protocols	60				

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

Summary Progress Report
Fifth Year - 2022
M49-M57

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2. OH-HARMONY-CAP.7	Delivery of practical workshops on the harmonised protocols	54-60			
JIP04-OH-HARMONY-CAP	M-IA2.2. OH-HARMONY-CAP.8	Delivery of e-learning sessions on the harmonised protocols	60			

6.1.2.2.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Gill A, Dussault F, McMahon T, Petronella N, Wang X, Cebelinski E, Scheutz F, Kelly Weedmark K, Blais B, Carrillo C. Characterisation of atypical Shiga toxin gene sequences and description of Stx2j, a new subtype. J Clin Microbiol 2022 Mar 16;60(3):e0222921. doi: 10.1128/jcm.02229-21 https://zenodo.org/record/6637837#.YxHBTXbP2Uk . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6637837	Yes	March 16 th , 2022	

6.1.2.2.5 Additional output

Three posters presented by: 33-NVI, Typing and Characterization methods of Shiga toxin producing E. coli. 9-BfR, Microbiological sampling and analyses in the food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes. 1-ANSES, OH-HARMONY-CAP WP4: selection of harmonized protocols for the detection and characterization of model pathogenic microorganisms. OH-HARMONY-CAP project leader presented the project at the Project Leaders Forum (PLF), April 12th ASM 2022

OH-HARMONY-CAP are organising the third One Health CPD module together with the National Food Institute at the Technical University of Denmark (12-DTU). The aim is to bring together professionals and experiences (from the perspectives of both trainers and trainees) from different domains and encourage to seek out new synergies and collaborations

6.1.2.2.6 Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

First, the development of the first OHLabCap tool using the EU online survey tool is in itself a major achievement, which is open for adaptation by other key stakeholders in the OH field such as FAO and WHO, who are conducting similar surveys. The inclusion of private food operators and laboratories in the mini survey of this project is – to our knowledge - the first of its kind and could potentially represent an improvement in the communication between the private sector and One Health authorities. Both parties could benefit from the results. The involvement of these stakeholders could in return serve as inspiration for the further development of tools intended to measure the dimensions and targets in the OHLabCap tool (D-IA2.2.OH-HARMONY-CAP 2.4, M54).

Second, the proposed harmonised procedures will have an impact either in the activities of this project, as they will not only be the subject of training sessions, but also represent methodologies available to

the scientific community through the dissemination of the WP4 results. The strategy designed in WP4 for ranking protocols can represent a tool that may be applied, following ad hoc remodulation, for the definition of fit-for-purpose procedures for microorganisms other than those considered in this project.

Third, considerable data generated by the human, animal, food, feed and environmental testing laboratories throughout Europe is not reported because this is not required under the current regulatory framework. This data is essential to provide the scientific basis for food safety policy development. The conceptual harmonised data reporting and management system will also address this issue and provide a user-friendly mechanism for harvesting this information.

Fourth, the e-learning sessions will represent an important outcome, being available also for a large public far beyond the project's participants. In fact, these video documents will be published on the OH-HARMONY-CAP website to ensure the maximum dissemination of the contents and impacting in the transfer of knowledge to a larger scientific community.

Fifth, the results of OH-HARMONY-CAP will improve One Health interoperability across NRLs on three target areas: Sampling & testing, characterisation, and data management & harmonised reporting. By identification of gaps, the project supports best practices to detect and characterise foodborne pathogens across the One Health sectors. Surveillance strategies can then be adjusted based on the developed guidance for improvement of One Health interoperability across NRLs.

From a societal point of view, OH-HARMONY-CAP contributes to the decrease of AMR burden and of exposure to foodborne zoonotic agents through improved surveillance, diagnosis and data analysis.

Finally, all the work packages have underlined the importance of being able to adjust and adapt to the ongoing and ever changing challenges in the field of microbiology.

Additional output

Three posters presented by:

- 33-NVI, Typing and Characterization methods of Shiga toxin producing E. coli. 9-BfR, Microbiological sampling and analyses in the food business operators' HACCP-based self-control programmes.
- 1-ANSES, OH-HARMONY-CAP WP4: selection of harmonized protocols for the detection and characterization of model pathogenic microorganisms.
- 13-SSI, OH-HARMONY-CAP project leader presented the project at the Project Leaders Forum (PLF), April 12th ASM 2022

OH-HARMONY-CAP is organising the third One Health CPD module together with the National Food Institute at the Technical University of Denmark (12-DTU). The module will draw from the experiences and new knowledge from three One Health EJP Joint Integrative Projects: OH-Harmony-CAP, MATRIX, and CARE. This module will discuss the role of diagnostics and related challenges from both the microbiological and epidemiological perspectives. Outbreak case studies based on real outbreaks will actively engage both epidemiologists and microbiologists, walking participants through the different roles that each group plays during an outbreak scenario. This structure will allow each group to improve their understanding of the perspectives of the other when dealing with an outbreak together, focusing on the effects of applying rapid and/or harmonised diagnostic tests.

Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project

First, the development of the first OHLabCap tool using the EU online survey tool is open for adaptation to other key stakeholders in the OH field such as FAO and WHO, who are conducting similar surveys. The inclusion of private food operators and laboratories in the mini survey of this project is – to our knowledge - the first of its kind and could potentially represent an improvement in the communication between the private sector and One Health authorities.

Second, the proposed harmonised procedures for STEC/EPEC and the decision tree for *Cryptosporidium* will have an impact either in the activities of this project, as they will not only be the subject of training sessions, but also available to the scientific community through the dissemination of the WP4 results. These tools may be applied, following *ad hoc* remodulation, for the definition of fit-for-purpose procedures for microorganisms other than those considered in this project.

Third, considerable data generated by the human, animal, food, feed and environmental testing laboratories throughout Europe are not reported to neither EFSA nor ECDC because this is not required under the current regulatory framework. These data are essential to provide the scientific basis for food safety policy development.

Fourth, the e-learning sessions will represent an important outcome, being available also for other than the project participants. In fact, these video documents will be published, among others, on the OH-HARMONY-CAP website to ensure the maximum dissemination of the contents and impacting in the transfer of knowledge to a larger scientific community.

Fifth, the results of OH-HARMONY-CAP may improve One Health interoperability on three target areas: Sampling & testing, characterisation, and data management & harmonised reporting. By identification of gaps, the project supports best practices to detect and characterise foodborne pathogens across the One Health sectors. Surveillance strategies can then be adjusted based on the developed guidance for improvement of One Health interoperability across NRLs.

From a societal point of view, OH-HARMONY-CAP contributes to the decrease of AMR burden and of exposure to foodborne zoonotic agents through improved surveillance, diagnosis and data analysis.

Finally, all the work packages have underlined the importance of being able to adjust and adapt to the ongoing and ever-changing challenges in the field of microbiology.

1.1.1.1.1.1 [Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations \(e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO\), networks, or national ministries](#)

OH-HARMONY-CAP is organising the third One Health CPD module together with the National Food Institute at the Technical University of Denmark (12-DTU). The aim is to bring together professionals and experiences (from the perspectives of both trainers and trainees) from different domains and encourage to seek out new synergies and collaborations.

Furthermore, OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX have prepared a thematic call for original publications, whether research, perspectives, or policy, in the domain of integrated One Health surveillance. This call was launched in the journal *Frontiers in Public Health*. The call will close end of October 2022. We hope that this call might collect some of the intermediate achievements of the OHEJP JIPs OH-HARMONY-CAP, CARE and MATRIX with a special focus on the integrative aspects of the projects' methods and strategies.

6.1.2.3 JIP05-R2-IA2.1-MATRIX

6.1.2.3.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

JIP05-MATRIX (here below MATRIX, <https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-matrix/>) is an EU-co-funded project within the framework of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP). It aims to advance the implementation of One Health Surveillance (OHS) in practice by building on existing resources, adding value to them, and creating synergies among the Animal Health (AH), Public Health (PH) and Food Safety (FS) sectors. Currently, nineteen partners from twelve European countries constitute the MATRIX Consortium.

MATRIX creates solutions for European countries to advance the implementation of OHS. During the reporting period of this document – month-49 (M49) to M57 – the major achievements of the project included:

- WP1 – Performing a comprehensive review of existing OHS systems, based on scientific literature and the hazard-specific experiences of MATRIX partners and of other institutes outside the project's Consortium
- WP2 – Defining a format to document best practices for data collection, data sharing, data analysis and interpretation, and the communication of results (including flow-charts and checklists) to operationalize OHS
- WP3 – Identifying appropriate output-based surveillance methodologies according to the objective of specific systems, covering for 3 hazards in 5 countries
- WP4 – Finalizing the OH-EpiCap tool and releasing a beta version of an online interface for the tool. The tool has been deployed across 5 hazards in 6 countries
- WP5 – Continuing the design and evaluation of a roadmap for OHS; adapting and extending the OHS Codex into a Knowledge Integration Platform (KIP) aligned with the MATRIX objectives and scope; reimplementation of mathematical models in the Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) format; continuing training and dissemination activities
- WP6 – Continuing the design of user-driven dashboards for collaboration and decision making in OHS
- Continuing to ensure that MATRIX work encompasses relevant pathogens by pairing the activities of Work Packages (WPs) with that of Hazard Tracks (HTs)

Following the revision of the original Work Plan [see the JIP05-MATRIX 12-Month Report Y4 (2021)] that occurred in 2021, the MATRIX Consortium advanced the planned activities during the first months of 2022. The project continued i) to benefit from the results produced by other EJP projects; ii) to expand the synergies and links among the different WPs and sectors, which is at the core of the aim of the project.

6.1.2.3.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WPO Coordination

JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T1 Internal coordination – M25-60

Activities included: i) managing routine meetings with the MATRIX Consortium and the WP/HT leaders; ii) supporting the routine management of WPs; iii) continuous documentation/reporting of the project progresses; writing the 9-month report for Year 5 (2022) in collaboration with WP and HT leaders; iv) routine and extraordinary budgetary management; v) ongoing housekeeping of the project webpage; vi) welcoming and orientating new colleagues in the Consortium e.g. after handover at partner institute level.

JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T2 External coordination and communication – M25-60

Activities included: i) routine communication with OHEJP WP4 and OHEJP Coordination Team; ii) communicating with other OHEJP projects (from the first and second call), and with external relevant projects and stakeholders (see *JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability*).

JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T3 Data management – M25-60

Within the MATRIX Consortium, the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (9-BfR) has had the responsibility of the MATRIX Data Management Plan since spring 2021. Partner 9-BfR is sending quarterly reminders for updates. A continuous update of the data management plan in the CDP-tool is ongoing.

JIP-MATRIX-WP0-T4 Sustainability – M25-60

The MATRIX Consortium continued working and advanced with the sustainability strategy of the project as per the plan developed during 2021. Notably:

- MATRIX partners initiated the documentation of their plans and/or opportunities to put into practice the solutions for OHS that the project is developing, once they are finalized.
- MATRIX partners launched the OHEJP MATRIX Webinar Series – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe (https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/MATRIX-Webinars-invitation_final.pdf). See *JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4 Training and dissemination* for a list of the conducted seminars as per June 2022.
- MATRIX partners are working on the special edition for the thematic call One Health Surveillance in Practice: Experiences of Integration among Human Health, Animal Health, Environmental Health, and Food Safety Sectors in the Journal *Frontiers in Public Health* (<https://www.frontiersin.org/research-topics/28964/one-health-surveillance-in-practice-experiences-of-integration-among-human-health-animal-health-envi>).

During the MATRIX Consortium meeting that took place in Berlin and online in March 2022, MATRIX partners and representatives from other JIPs, OHEJP, EFSA, European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and other initiatives discussed over the legacy of the JIP projects and how to ensure their sustainability. The output of that discussion is guiding the MATRIX sustainability strategy in 2022.

WP1 Existing frameworks and OH capacity

JIP-MATRIX-WP1-T1 Generate an inventory of existing frameworks for surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards, by sector (AH, PH, and FS) – M25-36

Although this task and its related deliverable (D-WP1.1) have been completed, the associated inventory is continuously updated to capture new surveillance systems.

JIP-MATRIX-WP1-T2 Generate suggestions for adaptation of existing frameworks into a common sectorial framework (AH, PH, FS) which can support surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards (OHS) – M37-54

The objective of this task is to provide recommendations in the form of a guideline to adapt existing sectorial frameworks into one common system for AH, PH and FS. The task performed a comprehensive review of existing OHS systems, based on scientific literature and the hazard-specific experiences of MATRIX partner and other institutes outside of the project's Consortium (in progress, 6 out of 15 planned are completed).

This task provides the content of deliverable *D-WP1.2 Description of a common framework for OH surveillance* (due in M54).

JIP-MATRIX-WP1-T3 Evaluation of the sectorial frameworks, for specific inter-sectorial hazards – M49-60

The task is ongoing as per September 2022. Eventually an interactive guide to adapt existing AH, PH and FS surveillance frameworks into multi-sectorial systems will be produced within the task. This task ensures the development and testing of the aforementioned interactive guide. This task also provides the content of deliverable *D-WP1.3 Report on the evaluation of the common framework using examples within the consortium* (due in M58).

WP2 Best-practices and multi-sectorial collaboration

JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T1 Mapping of the surveillance chain across all sectors for each hazard-track – M25-35

The task does not span the reporting period of this document. The task and its related deliverable (D-WP2.1) are completed.

JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T2 Identify cross-sectorial surveillance chain linkages, particularly, which outputs should be shared and how they should be shared for OH orientated decision making – M30-48

The task does not span the reporting period of this document. The task and its related deliverable (D-WP2.1) are completed.

JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T3 Propose best-practice guidelines and effective strategies for data collection, analysis, and dissemination aimed at multi-sectorial OH collaboration, for each specific hazard-track – M33-54

This task develops hazard-specific best practices for multi-sectorial collaboration and puts OHS into practice. A format has been defined to document best practices for data collection, data sharing, data analysis and interpretation, and communication of results, for three different surveillance purposes: i) measure the levels and temporal trends of exposure and burden of disease; ii) support early detection and response to outbreaks; iii) identify risk factors to implement control measures. A document providing general information on the context and contents has been drafted, which will be accompanied by four table-type attachments, one per sector (data collection, data sharing, data analysis, communication of results). In each table, the sector has been split into aspects, features, and steps, where relevant general and Hazard-specific annotations are gathered. This task provides the content of deliverable *D-WP2.2 Suggested best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration to achieve OHS, hazard-specific (hazard tracks)* (delivered in M54).

JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T4 Identify commonalities across the tracks, to propose a common OHS framework when applicable – M46-60

The task is ongoing as per September 2022. This task is summarizing the information collected by previous tasks, particularly WP2-T3, in which hazard-specific best practices for multi-sectorial collaboration are explored and described. This task provides the content of deliverable *D-WP2.3 Common framework of OHS* (due in M58) and will summarize the results coming from the activities conducted under WP2.

WP3 Output-based surveillance evaluation

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T1 Inventory of previous work and current practice – M25-36

The task does not span the reporting period of this document. The task is completed. The Milestone M-WP3.1 “*End of the first round of OHEJP projects: this will coincide with the end of the inventory and requirement analysis phase in most WPs*” was successfully accomplished in M48.

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T2 Identification of operational partners and stakeholders – M25-60

The task is ongoing as per September 2022. The originally planned stakeholder mapping exercise was delayed due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic and an Avian Influenza outbreak, as this WP is primarily implemented by partners working in the AH sector. However, this task spans the entire duration of MATRIX and the delay should not affect its outcome. Specific case studies about *Salmonella* in pigs (AH, PH and FS) and *Echinococcus multilocularis* (AH – domestic and wildlife, PH) were set up.

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T3 Selection of appropriate output-based surveillance systems – M37-54

Participating partners have identified appropriate output-based methodologies according to the specific objective of the surveillance system they have selected i.e. *Salmonella* in layer flocks (21-APHA), *Salmonella* in pigs (41-SVA), *Salmonella* Dublin in cattle (University of Copenhagen), SARS-CoV-2 in companion animals (31-WBVR) and *Echinococcus multilocularis* in red fox and stray dog populations (34-PIWET). This task provides the content of deliverable D-WP3.1 Report on the output-based surveillance system selection methodology for each country and as many of the approaches as possible (delivered in M54).

JIP-MATRIX-WP3-T4 Development of evaluation strategies for surveillance systems based on output-based metrics – M40-60

The task is ongoing as per September 2022. This task is looking at strategies to evaluate the effectiveness of surveillance systems within the three sectors: AH, PH and FS. Participating partners are reviewing the appropriate output metrics that are to be used to develop a country-specific standard for evaluation. Deliverable D-WP3.2 Combined report for all subtasks within the development of output-based metrics (due in M58) will incorporate and summarise i) the inventory of previous work (based on a literature review); ii) the stakeholder mapping and iii) the development of evaluation strategies.

WP4 Benchmarking tool for characterising, monitoring and evaluating OH capacities and capabilities (EUEpiCap)

JIP-MATRIX-WP4-T1 Review of existing methods for surveillance systems evaluation – M25-39

The task does not span the reporting period of this document. The task and its related deliverable (D-WP4.1) are completed.

JIP-MATRIX-WP4-T2 Development of the surveillance capacity benchmarking tool – M37-54

Building on WP4-T1, in this task a questionnaire was created, with a scoring system, to evaluate capacity and capability of a system against a specific hazard. The questionnaire is currently being finalized, pending minor edits as we gather feedback. An R Shiny-based interface was also developed (currently in beta version - <https://carlijnboogaardt.shinyapps.io/OH-EpiCap/>) to deploy the tool and automatically generate a country profile report, as well as explore outcomes through various visualization options. A tutorial has been created (https://onehealthjep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/OHEJP_MATRIX_OH-EpiCap_user_guide_2022_06.pdf) to explain how to use the tool. The tool was reviewed by the MATRIX consortium and experts in OH and multi-sectoral surveillance, including the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). The OH-EpiCap tool and the questionnaire have been already piloted with antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in Portugal and in France, psittacosis in Denmark, *Salmonella* in Germany, in the Netherlands, and in France, *Campylobacter* in Sweden, and *Listeria* in the Netherlands. In the framework of the CoEvalAMR project, the tool will be applied to AMR surveillance systems in other countries and the tool itself will also be evaluated. This task provides the content of deliverable D-WP4.2 OH-EpiCap tool and tutorial (delivered in M54).

JIP-MATRIX-WP4-T3 Application and evaluation of the tool – M49-60

The task is ongoing as per September 2022. Based on the results of task WP4-T2, this task provides the content of deliverable D-WP4.3 Report on the implementation of evaluation approaches on two studies cases (due M58).

JIP-MATRIX-WP4-T3 Application and evaluation of the tool – M49-60

The task is ongoing as per June 2022. Based on the results of task WP4-T2, this task provides the content of deliverable *D-WP4.3 Report on the implementation of evaluation approaches on two studies cases* (due M58).

WP5 Outreach and roadmap

JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T1 Perform a requirement analysis for national OH surveillance roadmaps – M25-51

The task and its related deliverable (D-WP5.1) were completed in M51 as per updated Annual Work Plan (AWP) Year 5.

JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T2 Develop a national OH surveillance roadmap – M37-60

The task is ongoing as per September 2022.

In late 2021, MATRIX identified additional synergies with the JIP COHESIVE on the topic of OHS roadmaps and the two projects strengthened their collaboration and exchanges. Accordingly, the activities of the MATRIX WP5-T2 were adapted (see the updated AWP Year 5). MATRIX is now evaluating and further developing the roadmap developed by JIP COHESIVE (<https://www.ohras.eu/>). Systems thinking workshops were conducted in Sweden and Denmark during spring 2022. The webpage and guidelines of the roadmap are currently being updated considering the results of the requirement analysis (WP5-T1), and results/solutions from other work packages that can contribute to different steps of the roadmap. User stories from workshops that were performed in Sweden, Denmark and Norway will also be included.

This task provides the content of deliverable *D-WP5.2 OHS roadmap template document* (due in M58).

JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T3 Knowledge-Integration Platform – M25-60

The task is ongoing as per September 2022. The development of the Knowledge-Integration Platform is progressing in frequent task-specific meetings. In the past, the OHS Codex, which was developed in the JIP ORION project, was extended to serve as a Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP) for MATRIX as well. This was done by adding a new principle that focuses on surveillance planning and management, updating the existing principles and including new methods, training materials and examples of OHS reports. This work resulted in what is today known as the “OHS Codex: The Knowledge integration platform” (OHS Codex/KIP, <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>). In 2022, all MATRIX solutions developed in the project to advance OHS in practice will be included in the OHS Codex/KIP. The OHS Codex/KIP also aims at raising awareness of the work achieved by other One Health EJP projects (e.g., One Health EJP Outcome Inventory) and create synergies with other initiatives relevant for the OH community such as the Surveillance and Information Sharing (SIS) Operational Tool (OT) developed by Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) and World Health Organization (WHO).

The OHS Codex/KIP also continues to support the aspect of exchanging mathematical models efficiently between different OH sectors via the Food Safety Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) format (see <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/fsk-ml-food-safety-knowledge-markup-language/>). In June 2022, two dissemination activities take place to promote the adoption of the FSKX format by OH professionals and modellers (see WP5-T4 here below). Furthermore, during 2022 three new models (dose-response, exposure model and population risk model for *Campylobacter*) have been re-implemented in the FSKX format.

JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4 Training and dissemination – M25-60

The task is ongoing until the end of 2022. MATRIX partners are contributing to enrich the opportunities for training and dissemination, which are planned in frequent task-specific meetings.

List of training and dissemination activities in 2022 – see the JIP05-MATRIX 12-Month Report Y5 (2022) for a full list of the project’s training and dissemination activities in 2020 and 2021

OHS Briefings	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inform about OHS initiatives and projects on EU level will actively involve stakeholders, such as EFSA and ECDC e.g. webinars/meetings 	
2022 February 24 – WP6 presentation – Di Pasquale (28-IZSAM), Presentation about the COHESIVE Information System – available at: https://svasweden-my.sharepoint.com/:p:/g/personal/fernanda_dorea_sva_se/EQ03yX1dzYfInl9jvHe4ccBKwniT8WCicyjw8DiLbqDxw?e=KgwnUD	
25 March 2022 – OHEJP WP5 Dissemination Workshop, Improving One Health Preparedness to (re)emerging infectious threats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cito and Amato, Mapping existing surveillance chains at country level (MATRIX WP2) Hénaux and Prada, How to assess capacity to perform One Health surveillance? (MATRIX WP4)
11-13 April 2022 – One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 – Eves et al., Barriers and facilitators to one health surveillance at the national level in Europe: a systematic review of the literature (poster, WP5)	
11-13 April 2022 – One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 – Gustafsson and Grøneng, A practical manual for one health surveillance dashboards (poster, WP6)	
19 April 2022 – WP6 presentation – Dibba White (23-SSI), Presentation about the work behind the Danish COVID-19 dashboard – available at: https://svasweden-my.sharepoint.com/:p:/g/personal/fernanda_dorea_sva_se/EWuYKUWnJX9KrQ_uEcPLeI8BpiwLd9OcMySIFb11-UpCqA?e=5j4ZoS	
27-28 April 2022 – Greifswald One Health Conference 2022 – An inventory of zoonotic and food borne disease surveillance systems: expanding and understanding the One Health knowledge base (poster, WP1)	
03-05 May 2022 – International conference on animal health surveillance (ICAHS) – Tegegne et al., OH-EpiCap: a semi quantitative tool for the evaluation of One Health surveillance capacities and capabilities (poster, WP4)	
03-05 May 2022 – International conference on animal health surveillance (ICAHS) – Lefèvre et al., Evaluating the capacities and capabilities of a One Health surveillance system is feasible: a case study on psittacosis in Denmark (poster, WP4)	
19 May 2022 – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: WEBINAR SERIES 2022 – OH-EpiCap tool	
8 June 2022 – Solutions for One Health Surveillance in Europe, OHEJP MATRIX: webinar series 2022 – food safety knowledge exchange (fskx) format	
20 June 2022 – EFSA ONE Conference 2022, Side Event – workshop for one health professionals on efficient exchange of mathematical models and data analysis procedures with the harmonized fskx format	

Training materials e.g., tutorials, videos, and guidelines	
FSKX format, RAKIP Model repository and FSK-Lab supporting training material in Moodle platform (https://bfr-elearning.de/ Username: fsk-workshop21; Password: Matrix.2110)	

WP6 Decision and collaboration dashboards

JIP-MATRIX-WP6-T1 Country-based Identification of existing cross-sectorial OHs activities – M25-36

The task does not span the reporting period of this document. The task is completed.

A live document titled *Decision and Collaboration Dashboards: an Inventory* (<https://sva-se.github.io/MATRIX-dashboards/>) collects the ongoing developments of the entire WP and a list of the planned, ongoing or finished dashboard projects of participating partners.

JIP-MATRIX-WP6-T2 Defining the content needs for cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards – M34-60

The task is ongoing as per September 2022. Following the work in MATRIX WP6-T1, and considering the hazards of relevance to MATRIX, this task invites partners to have inter-agency discussions on the possibilities and problems that can be addressed with joint analyses and/or visualization of data. The design of cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards is driven from the end user perspective, including information gaps and methodological limitations, technical and legal barriers associated with data sharing. This task provides the content of deliverable *D-WP6.1 User manual for construction and implementation of OH dashboards using open source tools (source codes)* (due in M58).

JIP-MATRIX-WP6-T3 Technical implementation and testing of dashboards – M37-60

The task is ongoing as per September 2022. This task implements country-specific, cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards. The deliverable of this task will be a dashboard inventory, to be used within MATRIX and hopefully beyond. A specific focus is on the sustainability of information (data usefulness and relevance) and the technical sustainability of dashboards (the used platforms). This task provides the content of deliverable *D-WP6.2 A practical manual to the use of dashboards in OHS practice, including recommendations for sustainability* (due in M58).

MATRIX Hazard Tracks

The problem-oriented approach of the project is reflected in the creation of hazard-specific tracks to ensure that the solutions that MATRIX develops are relevant to specific pathogens. MATRIX can be represented as a frame of activities and hazards. The hazards were chosen based on the operational priorities of MATRIX partner institutes and their One Health relevance. They are *Listeria*, *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and emerging threats, including antimicrobial resistance.

Figure 1 shows an overview of the current links between WPs and HTs in MATRIX.

In 2022, HT leaders have initiated a process of documentation and capitalization of the lessons learned while ensuring the representativeness and relevance of a specific hazard in the work of the different WPs. Monthly meetings are organized accordingly.

Figure 1 – MATRIX of actual (blue) and planned (orange) links between WPs, HTs and countries of coverage (as relevant) as per September 2022.

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
Listeria	Norway	Human / Food / Animal Sector Norway, Italy, Netherlands		Netherlands		
Salmonella	France	Human / Food / Animal Sector France, Spain, Germany, Norway, UK	Human / Food / Animal Sector UK, Sweden, Denmark	France*, Netherlands, Germany	Sweden	
Campylobacter		Human / Food / Animal Sector France, Germany, Norway, Denmark, Sweden		Denmark		Norway
Emerging threat: Hepatitis E		Human / Food / Animal Sector Portugal, Netherlands, Italy, Norway		Italy		
Emerging threat: SARS-CoV-2		Animal Sector UK	Human / Animal Sector Netherlands			
Emerging threat: Echinococcus M.			Human / Animal Sector Poland			
Emerging threat: AMR	England			France - Portugal - More applications coming in the framework of the CoEvalAMR project		
Emerging threat: Psittacosis				Denmark		
Emerging threat: WNV	Italy, Austria					
Emerging threat: Zoonotic pathogens	Tanzania					Sweden
Whole Genome Sequencing for microbial pathogens						Italy

Actual contribution
Follow-up/Planned

*Planned OH-EpiCap tool evaluations. AMR: Antimicrobial Resistance; WNV: West Nile Virus

6.1.2.3.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2022 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19 pandemic), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP1.2	Description of a common framework for OH surveillance	54			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022 Public Johanna Dups-Bergmann, & Carola Sauter-Louis. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP1.2 Description of a common framework for One Health surveillance. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7064374	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP2.2	Suggested best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration in order to achieve OHS, hazard-specific (hazard tracks)	54			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022 Public Francesca Cito, Laura Amato, Taran Skjerdal, Stine Kjær Lefèvre, Joaquin Prada, Charlotte Cook, & Caroline Eves. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP2.2 Best practices. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7053387	1, 6

JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP3.1	Report on the output-based surveillance system selection methodology for each country and as many of the approaches as possible	54		<p>The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022</p> <p>Public</p> <p>Verity Horigan, Beate Conrady, Liza Rosenbaum Nielsen, Hans Houe, Mark Arnold, Jo Lawes, Rob Davies, Arianna Comin, Beth Young, Estelle Ågren, Lukasz Bocian, Anna Zietek-Bocian, Agnieszka Stolarek, Mirek Rozycki, Rob Dewar, Sam Rivers, Alex Kent, Jose Gonzales, Nora Gerhards, & Wim van der Poel. (2022). D-WP3.1_MATRIX Report on output-based surveillance system selection methodology. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6984562</p>	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP4.2	OH-EpiCap tool and tutorial	54		<p>The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022</p> <p>Public</p> <p>Viviane Henaux, Henok Tegegne, Carlijn Bogaardt, Renaud Lailier, Lucie Collineau, & Joaquin Prada. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP4.2 OH-EpiCap tool and tutorial. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7006654</p> <p>Note: the change in the name of the tool from “EU-EpiCap” to “OH-EpiCap”, which was approved by OHEJP WP4 in March 2022,</p>	1, 6

						was not documented in the AWP 2022 at the time this report was first drafted (June 2022).	
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP5.1	Report on requirement analysis for "OHS roadmap template"		51		Public Eves, Caroline, Friesema, Ingrid, Skjerdal, Olaug Taran, Holmberg, Mia, Ågren, Estelle, Lopez de Abechuco, Estibaliz, Daugaard Larsen, Helle, Kjær Lefèvre, Stine, & Benedetti, Guido. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP5.1 - Report on requirement analysis for "OHS roadmap template". Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504418 Note: the last extension of this deliverable (from M48 to M51), which was approved by OHEJP WP4 in October 2021, was not documented in the AWP 2022 at the time this report was drafted.	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP0.2	Data Management Plan – final	58			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP0.3	Sustainability document	58			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP1.3	Report on the evaluation of the common framework using examples within the consortium	58			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP2.3	Common framework of OHS surveillance	58			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022	1, 6

JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP3.2	Combined report for all subtasks within the development of output-based metrics	58			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP4.3	Report on the implementation of evaluation approaches on two studies cases	58			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP5.2	OHS roadmap template document	58			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP6.1	User manual for construction and implementation of OH dashboards using open source tools (source codes)	58			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022	1, 6
JIP05-MATRIX	D-WP6.2	A practical manual to the use of dashboards in OHS practice, including recommendations for sustainability	58			The original delivery date was updated in the AWP 2022	1, 6

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JIP/ JRP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2022 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
JIP05-MATRIX	M-WP4.1	Deployment of the EUEpiCap survey tool in several	54			Uploaded to Zenodo

		European countries on study cases				Viviane Henaux, Henok Tegegne, Carlijn Bogaardt, Renaud Lailler, Lucie Collineau, & Joaquin Prada. (2022). Milestone M-JIP-MATRIX-WP4.1 Deployment of the OH-EpiCap survey tool in several European countries on study cases. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7006609
JIP05-MATRIX	M-WP6.1	Dashboards operational within the pilot participating agencies	54			

6.1.2.3.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Sundermann EM, Nauta M, Swart A (2021). A ready-to-use dose-response model of <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> implemented in the FSKX-standard. Food Modelling Journal 2: e63309. Doi reference: https://doi.org/10.3897/fmj.2.63309 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/4923018	Yes		Yes, 0 Euro
Sundermann EM, Correia Carreira G, Käsbohrer A (2021). A FSKX compliant source attribution model for salmonellosis and a look at its major hidden pitfalls. Food Modelling Journal 2: e70008. Doi reference: https://doi.org/10.3897/fmj.2.70008 Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/5674165#.YZ5rANDMJPY	Yes		Yes, 0 Euro

6.1.2.3.5 Additional output

See above the list of activities covered by the *JIP-MATRIX-WP5-T4 Training and dissemination*.

Relevant outputs from JIP-MATRIX-WP2-T1 have been included in the Ph.D. project of an expert from 28-IZSAM, member of the MATRIX Consortium and specifically working on WP2, as a case study on the application of the OH Approach. The project focused on case studies about the application of OH in different contexts, i.e. vector-borne and food-borne diseases. The project belongs to the Ph.D. course in “Infectious Diseases, Microbiology and Public Health” at the Sapienza University of Rome (Italy).

The infrastructure for the BIOPIGEE Glossary developed in 2021 within MATRIX to support the JRP BIOPIGEE project is further maintained in 2022. The BIOPIGEE Glossary allows users to filter, search and read terms and definitions created within BIOPIGEE (<https://bit.ly/3oQwbom>).

6.1.2.3.6 Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

MATRIX creates solutions for European countries to support and to advance the implementation of OHS. All the solutions are relevant achievements with an impact. See a list and description of the MATRIX Solutions for OHS at the project’s webpage (<https://onehealthjp.eu/jip-matrix/>).

6.1.2.3.7 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

In 2022, the MATRIX Consortium expanded and strengthened its networking with representatives from the EFSA, the ECDC, the SIS OT of the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide, and the project SafeConsume. For example, representatives of the aforementioned agencies, initiatives and projects participated and contributed to the works of the MATRIX Consortium meeting that was held in March 2022. Also, MATRIX representatives participated in the training activities of the SIS OT in May 2022.

Thanks to the collaboration with other JIPs of the second call, JIP CARE and JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP, partners 13-SSI and 12-DTU are currently collaborating to develop the OHEJP Continuing Professional Development training in November 2022, also drawing the lessons learned from the 3 projects.

Several MATRIX members were also members of the JIP ORION project, and thus they were able to transfer results and add value to them within MATRIX. MATRIX WP1 leaders were also leaders of the WP on epidemiological knowledge sharing in OH in JIP ORION. Leaders of MATRIX WP5 and MATRIX WP6 were part of an initiative in JIP ORION – called “supra-national One-health pilot” that was working closely with EFSA and ECDC to determine how the OH tools developed in JIP ORION can be applied at the European Union level. We expect this work to directly benefit the roadmap and outreach work that is being developed in MATRIX WP5.

MATRIX WP1 has been working closely together with WP2 of JIP ORION, where 10-FLI was actively involved. MATRIX WP1 is further building on JIP ORION’s OH surveillance inventories. Also, the experience of JRP NOVA is considered within MATRIX WP1-T2 through ongoing interviews. The final guidelines delivered by the WP will also be developed in collaboration with JIP COVRIN. In Germany, collaborations were continued between the MATRIX WP1 leaders (10-FLI) and OHEJP partners at 9-BfR. Furthermore, 10-FLI is engaged in different working groups and projects with EFSA, working on surveillance and different animal diseases, and EFSA, regarding their terminology and inventory variables.

MATRIX WP2 leaders have also been leaders of the JIP COHESIVE WP4 regarding a data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control as well as deputy leaders of the JRP NOVA WP2-T1 about the availability of food purchase data and barriers. MATRIX WP2 is also collaborating with the JRP BeONE in the evaluation and implementation of national level data sharing as lead and deputy lead on several tasks. In addition, national-level collaborations were developed in France with surveillance actors: French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, national reference laboratories on *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*; and Santé Publique France, the National Public Health Agency. These experiences contribute to the work e.g. WP2-T3 lessons learnt from JRP NOVA.

In addition, the MATRIX WP2 leader is the coordinator of the SIGMA Consortium, a project funded by EFSA, which aims at finding solutions for facilitating the exchange of data between Member States and EFSA. Although the SIGMA project is limited to AH issues, the data mapping solutions and the tools under development in this project are of interest for MATRIX, as possible approaches applicable also in FS. 28-IZSAM is also the coordinator of the EFSA Tender on OH Zoonoses. The tender aims to provide support to EFSA and ECDC in the production of the EU OH Zoonoses yearly report, in the related zoonoses online interactive data visualisation dashboards and story maps. Moreover, experts from 28-IZSAM have been involved in the One Health EJP SimEx as the Local Exercise Leader (LEL) and the Local Evaluator, for the Animal Health sector.

MATRIX WP3 connected with and received support from EFSA, which provided information on current output-based surveillance within the EU and links to the EFSA catalogue browser. Additionally, WP3 have been in contact with members of the JIP COHESIVE to assess the potential of using Mendelow's matrix for Task 2 – identification of operational partners and stakeholders.

In the framework of the MATRIX WP4, national-level collaborations were developed in France with the Food chain surveillance platform (website, in French: <https://www.plateforme-sca.fr/> - description of platform objectives and organisation), especially the research group on *Salmonella* surveillance. International collaborations were identified with ECDC regarding the OH-LabCap tool by JIP OH-HARMONY-CAP and with FAO regarding the SIS OT. Members of MATRIX WP4 also lead activities in JIP COVRIN WP3, with significant benefits to extending MATRIX surveillance work in the area of the hazard SARS-CoV-2.

MATRIX WP5 is collaborating extensively with other projects. MATRIX WP5 member participated in the first JRP DISCoVer Stakeholder Web-meeting and got the chance to determine potential synergies and collaboration. The extension of the FSKX format planned in WP5 is also relevant for the JRP RADAR project. In the JRP RADAR project, a model repository was developed that use the FSKX format, and we are in close communication with the responsible partners. In MATRIX WP5-T3, additional models compliant to the FSKX format were implemented and provided via the RAKIP-Web model repository. The continuous extension of the FSKX format allows to annotate mathematical models from various One Health related domains. To promote these activities also after the end of MATRIX, members of the project joint the Risk Assessment Modelling and Knowledge Integration Platforms (RAKIP) Initiative (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/rakip-web-portal/>). The RAKIP Initiative was founded by ANSES, DTU Food, and BfR. Several institutes joint the RAKIP Initiative during 2022, among them EFSA, SSI, SVA, Ruokavirasto and RIVM. The main objective of the RAKIP Initiative is to continuously improve and extend the community-driven FSKX format e.g. towards One Health.

The work done in MATRIX WP5 on the OHS Codex/KIP also identified high synergies with the work of the FAO/OIE/WHO SIS OT-team. MATRIX WP5 is in close contact with the SIS OT-team to align the work and identify reciprocally beneficial outcomes.

Based on the presentation held at the Cogwheel workshop in November 2020, the SafeConsume community is interested in supporting the OHS Codex and will be invited to joining upcoming meetings. The close collaboration between MATRIX and JIP ORION was continued i.e. former members of JIP ORION participated regularly in MATRIX workshops. For example, several JIP ORION team members

continue to serve on the OHS Codex/KIP steering board, which meets monthly to ensure the update and maintenance of the OHS Codex/KIP.

MATRIX WP5-T2 has established a strong collaboration with JIP COHESIVE and will continue to build upon its work on systems thinking. This task will utilize and benefit greatly from the experience and expertise of both the JIP COHESIVE project leader (30-RIVM) and the Epidemiology Department at the University of Zurich in planning and conducting several Systems Thinking workshops. MATRIX has hosted these workshops in selected partner countries to introduce the systems thinking methodology and create an interactive platform for the mapping of the current surveillance system of a hazard of relevance in each country. WP5-T2 will also build upon the roadmap developed in JIP COHESIVE using knowledge gathered in the WP5-T1 Requirement Analysis and the various Systems Thinking workshops held.

A collaboration with the JRP BIOPIGEE continued. Several terms related to biosecurity measures in primary pig production were defined within the JRP BIOPIGEE project. Within MATRIX we supported the project with an infrastructure that was developed in the former JIP ORION project for the OHEJP Glossary (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/ohejp-glossary/>), and adapted the infrastructure to the needs of the JRP BIOPIGEE consortium. The result is an online solution to host, search, filter and access the terms and definitions defined by the BIOPIGEE consortium (<https://bit.ly/3oQwbom>). Furthermore, it was agreed between MATRIX and JRP BIOPIGEE to place the link on the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-biopigee/>). MATRIX supports the JRP BIOPIGEE project to disseminate the project Glossary and to make the definitions used in JRP BIOPIGEE findable, accessible, and reusable.

WP6 deals with the creation of “data for decision dashboards”. The WP is collaborating with a similar WP in the OHEJP project JRP BeONE. The JIP ORION project has identified data sources that are already public or shared across sectors. The JRP NOVA project has built automated routines for data analyses and visualisation when trend monitoring is possible. The MATRIX project builds on these results and the experience gained through the dashboard development work to create an information centre, which will serve as a best-practice guide for OHS dashboards.

6.1.2.4 JIP06- SARS-CoV2 Research Integration and Preparedness-COVRIN

6.1.2.4.1 Summary of the work carried out in the Project

In Year 5 of the One Health EJP COVRIN project, research work and integration activities were continued as planned on the two main overall operational objectives: A) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2, B) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. In the research area 1) Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal reservoirs and hosts, and the environment, data of SARS-CoV-2 genome testing were further shared and immunoassays methodologies were further shared and harmonized. Approaches in the tasks on assessment of bioavailability were agreed and further developed. In work package 2 on SARS-CoV-2 characterization, genome analyses and next generation sequencing of detected isolates and metagenomic sequencing of different samples were taken forward. At least two surveys were executed to make a summary description of protocols and to make an overview of the key steps of the bioinformatics analyses. A bioinformatics ring trial was prepared to harmonize bioinformatics pipelines. Regarding *in vitro* and *ex vivo* biological characterization of circulating SARS-CoV-2 strains, cell line models have been collated and shared between partners. Animal model protocols have also been categorized and shared between partners. This will allow better analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission. In work package 3 on SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment and surveillance, formats/procedures for sampling and surveillance in wildlife, livestock and pets and the environment were evaluated and reported. Several workshops were organized to involve partners in the surveillance data collection. A review of surveillance activities in the different countries was produced. Risk factors for virus transmission in wildlife reservoirs, food producing animals and the environment

are being studied and analyses of transmissions in pets were produced. An overview of models and parameters to assess transmission in animals was reported. All from a One health perspective. In work package 4 of COVRIN on coronavirus preparedness, isolations of virus from different wildlife species were performed. As a start on the evaluations of the impacts on ecological factors and interventions, a report on relevant sample types and hot spots for coronavirus sampling was put together. In year 5, more work was done on the study of virus – host interactions and on the identification of drivers of virus emergence through evaluation of phylodynamic and cross-species interactions with focus on zoonotic and reverse zoonotic aspects and adaptations. Generated data and research outcomes will be used to develop control strategies, intervention strategies and prevention.

6.1.2.4.2 Progress of the project: description of activities

WPO - Coordination

JIP06-WP0-T0.1 - Internal project organisation (M40 – M63)

ST0.1.1 – Development of SharePoint for data exchange (M40 – M42)

Sub-task completed.

ST0.1.2 – Management reporting year 1 (M40 – M51)

Management reports drafted are uploaded on the SharePoint.

JIP06-WP0-T0.2 - Communication and reporting (M40 – M63)

ST0.2.1 – Communications reporting year 1 (M40 – M51)

The COVRIN project page and group have been set up on the OH EJP website. A comprehensive list of contact details for each work package, task and subtask has been compiled and uploaded to the secure area of the OHEJP website and is in use for organising meetings and compiling reports. Input to the twelve-month report was collated from work package coordinators, and a draft version of the report was submitted to OHEJP WP4 on time. The report will be uploaded onto the SharePoint.

JIP06-WP0-T0.3 - Meetings and stakeholder connections (M40 – M66)

ST0.3.1 – Scoping exercise on related projects (M40 – M45)

Sub-task completed.

ST0.3.2 – Organisation and evaluation of the kick-off meeting (M40 – M48)

Sub-task completed.

ST0.3.3 – Reporting mid-term (M40 – M57)

A series of regular work package meetings was started by June 2021 and all work packages have had update meetings. Several presentations of the COVRIN project were held for stakeholders, REA, OHEJP SSB and OHEJP PMT. Mid-term meeting was held 27th June 2022. Due to the COVID19 outbreak this was an online meeting. Updates and outputs of all 5 work packages were presented by the work package leaders. The meeting was chaired by project leaders Wim van der Poel and Daniel Horton. Presentations are available on the COVRIN project group site and a document including the agenda and the pdfs of the presentations will be uploaded on Zenodo.

WP1 - Detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal reservoirs and hosts, and the environment

JIP06-WP1-T1.1 - SARS-CoV2 genome detection in livestock, wildlife, pets and environmental samples (M40 – M63)

Testing for SARS-CoV-2 by genome detection (with molecular methods) continues in the participating COVRIN laboratories as the most widely implemented method of detection. SARS-CoV-2 has been

detected in 23 different animal species (as of 30th June 2022). Samples from domestic animals from North America and Europe are overrepresented among reported data (WOAH 2022).

Six molecular assays have been assessed in partner laboratories and shared, including real-time quantitative PCR and nested PCR. These data will contribute to deliverables 1.1.1, 1.1.2 and 1.1.3 reports on available data from virus genome detection in companion animals, wildlife and the environment due month 63, and will also contribute to activities in WP3 (surveillance). In addition, a general CoV probe capture target enrichment assay has been designed and shown to increase the sensitivity of detection by two orders of magnitude.

ST1.2.1 – Evaluation of virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals (M40 – M63)

Another important but less used type of assay is rapid antigen tests that detect the viral proteins, often using immunochemistry for rapid application. More than five possible assay protocols have been compiled (FLI, PIWET, APHA). A draft proposal for a harmonized protocol for rapid antigen test establishment and comparison has been developed and an interlaboratory trial is ongoing. The protocol database and finalised comparison will contribute to Deliverable 1.2.1 “Report on methods for virus antigen detection in clinical samples from animals”, due M63.

ST1.2.2 – Evaluation of antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife (M40 – M63)

The final crucial type of test is serology, indirectly detecting current or previous infection through the presence of specific antibodies. The parallel database for sharing of established protocols for antibody detection between partners now includes Double antigen ELISAs (IZSLER), virus neutralisation test (VNT) (APHA, IZSLER), Pseudotype Virus Neutralization test (APHA), and another ELISA INGEZIM COVID 19 S VET – INGENAZA (PIWET)).

Novel antibodies for use in serological assays and antigen detection tests have also been generated and are being assessed. These include antibodies against the nucleoprotein (N protein) and spike protein using recombinant proteins expressed in *E. coli* and Baculovirus respectively, and against whole inactivated virus. These Mabs are being assessed for their ability to bind different Sars-CoV-2 variants with potential for use in antigen tests. Finally, the recombinant proteins themselves are being assessed for their potential in double-antigen ELISAs which can be used to detect antibodies in any species

Results will contribute to Deliverable 1.2.2 “Report on available data from antibody testing in livestock, companion animals and wildlife”, due M63.

JIP06-WP1-T1.3 - Definition of bioavailability of virus in fomites, water and in the environment (M40 – M60)

This task is important to understand the relevance of detecting virus in the environment, by assessing whether the virus is infectious over time and at different temperatures. Approaches being used include literature searches to collect infectivity data from other sources than available from partner institutes and data input from research activities of partner institutes collected via an inventory sheet.

ST1.3.1 - Discuss the relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 in fomites and the environment (M40 – M60)

Detection data can provide insight whether and to which extent different environmental routes may play a role in the human-animal transmission of SARS-CoV-2. A graphical scheme was drafted to provide an overview of various potential environmental routes that may play a role in human-animal transmission of SARS-CoV-2. Next to the relevance of detecting SARS-CoV-2 in the environment, challenges faced by environmental sampling of live SARS-CoV-2 have been discussed during project meetings, but it needs further elaboration. The definition of bioavailability has been commented to be a term that is not (commonly) used within the field of virology. The terms infectivity or viability were suggested as better alternatives and will be used in future reporting.

ST1.3.2 - Assess infectivity of the virus over time, and at different temperatures (M40 – M60)

Infectivity data of live SARS-CoV-2 from environmental sampling (field studies) is still only limitedly available among partner institutes. Activities of partner institutes that are continuing in this area include for example persistence in food and packaging, sewage water surveillance (humans), experimental SARS-CoV-2 studies on survival/decay in environmental matrices, SARS-CoV-2 transmission in animal models, environmental sampling at (mink)farms and in aerosols. To obtain information on infectivity of SARS-CoV-2 in environmental sources of both field and experimental studies, a literature search will be conducted. Literature searches and data collection from partner institutes continue, and together will contribute to deliverable 1.3 report on the bioavailability of virus in fomites, water and the environment due in M60.

sST1.3.3 - Comparison with RNA quantification (PCR versus live virus) to inform risk assessments (M40 – M60)

Work on this task is still to be started. A discussion on the difference in outcome of RNA and live virus detection will be part of the report outline. Detection data of live SARS-CoV-2 studies will be compared to detection data from PCR studies (obtained in T1.1). Initial meetings within WP1 are underway to do this.

WP2 – SARS-CoV-2 characterization

JIP06-WP2-T2.1 – Genome analyses (M40 – M54)

Task 2.1 is focused on the analyses of whole genome sequences of SARS-CoV-2 strains circulating in humans and animals. This involves the exchange of methodologies among partners (sub-tasks 2.1.1 and 2.1.2), as well as phylogenetic analyses and investigation of potential virulence traits (sub-task 2.1.3). In parallel, this task also aims to support the selection of strains from other work packages that may be used for downstream biological characterization in vivo and in vitro.

ST2.1.1 – Protocol repository (M40 – M45)

Sub-task completed.

A final and more comprehensive version of the protocol repository will be publicly released at the end of the project.

ST2.1.2 – Harmonisation of sampling and methods for NGS (M40 – M50, extended from M48)

Within ST2.1.2, a bioinformatics ring trial is being prepared to assess the reproducibility of the bioinformatics pipelines (i.e., from raw reads to consensus sequences/list of mutations) currently being applied for routine genome analyses of SARS-CoV-2 (and other coronaviruses) within the partner institutes. Ten partners confirmed their availability to participate in this exercise, which will involve the analysis of a batch of: i) 27 SARS-CoV-2 NGS fastq files obtained from distinct sample sources, using different wet-lab protocols and/or sequencing technologies; ii) five NGS fastq files obtained from other coronaviruses (optional). To accommodate constraints faced during the preparation of the ring trial and to give partners sufficient time to analyse the test dataset (this is especially important due to the current increase global workload associated with genomic surveillance of the emergent Omicron variant), the deliverable D2.1.2 “Report on the comparisons of variants and reference sample exchange” has been postponed.

ST2.1.3 – Development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment (M40 – M54)

ST2.1.3 is building bridges between several EJP projects to promote the integration of bioinformatics tools that enable phylogenetic analysis and investigation for virulence traits (e.g., mutations known to play a direct role in receptor binding or antibody recognition) that can aid the identification of drivers for the emergence and spread of new viral threats and the generation of supportive data for risk assessment. IZSAM (IT, P28) team is developing and refining a method for rapid large-scale phylogenetic inferences (Di Pasquale et al, BMC Genomics, 2021.)

On behalf of several One Health EJP projects (TELE-VIR, BeONE), INSA (PT, P36) is developing a bioinformatics tool for: i) viral detection and genome-based surveillance (<https://insaflu.insa.pt>), ii) clustering analysis and rapid association of pathogen genetic clusters with surveillance (clinical /epidemiological) metadata (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>), iii) rapidly screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes (aln2pheno).

Deliverable report delayed due to the contributing partner's involvement in viral disease outbreak responses SARS-CoV-2 plus other notifiable pathogens.

D2.1.3	Report on the development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment.	M54 >> M56
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JIP06-WP2-T2.2 - In vitro and ex vivo biological characterization of SARS-CoV-2 (M40 – M57)

Task 2.2 is focused on the assessment of in vitro systems for characterization of SARS-CoV-2 strains. Ex vivo explants and air-liquid interphase cultures of several animal species will be infected with SARS-CoV-2. Viruses replicating in those systems will be characterized with respect to genome analysis, viral growth and host responses.

ST2.2.1 – Cell culturing (M40 – M48)

Sub-task completed. A final and more comprehensive version of the protocol repository will be publicly released at the end of the project.

ST2.2.2 Antigenicity studies [D2.2.2 – March 2022]

ST2.2.2 is focused on the development and validation of serological techniques suitable for detecting the presence of SARS-CoV-2 antibodies. Experimental data include tests using sera from domestic, wild and human animals on a series of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and virus neutralisation test (VNT). A series of serological tests capable of detecting different types of antibodies (total antibodies, IgG or neutralising antibodies) against different antigens (such as the nucleoprotein (N protein) or receptor binding domain (RBD) of the spike (S) protein) were evaluated. Antibodies against the nucleocapsid (N) protein were detected using different ELISA methods, commercial kits or developed in-house by the partners. The detection of Ab against the spike protein (S) was performed using different ELISA tests for total neutralising antibodies (surrogate virus neutralisation test (sVNT)), double-antigen commercial ELISA tests, a lentivirus-based SARS-CoV-2 pseudotype neutralisation test (pVNT) and the virus neutralisation test as gold standard (VNT). The diagnostic performance of a whole-antigen ELISA generated using a GLP-inactivated virus-infected Vero E6 culture extract was also analysed. The serological results obtained showed a higher sensitivity of diagnostic tests capable of detecting antibodies to the S-protein than those capable of detecting antibodies to the N-protein. With regard to ELISA tests for the detection of anti-N antibodies, a higher diagnostic performance was observed using the two double-antigen ELISA tests (Eradikit™ and DAS-N-ELISA) compared to the indirect ELISA. The GenScript SARS-CoV-2 sVNT ELISA and the pVNT showed a high correlation with the SARS-CoV-2 VNT and were able to efficiently discriminate SARS-CoV-2 antibody-positive and antibody-negative serum with the same efficiency as the VNT. Cross-reactivity of pre- and post-pandemic human and farm animal sera with alpha- and beta-coronaviruses (CoV) including SARS-CoV-2 were also investigated. Results demonstrate that although SARS-CoV-2 is antigenically distinct, cross-reactivity should be considered when interpreting serological assays and this will vary between ELISA and VNT.

ST2.2.3 Complex cultures [D2.2.3 – August 2022]

ST2.2.3 sought to investigate SARS-CoV-2 replication in various complex cell culture systems such as air-liquid interphase (ALI) cultures, ex vivo organ cultures or organoids of several animal species. At FLI, established ALI-cultures from pigs and ferrets, where bronchial epithelia are considered non-susceptible to SARS-CoV-2 infection, were confirmed to be resistant to infection with SARS-CoV-2 B.1. To study SARS-CoV-2 infection in animal models with more pronounced SARS-CoV-2 lung infection primary bronchial epithelial cells from hamsters were tested for ALI-cultivation. Whereas ALI cultivation turned out to be inefficient for the hamster model, stone marten ALI-cultures were resistant

to infection with various SARS-CoV-2 viruses (B1, human isolated of mink origin, alpha, delta). Complementary, precision lung slice cultures ALI-cultures have been established and used (WBRV and FLI) and lung organoids for SARS-Cov-2 infection are being established at WBRV. This work will provide complex culture models for downstream analysis of SARS-CoV-2 replication in in-vivo like cell culture models. Currently, infection studies in PCLS and organoids are running and expected results will be included in report D2.2.3 which was postponed to M60.

D2.1.3	Report on complex cultures.	M56>> M59
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JIP06-WP2-T2.3 – Development and optimization of animal models (M43 – M60)

Task 2.3 focuses on the development of animal models of SARS-CoV-2 infection and biomarkers analysis.

ST2.3.1 – Animal model protocols (M43 – M45)

Sub-task completed.

ST2.3.2 – Pathology toolbox (M43 – M51)

Within ST2.3.2 work has been ongoing to develop, optimise and share reagents and methodologies for pathological analyses amongst the COVRIN participants. These activities have not been solely focussed on viral detection, but also in understanding the localisation of the SARS-CoV-2 receptors within host tissues of different animal species. This work was published here: <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14232>, but is currently being expanded to assess different host receptors in a wider range of species that will be made available under JIP06-WP2-D2.3.2 “Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes” in early 2022. This work will further increase our understanding of SARS-CoV-2 pathogenesis in animal species, as well as enable better evaluation of the potential host range of SARS-CoV-2 in wildlife species. Pathology Toolbox JIP06-WP2-D2.3.2 report per species is available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6259840>).

ST2.3.3 Establishment of virus-host interaction parameters

Work within ST2.3.3 by COVRIN participants: FLI (P10), WBVR (P31), NVI (P33) is progressing. Techniques include: Transcriptome – RNASeq, Proteomics, Metabolomics, Bead-based multiplex analysis (xMAP), Biomark Fluidigm qPCR platform, Mucosal protease activity, Plasma organ injury biomarkers and cytokines, and Multicolor RNA-Scope. Antiviral responses in cells will be analysed and an in vivo trial is scheduled. This work includes a multi-omics approach for biomarker identification. The deliverable D2.3.3 is due in M60.

JIP06-WP2-T2.4 - Analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic transmission (M49 – M63)

Task 2.4 will seek to use the outcomes of studies conducted under the first three tasks in WP2, as well as those in other work packages to analyse virus traits focussing on the potential for zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission, NGS results from virus isolates acquired from animals (i.e. livestock; pets, wildlife or zoo animals), experimental challenge studies and from already documented zoonotic and reverse zoonotic events (e.g. mink-human-mink, others) will be used to identify and map regions of interest in the virus genome responsible for these transmission events. Frequent or reoccurring mutations will be analysed in silico and experimentally regarding their ability to change virus traits (i.e., replicon system to assess viral RdRp activity, overall virion stability in different environmental conditions or fusion activity).

Most of the work that will be completed under Task 2.4 began in Month 50-51 and is dependent on experiments on virus traits related to zoonotic transmission are dependent on T2.2 and 2.3 that are currently being planned/conducted.

ST2.4.1 Variant analyses species jumps [D2.4.1 – M54 2022], delayed until M57

This subtask is led by ANSES P1.

Partners are sequencing PCR products from SARS-CoV-2 and pan-Coronavirus positives to determine sequence changes when the viruses switch species. For example, from human COVID cases into animals that share homes (pets) with positive cases or are captive zoo animals cared for by their keepers. In the UK this includes 3 dogs, 1 cat and 3 tigers respectively. The viruses are Delta variants, pre-alpha virus and Delta virus respectively, deeper sequence analyses are ongoing.

ST2.4.2 – Identification of antigenic site modifications (M49 – M57)

Work on ST2.4.2, relating to antigenic cartography of SARS-CoV-2 variants, has been able to progress utilising materials and data that were already available. Antigenic cartography is a series of techniques for quantifying and visualising antigenic relationships between antigens, based on serological titre data. In the influenza field, it is used to explore the patterns of antigenic evolution, and to help select vaccine strains each year; additionally, antigenic distances between virus variants can be compared with genetic distances, to study the molecular basis of antigenic evolution. Initial antigenic maps of SARS-CoV-2 variants, based on published serological data, have been produced for internal review. Discussions are ongoing with regards to the application of antigenic cartography to data generated by COVRIN partners. Additionally, in an informal meeting between University of Surrey (UoS) and APHA, it was proposed to compare antigenic maps for SARS-CoV-2 variants using sera from across different animal models (ferret, hamster and rabbit), as well as human sera where available, in collaboration with the Statens Serum Institute (SSI; a partner of UoS in JRP TELE-Vir). In a separate collaboration, antigenic cartographic analysis of SARS-CoV-2 variants was performed for data derived from elderly human vaccinees ([Neutralizing antibody activity against 21 SARS-CoV-2 variants in older adults vaccinated with BNT162b2 | Nature Microbiology](#)).

Antigenic distances have been estimated for 9775 (Wuhan), Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta, Omicron BA.1 variants using human and animal sera (rabbit) other animal sera are being sourced; companion animal and wildlife.

ST2.4.3 In vivo studies virus variants [D2.4.3 Undertake and report on a virus variant in vivo follow-up study M60 delayed to M63]

Partners 10, 21, and 28 are undertaking in vivo experiments with SARS-CoV-2 variants (alpha, beta gamma, delta) in hamsters, ferrets and humanised mice respectively, investigating infection parameters, drug efficacy, modes and routes of transmission contact and aerosol, disease pathogenesis, and virus survival on bio-matrix i.e. fur and skin. Manuscripts are in preparation. Compellingly high SARS-CoV-2 susceptibility of Golden Syrian hamsters suggests multiple zoonotic infections of pet hamsters during the COVID-19 pandemic. C. Blaurock, et al., bioRxiv 2022.04.19.488826; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.04.19.488826>, Stegman KM et al., iScience [https://www.cell.com/iscience/pdf/S2589-0042\(22\)00563-6.pdf](https://www.cell.com/iscience/pdf/S2589-0042(22)00563-6.pdf)

WP3 – SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment and surveillance

JIP06-WP3-T3.1 - Integration of surveillance activities (M40 – M63)

ST3.1.1 – Design format and procedure for surveillance data (M40 – M45)

Sub-task is completed.

ST3.1.2 – Collection of surveillance data (M40 – M54)

In Y5, a database has been created, with access to data requiring approval by the data holders/contacts for each of the countries, these, along with a summary of the data and uploaded to the OHEJP COVRIN group site <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7006321> as part of deliverable D3.1.2.

ST3.1.3 – Identification of additional sources of surveillance data (M40 – M57)

For data sources identified in Subtask 3.1.3, any data that can be accessed or retrieved will be added to and integrated in the database using the same protocol from D3.1.1. A systematic review is being conducted on the prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 infection in household dogs and cats, specifically

evaluating alternative sources of information, which will be submitted for publication in the second half of 2022 and inform the upcoming Deliverable D3.1.3. Deliverable D3.1.3 has been drafted and will be submitted in M57 according to planning. The primary goal of Task 3.1 is the integration of surveillance data. The harmonized and integrated database developed as part of Task 3.1 activities will serve as a source of parameters for risk models in Task 3.4 and other risk assessments in WP4. Given the primary use of data, in consultation with Task 3.4 and WP4, Deliverable D3.1.3 focuses on collecting and summarizing SARS-CoV-2 prevalence data in dogs and cats from published studies as the most relevant type of studies for the extraction of data and their integration into a common framework. In parallel with Deliverable D3.1.3, a scientific article has been prepared and submitted for publication.

JIP06-WP3-T3.2 - Mapping of surveillance data (M40 – M63)

ST3.2.1 – Evaluation of current surveillance activities (M40 – M48)

Sub-task is completed.

ST3.2.2 – Identification of key stakeholders (M40-M63)

Progress has been made in the identification of stakeholders, which relates to Deliverable D3.2.2.

JIP06-WP3-T3.3 - Risk factors for virus transmission (M40 – M63)

This task, risk factors for virus transmission, has been initiated through meetings of task leader and contributors and will be dependent on the outcomes from T3.1, 3.2 and Work package 1.

ST3.3.1 – Analyses of transmission in pets (M40 – M54)

The first point in this task has been completed; the online epidemiological survey has been designed and is available for contributors to complete at: <https://forms.gle/JXwjxX1x5ULmSPmu9>. Additionally, the sampling protocol was designed. Both documents were shared with the task 3.1. The conceptual assessment of the epidemiological survey was carried out in a region of Spain with a high prevalence of SARS-Cov2 infection. In order to collect epidemiological and clinical data on family groups affected by the disease and their pets, a network of veterinary clinics has been created to provide sampling points for the pets. In order to evaluate heavily and normally exposed pets, the SARS-Cov2 affected family groups include both hospital health workers and not health workers pet owners (informed through the vet clinic network). The WP3 meeting in Q1 of 2022 marked the beginning of the process of disseminating the online survey and the sampling protocol to other partner groups and countries. The preliminary results were presented at the biannual International Meeting on Emerging Diseases and Surveillance (IMED) 2021 meeting under the title "SARS-CoV-2 in pets of infected family groups in a severely affected region of Spain". The study was selected for publication in the International Journal of Infectious Diseases (IJID): A. Mendez, M.A. Jiménez-Clavero, C. Calvo, E. Pérez-Ramírez, J. Fernández-Pinero, F. Llorente, T. Sainz, P. Aguilera-Sepúlveda, S. Alcolea, L. Escolano, C. Cano, I. Novoa, A. De la Torre, I. Iglesias (2022) SARS-CoV-2 in pets of infected family groups in a severely affected region in Spain, International Journal of Infectious Diseases, Volume 116: S25. ISSN 1201-9712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.12.059>. A manuscript with the analysis of transmission in pets, linked to Deliverable D3.3.1 "Report on epidemiological survey design and clinical data", is currently being finalised. Deliverable D3.3.1 is available in OHEJP page (<https://onehealth.ejp.eu/groups/covrin/documents/>) and will be made available in zenodo once the related publications are completed.

ST3.3.2 – Study of the epidemiology and risk factors in pets (M40 – M63)

Extending on ST3.3.1, and in collaboration with other WP3 tasks, progress has been made on this evaluation.

JIP06-WP3-T3.4 - Models for transmission routes and risk assessment in a One Health perspective (M40 – M63)

ST3.4.1 – Listing of existing models (M40 – M45)

An overview is made of the different dynamics models and required parameters to test hypotheses regarding the role of animals as potential reservoir hosts and parameters needs. A code library is being developed and will be made available with later deliverables, once finalised. It is currently being used and shared internally with collaborators within the COVRIN project to apply for the analysis of transmission from experiments done within COVRIN or data collected from the systematic reviews.

ST3.4.2 – Reviewing transmission parameters (M40 – M54)

As part of Deliverable D3.4.2 “Systematic review report and quantification of transmission parameters for different animal species”, systematic reviews (SR) were carried out to collect data and generate summaries for this biological information matrix. Three SR reviews on this topic have been finished: assessing persistence in pets (Decaro et al. 2021a); human-to-dog transmission (Decaro et al. 2021b); and assessing the risk of cat-to-cat transmission of SARS-CoV-2 (Gonzales et al. 2021). SR are still ongoing to assess the infection and transmission dynamics of hamsters and ferrets, as well as household data and experimental data (in cats) and vaccine trials (macaques).

Decaro, N., Grassi, A., Lorusso, E., Patterson, E. I., Lorusso, A., Desario, C., Anderson, E. R., Vasinioti, V., Wastika, C. E., Hughes, G. L., Valleriani, F., Colitti, B., Ricci, D., Buonavoglia, D., Rosati, S., Cavaliere, N., Paltrinieri, S., Lauzi, S., Elia, G., & Buonavoglia, C. (2021). Long-term persistence of neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in pets. *Transboundary and emerging diseases*, 10.1111/tbed.14308. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14308>

Decaro, N., Vaccari, G., Lorusso, A., Lorusso, E., De Sabato, L., Patterson, E. I., Di Bartolo, I., Hughes, G. L., Teodori, L., Desario, C., Colitti, B., Ricci, D., Buonavoglia, D., Rosati, S., Martella, V., Cammà, C., Agrimi, U., & Elia, G. (2021). Possible Human-to-Dog Transmission of SARS-CoV-2, Italy, 2020. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 27(7), 1981–1984. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2707.204959>

Gonzales, J.L.; De Jong, M.C.M.; Gerhards, N.M.; Van der Poel, W.H.M.(2021) The SARS-CoV-2 reproduction number R0 in cats. *Viruses* 2021, 13(12), 2480; <https://doi.org/10.3390/v13122480>.

ST3.4.3 – Listing of susceptible hosts and relative risk (M40 – M60)

Integrating on the work from ST3.4.2, and T3.3, progress on the listing of susceptible hosts and relative risk is being completed.

ST3.4.4 – Reviewing of challenge experiments (M40 – M63)

As part of Deliverable D3.4.4 “Report on systematic review of challenge experiments using different host species”, a SR was carried out on challenge experiments in non-human primates (Counotte et al. pre-print):

Counotte, M. J., de Souza Santos, M. A., Stittelaar, K. J., van der Poel, W. H. M., & Gonzales, J. L. (2021). Assessment of the efficacy of SARS-CoV-2 vaccines in non-human primate studies - a systematic review. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/u3fwj>

ST3.4.5 – Description of transmission characteristics in mink (M40 – M63)

Work on the analysis of the spatio-temporal transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in minks (between farm transmission) has been performed and a manuscript is currently under review, which will link to deliverable D3.4.5.

WP4 - Coronavirus preparedness

JIP06-WP4-T4.1 - Virus-host interactions (M40 – M63)

ST4.1.1 – In vivo and in vitro studies of animal coronaviruses (M40 – M57)

Research is ongoing within this task: In several partner institutes animal coronaviruses are being passaged *in vitro* and *in vivo* and *ex vivo* in their homologous host or in alternate animal hosts, cells or

tissues. *In vitro* studies for this deliverable will be submitted in M57 according to the initial planning. However, *in vivo* studies have been delayed due to restrictions on movement of animals following the avian influenza crisis. *In vivo* trials are programmed for October 2022, December 2022 and January 2023, thus this section of D4.1.1 will be submitted in M63. Due to the avian influenza outbreaks, a delay of the deliverable for task was expected already.

ST4.1.2 – *In vitro* and ex vivo studies of experimental co-infections (M40 – M63)

Experimental co-infections are being performed *in vitro* or *ex-vivo* in several institutes. This subtask seems to have an overlap with subtask 4.1.1. Therefore, an inventory will be made of ongoing studies, and reporting will be combined with subtask 4.1.1. Genetic make-up of viral progeny will be investigated by deep sequencing.

ST4.1.3 – *Virus isolation from wildlife (hedgehogs) (M40 – M63)*

Work on the isolation of hedgehog coronavirus has been executed. However, coronaviruses were not successfully isolated from hedgehogs. Coronavirus sequences were obtained and will be reported. Studies on the zoonotic potential of the viruses cannot be performed.

JIP06-WP4-T4.2 - *Drivers of virus emergence (M40 – M63)*

ST4.2.1 – *Analyse coronavirus phylodynamics at global time and geographical scales (M40 – M49, extended from M42)*

To improve the understanding of factors affecting coronavirus genetic diversity and evolution in domestic animals and wildlife, global time and geographical phylodynamics of animal coronaviruses are being studied. This includes samples of minks, bats, dogs and other species. Phylogenetic relationships between coronaviruses are analyzed between animal species, and within one coronavirus species in different breeding facilities or operations.

An evaluation of potential sample types and hot spots for SARS-CoV-2 infections has been made, and a report about this has been written: Deliverable D4.2.1 “Relevant sample types and hot spots for coronavirus sampling” (<https://zenodo.org/record/5848638>). This deliverable was delayed due to a delayed start of the project and staffing issues due to COVID-19.

ST4.2.2 – *Trace relevant virus mutations and recombinations (M40 – M51)*

An *in vivo* study with TGEV and PEDV is set up in pigs. Studies on relevant mutations and recombination events in coronavirus isolates to gain insights into genetic variation under “natural” conditions (as compared with ST4.1.1 and ST4.1.2) are going to be performed. Virus sequencing protocols are being evaluated and discussed.

ST4.2.3 – *Evaluate the impact of ecological factors and interventions (M40 – M63)*

Of surveyed SARS-CoV-2 outbreaks the observed genetic changes are being investigated concerning their correlation with ecological factors (species interactions, habitat etc) and human interventions (vaccination, trading of animals), and how such factors may impact coronavirus evolution (evolution rates, composition of recombinants, possible contribution of vaccine viruses). This is done for the mink outbreak in the Netherlands to gain more insight into the role of ecological factors and human interventions. Other SARS-CoV-2 outbreak samples may be included in these studies.

JIP06-WP4-T4.3 - *Virus emergence risk modelling (M40 – M63)*

This task is underway following successful task leader meetings: specific animal communities will be followed over a predefined period (RT-PCR, NGS) to monitor intra-community CoV genetic variation. Data from other WPs and other WP4 tasks will be used to assess the potential of CoV genetic variation on future emergences (for animal species and humans). Samplings have been started as part of a longitudinal study of genetic variation under ‘natural’ conditions (to be compared with T4.1 and T4.2).

ST4.3.1 – *Follow coronavirus contaminations in bats (M40 – M60)*

Samplings have been started of bat colonies in natural areas.

ST4.3.2 – Follow coronavirus contaminations in cats (M40 – M63)

Samplings have been started of cats in domestic environments. A monthly fecal sampling of cats and kittens under breeding farm conditions is performed to assess the impact of human interventions (link with ST4.2.3). Faecal samples are seldomly tested SARS-CoV-2 positive. Also in cats, the virus seems to be mainly transmitted through the respiratory tract. NGS analyses of samples will be performed in the second half of 2022.

ST4.3.3 – Follow coronavirus contaminations in wildlife (M40 – M63)

Various groups of wildlife have been sampled and tested for coronaviruses. This includes bats, foxes, marmots, deer, etc. Frequent samplings of animals hosted in wildlife shelters (incl. hedgehogs) are being performed to assess the impact of modified interactions on the evolution of wildlife coronaviruses (link with ST4.2.3).

ST4.3.4 – Risk assessment and modelling of animal coronavirus evolution (M40 – M63)

Data from WPs 1, 2, 3 and WP4 tasks will be integrated to model which animal species/conditions offer the highest potential for future emergencies. This work includes a literature review and an overview on how deliverables of the COVRIN project can contribute to a coronavirus risk assessment.

6.1.2.4.3 Progress of the research project: deliverables and milestones

Deliverables

JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 <i>(month)</i>	Date delivered on Project Group <i>(month)</i>	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date <i>(month)</i>	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.1.2	First management report	51				
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.2.1	First annual communication report	51				
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.3.3	Report Mid-term meeting (presentations)	57	55		Mid-term meeting was held 27 th June 2022. Due to the COVID19 outbreak this was an online meeting. Updates and outputs of all 5 work packages were presented by the work package leaders. The meeting was chaired by project leaders Wim van der Poel and Daniel Horton. Presentations are available on the COVRIN project group site and a document including the agenda and the pdfs of the presentations will be uploaded on Zenodo.	8
JIP06-COVRIN	D0.3.4.1	(optional ST) Ad hoc reports to REA and					8

JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		EU stakeholders on relevant interim knowledge/data results as relevant for potential risk assessment and/or risk management activities					
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.1.2	Report on the comparisons of variants and reference sample exchange	48		50	Delivery date changed to accommodate some constraints faced during the preparation of a bioinformatics ring trial and to give partners more time to run the test dataset.	
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.1.3	Report on the development of an algorithm for novel virus assessment.	54				
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.2.2	Report on assessment of VNA techniques and comparison with ELISA reactivity data.	51	51			2

JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.2.3	Report on complex culture viral characterisation.	57		60		
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.3.2	Report on pathology per species and investigative toolboxes.	51				
JIP06-COVRIN	D2.4.1	Collated partner outcomes of virus trait change as a result of species change including cell receptor affinity.	54		60		
JIP06-COVRIN	D.2.4.2	Report on in silico and antigenic cartography analysis of antigenic site adaptation traits.	57	57		Publication available Neutralizing antibody activity against 21 SARS-CoV-2 variants in older adults vaccinated with BNT162b2 Nature Microbiology A report on other species responses on zenodo	4,5, 8 (network)
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.3.1	Report on epidemiological survey design and clinical	54	54		https://onehealthejp.eu/groups/covrin/documents/	3

JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		data (including anamnesis and lab results).					
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.2	Systematic review (SR) report and quantification of transmission parameters for different animal species.	54	54		Public Gonzales et al. (2021) Two other reviews ongoing	
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.4	Report on SR of challenge experiments using different host species	63	54		Public Counotte et al. (2021)	
JIP06-COVRIN	D3.4.5	Report describing the transmission characteristics of the mink outbreaks for the countries where data was available.	51				
JIP06-COVRIN	D4.1.1	Reports of in vivo and in vitro experimentations	57				

Milestones

JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
COVRIN	JIP06-WP4-M4.1	In vitro and in vivo experiments performed	54			On target
COVRIN	JIP06-WP4-M4.2	Samples collected under farming and natural conditions	57			On target
COVRIN	JIP06-WP4-M4.3	Coronavirus evolution under experimental and natural conditions analyzed	63			On target
COVRIN	JIP06-WP4-M4.4	impact on the capacity to cross the species barrier evaluated and risk modeled	63			On target

6.1.2.4.4 Follow-up of the recommendations and comments by the Ethics Advisors

No further comments have been received from the Ethics Advisors.

Project number	Project name	Requirements Ethical Reviewers, August 2021	Comments Project Leaders, Sep 2021	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, January 2022	Comments Project Leaders, 2022	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, 2022
JIP06	COVRIN	Human Sample: In case Human samples will be manipulated, their source must be revealed and the relevant authorisations to obtain them must be presented;	Importance of this cannot be understated and is acknowledged. All partners handling human samples have the necessary national authority and licenses in place. Sources of samples and relevant approval will be included in the deliverable reports			

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Project number	Project name	Requirements Ethical Reviewers, August 2021	Comments Project Leaders, Sep 2021	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, January 2022	Comments Project Leaders, 2022	Recommendations Ethics Advisors, 2022
JIP06	COVRIN	Animal: in Tasks 2.3 animal models of SARS-CoV-2 infection will be developed, the beneficiaries must demonstrate the implementation of the 3Rs and must present the ethical authorization to conduct the experiments in these animals;	Experiments involving animals will only be undertaken following independent ethical review and under relevant national licences. These will be explicitly stated in the relevant deliverable reports.			
JIP06	COVRIN	Safety: the beneficiaries must demonstrate that appropriate safety procedures have been put in place to protect the staff involved in the inoculation studies using different coronaviruses. Also, in case of the manipulation of contaminated Human samples, appropriate safety procedures must be established.	Work on Sars-CoV-2 requires very specialist containment facilities and partners contributing to tasks involving virus propagation and culture are only those with facilities and procedures that meeting or exceed relevant national and international standards.			

6.1.2.4.5 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Impact of animal saliva on the performance of rapid antigen tests for detection of SARS-CoV-2 (wildtype and variants B.1.1.7 and B.1.351) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2021.109243	Yes		
Differential susceptibility of SARS-CoV-2 in animals: Evidence of ACE2 host receptor distribution in companion animals, livestock and wildlife by immunohistochemical characterization DOI: https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14232 Zenodo Reference: https://zenodo.org/record/5795457#.YcG5QGjP3IU	Yes	No	4100
Newman, J., Thakur, N., Peacock, T.P., Bialy, D., Elreafey, A.M., Bogaardt, C., Horton, D.L., Ho, S., Kankeyan, T., Carr, C., Hoschler, K., Barclay, W.S., Amirthalingam, G., Brown, K., Charleston, B., Bailey, D., 2021. Neutralising antibody activity against SARS-CoV-2 variants, including Omicron, in an elderly cohort vaccinated with BNT162b2. medRxiv. https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.23.21268293	Yes		
Gonzales JL, de Jong MCM, Gerhards NM, Van der Poel WHM. The SARS-CoV-2 Reproduction Number R0 in Cats. Viruses. 2021; 13(12):2480. https://doi.org/10.3390/v13122480	Yes		1578
Decaro, N., Grassi, A., Lorusso, E., Patterson, E. I., Lorusso, A., Desario, C., Anderson, E. R., Vasinioti, V., Wastika, C. E., Hughes, G. L., Valleriani, F., Colitti, B., Ricci, D., Buonavoglia, D., Rosati, S., Cavaliere, N., Paltrinieri, S., Lauzi, S., Elia, G., & Buonavoglia, C. (2021). Long-term persistence of neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in pets. Transboundary and emerging diseases, 10.1111/tbed.14308. https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14308	Yes		
Decaro, N., Vaccari, G., Lorusso, A., Lorusso, E., De Sabato, L., Patterson, E. I., Di Bartolo, I., Hughes, G. L., Teodori, L., Desario, C., Colitti, B., Ricci, D., Buonavoglia,			

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
D., Rosati, S., Martella, V., Cammà, C., Agrimi, U., & Elia, G. (2021). Possible Human-to-Dog Transmission of SARS-CoV-2, Italy, 2020. <i>Emerging infectious diseases</i> , 27(7), 1981–1984. https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2707.204959			
Counotte, Michel J., Mariana A. de Souza Santos, Koert L. Stittelaar, Wim H. van der Poel, and Jose L. Gonzales. 2021. "Assessment of the Efficacy of Sars-cov-2 Vaccines in Non-human Primate Studies - a Systematic Review." OSF Preprints. April 23. doi:10.31219/osf.io/u3fwj .	Yes		

6.1.2.4.6 Additional output

Med-Vet-Net Association Workshop – SARS-CoV-2 at the Animal-Human Interface COVRIN presentations:

- Wim van der Poel (WBVR) – ‘Study of SARS-CoV-2 in mink, a One Health approach’
- Gabriele Vaccari (ISS) – ‘Circulation of Coronaviruses in wild animals in Northern Italy’
- Sophie Lepoder (ANSES) – ‘Epidemiological role of domestic animals in SARS-CoV-2 transmission: where are we?’
- Richard Delahay (APHA) – ‘Assessing the risks of SARS-CoV-2 in wildlife’
- Joe James (APHA) – ‘Tools to study SARS-CoV-2: Virology, Serology and Animal Models’
- Elodie Monchatre-Leroy (ANSES) – ‘Intransal type I interferon treatment in the SARS-CoV-2 hamster model’
- Fabian Lean (APHA) – ‘The pathology of SARS-CoV-2 and tools to study host range’
- Rachel Taylor (APHA) – ‘A Global world: assessing the risk of human travel to the spread of SARS-CoV-2 and preparing for the next Disease X’
- Daniel Horton (UoS) – ‘Quantifying antigenic variation between SARS-CoV-2 variants’
- Paul Brown (ANSES) – ‘Genome evolution of the coronavirus IBV depending on immune status: considerations for SARS-CoV-2 vaccination’
- UK-International Coronavirus Network Launch Event COVRIN presentations:
 - Wim van der Poel (WBVR) – One Health and Zoonoses
 - Sharon Brookes (APHA) – Surveillance, Detection and Characterisation
 - Martin Groschup (FLI) – Surveillance, Detection and Characterisation
- Recording of the event is available here: <https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/health-and-life-sciences/research/uk-international-coronavirus-network/launch-meeting/>

6.1.2.4.7 Outcomes (deliverable, publication, folder, tool, etc.) of the project that might be suited for communication purposes to various audiences, for instance food safety or AMR scientists, national and international stakeholders, specific professionals, the general public, etc.

6.1.2.4.8 Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries

COVRIN cooperates with a lot of nationally funded projects in partner countries, and also with international organizations like WHO, FAO, ECDC and EFSA. Links have been established with international research networks and projects like the UK Coronavirus network, the PREZODE network and the ERRAZE project. COVRIN research outputs are reported nationally and internationally. All significant results have been reported to national Ministries and also to ECDC and EFSA as appropriate. Preliminary findings have been presented at meetings and conferences on emerging diseases (i.e. IMED 2021) The aim is to make all COVRIN results available for the entire scientific community, primarily through peer reviewed publications, and also to the general public.

6.1.3 Task 4.3: Integrative support

6.1.3.1 Subtask 4.3.1: Alignment with strategic initiatives at EU level:

Collaboration with other EU initiatives has, during the OHEJP full period, been supported by a total of eight cogwheel workshops (CWs) organised by WP4 to allow key actors and relevant partners within the OHEJP, typically Project leaders or WP leaders within Joint Research Projects (JRPs) or Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs), to identify synergies, joint priorities, and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. These workshops have resulted in interactions between and collaborations with JRPs and JIPs as well as with other EU projects and initiatives. As an example, several tools produced in ORION and COHESIVE are now integrated in the global SISOT toolbox, developed in collaboration between FAO, WHO and OIE. The JIPs currently running have established collaboration with EFSA on data collection and risk assessment. A report has been produced summarizing the eight Cogwheel workshops that has been conducted during the years. This report is available on the public part on the OHEJP website

The activities of the simulation exercise SimEx are presented in Task 4.6.

6.1.3.2 Subtask 4.3.2: Support function for integration of additional partners in ongoing JIP:

This subtask is responsible for so called integrative missions, aimed at helping OHEJP partners that are not originally partners of the JIPs to join. Six new partner institutes joined the OHEJP during Y4 and three of them have become partners in the ongoing JIPs.

There was no budget allocated for Short Term Integrative Missions (STIMs) or Integrative Mentorings (IM) Y5, and consequently no such activities have been performed.

Subtask 4.3.3: Scientific meetings to enhance and leverage integration:

In total four Thematic integrative meetings (TIMs) have been arranged by WP4. The TIMs aim to facilitate integration across domains, but within themes, addressing specific thematic integrative needs and opportunities.

On 22nd February 2022 the WP 4 team organised the fourth Thematic Integrative Meeting (TIM). The theme of this 2,5-hour virtual meeting was "Data sharing across disciplines". The TIM was attended by approximately 120 persons across sectors and from altogether 16 countries. The target groups were the Joint Research Projects, Joint Integrative Projects, stakeholders and the EURLs. During the meeting three presentations were given on legal aspects and requirements of data sharing and on examples of solutions how cross-sectoral data sharing can be done in outbreak investigations, research projects or risk assessments. Build trust and know your data was the key messages of one of the presenters. For more information see deliverable D4.26.

The WP4 team also contributed to the organisation of the ASM 2022 in Orvieto, Italy.

6.1.4 Task 4.3: Organisation of call for additional JIPs for the period Y3-Y5

N/A

6.1.5 Task 4.5: Open data management

All projects have appointed DMP Leaders that manage the project specific Data Management Plans (DMPs). For the first call projects three different templates have been used. The final versions are or should be uploaded to the DMP Group on the OHEJP website and to Zenodo. The second call projects use the online software tool CDP (Lisam®). All second call DMP Leaders have got training in the CDP tool. In collaboration with WP5 a link from the CDP-tool to the Outcome Inventory has been set up and the public content of the DMPs can be reached by the stakeholders via a Reader's view. In this way data can be accessed before the projects are finished. Finalized DMPs have been reviewed by the DMP

Committee and suggestions for improvements communicated to the DMP and Project Leaders. The final DMPs are uploaded to the OHEJP website and when approved to Zenodo. The DMPs of ongoing JRP/JIPs are annually reviewed by the DMP Committee. The overarching OHEJP DMP is also under revision. All OHEJP WPs and Comms Team are asked to provide data and other relevant outcomes that are not listed elsewhere. The work to put this into the CDP-tool is made by WP4. The original OHEJP DMP, found in D4.4 Data Management Plan will be completed with an D4.4 annex.

6.1.6 Task 4.6: OHEJP Simulation Exercise SimEx

The “OHEJP SimEx” is an outbreak response exercise designed and conducted under task 4.6 of WP4, starting Y4. It is a tabletop exercise with practical tasks partially based on the ECDC handbook on simulation exercises (2014).

The SimEx project completed the planning process, including budget and resource allocation, foundation, and design and development of the scenario and evaluation, in M52 and entered the conduction phase. Twenty OHEJP partner institutes, several external institutes and other authorities, in total from eleven countries participated in the national conductions of SimEx taking place during M53–55 and for one country in M57. The aim is to develop the One Health capability, capacity, and interoperability of authorities in Public Health, Animal Health and Food Safety and provide an opportunity to practice together. The scenario, created and written by the SimEx Project Team, focuses on a foodborne zoonosis outbreak and consists of three parts, each connected to one of the main objectives i.e., data sharing, communication, and role and functionality of currently available systems. The period in the scenario covers early detection, tracing, assessment, and communication. In September all OHEJP partner institutes that had signed up for the exercise and several external institutes had completed the conduction. In addition, some partner institutes had invited representatives from ministries.

An important part of the SimEx project was to plan and conduct a workshop for the National and Local Exercise Leaders (NELs and LELs). This workshop was organized on 21-23 March 2022. The first day was an open session with lectures by experts from ECDC, EFSA, FAO and OHEJP, where they shared experiences and lessons learned from disease outbreaks and the use of a One Health perspective as well as exercises in general. The second part (days two and three) was for LELs and NELs only and focused on learning more about the conduction procedure, the scenario, and some tools developed within the OHEJP Joint Integrative Project COHESIVE, and the responsibilities of NELs and LELs. Another important purpose of the workshop was to provide an opportunity for NELs and LELs to ask questions and to meet and discuss and plan the conduction on a national level. A report on the SimEx workshop has been finalized. The results of SimEx has been presented to the SimEx Steering Board and will be presented at the SSB-meeting in Riga in September. At this meeting some national exercise leaders will also give their view about the performances of the exercise and gained knowledge.

6.2 Deliverables and Milestones

6.2.1 Deliverables

Del. Rel. No	Deliverable title	Submission
D4.24	Report on evaluation of finalised JIPs, 1st round	M53
D4.26	Report from thematic meeting IV	M54
D4.27	4th periodic report on JIPs	M51

6.2.2 Milestones

N/A

7 WP5 - Science to Policy translation to stakeholders

7.1 Work carried out to date

7.1.1 Task 5.1: Identification of the stakeholders and establishment of communication links

The fifth reporting year (M49-M57) was focused on continuation of dialogue and dissemination with Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA, and with other European and global stakeholders, as well as with national stakeholders (representatives of ministries of authority, represented in the POC). Effort was put in identification of interested parties not traditionally regarded as One Health EJP stakeholders, and targeted dissemination.

The Stakeholders Committee

Exchange with contact officers from the stakeholders' organisations continued to be very good. The Stakeholders Committee covers the whole One Health spectrum (human-animal-environment), at the European as well as international level. The Stakeholders Committee is composed of the key EU Stakeholders, ECDC and EFSA, the European Environment Agency (EEA), the European Medicines Agency (EMA), as well as the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE, now WOA), and the World Health Organization regional office for Europe (WHO-Euro). There were changes in contact representatives of EEA and WOA, but such changes were smooth, with the former representatives briefing and introducing the new representative to the OHEJP before official meetings.

Communication with stakeholders was active by email, on the One Health EJP website, and by web-meetings. One of the major instrument is the Stakeholders Committee Meeting (SCM).

The Stakeholders Committee Meetings

The 8th SCM took place on the 22th of November 2021 as an online event (due to the COVID-19 restrictions). It was attended by EFSA, EMA, OIE, WHO-Euro and the EU funded project JPI-AMR. Representatives of the organisation that were not able to join received all the informative material (presentations, meeting's minutes etc.).

The first part of the meeting focused on updates targeted to stakeholders, and on sustainability. WPs of the OHEJP presented:

- The OHEJP Simulation Exercise 2022 (SimEx), an opportunity to practise capabilities and capacities in dealing with an outbreak with a One Health perspective (led by WP4);
- The Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 and the plan for a Stakeholder Conference, the latter important to highlight the impact that OHEJP can have on the scientific, policy, but also societal and economic aspects. Part of the event will be in fact targeted to the industry and private sector;
- the Dissemination Workshop series: an initiative of WP5 aimed at targeted dissemination the OHEJP-developed solutions to stakeholders with decisional power;
- Plans for a policy event, a high-level meeting to ensure long-lasting legacy of the OHEJP (led by WP1);
- The gap analysis to identify opportunities for innovation (led by WP2);
- The Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 2021-2030, a flagship sustainability initiatives aimed at continuing a number of One Health EJP activities and at making available the outcomes (outputs, deliverables, publications) after the end of the consortium (led by WP7).

The meeting then moved to discussing the impact of selected One Health EJP activities: comparing the perception of the OHEJP and of the stakeholders helps to adjust dissemination activities of the consortium. In particular the projects ARDIG and OH-HARMONY-CAP presented their outcomes, followed by discussion on the potential impact at the policy, societal and economic level of the projects and of the OHEJP as a whole.

The stakeholders noted that the outcomes of the OHEJP can have an impact also outside of the borders of the European Union, in the whole European region and beyond, and highlighted the importance of global dissemination of outcomes. They also acknowledged that the One Health EJP is having an impact on the day-to-day work of partner institutes, but also at the higher policy level, advising ministries to develop legislations towards One Health.

In preparation to the meeting, WP5 distributed to the stakeholders the 6th Targeted Report to Key EU Stakeholders (Task 5.4), and the D2.8 Report on scientific developments and opportunities for innovation (WP2).

The 8th SCM took place in conjunction with the PMC-POC meeting, the latter joined by representatives of ECDC and EFSA.

The 9th SCM took place on the 13th of April 2022, during the ASM 2022, as a hybrid event, with the possibility to join in person in Orvieto, Italy, and online. It was attended by ECDC, EFSA, EEA, FAO, OIE and the EU funded project JPI-AMR. Representatives of the organisation that were not able to join received all the informative material (presentations, meeting's minutes etc.).

The aims of the meeting were to discuss the involvement of the stakeholders in the sustainability of the One Health EJP outcomes, and to update the stakeholders on selected projects.

ECDC and EFSA presented the plans of future One Health initiatives of their organisations, and the possible support that the One Health EJP can provide. It was emphasized that it is important to operationalise the One Health approach by putting solutions into practice, something that the One Health EJP can support. EEA noted the increasing emphasis on interactions between environment and health, aware that the knowledge base relating to the 'ecosystem health' dimension of One Health needs to be significantly expanded. Sustainability of the consortium was also highlighted during the discussion on the SRIA 2021-2030. This included the preview of a table depicting a few outcomes of OHEJP projects readily available, organised by domain and scope, and selected for possibly being of particular relevance for ECDC, EFSA, DG-AGRI and DG-SANTE (an activity led by WP7 and supported by WP5). The stakeholders agreed that the SRIA should look also at societal, institutional and environmental dimensions, as all of them are critically important for the success of emerging international policy One Health agendas.

Background documents of the meeting were the 7th Targeted Report to Key EU Stakeholders (Task 5.4), and the table of outcomes selected for possibly being of particular relevance for ECDC, EFSA, DG-AGRI and DG-HEALTH.

In addition to SCMs, the stakeholders were always kept up to date with tools such as the aforementioned Targeted Reports (Task 5.4), the One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI, Task 5.3), the Data Management Plan (DMP) Reader (Task 5.4), and Dissemination Workshops (Task 5.4).

It has to be noted that the SCMs, beside being occasions of discussion between the stakeholders and the One Health EJP, are also seen as a high-level forum for exchange between the stakeholders across sectors, and an opportunity to create new links between them.

The 10th SCM is planned for November 2022, in association with the POC/PMC meeting.

Interaction with other interested parties not included in the Stakeholders Committee

As the One Health approach evolves integrating more disciplines, it was deemed relevant of the OHEJP to search connections with stakeholders not included in the Stakeholders Committee, for example those coming from the social sciences, or private sector.

A collaboration with the initiative One Health Social Science was initiated. This was based on a previous collaboration with the One Health Commission and with WHO-GOARN (Task 5.3), and started as an investigation on the contribution of the social science sector to COVID-19 response actions. An oral presentation was accepted for the 9th International Conference on Social Sciences (Nov 2022), and further work is ongoing.

Another example of interactions with sectors other than animal health, human health and food safety, is the participation, after invitation, to the Geneva Health Forum 2022, an event notably engaged by NGOs, funding bodies, and humanitarian associations. OHEJP was invited to join not just the main conference, but also to share its expertise in one workshop on One Health education activities, and one on science-policy interface.

Possible impact on the private sector was demonstrated by WP5 being invited in the panel discussion “The balancing act of public, animal and environmental health. How to translate this to policy?” of AnimalHealth Europe, an association of veterinary drugs manufacturers. The OHEJP was invited to join the event alongside the WOA, DG-SANTE, WHO-Euro and other prominent organisations.

The Stakeholder Conference

The main forum for interaction with a broad range of stakeholders will be the Stakeholder Conference. This two-day event will take place at the end of the OHEJP in 2023 in order to have all the deliverables and outcomes available, to allow maximum exploitation of results.

The first day will be addressed at policy and decision makers at the national, EU and international level, to highlight the impact and the potential impact of OHEJP-developed solution, and to encourage the stakeholders to pick them up.

The second day will focus on a wider scope of stakeholders, including research institutes, projects, initiatives, and private sector. This will represent one of the main efforts of the OHEJP for broad dissemination.

During Y5 the organisation of the event was carried on.

7.1.2 Task 5.2: Identification of the research needs of EU stakeholders

WP5 has a number of tools in place to gather the needs of EU and international stakeholders.

Scanning of stakeholders' documents

Regular scanning of stakeholders' documents (publications, reports, regulations, press releases, speeches etc.) is performed, and identified needs are summarised in monthly documents stored in thematic groups of the OHEJP website, where they are available to consortium members and stakeholders. To ease access to such documents, they are also accessible through a [dedicated page](#) of the One Health EJP website. The document consists of initial pages with highlights of the month, followed by news summarised in order to highlight information useful for the One Health EJP. This activity is performed in order to keep the consortium up to date with stakeholders' needs, knowledge gaps, policy trends, new regulations, future risks etc. Future knowledge gaps and policy needs are tagged for easy recovery of information.

The websites scanned are updated as needed. At the moment the following websites are scanned: ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, EC Press Corner, European External Action Service, DG-SANTE, European Health Union, JRC, Scientific Committee on Health, Environmental and Emerging Risks (SCHEER), European Council and Council of the EU, European Parliament, EU Action on AMR, European Health Data Space, EC public health, European Parliament Think Tank, EU Health Policy Platform, FAO (including regional

offices), WHO (including regional offices), OIE/WOAH (including regional offices), UNEP, ProMED-AMR, Horizon Magazine, One Health Initiative, One Health Commission, Eco Health Alliance, CIDRAP, Health Policy Watch, EFPIA (European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations), Animalhealth Europe (association of animal medicines industry).

WP5 dissemination activities are complementary to the general dissemination activities of the One Health EJP (WP1, Communications Team) and the results of the scanning of stakeholders' documents are available to support other means of dissemination (e.g. social media). In addition intelligence from such scanning exercise is used to inform the SRIA on trends of stakeholders' needs and key policies (WP7 Task 7.2).

Direct communication of needs

While the activity of scanning of stakeholders' documents helps keeping the consortium up to date with general needs of the stakeholders, it is an indirect way to identify them. Direct, active dialogue with stakeholders is important and focuses on research and integrative needs in the area of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats. The two approaches supplement each other.

Following earlier discussions, a virtual helpdesk was established to allow easy communication about ad hoc needs. The helpdesk is mainly run by communication through email and can be complemented through a thematic group of the One Health EJP website, allowing documentation of the steps taken to respond to the communicated needs if needed. Most importantly, personal communication via email is well established, and a number of web-meetings were organised to discuss the identified needs, expectations of the stakeholders, and the support that the One Health EJP can offer.

Involvement in sustainability

WP5 also contributes to the sustainability aspects of the OHEJP (led by WP7). Because not all of the stakeholders' needs can be addressed within the lifespan of the consortium, WP5 supports activities of WP7, notably the drafting of the table of outcome (part of D7.1 "Analysis of outcomes and uptake of EJP's outputs by stakeholders") and of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA, Task 7.2).

The table of outcomes of D7.1 consists in a selection of OHEJP-developed outcomes possibly being of particular relevance for ECDC, EFSA, DG-AGRI and DG-SANTE. Entries include the name of the project with a link to the project webpage, where a contact is readily available, a brief description of the outcome, and, if available, the link to access the outcome itself and reference to papers if more insights are needed. Such outcomes are categorised into domains (FBZ, AMR, ET, or JIP), and following the integrative strategy matrix, which helps to select the correct outcome based on particular situations (e.g. design and implementation of surveillance activities, laboratory methods, reference material). Such outcomes were first selected by WP5 based on the One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI, Task 5.3), summarised, validated by JIPs and JIPs with the support of WP3 and WP4, and finally the style of the resulting table was improved by WP5 and WP7, and incorporated in D7.1.

WP5 also supports drafting the SRIA, an activity led by WP7. WP5 contributed in describing relevant stakeholders of the OHEJP and related current and future needs, summarising new policies relevant for the future of One Health, and describing how the OHEJP supports EU and international activities.

7.1.3 Task 5.3: Linking of the scientific capacity available in the EJP with the stakeholders' identified needs: closure of knowledge gaps

The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory

The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI, previously referred to as "capacity map") is a tool linking the stakeholders' needs with the scientific and integrative results of the consortium. It highlights outcomes of the OHEJP, supports dissemination of results of the various activities within the consortium (e.g. research projects, integrative activities), and depicts to some extent complementarity

with activities outside the OHEJP. The OHOI is a public online database accessible to all through a [dedicated page](#) in the OHEJP website. As such, it targets not just European and international stakeholders, but also national stakeholders, other interested parties (e.g. private sector, other One Health initiatives), and supports internal and external collaboration and dissemination. As an internal dissemination tool, the OHOI helps identifying potentially overlapping activities as they emerge, thus minimizing the risk of duplication of work.

The OHOI is split between an Outcome section and an Updates section.

The Outcome section lists the outcome of the consortium (databases, biobanks, computational methods, pieces of hardware, etc.), gives general information on the specific outcome, highlights the added value by depicting to a certain extent similar activities in place outside of the consortium, and links to specific resources if available. Most importantly it gives the contact information of the persons in charge, facilitating contacts in case more insights are desired.

The Updates section illustrates the progress of the different areas covered in the OHOI in a timely manner. It gives updates on the activities of JIPs and JRPs which are completed, in progress or planned, with reference to the source material where the information was acquired. If an update deals with a specific outcome, it links to the Outcome section of the OHOI. Contacts of the persons responsible for the update are also given. Old updates are available in the Archive section, in order not to overload the database.

The OHOI opens with a short text introducing the tool, and linking to other resources where outcomes are available, like the publication page, the projects' page and, importantly, the Data Management Plan Reader (Task 5.4). The OHOI has a search function to ease navigation and browse the inventory, as well a "new update" column that highlights newest updates. In addition to browsing the database, data of the OHOI can also be downloaded.

The backbone of the inventory was implemented in the form of a relational database, using the commercial software Caspio.

The OHOI was shaped following thorough discussion with the PMT and the key EU stakeholders. Suggestions and comments are still being taken into consideration and based on them the OHOI is being constantly improved.

Besides the design, initial population of the database, deployment, and technical curation, WP5 is also in charge of the update of the OHOI. WP5 updates the OHOI mostly taking information from the annual reports, deliverables and publications, but also from personal communications. WP5 gathers information, which, after being validated by the project leaders, is uploaded on the OHOI. Alternatively, project representatives can require an immediate editing/addition by contacting WP5.

In Y5, WP5 performed a general update of the Outcome section, and a further update is planned before the end of Y5.

Feedback gathered during Y5 pointed out the overwhelming amount of information in the Updates section (more than 1000 entries, including those in the archive), and discussion centred around how to make the information more focused, while maintaining optimal transparency. It was decided to move all the entries of the Updates section in the Archive, while keeping in the foreground the Outcome section, which was seen as most useful.

It was further decided to keep the OHOI available after the end of the OHEJP as a repository of outcomes developed within the consortium. After September 2023, the OHOI will still be available through the One Health EJP website and through the MedVetNet association website.

The OHOI is advertised on newsletters, at meetings, at international conferences, on the One Health EJP website, and through other means (for example it was published in the introduction of MATRIX/ORION OHS Codex/KIP).

To avoid duplication of efforts within the OHEJP and to support dissemination, WP5 is also involved in the DMP Committee (Task 5.4), supervised by WP4, to coordinate and link the DMP with the OHOI.

WP5 is also in charge of more targeted means of dissemination: the targeted reports and the thematic reports, in which the identified needs of the stakeholders are linked with the OHEJP activities (Task 5.4).

Other ad hoc support at the global, European, and national level

Another way in which knowledge gaps are being closed is through setting up activities to support specific stakeholders' needs with specific actions, as well as through the development of specific strategies addressing interests of national, EU and international stakeholders, as agreed following consultation with stakeholders.

One example is the collaboration with the WHO-Global Outbreak Alert and Response Network (GOARN) – of which the OHEJP is a partner – and the One Health Commission. During Y4 a global survey was ran together with the two organisations to examine the value of One Health workforce and of One Health networks in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. This resulted in a joint publication in Y5 ([Streichert et al., 2022](#)).

After discussion in the SCMs and following stakeholders' invitation, the OHEJP joined the Partner Platform of the Tripartite's One Health Regional Coordination Mechanism in late 2021. During Y5, OHEJP contributed to the ToR of the Partner Platform, and discussion continued on how to best support the One Health Regional Coordination Mechanism through targeted dissemination of OHEJP-developed solutions.

This Tripartite initiative is part of a number of global initiatives that the OHEJP supports to expand the dissemination and outreach of One Health EJP results beyond the borders of Europe. A further example of contribution to the global One Health agenda during Y5 is the input to the ToR of the One Health Expert Panel (OHHLEC).

The OHEJP also supports other global initiatives: the WHO-GOARN; the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide's Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Tool (SISOT), which features outcomes of the OHEJP; and the international One Health initiative PREZODE, by joining a number of discussions to help setting up the initiative.

Thanks to the strong connections built in the previous years, the OHEJP was involved in the discussions on the JPI-AMR Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), as well as in the JPI-AMR Prevention and Interventions Roundtable discussion.

Not just international stakeholders, but also European stakeholders well acknowledge the closure of knowledge gaps provided by the OHEJP, and its potential in shaping the future One Health agenda. This was seen for example by EFSA inviting OHEJP representatives to contribute to the EFSA Advisory Forum. OHEJP further made use of its expertise and knowledge to provide input to two EU Stakeholders' Consultations: the 2023 Stakeholders' Targeted Consultation on EU4Health priorities, strategic orientations and needs (we were also invited to present our view at the EU4Health Stakeholders' event, see Task 5.4); and the Stakeholders' Consultation on the new EU Global Health Strategy. It has to be noted that the contribution of the OHEJP to the stakeholders' consultation is often taken into account (or at least so it seems). For example, in 2021 OHEJP took part in the consultation on the GOARN 2022-2026 strategy (in written form and by taking part in the global meeting of partners, see deliverable D5.9), and indeed One Health has been included as a GOARN Area of Work.

Closure of knowledge gaps was also notable by national stakeholders, for example by OHEJP reports being used by national ministries. Moreover national stakeholders followed with interest the

Dissemination Workshops, organised in collaboration with WP3, WP4 and WP6, and set up to address stakeholders' needs (Task 5.4).

Targeted reports

Targeted Reports to Key EU Stakeholders are regular reports disseminated ahead of the SCM meetings (i.e. twice per year, Task 5.1). These Targeted Reports are a key tool to disseminate concise updates, with the objective of keeping the One Health EJP stakeholders up-to-date with:

- News of the One Health EJP consortium and events of interest for the stakeholders;
- Outputs of projects, with focus on those communicated by ECDC and EFSA as being of particular interest;
- Impact achieved by finished projects;
- Recent scientific publications.

Although Targeted Reports are aimed at ECDC and EFSA, all the stakeholders' organisations have access to them, and WP5 encourages internal dissemination in the stakeholders' organisations. In Y5, two Targeted Reports were produced.

7.1.4 Task 5.4: Dissemination of new knowledge, tools and materials

WP5 implemented a variety of general (e.g. the OHOI, Task 5.3) and tailored dissemination strategies in order to meet the needs of national, European and international stakeholders. This maximises the impact of the consortium's outputs and ensures that the tools and results of the OHEJP are used in a timely manner.

The overall dissemination strategy is regularly discussed with stakeholders, particularly during the SCMs, and subjected to revision.

Support to the Data Management Plan

WP5 is part of the Data Management Plan (DMP) committee, led by WP4, which supports JRPs and JIPs to draft and publish their respective DMPs. WP5 was involved in the evaluation of final DMPs () of finished projects, and took care that they were correctly uploaded on Zenodo. Within the DMP committee, WP5 focuses on the FAIRness aspects from the point of view of the stakeholders. After several feedback rounds and exchanges with the company providing the CPD software, a public DMP reader was set up, through which it is possible to have access to DMPs of the second call projects (projects that are still ongoing). The DMP reader is accessible through a dedicated webpage on the OHEJP website. Given that DMPs are living documents, normally available only after the end of the projects, having a DMP reader for ongoing projects improves the transparency of OHEJP activities and timeliness of dissemination of outputs. In the same webpage, also DMPs of finished projects are easily available.

During Y5 WP5 contributed to the evaluation of 17 projects' DMPs.

Given the similarity of scopes between the DMP and the OHOI, to maximise their added value and avoid duplication of work, WP5 linked the DMP with the OHOI: the DMP webpage is in fact reachable also through the OHOI.

Dissemination of OHEJP calls and events to the stakeholders, and dissemination of stakeholders' calls within the OHEJP

Dissemination efforts go both from the consortium to the stakeholders, and from the stakeholders to the consortium.

Calls for OHEJP initiatives are disseminated to the relevant stakeholders (EFSA, ECDC, EEA, EMA, FAO, OIE, WHO-Euro) with the kind request for further internal dissemination within the stakeholder's agency. In addition, stakeholders play a role also in broader dissemination of OHEJP calls and tools through their newsletters (e.g. EFSA and One Health Commission newsletters), and websites (e.g. One Health Tools & Toolkits page of the One Health Commission).

Stakeholders, aware of the outreach of the OHEJP network, also request their calls to be disseminated within the OHEJP, for example the Call for Applications for the selection of members of the AMR One Health Network, requested by EMA, and the WHO-GOARN Call for Nominations for the GOARN Steering Committee 2022-26.

Dissemination to national, European and international stakeholders: the Dissemination Workshop series

Dissemination Workshops are a form of scientific support to stakeholders which addresses specific needs of national, EU and international stakeholders. Target audience is mostly national stakeholders: experts at the level of ministries (e.g. risk managers with a scientific background) and decision/policy makers (upper level of the hierarchy, POC members with limited scientific background). Although addressed primarily at national stakeholders, EU (ECDC, EFSA, EEA, EMA) and international (FAO, OIE, WHO-Euro) stakeholders are welcome to participate. To ease participation, the workshops are organised as online events.

The Dissemination Workshop series was initiated by WP5, and its format was defined after thorough discussion with the PMT and with Project Leaders. These workshops focus on the impact of One Health EJP-produced solutions, e.g. case studies on how the solutions have been used in a country, how they were/could be applied in specific situations, and how they benefit the prevention, detection, and response using the One Health approach. Each Dissemination Workshop is centred around one topic, with several projects contributing to different aspects. Given the varied technical background of the audience, the Dissemination Workshops focus on examples of applications rather than on the scientific side, avoiding technical details and using an appropriate language.

Before each workshop, a briefing flyer is produced, with information on the scope of the workshop, and after the workshop a concise report of outcomes (highlights, key messages, recommendations and future needs) is distributed to the participants.

Information on the Dissemination Workshops is not made public to keep the audience as specific as possible. Information is rather disseminated through POC, PMC, SSB and the Stakeholders Committee with the request of forwarding to relevant decision makers.

The workshops consist of an initial part of presentations by invited scientists, and an important second part of dialogue between the scientists (speakers) and the policy makers (audience). During this phase, needs of both the groups are exchanged, and the discussion highlights how the scientists can support policy makers, and vice versa. This is a unique opportunity for bridging the gaps between science and policy.

The topics of the Dissemination Workshops should reflect the interests of the audience, therefore in Y4 a survey was initiated involving POC, PMC, SSB, and stakeholders' organisations. The survey helped WP5 to identified topics of interest for workshops during Y5.

The first Dissemination Workshop was held in October 2021 and was centred around metagenomics. It had 143 participants from 20 European countries. The second Dissemination Workshop was held in Y5 and dealt with Improving One Health Preparedness to (re)emerging infectious threats. It saw the participation of 110 participants from 17 European countries. Interestingly, while in the first workshop most of the audience was from food safety sector, in the second one the participants were equally distributed between human, animal, food, and the One Health sector. This improvement could be

attributed to a more general interest in the topic, but also to a more accurate dissemination of the event.

After both the workshops an evaluation survey was distributed to the participants, and both the workshops were evaluated very positively by the participants (e.g. on a score from 1 to 5 to the question “how useful for you personally was it to attend this event?” the average score was 4.5 for the first event, and 4.1 for the second). Based on such feedback the format of the next Dissemination Workshops will be adjusted.

To maximise the impact of the Dissemination Workshops, the final reports are uploaded on Zenodo, and made available through the [Science to Policy Translation webpage](#).

Further dissemination of results

Additional dissemination of WP5 results is achieved through presentations in international conferences and at stakeholders’ meetings. So far in Y5 WP5 was represented in the following events of broad outreach:

- Annual Scientific Meeting 2022: two posters
- 4th international conference on animal surveillance and health: poster presentation
- Geneva Health Forum 2022: poster presentation
- Animalhealth Europe annual event: invited panellist
- ONE – Health, Environment, Society – Conference 2022 (ONE2022): one poster, WP5 representative was invited as panellist, and a side event was organised by WP5 and the Communications Team
- The 9th International Conference on Social Sciences 2022: oral presentation (accepted, Sep. 2022)
- EU4Health Stakeholders’ event: based on the consultation submitted prior to the event, we were invited to submit a poster and to present our experience and proposition regarding the future of One Health within EU4Health

Additional dissemination in OHEJP meetings with national stakeholders and other parties was achieved in: SSB meeting, POC/PMC meeting, ESAB meeting, OHEJP review meeting.

Among the aforementioned events, the ONE2022 should be noticed. ONE2022 was organised by EFSA and sisters agencies ECDC, ECHA, EEA, EMA and JRC. In the frame of the conference, the OHEJP was encouraged by EFSA to organise a [side event](#).

WP5, in collaboration with the Communications Team, organised the side even entitled “[One Health European Joint Programme: Lessons learnt from a European multidisciplinary initiative](#)”. The objectives of the event were to introduce the OHEJP, to inspire and encourage all (from early career colleagues to high-level stakeholders) to learn about the One Health approach, to share experiences of working in a multidisciplinary environment and to reflect on the One Health approach along with the benefits of cross-sectoral collaborations from a personal and professional development point of view at institutional, national and European level. The side event took the form of a high-level round table discussion, and saw participation of representatives of ECDC, EFSA, One Health High Level Expert Panel, WHO-Euro, the MedVetNet Association, as well as representatives of the OHEJP PMT, project leaders and PhD students. The hybrid nature of the event allowed broad participation.

In addition to the organisation of the side event, a representative of WP5 was one of the invited panellists of the thematic session “Making a difference: bridging EU research and policy”, next to representatives from the European Parliament, EEA, EFSA, EMA and ECHA, moderated by representative of ECDC.

7.2 Deliverables and Milestones

7.2.1 Deliverables

N/A

7.2.2 Milestones

N/A

8 WP6 - Education and training

8.1 Work carried out to date

8.1.1 Task 6.1: Short-Term Missions

In M54, D6.14, report on short term missions 2021 was submitted and uploaded to Zenodo and to the OHEJP website. The reports of the successful STMs that took place in 2021 and to date in 2022 have been received and case studies created. The case studies have been uploaded to the STM 2021 page and STM 2022 page of the OHEJP website, and these were disseminated via several internal and external channels- e.g. social media and newsletters. Case studies of the remaining STMs will be created when the reports have been received.

The extended call for STM applications in 2022 resulted in 5 applications. Each application was sent to three independent reviewers and are currently being evaluated for quality, strategic fit and cost effectiveness. Four of the applications were recommended for funding by the reviewers and then the project management team. The award letters have been sent out to the applicants.

8.1.2 Task 6.2: Workshop programme (satellite to Annual Scientific Meetings)

The ASM Satellite workshop 2022 was held online on 14th April 2022, hosted by the University of Surrey and the National University of Ireland, with the theme: mobile detection platforms for One Health diagnostics applications. The workshop was open to internal and external audiences and was targeted towards PhD candidates, and junior researchers and professionals. Invited speakers from the University of Surrey and National University of Ireland, Galway, presented on their experience of factors influencing the design of diagnostic assays for One Health applications, including sample types (environmental, clinical from humans or animals), target sequences and assay format, reflecting on current standard diagnostics in public and animal health. This workshop highlighted two diagnostic techniques: LAMP and LEC-LAMP, with a hands-on interactive session on designing LAMP and LEC-LAMP assays. The workshop was a great success, with over 60 delegates.

The ASM Satellite workshop 2022 page with flyer and programme can be found [here](#). The event website page and promotional branded tools for the event were produced by the OHEJP communications team.

The ASM 2022 deliverable report D6.16 will be submitted in M60 as planned.

8.1.3 Task 6.3: 'One health' Summer School for medical and veterinary science

The OHEJP 'Final' summer school is to be held by the University of Surrey in December 2022. The budget and proposal will be submitted by the end of September 2022. The theme of the final school will be sustainability in One Health, emphasising the importance of training and education for the OHEJP legacy, and covering related topics such as effective communication, commercialisation, and policy, in addition to sustainability with regards to FBZ, ET and AMR.

8.1.4 Task 6.4: Doctoral Training Programme

In M49-54, WP6 continued to support and monitor the progress and dissemination activities of the PhD projects. This included providing guidance to the PhD main supervisors and their respective PhD candidates to ensure WP6 can monitor the progress of the projects effectively through submission of their project deliverables and publications. WP6 ensured that the PhD deliverables submission, dissemination, and reporting procedures were updated and adhered to, along with the scientific publication policy.

In total, in M49-54, 18 deliverables were achieved, and two publications were produced. Further details of the progress of each PhD project are discussed in more detail in the individual PhD reports in this deliverable.

All public deliverables and publications were uploaded to Zenodo by the PhD supervisors, and subsequently, to the PhD project pages on the website by the OHEJP communications team, who wherever possible, promoted these dissemination activities through our social media channels.

All confidential deliverables have been uploaded to the private space of the OHEJP website in individual project groups to which the supervisor and student have access and control.

In M49-50, all PhD supervisors and their students submitted their 12-month reports reporting on the progress, outcomes, and collaborative activities over M37-48. WP6 worked closely with the supervisors and advised them as required to complete the template reports. WP6 then worked with the individual 12-month reports to produce the deliverable report - D6.22: 4th periodic report on PhDs, submitted in M53.

Annual Scientific Meeting

The PhD candidates were well represented at the Annual Scientific Meeting in M52. Sixteen of the PhD candidates shared their work at the ASM. Twelve presented their work as a poster, and four as an oral presentation (one was presented by their supervisor as they could not attend – LIN-RES). One of the PhD candidates, Olivia Turner, won the Early Career Oral Presentation, for her PhD project WILBR on “Contribution of wild birds to AMR in the environment and on farm.”

Three Minute Thesis Competition

WP6 also hosted and organised the Three Minute Thesis (3MT) PhD competition at the ASM 2022. Fifteen of the PhD candidates participated (8 in person and 7 online) and showcased their projects in this competition to a very high standard. The winner of the 3MT 2022 was selected and announced at the close of the ASM - Marieke de Cock, PhD project DESIRE on “Developing evidence-based surveillance for emerging rat-borne zoonoses in changing environments.”

Round Table Discussions

WP6 also hosted the PhD Round Table discussion, where students presented two slides, discussing their PhD learning experience so far and the policy impact of their project. Fourteen PhD candidates presented, 8 in-person and 6 online.

Other training activities

Some PhD candidates also participated in the other training activities by WP6 to learn and expand their networks with a new generation of ‘One Health’ researchers. One of the STMs awarded in 2021 to Marieke de Cock (DESIRE) was carried out in M51-52. Two PhD candidates that applied to the STM 2022 call – Laura Gonzalez Viletta (EnvDis) and Ingrid Cardenas Rey (VIMOGUT), have also completed their STMs in M52-54.

To report the progress of the project and to evaluate the COVID-19 impact, PhD supervisors and students submitted a 9-month summary progress report to WP6 through the templates provided, to inform the content this Summary Progress Report Y4. The 9M PhD reports can be found below.

8.1.4.1 PhD01-R1-AMR2-ECO-HEN

8.1.4.1.1 Summary

Although the student salary was only covered by OHEJP until March 15th, during these nine months, from January 2022 to September 2022, she has carried out the following activities:

- In April, she joined the annual scientific meeting (One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022) in online format. During the congress, the student had the opportunity both to share part of her work over a poster format entitled “Putative APEC isolates from healthy animals and eggs in a laying-hen commercial farm” and to listen to the work of other colleges. In addition, she presented a poster.
- During the OHEJP-ASM 2022, she participated in the 3 minutes’ thesis competition, in which she was able to summarise her project and present it to her colleagues. This contributed to the development of her oral and written dissemination skills.
- During the same congress, she participated in a round table discussion, where she was able to talk about her PhD progress, skills acquired during the PhD, and the policy impact the project could have. She has also listened to the talks of other colleagues, sharing what each had learned during the thesis.
- The student attended an online workshop on advanced bioinformatics in R. In this workshop she learned how to deal with omics data in R software, focusing on variants in the human genome associated with diseases
- The student has attended the doctoral seminars organized by the university. As she did last year, her classmates summarized their thesis and the progress made by them.

All data analysis has already been carried out, up to task 8.1. Tasks 8.2 and 9 (manuscript and thesis draft) have been delayed due to several reasons. In addition to the pandemic, which forced us to delay lab work, we were missing sequence data without which we could not perform some data analysis. In addition, having finished her grant, the student found a job in another research institute, which led us to delay the last two tasks.

8.1.4.1.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

WP8. Flow of AMR isolates from animals to egg shells.

WP9 continues based upon what was achieved during the second annual period of the OHEJP and is devoted to analysing relationships between AMR bacteria of laying hens and eggs.

T8.1. Bioinformatics analysis of the WGS: achieved. The study of the transmission of resistance genes and mobile genetic elements is already finished.

T8.2. Data analysis and scientific manuscript preparation. A second manuscript has not been written yet, as we are using a new focus.

WP9. Writing of PhD thesis.

In October 2021 the writing of the thesis started. As mentioned above, the writing was being done at the same time as some missing analyses. The delay in writing is mainly due to the fact the student left her position at VISAVET since her doctoral fellowship ended (15/03/2002), and she started working at another research institute, writing the document on her free time.

8.1.4.1.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number <i>(Include original number, if different)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Include original name, if different)</i>	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 <i>(month)</i>	Actual Delivery Date <i>(month)</i>	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date <i>(month)</i>	Comments <i>(Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)</i>
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	<i>from the actual one)</i>	<i>from the actual one)</i>				
PhD1-AMR2-ECO-HEN	D-E14-5.1.	A list of plasmids putatively present on <i>E. coli</i> isolates	M27 (March 2020)	M31 (July 2020)		
	D-E14-6.1	A list of <i>E. coli</i> from animals isolates to be sequenced	M28 (April 2020)	M33 (July 2020)		
	D-E14-6.2.	Manuscript	M33 (September 2020)	M43 (July 2021)		https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378113522001237?via%3Dihub https://zenodo.org/record/6626506
	D-E14-7.1.	A list of <i>E. coli</i> from eggs to be sequenced	M37 (January 2021)	M36 (December 2020)		
	D-E14-8.1.	Manuscript	42 (June 2021)	48 (February 2022)	58 (October 2022)	Under preparation The topic of this manuscript has been changed due to the final results obtained. Consequently, we have not a tentative delivery date.
	D-E14-9.1.	Doctoral thesis draft	48 (December 2021)	53 (May 2022)	58 (October 2022)	Delayed as mentioned into the text.

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
PhD1-AMR2-ECO-HEN	M-E14-1	Updated list of phenotypic features of the <i>E. coli</i> isolates collection	M15 (March 2019)	Yes		
	M-E14-2	Training of the PhD-student on bioinformatic analysis of raw sequences	M17 (May 2019)	Yes		Achieved September 2019
	M-E14-3	New sequenced <i>E. coli</i> isolates from animals	M33 (September 2020)	Yes		Achieved April 2021
	M-E14-4	New sequenced <i>E. coli</i> isolates from eggs	M37 (January 2021)	Yes		Achieved October 2021

8.1.4.1.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Clonal and plasmid-mediated flow of ESBL/AmpC genes in <i>Escherichia coli</i> in a commercial laying hen farm https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetmic.2022.109453 https://zenodo.org/record/6626506	OHEJP is not mentioned in the acknowledgement section but it is under funding organizations		0 €

8.1.4.1.5 Additional output

One communication was presented at the One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 (11th -13th April 2022, Orvieto, Italy). “Putative APEC isolates from healthy animals and eggs in a laying-hen commercial farm”. Online format (P05).

8.1.4.1.6 Remarkable outcomes

The results of this project show that the dynamics of *E. coli* AMR determinants in animal crowded populations with a negligible use of antimicrobials, like laying hens, follows a Russian-dolls model where different genetic platforms are sequentially involved.

The level of AMR resistance generally decreased from the incoming day-old chicks into the farm to laying hens, but did not disappear.

At the bottom level, AMR determinants in *E. coli* can be alone or, more frequently linked into integrons and/or multidrug-resistance regions (MDR-regions). Then, these pieces can be located into plasmids or the bacterial chromosome. Finally, any of the previously mentioned platforms can be find into (and spread by) *E. coli* clones.

Horizontal transfer of AMR determinants between *E. coli* isolates in this population was mainly due to plasmids carrying MDR-regions and/or integrons, whereas the vertical transfer was related to clones where different models regarding maintenance, loss and acquisition of AMR-carryings pieces has been detected.

Integrons are the most detected linking piece for only a reduced number of AMR determinants (*sul*, *dfrA* and *aadA* gene families), showing a minor role on the global flow of AMR. The most frequently detected AMR determinants in our study (gene families *tet*, *bla* and *str*, among others) were more prone to be linked in changing MDR-regions carried by plasmids or the chromosome.

8.1.4.1.7 Impact & relevance

As mentioned in previous reports, during this period (January-September 2022) the PhD project has not been in direct collaboration with external institutes; nevertheless, the PhD student is in close contact with VISAVET researchers working in other ongoing OneHealthEJP projects like ADONIS, DISCoVeR and MATRIX for improving their bioinformatics skills. In addition, the results of the thesis, presented in posters, the on-going-publications and finally in the thesis, can serve to inform other researchers in partner institutes involved.

8.1.4.1.8 List of dissemination and communication activities

- Participation in a workshop

8.1.4.2 *PhD03-R2-AMR2.1-HME-AMR*

8.1.4.2.1 Summary

This project, which focuses on the impact of the presence of heavy metal (in this case zinc) in soil on the resistome both in the soil and foods produced from the land, commenced in February 2021. As reported previously there were significant delays in student recruitment due to COVID-19 related travel restrictions. In the last 9 months, Elena has progressed work on her scoping review, which is almost complete and ready to be submitted for consideration for publication. To facilitate the writing process, Elena attended the CMNHS Writing for Research Purposes Workshop from February to April for a total of 30 hours, which provided a better understanding of writing an academic paper in English. In addition to this the student has completed a number of training modules and workshop in relation to data analysis, conducting research, antimicrobial resistance and One Health methodologies and approaches.

The first experimental study of the project has been completed. Field plots were set up in two geographically distinct regions, with zinc added to some plots and not to others at each site. Soil samples were taken at both sites (22 zinc added, 22 no zinc added) and returned to the lab. Each sample was analysed for the presence of Enterobacterales, ESBL-producing Enterobacterales, carbapenamase producing Enterobacterales and ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacterales using culture based SOPs in place in the lab. Presumptive isolates obtained from this sampling were identified by MALDI-TOF. The ones confirmed as Enterobacterales were then tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility by disc diffusion in accordance with EUCAST criteria. In the current reporting period genomic analysis on the resistant Enterobacterales was conducted through whole genome sequencing, and the phenotypic profiles were compared with the genotypic ones. This study is now being prepared for publication. Soil samples from each plot were also stored for later DNA extraction for metagenomic analysis.

8.1.4.2.1.1 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

Task 1 (Study 1) Comparison of the resistome in low and high metal containing soils

Discussions on site selection have taken place with Geological Survey Ireland (GSI). GSI have provided detailed mapping data on soil zinc concentrations across Ireland which will enable site selection. In addition the student will partner with colleagues in Teagasc Johnstown Castle to utilise portable technology for zinc measurement when on site to identify the most suitable sampling regions. Sampling will commence in Summer 2022. Analytical SOPs are in place from Study 3 which has been completed already.

Task 2 (Study 2) Comparison of the resistome in bovine milk filters from cattle grazing on grass in low and high metal areas

Sampling for this study will follow from site selection for Study 1 and will take place in the summer of 2022. Analytical SOPs are in place. Suitable farms will be selected through consultation with the Teagasc advisory (extension) service and discussions are underway in this regard.

Task 3 (Study 3) Comparison of the resistome in zinc amended and non amended soil used for horticultural crop production

As indicated in previous reports high level zinc oxide supplementation of pig diets will no longer be permitted in the EU from 2022 and therefore it is expected that the zinc levels present in pig slurry will decrease. Due to this and the desire to reduce the variables it was deemed appropriate to focus on the impact of direct zinc amendment, as may occur in horticultural crop production, and compare soils in paired plots with and without amendment to monitor and changes in the resistome. This also provides

the opportunity to monitor changes in AMR organisms present in crops produced in these soils. The deliverable associated with this study is unchanged. Due to sampling practicalities this study was undertaken first.

Work on this task is now finished. Sampling has been completed on two sites (160 samples in total), the presence of Enterobacterales, ESBL-producing Enterobacterales, carbapenamase producing Enterobacterales and ciprofloxacin resistant Enterobacterales was conducted using culture based SOPs and confirmed by MALDI-TOF analysis. A total of 21 Enterobacterales, including 16 *Serratia fonticola*, 2 *Escherichia coli*, 1 *Morganella morganii*, 1 *Citrobacter freundii* and 1 *Enterobacter cloacae*, were identified and tested for antibiotic susceptibility by disc diffusion. The DNA of the 21 Enterobacterales was extracted using a DNAeasy kit and then analysed for whole genome sequencing. The obtained results were compared with the phenotypic results of the AST analysis.

Task 4 (Study 4) Genotypic comparison with antimicrobial resistant Enterobacteriaceae with human, environmental and animal isolates from Irish and EU reference laboratories

Dr Burgess and Prof Morris have suitable banks of isolates from animals and the environment for comparison with isolates obtained as part of this project and will utilise public repositories of sequenced isolates and collaborations with reference laboratories to increase the diversity of isolates for comparison. The selection of strains for comparison will be dependent on the identity of isolates obtained in studies 1, 2 and 3 of this project. This work will commence in late 2022.

8.1.4.2.1.2 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	D-PhD03-1.1	Report on AMR bacteria present in soils of differing heavy metal content	M60		M69	Delay in student starting project and rearrangement of study commencement order will delay the first deliverable being achieved.
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	D-PhD03-1.2	Report on the impact of the application of heavy metal containing amendments to AMR bacteria in soil	M54		M60	The study has been completed and is currently being written up for publication.
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	D-PhD03-1.3	Report on AMR bacteria present in	M66			Delay in student starting project

		milk filters from animals grazing in areas of differing heavy metal content				will delay the achievement of this deliverable.
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Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	1	SOP in place for sampling culture based analysis	27	Yes	M40	Delayed due to the late recruitment of student but the SOPs for culture based analysis are now in place and have been utilised in the first sampling study undertaken.
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	2	Sequences of sufficient quality obtained from metagenomic analysis	35	No	M58	Delayed due to late recruitment of PhD student

8.1.4.2.1.3 Publications and additional outputs

Not applicable yet.

8.1.4.2.1.4 Remarkable outcomes

Not applicable yet.

8.1.4.2.1.5 Impact & relevance

Dr Burgess and Prof Morris currently collaborate on the Irish EPA funded project AREST which examines antimicrobial resistance in the environment and contribute to One Health orientated AMR research and policy making at a national and international level. This project is highly complementary to those activities and will facilitate an increasing collaborative relationship between the research groups. Dr Burgess has worked previously with Dr Johannessen of the Norwegian Veterinary Institute as part of the HUPLANT Control COST action focusing on microbial food safety issues and this project will further develop this relationship. This project has also led to Dr Burgess forging collaborative linkages with Geological Survey Ireland in relation to heavy metal mapping and with the SFI funded VISTA MILK research centre. This work has also contributed to Dr Burgess and Prof Morris submitting an application for national research funding on AMR mitigation measures in the environment.

8.1.4.2.1.6 Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

8.1.4.2.1.7 Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

A number of meetings have taken place with Geological Survey Ireland and through collaboration with the Tellus survey (<https://www.gsi.ie/en-ie/programmes-and-projects/tellus/Pages/default.aspx>). This is enabling the selection of suitable high and low metal content soils across Ireland for resistome analysis as part of study 1 and farms for selection as part of study 2.

As part of Study 3 we have collaborated with a nationally funded project which is focused on the impact of different soil amendments on cadmium uptake in food crops. We focused on plots where zinc has been applied and use the corresponding control (no amendment) plots for comparison.

This project is complementary to the EPA funded AREST project (<https://www.nuigalway.ie/medicine-nursing-and-health-sciences/medicine/disciplines/bacteriology/research/arest/>) which is examining antimicrobial resistance in the environment. Prof Morris is the coordinator of this project and Dr Burgess is a participant. The culture based methodologies being employed in AREST will be particularly relevant for HME-AMR. The student will have the opportunity to collaborate with these colleagues for methodologies and isolate characterisation.

Dr Burgess and Prof Morris both contribute to Ireland's National Action Plan for Antimicrobial Resistance which has recently been updated and the results of this project will contribute to achieving the objectives of that plan.

HME-AMR is complementary to an ongoing PhD project in Dr Burgess' group focusing on the impact of zinc oxide supplementation on the porcine resistome which will facilitate a smooth transition for the HME-AMR student in relation to methodologies and analysis.

HME-AMR is complementary to a project led by Dr Orla O'Sullivan as part of the SFI funded VistaMilk project (<https://vistamilk.ie/>) which is examining the soil resistome in different sites across Ireland. Dr Burgess and Dr O'Sullivan will collaborate to ensure synergy of the projects and avoid duplication.

8.1.4.2.1.8 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
CMNHS English Language Workshop	Writing skills	Feb-Mar-Apr (30 hours)	NUIG-English Language Centre
Research Integrity	Training to conduct research	April 2022	Epigeum
Bioinformatic Workshop	Data analysis	20/05/2022 27/05/2022 13/06/2022	Teagasc
JPIAMR Workshop- New perspectives on bacterial drug resistance	Antimicrobial resistance	09/06/2022	JPIAMR
UCD One Health Conference 2022	One Health	15/06/2022	UCD

ONE – Health, Environment, Society – Conference 2022	Antimicrobial resistance	21-24/06/2022	EFSA
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8.1.4.2.2 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM		
Date:	April 11-13 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy /in person		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (poster)
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM		
Date:	April 11-13 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy /in person		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (Thesis in 3 minutes)
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	

<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM		
Date:	April 11-13 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy /in person		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes (Roundtable discussion talk)</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	ONE Conference 2022
Date:	June 21-24 2022

Place:	Brussels/online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes (poster)
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Num ber		Numbe r
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

8.1.4.3 PhD04-R2-AMR2.1-KENTUCKY

8.1.4.3.1 Summary

Salmonella enterica serovar Kentucky (*S. Kentucky*) is a common causative agent of gastroenteritis in humans. It is one of the most notorious *Salmonella* serotypes, as it is strongly associated with antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Ciprofloxacin-resistant *S. Kentucky* can gain additional antibiotic resistance determinants through the acquisition of locally circulating plasmid-borne ESBL, AmpC, and/or carbapenemase genes. Most recently, the situation has worsened, as ECDC launched an Urgent Inquiry (UI-464) on a CIP^R *S. Kentucky* ST198 strain carrying a chromosomally integrated *bla*_{CTX-M-14b} gene encoding for cephalosporin resistance. The insertion event was traced back to Malta, but the strain has already spread to Belgium, the UK, and five other EU countries. In this Ph.D. project, we investigate (i) what explains the evolutionary success of the multidrug-resistant *S. Kentucky* ST198 clone, and (ii) what are the mechanisms of the integration (and potential further transfer) of the ESBL gene in its chromosome. As of 2022, 654 IncHI uniquely typed plasmids are found around the world. Most of these plasmids are found in *S. enterica*, *E. coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Moreover, IncHI plasmids are important spreaders of antibiotic resistance genes, ca. 40% of colistin resistance-carrying plasmids in Europe, belong to the IncHI group. Due to its clinical significance, the *S. Kentucky* resident-IncHI- mega-plasmid carrying the ISECP1-*bla*_{CTX-M-14B} transposition unit was chosen as a focal point for our fluorescent tagging strategy. Yet, wet-lab experiments backed with *in silico* analysis indicated that the plasmid is non-conjugable, most probably due to truncation in the transfer region. Thus, we reasoned to shift to the prototype IncHI1 plasmid (R27), a self-transmissible plasmid with fully

characterized conjugation machinery (Craig et al., 2000) and is capable of transfer between members of the *Enterobacteriaceae*.

The transposition mechanism of ISECP1 is obscure so we decided to develop fluorescent reporters based on the partitioning system *parS*/*ParB* to differentially label the pR27 backbone and the ISEcp1-*bla*_{CTX-M-14b} unit. *parS* is a cis-acting centromere-like sequence to which a partitioning protein *ParB* selectively binds. Two alternative partitioning systems were instigated namely, P1 Phage-derived and *Lactococcus lactis*-derived *parS*/*ParB*. The later system has minimal interference with DNA replication. Yet, the system is derived from gram-positive bacteria and needs to be optimized to a gram-negative host. First, we labeled the pR27 backbone with a P1-*parS* sequence. Next, we tagged ISECP1-*bla*_{CTX-M-14B} transposition with *lactis-parS* sequence *in vitro*, followed by cloning the assembled unit into pR27. Then we codon-optimized *lactis-parB* protein according to *Salmonella* codon usage and fused the optimized-*parB* to *msf-GFP* under an IPTG inducible promoter. We tagged optimized *parB* at the N-terminus and C-terminus with both flexible and rigid linkers. Yet we failed to obtain localized foci *in vivo*.

We decided to move to alternative fluorescent reports based on P1/ pMT partitioning system (Nielsen et al., 2006). In parallel, the *in vitro*- mating assays of pR27 indicated a conjugation efficiency of 10^{-5} - 10^{-6} at 25C which is challenging to study under the fluorescent microscope. Hence, several genetic approaches were instigated to increase the conjugation efficiency to be able to track the transfer event in real-time. first, we replaced the conjugation repressor *htdA* with pMT *parS* sequence to obtain a 2-3 log increase in the conjugation efficiency (Whelan et al., 1994). Next, we tried overexpressing *trhR* and *trhY* genes *in trans* to further increase the conjugation efficiency Since *TrhR* and *TrhY* are involved in the activation of the expression of the four *Tra* operons of pR27. Finally, we opted for knocking out the nucleoid-associated proteins H-NS which is known to repress the conjugation of pR27. The aforementioned approaches resulted in a 4 log increase of the conjugation efficiency of pR27 at 25C (ca. 1 in 10). Next, we *in vitro*-labeled the ISECP1-*bla*_{CTX-M-14B} transposition unit with P1-*parS* sequence and cloned it into pR27, yielding the reporter double *parS* labeled plasmid (R27 [Δ *htdA*::*frt*-*Cm*-*frt*- pMT*parS* -ISEcp1-P1*parS*-*bla*_{CTX-M-14b}]) which conjugate at a frequency of 1 in 10 at 25C. To visualize the transfer of pR27 in real-time we constructed a recipient strain (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ *ara*::*tetR*-*Km*-*CFP*:P1*parB*-*YGFP*:pMT*parB*), which encodes orthogonal *ParB* proteins (Nielsen et al., 2006) fused to fluorescent reporters. Via a microfluidic platform we were able to track in real-time the transfer of double *parS* labeled plasmid (R27 [Δ *htdA*::*frt*-*Cm*-*frt*- pMT*parS* -ISEcp1-P1*parS*-*bla*_{CTX-M-14b}) from a donor *S. enterica* cell (MA8058 Δ pSLT; Δ *hns*) to a recipient cell (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ *ara*::*tetR*-*Km*-*CFP*:P1*parB*-*YGFP*:pMT*parB*).

8.1.4.3.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

Insertion of P1-*parS* and *lactis-parS* labeled transposition unit into pR27

pKD46, a plasmid with temperature-sensitive replicon, encoding lambda Red recombinases was electroporated into MA8508 Δ pSLT strain. Next, pR27 was conjugated by filter mating to MA8508 Δ pSLT containing pKD46. In short, cultures of the donor (*E. coli*, pR27) and recipient strains (MA8508 Δ pSLT containing pKD46) were grown in LB supplemented with the required antibiotics at 25°C in static conditions for 16 h. Cells were washed with 0.1M MgSO₄ to eliminate the antibiotics. The recipient strain suspension (0.4 ml) and donor strain suspension (0.1 ml) were mixed on a 0.22 μ m membrane and incubated at 25°C for 2 h. Serial dilutions were plated in appropriate media to select for trans-conjugants (MA8508 Δ pSLT containing pKD46 and pR27).

P1-*parS* was then PCR amplified as P1-*parS*-*frt*-*cat*-*frt* fragment and electroporated into MA8508 Δ pSLT containing pKD46 and pR27 to be inserted in an intergenic region on pR27 backbone via lambda red recombineering (Datsenko et al; 2000). Next, we flipped the chloramphenicol cassette using pCP20, a plasmid encoding *Flp* recombinase. To label the ISEcp1-*bla*_{CTX-M-14b} unit with *Lactococcus lactis*-derived *parS*, we PCR amplified the unit as two fragments with the 18bp *parS* sequence as an overhang

(GGGGCTAAATTTAGCCCC). The two fragments were then assembled *in vitro* by gibsson assembly and inserted into pR27 backbone by homologous recombination (Datsenko et al; 2000). The 18bp parS sequence was inserted downstream the terminator region of the ISEcp1 gene and upstream the promoter region of bla_{CTX-M-14b} gene. We then confirmed the insertion of P1 and *Lactococcus lactis*-derived parS together with the conservation of the ISEcp1, bla_{CTX-M-14b} genes by sequencing.

Optimizing P1-ParB and Lactis-ParB Proteins

First, we separately inserted by recombineering the two parS sequences into the chromosomes of MA8508ΔpSLT to serve as a positive control for fluorescent microscopy. Next, we transformed the MA8508ΔpSLT labeled with P1-parS and lactis-parS with pALA2705 and pMK17-01 respectively. pALA2705 plasmid encodes P1-parB N-terminally fused to mCherry whereas pMK17-01 encodes lactis-parB C-terminally fused to msfGFP. Time-lapse microscopy experiments showed only localized foci with P1-parB-mCherry, indicating that lactis-parB failed to bind its cognate parS sequence. Thus we reasoned to codon optimize the lactis-parB protein to a gram-negative host using the genescript™ platform. Then the codon-optimized lactis-parB protein was then cloned into a variant of pALA2705 encoding GFP to obtain pALA2706 (lactis-parB N-terminally fused to GFP). pALA2706 was then transformed into MA8508ΔpSLT labeled with lactis-parS. Microscopy experiment showed again diffused fluorescence. We thought to change the fusion type into C-terminal fusion and try different linkers. In short, pALA2706 was PCR linearized to remove GFP- lactis-ParB. Then msfGFP and lactis-ParB were PCR amplified, assembled *in vitro* to produce lactis-parB C-terminally fused to msfGFP with two different linkers (SSSRGSGGEAAKAGS, (SGGGG)₄), and ligated back to PCR-linearized pALA2706 by gibsson assembly. The two variants of the plasmid were then separately transformed to MA8508ΔpSLT labeled with lactis-parS. yet we failed to obtain localized foci. The inability of *lactis*-ParB to bind its cognate parS sequence *in vivo* may be attributed to improper folding in gram-negative host despite being codon-optimized. It is also possible that parB fail to oligomerize upon binding so we don't observe the localized focus over the background diffused fluorescence. Moreover, in *E.coli*, the integration host factors (IHF) bind specific sequences on P1-parS and facilitate the binding of P1-parB to P1-parS (Barbara Funnel., 1991) and since lactis-parS does not carry an IHF-binding sequence it might have failed to attract the partitioning machinery.

Construction of a reporter plasmid based on P1, pMT parS/ ParB partition system

pR27 displays a conjugation efficiency of ca. 10⁻⁵ at 25°C and ca. 10⁻⁷ at 37°C. Since conjugation of the wild-type R27 plasmid is only a one in a 10⁻⁵ event, three genetic engineering approaches were instigated to increase the conjugation efficiency of pR27 to maximize the likelihood of observing the conjugation in Real-time. **(i)** The first approach was knocking out the conjugation repressor HtdA which is involved in the repression of four tra operons and has a pivotal role in the growth phase dependency of R27 conjugation. In short, pMT parS was PCR amplified as pMT-parS- frt-cat-frt fragment, and the fragment was electroporated into MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27 to replace *htdA* gene. *In vitro* conjugation assay has shown a 2-3 log increase in the conjugation efficiency of pR27, *htdA* mutant as compared to the wild type. We then labeled the transposition unit with P1-parS as previously described followed by electroporation into MA8508ΔpSLT containing pKD46 and pR27(pMT-labelled, Δ*htdA*), yielding double parS labelled pR27 (R27 [Δ*htdA*::frt-Cm-frt- pMTparS -ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]). **(ii)** Next, we opted for overexpressing the conjugation regulators TrhR and TrhY which are known to activate the expression of four different Tra operons (Gibert et al; 2016). The *trhR* and *trhY* genes were PCR amplified and assembled *in vitro* (i.e. Gibson assembly) under a strong constitutive promoter (J23119). The assembled construct was electroporated (MA8058 pKD46 ΔpSLT), to be inserted into an intergenic region, flanked by two terminators to prevent read-through. The transformants were PCR confirmed, however, the sequencing data showed multiple mutations resulting in an early stop codon in *trhY*. In a second attempt, we tried to over-express *trhR* and *trhY* in cis on pR27 (R27 [Δ*htdA*::frt-Cm-frt-pMTparS]). The native promoter of *trhR* and *trhY* was replaced by the strong constitutive promoter (J23119). After the exchange of the native promoter, the construct

was PCR confirmed, however, frameshift mutations were found in the trhR rendering the construct not functional. Previous work by Fornes et al. (2005), and Gibert et al. (2014) suggests that conjugation of R27 can be increased by either knocking out the *hns* gene of the chromosome of the donor cells or the plasmid itself. (iii) The third approach to increase the conjugation efficiency was thus based on the deletion of *hns* in the chromosome of the donor strain (MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT). In short, The ORF of *hns* was replaced by *frt*-Km-*frt* except for the first 11 amino acids (MA8058 pKD46 Δ pSLT Δ hns::frt-Km-frt). Next, The double *parS* labelled plasmid (R27 [Δ htdA::frt-Cm-frt- pMTparS -ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]) was conjugated from a Δ hns strain *S. enterica* strain (MA8058 Δ pSLT). The respective conjugation frequencies were calculated as the transconjugant over recipient ratio (T/R) and the transconjugant over donor ratio (R/D). At 25°C the T/R conjugation efficiency is ca. 1.12×10^{-1} and the T/D conjugation efficiency is ca. 7.70×10^{-2} . Hence, Conjugation efficiency has increased from ca. 10^{-5} (pR27 wild type) to ca. one in 10 by knocking out both HtdA and H-NS.

Construction of the fluorescent recipient strain to visualize the transfer of pR27 in real-time.

Next, a recipient strain, which encodes orthogonal ParB proteins (Nielsen et al., 2006) fused to fluorescent reporters (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ ara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB), was assembled, to visualize the double *parS* tagged R27 plasmid. These proteins are under the control of an inducible, non-leaky promoter PLtetO-1 which is repressed by TetR. The system can be induced with 200 ng/mL anhydrotetracycline (aTc). We reasoned to assemble cognate *parB* proteins fused to fluorescent markers into a chromosomal operon under the control of an inducible promoter to avoid ectopic expression from the plasmid. The strain was constructed through 3 consecutive steps. First, the arabinose operon was deleted from MA8058 Δ pSLT strain and replaced by tetA-sacB cassette by positive selective on tetA. Second, the cognate *parB* proteins translationally fused to fluorescent reporters (CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB) were PCR amplified and electroporated into MA8058 Δ pSLT, pkd46, Δ ara::tetA-sacB to replace tetA-sacB under the native arabinose promoter by negative selection against sacB/tetA. (Li et al., 2013). Finally, the native arabinose promoter was crossed out and replaced by an inducible, molecularly evolved PLtetO-1.

Next, to validate both the reporter plasmid and the recipient strain, pR27 plasmid labelled with pMTparS and P1parS (R27 [Δ htdA::frt-Cm-frt-pMTparS ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]), was conjugated to the recipient strain (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ ara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB) and the resulting transconjugants were tracked in real-time with fluorescence microscopy (AB-glycerol at 30°C; ATC at final conc. 200 ng/ml). This results in overlapping foci between the green (YGFP) (the plasmid backbone) and blue (CFP) (the transposon) channel as can be seen in Figure 1. The foci are shown in the mid-cell at 0 min, 18 min, and 36 min (after cell division). At 90 minutes two foci are segregated from the mid-cell before cell division (Lawley et al., 2003). Recipient cells that carry WT pR27 showed only diffused fluorescence (data not shown) indicating that the localized green and blue foci are likely due to the pMT-parS (plasmid backbone) and P1-parS (transposon) respectively.

Figure 1. Recipient cell with double *parS* labelled R27 with YGFP and CFP fluorescent foci. The double *parS* labelled R27 plasmid (R27 [Δ htdA::frt-Cm-frt- pMTparS ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]) was conjugated to the recipient strain (MA8058 Δ pSLT Δ ara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB). The resulting transconjugants were followed with time-lapse fluorescence

microscopy on AB-glycerol pads at 30°C. Both the YGFP (plasmid backbone) and CFP (transposon) foci are overlapping at the mid-cell during the time-lapse (0-36 min). The plasmid is segregating from the mid-cell after 90 minutes. Pictures are an overlay of phase contrast, green fluorescence, and blue fluorescence.

Tracking the transfer dynamics of pR27 in real-time via microfluidics

The next step was to track the conjugation of the R27 plasmid using time-lapse fluorescence microscopy. This was performed numerous times but did not yield any conjugation events. Recent research performed by Carranza et al. (2021) also did not observe any conjugation events with time-lapse fluorescence microscopy. They hypothesize that the agar pad might be inhibiting the conjugation. Nolivos et al. (2019) were able to capture conjugation events in real-time only via a microfluidic platform. Hence, we reasoned to use a microfluidic platform to track the conjugation in real-time. Donor cells (MA8058 ΔpSLT; Δhns; pR27 [ΔhtdA::frt-Cm-frt- pMTparS -ISEcp1-P1parS-blaCTX-M-14b]), were mixed with recipient cells (MA8058 ΔpSLT Δara::tetR-Km-CFP:P1parB-YGFP:pMTparB) in 1:4 ratio respectively and loaded into a chamber in a microfluidic chip. Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy was performed at 25C with an inverted Ti-Eclipse, Nikon microscope. GFP filter (FITC single emission filter and quad-edge dichroic filter-395/470/550/640 nm) and CFP filter (Emission filter Em475/20+triple excitation filter) were used. Snapshots of the cells were made every 15 for a total of 6h. After 90 min foci started to emerge indicating a transfer event.

Figure 2. A 1:4 mixture of the donor (non-fluorescent) and recipient cells (fluorescent) growing at 25C in a microfluidic chamber under inverted Ti-Eclipse, Nikon microscope. On the Left panel, cells after loading into the chip (t0) show a mixture of non-fluorescent donor cells and recipient cells with diffused fluorescence. The right panel shows some of the recipient cells after 90 min (t90) start showing localized foci, marking independent conjugation events.

8.1.4.3.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)
	D6	Paper 2 (Tentative title). Characterization of factors	M57		>M60	Given the results explained in

		influencing the transfer of ESBL genes from plasmid to chromosome.				section 2, we aim for publication in 2023
	D7	Paper 3 (Tentative title). The prevalence of ISEcp-1 mediated transfer of ESBL genes to the chromosome among clinically isolated Enterobacteriaceae	M57		>M60	Given the results explained in section 2, we aim for publication in 2023

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	M5	Research visit to INRAE	M52	No	M57	Planned September 2022

8.1.4.3.4 Publications and additional outputs

No peer-reviewed papers have been published yet, they are planned for 2023 (see above).

8.1.4.3.5 Additional output

The following poster and oral presentations have been done:

- Albasiony, A., Ceysens, P.J., Aertsen, A. (2021) Exploring the ISECP-1 mediated chromosomal integration of blaCTX-M-14 in Salmonella Kentucky. Annual Scientific Meeting OHEJP, June 9-11th, 2021. Poster presentation.
- Albasiony, A., Ceysens, P.J., Aertsen, A. (2022) Exploring the evolutionary success of the antibiotic resistant Salmonella Kentucky ST198. Annual Scientific Meeting OHEJP, April 11-13th, 2022. Poster presentation.
- Albasiony, A., Ceysens, P.J., Aertsen, A. (2022) Exploring the evolutionary success of the antibiotic resistant Salmonella Kentucky ST198. International Symposium Salmonella and Salmonellosis I3S2022. June 20-22, Saint-Malo, France. Oral presentation.

Impact & relevance

The Kentucky project units **Sciensano**, **INRAE** and Laboratory of Food Microbiology of **KULEUVEN** (BEL), which clearly have complementary expertise. Sciensano holds the National Reference laboratory of Salmonella and has experience in short-and long read sequencing. **Prof. Abram Aertsen's** group uses analytical genetics and live (single) cell biology approaches to study the spread, establishment and adaptive phenotypic impact of mobile genetic elements. **Benoît Doublet** and his team have long-term

expertise in plasmid biology, and will study the transfer dynamics of these elements. It is clear these groups, which have never collaborated before, will greatly learn from each other, and will exchange knowledge, strains and experiences along the way. The final goal is to improve our methodologies and understanding of transfer dynamics of these mobile elements, and its impact on antimicrobial resistance.

Exploring the evolutionary success of the antibiotic resistant Salmonella Kentucky ST198

Alan Albarany^{1,2} · Pieter-Jan Ceyssens¹ · Abram Aertsen²

1. Department of Bacterial Diseases, Sciensano, Brussels, Belgium
2. Department of Microbial and Molecular Systems, Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Leuven, Belgium

Salmonella Kentucky (S. Kentucky) is a common cause of agent of gastroenteritis in humans. It is one of most notorious Salmonella serotypes, as it is strongly associated with antimicrobial resistance. Ciprofloxacin-resistant S. Kentucky belongs to a single sequence type (ST198), which acquired an IncI-type, mega-plasmid, producing ESBL, with successive transposition of ESBL gene (bla_{CTX-M-15}) from the plasmid to the chromosome. The multiple drug resistant clone spread across the EU continent, which was subject to an urgent inquiry (SI-464) of the ECDC. In this context, our research aims to elucidate horizontal gene transfer dynamics of conjugative plasmids and subsequent transposition of the carried IS elements at a single-cell resolution.

METHODS

We are developing fluorescent reporters based on orthogonal parS/ParB systems to differentially label the plasmid backbone and the IS_{CTD1-46}-M₂₅₂-parA unit.

The reporter systems should enable studying the relevant horizontal transfer dynamics, including conjugation and transposition, at a fine- and intracellular level using time-lapse fluorescence microscopy and microfluidics.

RESULTS

- computationally, we determined the boundaries of the 2.5KB transposition unit harboring the IS_{CTD1-46} adjacent to an insertion-like sequence-IS_{Ecpt1}.
- We knocked out the conjugation repressor *ARA5A* in the IncI-paratypic plasmid (pI27) and replaced it with pMT-derived parB.
- Next, we cloned the transposition unit into pI27 and labeled it with P1-derived parS.
- Subsequently, we assembled the cognate ParB proteins fused to fluorescent markers under a non-leaky inducible promoter.

CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

The transposition of resistance genes from plasmid to chromosome adds an important dimension to the spread and acquisition of bacterial resistance. Understanding the drivers of this transfer can help to control its occurrence.

This poster is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 772830.

8.1.1.1 Interactions with on-going JRP/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Long-read sequencing was performed according to methodology derived from the Full Force project (JRP-14). Short-term travel grant was obtained through MVNA.

8.1.4.3.6 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Supervised Master Student thesis (Bioscience Engineering, Gene Technology)	Supervision skills	01/09/2021-30/06/2022	KULeuven

8.1.4.3.7 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022		
Date:	2022-04-11 to 2022-04-13		
Place:	Hybrid		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No

<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	530	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>	10	<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>	10		

Name of the activity:	<i>International Symposium Salmonella and Salmonellosis I3S2022</i>		
Date:	<i>2022-06-20 to 2022-06-22</i>		
Place:	<i>Saint-Malo, France</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		No
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	300	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>	25	<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>	5		

8.1.4.4 PhD05-R2-AMR2/6.1/ET5-METAPRO

8.1.4.4.1 Summary

During these 9 months of 2022 we have been continuing with some of the experiments that were done in the last part of 2021. As stated in previous reports, we were able to detect next-generation aminoglycosides resistance determinants and to evaluate their genetic surroundings. The information obtained with that analysis revealed that the prevalence of these determinants is very low in the gut microbiome of different animals and that the Order *Eubacterium* may play an important role as reservoir of such genes. Therefore, during this year we have been exploring different culture approaches to isolate the bacteria harbouring next-generation aminoglycoside resistance genes. So far, we have made some advances, but unfortunately, we have not been able to isolate such reservoir bacteria. We are exploring new techniques and culture free methods, such as microfluidic approaches to enrich the bacterial species acting as reservoir.

We have also continued with the metagenomic analysis of more projects available via open repositories to find other hotspots for next-generation aminoglycoside resistance. We were able to detect a few potential candidates, but we need to still perform more analysis to be confident of such results.

In addition to find resistance determinants, we used the first part of this year to evaluate the effect of antimicrobial use on the selection of next-generation aminoglycoside resistance determinants. We were able to obtain a small dataset of farms using and not using aminoglycosides to compare the potential effect of the compounds on our target genes selections. We explored this associations for some genes, like *aac(3)-IV*, and we observed that aminoglycoside use promote increasing levels of such genes in poultry. Furthermore, we also concluded from our analysis that this increase on gene level was due to enhanced mobility of the mobilisation unit where it is embedded rather than a successful gene-bacterium association. We want to complement these *in silico* observations with *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments to try to confirm whether our conclusions are true. For that purpose, we have optimised qPCR reactions to couple with the metagenomic data. We are discussing with our collaborators from University of Surrey to see if the *in vitro* gut models that they have developed suit our necessities and perform experiments there.

8.1.4.4.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

M1 – Spanish sampling design: since during the pandemic situation was very difficult to obtain samples from the sampling points proposed, we performed the metagenomic analysis first from samples already collected in our lab and from other metagenomic projects present in accessible databases. This first *in silico* analysis offered information of which environments most likely harbour next-generation aminoglycoside resistance determinants, so that led us to make changes in the initial sampling design. Now, only samples coming from hotspots are targeted.

M2 – Spanish sampling execution: we have collected samples from several animal sources (more than one sample per animal environment) and we are still looking for new potential human and environmental sampling sources that meet the new criteria proposed for the sampling.

M3 – Metagenome sequencing of the Spanish sampling: sequencing of several samples has been performed also using Oxford Nanopore long reads technology. Is expected the sequencing of new samples in the coming months

M4 – Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the Spanish sampling: due to the preliminary results of the *in silico* analysis performed, we changed the objective of this task. Now, the aim is to isolate and culture all the bacteria that act as a reservoir of the next-generation resistance determinants of interest.

M5 – United Kingdom sampling design: we are discussing with our UK partners the viability to perform a sampling or if it is best to use already collected samples that they have access to. We are also discussing the possibility to perform complementary experiments to explore to a deeper extent some of the results we are obtaining.

M6 – United Kingdom sampling execution: since we are still evaluating which samples to use, this task is going to be delayed to later in the year.

M7 – Metagenome sequencing of the United Kingdom sampling: since we are still evaluating which samples to use, this task is going to be delayed to later in the year.

M8 – Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the United Kingdom sampling: since we are still evaluating which samples to use, this task is going to be delayed to later in the year. Again, like in the Spanish sampling, all bacteria are going to be targeted instead of only enterobacteria.

M9 – Analysis of the genomic and metagenomic data from the first sampling: analysis of metagenomic data from open repositories were downloaded and analysed. Our metagenomic pipeline was evaluated with these projects and promising results were obtained. Detection of next-generation aminoglycoside resistance determinants has been produced and resistance genes were assembled. We are still carrying on with the analysis of more samples collected.

M10 – Guideline for early detection of plazomicin resistance determinants to preserve plazomicin for human clinical use: we are going to delay this task and couple with thesis manuscript writing if enough data are obtained.

M11 – Thesis manuscript: this task is not due to take place until later this year.

M12 – Thesis defence: this task is planned for next year.

8.1.4.4.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)
	D2	Guideline for early detection of plazomicin resistance determinants to preserve plazomicin for human clinical use	Sep 2022 (M57)		Dec 2022 (M60)	We need to gather more data to see if we are going to be able to write such guideline
	D3	Thesis	Dec 2022 (M60)		Mar 2023 (M63)	

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	M10	Guideline for early detection of plazomicin resistance determinants to preserve plazomicin for human clinical use	Sep 2022 (M57)	No	Dec 2022 (M60)	We need to gather more data to see if we are going to be able to write such guideline
	M11	Thesis manuscript	Dec 2022 (M60)			
	M12	Thesis defence	Feb 2023 (M62)			

8.1.4.4.4 Impact & relevance

This PhD project connects three major laboratories focused on the fight of Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR). These research groups have collaborated and participated together in other European projects in the past contributing substantially to the generation of knowledge to stop antimicrobial resistance spread. The fact that they are now collaborating tightly in the frame of this PhD project offers the possibility to maintain the great relationship that has been always present between the institutes and that has been highlighted by the numerous exchanges of students that have successfully had part between them. In addition, this PhD project offers the possibility to combine the different perspectives of the study of AMR taken by the different groups. Further, the topics included in this project allows us to open the collaborations with other research groups that complement the experiments performed and the participation of the group in projects following the same subject.

8.1.4.4.5 Interactions with on-going JRP/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

FARMED: Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-farmed/>). Since the objectives and the techniques of both projects are similar, the candidate is taking part actively in the tasks performed at UCM associated to this project.

EFFORT: Ecology from Farm to Fork Of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission (<http://www.effort-against-amr.eu/>). The group participated actively in the EFFORT project and its activities and resources are the foundation of the present research project.

JPIAMR: Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance. The lab is part of the NEAR-AMR (<https://www.jpiamr.eu/near-amr/>) and of the GAP-ONE (<https://www.jpiamr.eu/gap-one/>) projects. The candidate can benefit of these networks to extend the search of plazomicin resistance determinants in other parts of Europe and Africa or to estimate the economic burden of plazomicin resistance.

AVANT: Alternatives to Veterinary Antimicrobials (<https://avant-project.eu/>). The student will also be involved in the development and test of alternatives to antimicrobials.

DAMR-Una Europa: “Disseminate antimicrobial resistance knowledge and the use of whole genome sequencing on relevant bacterial pathogens during COVID-19 world emergency (<https://fredepasquali.wixsite.com/damr-project>). The student is taking part in this project teaching a webinar on metagenomics and collaborating on the sequencing of bacterial pathogens.

8.1.4.4.6 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
VI Jornadas de Bioinformática	Bioinformatics	24-25/02/2022	Universidad de Granada
Jornada “One Health, Salud Humana, Animal y Medioambiental. Impacto económico y social”	One Health	24/03/2022	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course “Aprende a manejar R y RStudio”	R language	30/05/2022 – 03/06/2022	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Course “Introducción a la estadística como herramienta metodológica para la investigación”	Statistics	07-15/06/2022	Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Course "Visualización de datos con Python"	Python language	13/06/2022 – 30/09/2022	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
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8.1.4.4.7 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>Oral presentation at One Health Annual Scientific Meeting 2022</i>		
Date:	<i>11 – 13th April 2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Orvieto, Italy</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	500	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>3 Minute Thesis Presentation at One Health Annual Scientific Meeting 2022</i>		
Date:	<i>11 – 13th April 2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Orvieto, Italy</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	

Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	500	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Poster presentation at 32 nd European Congress of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID)		
Date:	23-26 th April 2022		
Place:	Lisbon, Portugal		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	15000	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

8.1.4.5 PhD06-R1-ET5-PEMbo

8.1.4.5.1 Summary

WP1: Establishment of reference sequences from the main French clonal groups (M31-M48)

The ten new complete *Mycobacterium bovis* (*M. bovis*) genomes are finalised, validated and published in GenBank database.

WP2: Genome sequence analysis (M39-M54)

The precise search of the *IS6110* environment in new complete genomes allowed the study of the presence of a 2-4 bp duplication in the insertion site which reveals transposition event.

Whole genome single nucleotide polymorphism (WgSNP) and pangenomic analyses were continued with inclusion of previous genomes representing the French *M. bovis* diversity. WgSNP analysis allowed the definition of SNPs specific to the *M. bovis* group which were compared to previous studies. This analysis also allowed the selection of SNPs present in important genes for bacterial virulence and growth. Further studies are needed to better understand the consequence of these genetic events. Pangenomic studies confirm that the global genome organisation of *M. bovis* is remarkably stable with a high core gene similarity between genomes. However, some differences can be observed such as the genome length. These differences are partially explained by differences in *IS6110* copy number or the presence of deletions of different sizes that constitute regions of difference (RD) for these genomes. The specificity of these RDs for certain *M. bovis* groups and their consequence in partial or complete gene deletion were further investigated.

WP3: Analysis of the antigenic variability: biochemical and lipidomic studies (M40-M50)

In vitro growth rates in laboratory conditions of the 10 genotypes during WP1 is a trait that we observed to be differential between strains. The standardisation tests for growth kinetics study started in March but had to be stopped because the biosafety level 3 laboratory (BSL 3) is currently unavailable (from April until July 2022).

For this reason, the WP cannot be performed during Ciriac's PhD work. The lack of these data does not affect the final output of the project, as the bioinformatics analyses could be deepened to deduce putative phenotypic changes due to genetic modifications.

WP4: Valorisation and dissemination of results (M37-M56)

The first article on *IS6110* results is published in *Frontiers in Microbiology* in Evolutionary and Genomic Microbiology section (<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2022.891902/abstract>).

New complete genomes have been published in GenBank as mentioned previously.

A short communication on additional result on *IS6110* study is being drafted.

A second article on obtaining new reference genomes and their description is under co-author's revision.

It is anticipated that these articles will be submitted by the end of Ciriac's thesis.

Ciriac has presented results on *IS6110* study and obtaining new complete genomes at 3 conferences and 3 other events.

The thesis jury is constituted and has been validated by Ciriac's doctoral school. Writing of the PhD manuscript is ongoing. Ciriac has sent the first version of the introduction and material and method parts to his supervisor. The first draft of result and discussion parts are expected to be released in July. The manuscript is due to be submitted to the thesis jury at the beginning of September.

8.1.4.5.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

WP1: Establishment of reference sequences from the main French clonal groups

Task-1.2: Sequencing and de novo assembly (M27-M41)

The ten new complete *M. bovis* genomes are finalised, validated and published in GenBank database with embargo (December 2023) pending the writing and publication of the second article about these new complete genomes.

-Two strains were also sequenced with PacBio sequencing technology.

-These genomes were assembled with PacBio and Illumina sequencing technologies.

-The comparison between PacBio and MinION sequencing technologies was performed and shows a better accuracy of PacBio sequencing with more base generated. However, the genomes assembled with the different sequencing technologies are similar.

WP2: Genome sequence analysis

Task-2.2: Genomic markers analysis (M33-M44)

-Study of the duplication presence around the insertion site showed that almost all *IS6110* insertion sites have them except for IS present in the F9 strain family which presents a deletion in the 5' of this sequence.

-WgSNP analysis was performed in 100 strains which include the 10 new complete genomes, 4 old reference genome and 86 other genome representing the *M. bovis* French genotype diversity.

-7424 SNP were found and annotated. Their distribution appears to be linear (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of SNPs between the 10 new complete genomes.

-The search of SNPs specific to *M. bovis* clonal groups was performed and compared with the current knowledge (ongoing)

-A pangenomic study was carried out with the 100 genomes that showed a high core gene similarity (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Fig 1. Gene presence and absence in 100 strains. The phylogenetic tree on the left is based on pan-genome core gene using 1708 genes. Phylogenetic tree use A10 strain drawn at root with K3PU+F+I model. The new complete genomes are marked in red. The heatmap on the right shows gene presence in dark blue or gene absence in light blue. 4143 orthologous genes are identified. Core gene represents gene found in 100 or 99 genomes.

-The RD (region of difference) analysis defines certain genetic characteristics of *M. bovis* groups. The distribution of RD in the *M. bovis* genomes is not linear and 3 regions seem to be more often involved by this genetic event (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Distribution of RDs between the 10 new complete genome. Black arrows show the genomic region with many of RDs.

WP3: Analysis of the antigenic variability: biochemical and lipidomic studies

Task-3.1: Protein profiles determination (M40-M49)

Task-3.2: Lipidomic analyses (M40-M49)

- Acidic medium was designed and validated in laboratory.
- Standardisation test for growth kinetics study was started in March.
- However, the experiment had to be stopped because the biosafety level 3 laboratory (BSL 3) is currently unavailable (From April until July 2022).
- This WP will not be performed during Ciriac’s PhD work. However, the lack of these data does not affect the final output of the project. Indeed, further bioinformatics analyses were performed to infer the role of the genetic modifications on the phenotype of the bacterium.

WP4: Valorisation and dissemination of results

Task-4.1: Publication of results (M36-M56)

- The first article entitled “IS6110 copy number in multi-host *Mycobacterium bovis* strains circulating in bovine tuberculosis endemic French regions” is published in Frontiers in Microbiology (impact factor of 5.59 in 2022) in Evolutionary and Genomic Microbiology section.
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2022.891902/abstract>
- New complete genomes were published in GenBank database with embargo until 31/12/2023.
- A short communication on additional result on IS6110 study is being drafted.
- A second article on obtaining new reference genomes and their description is also being drafted.
- The goal is to submit these articles before the end of Ciriac’s thesis.

Task-4.2: Communication (M36-M56)

- One poster on IS6110 study was present during the “*M. bovis* congress” in Galway (Irlande).
- Two posters on new reference genomes were presented during the “*M. bovis* congress” in Galway (Ireland) and the ASMOHEJP2022 in Orvieto (Italy).
- One long oral communication was presented in English during the ABIES doctoral days 2022 in Paris (France) and in French during the SHH in Maisons-Alfort (France).
- Two short interventions (3 minutes thesis competition and Round Table discussion) were presented during the ASMOHEJP2022.
- Ciriac participated to EJP event “A day in the life of Ciriac Charles”.

Task-4.3: PhD manuscript writing (M36-M56)

- PhD manuscript is currently being written by Ciriac.
- First version of introduction and materials and methods part were sent respectively in M52 and M53 to his supervisor.
- The first version of result and discussion parts should will be finished by the beginning go July.
- The manuscript is due to be submitted to the reviewers the beginning of at September.
- Thesis jury was consolidated and validated by Ciriac’s doctoral school.

8.1.4.5.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference,

	<i>different from the actual one</i>		Work Plan 2021 (month)		date (month)	<i>reason and justification of delay, other comments</i>
	D-E5-5	Final steering committee	M42	None		This document is not requested by Ciriac's doctoral school.
	D-E5-6	Oral communication at a congress	M46	M52		Oral communication on new <i>M. bovis</i> complete genomes study in ABIES doctoral days 2022 congress.
	D-E5-7	Publication in an international journal	M46	M53		This deliverable is delay because writing/correction time and result improvement delayed by COVID-19 crisis. The article is published in Frontiers in Microbiology.
	D-E5-8	PhD manuscript	M48		M58	French version of PhD manuscript is planned to M58 (October 2022)
	D-E5-9	SHH2020 oral communication	M27	M53		New deliverables add. Oral communication (20min) in French at Maisons-Alfort (France). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581493
	D-E5-3.1	ASMOHEJP2020 oral communication	M29	M53		New deliverables add. Oral communication (3min) in English at Prague (Czech republic). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581483
	D-E5-10	LABIO AU LABO 2021 event	M37	M53		New deliverables add. Internet event. Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581428
	D-E5-11	MT180 2021 oral communication	M38	M53		New deliverables add. 3 minutes thesis competition in French. Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581480
	D-E5-12	ASMOHEJP2021 poster 1	M42	M53		New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Copenhagen (Danemark). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581523
	D-E5-12.1	ASMOHEJP2021 poster 2	M42	M53		New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Copenhagen (Danemark). Published in Zenodo in embargo: https://zenodo.org/record/6581535
	D-E5-12.2	ASMOHEJP2021 oral communication	M42	M53		New deliverables add. Oral communication (3min) at Copenhagen (Danemark). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581468
	D-E5-13	SHH 2021 oral communication	M45	M53		New deliverables add. Oral communication (20min) in French at Maisons-Alfort (France). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581474
	D-E5-14	JSDA2021 poster	M45	M53		New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Maisons-Alfort

						(France). Awarded "best poster presentation". Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581509
	D-E5-17	ANSES INTERVIEW 2021	M47	M53		New deliverables add. Internet event. Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581392
	D-E5-15	SFM poster 2021	M45	M53		New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Montpellier (France). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581542
	D-E5-16	Doc Avenir 2021 oral communication	M45	M53		New deliverables add. Oral communication (10min) in French. Awarded 1 st public price and 2 nd jury price. Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581466
	D-E5-18	ASMOHEJP2022 poster	M52	M53		New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Orvieto (Italy). Published in Zenodo in embargo: https://zenodo.org/record/6581531
	D-E5-18.1	ASMOHEJP2022 oral communication 1	M52	M53		New deliverables add. Oral communication (3min) in English at Orvieto (Italy). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581461
	D-E5-18.2	ASMOHEJP2022 oral communication 2	M52	M53		New deliverables add. Oral communication (5min) in English at Orvieto (Italy). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581451
	D-E5-19	M.bovis2022 poster 1	M54	M53		New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Galway (Ireland). Published in Zenodo in public access: https://zenodo.org/record/6581495
	D-E5-19.1	M.bovis2022 poster 2	M54	M53		New deliverables add. Poster presentation at Galway (Ireland). Published in Zenodo in embargo: https://zenodo.org/record/6581503

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	M-E5-8	Protein profiles	M42	None		This task will not be able to be completed
	M-E5-9	Lipidomic profiles	M42	None		This task will not be able to be completed

8.1.4.5.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
SHH2020 oral communication https://zenodo.org/record/6581493	Yes	Green Open Access	
ASMOHEJP2020 oral Communication https://zenodo.org/record/6581483	Yes	Green Open Access	
LABIO AU LABO 2021 event https://zenodo.org/record/6581428	Yes	Green Open Access	
MT180 2021 oral Communication https://zenodo.org/record/6581480	Yes	Green Open Access	
ASMOHEJP2021 poster 1 https://zenodo.org/record/6581523	Yes	Green Open Access	
ASMOHEJP2021 poster 2 https://zenodo.org/record/6581535	Yes	Green Open Access with embargo (31/12/2022)	
ASMOHEJP2021 oral Communication https://zenodo.org/record/6581468	Yes	Green Open Access	
SHH 2021 oral communication https://zenodo.org/record/6581474	Yes	Green Open Access	
JSDA2021 poster https://zenodo.org/record/6581509	Yes	Green Open Access	
ANSES INTERVIEW 2021 https://zenodo.org/record/6581392	Yes	Green Open Access	
SFM poster 2021 https://zenodo.org/record/6581542	Yes	Green Open Access	
Doc Avenir 2021 oral communication https://zenodo.org/record/6581466	Yes	Green Open Access	
ASMOHEJP2022 poster https://zenodo.org/record/6581531	Yes	Green Open Access with embargo (31/12/2022)	
ASMOHEJP2022 oral communication 1 https://zenodo.org/record/6581461	Yes	Green Open Access	
ASMOHEJP2022 oral communication 2 https://zenodo.org/record/6581451	Yes	Green Open Access	
M.bovis2022 poster 1 https://zenodo.org/record/6581495	Yes	Green Open Access	

M.bovis2022 poster 2 https://zenodo.org/record/6581503	Yes	Green Open Access with embargo (31/12/2022)	
IS6110 copy number in multi-host <i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> strains circulating in bovine tuberculosis endemic French regions Frontiers in Microbiology journal https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2022.891902 .	Yes	Green Open Access	

8.1.4.5.5 Remarkable outcomes

M. bovis complete genomes publication in genbank database.

Article publication in Frontiers in Microbiology in Evolution and Genomics of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex section. The title of the article is IS6110 copy number in multi-host *Mycobacterium bovis* strains circulating in bovine tuberculosis endemic French regions (<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2022.891902/abstract>).

8.1.4.5.6 Impact & relevance

The aim of this thesis project, a collaborative study between ANSES, Animal Health Laboratory (Maisons-Alfort) and INRAE, Infectiology and Public Health laboratory (Nouzilly), two French EJP Partners, is to better understand the complex biology of *M. bovis* through the study of the complete genomes of a large panel of isolates of interest. The first two parts aimed at obtaining reference sequence (WP1) and identifying large genomic events (WP2). This part of the project will be carried out at ANSES and with the support of Genoscreen, Lille, for the strains' Illumina and MinION sequencing. These new genomes allow to better describe the *M. bovis* groups. This precise description will allow to better describe the *M. bovis* French genotypes and try to understand the high prevalence of certain genotypes in France. Then, these new complete genomes will be useful for epidemiological study. The WP3 of the project consists of studying phenotypic traits that the genetic events disclosed by the genomic studies through analyses of antigenic variability, lipidomics and proteomics studies. However, this WP cannot be done because of the problems in BSL3 and COVID-19 pandemic which has fallen behind.

8.1.4.5.7 Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Biological samples The beneficiary must confirm that no Human and/or Animal samples will be collected for further analysis.	No human or animal samples will be collected for further analyses
Environmental and Health and Safety (H&S) Aspects The beneficiary must confirm that authorisations for relevant facilities (e.g. security classification of laboratory) have been obtained, and that safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.	Authorisations for relevant facilities have been obtained, and safety procedures conforming to relevant local/national guidelines/legislation are followed for staff involved in this project.
Non EU countries (<i>putative collaboration with Argentina</i>) The beneficiary must provide details on the material which will be imported to/exported from EU and confirm that the adequate authorisations have been obtained.	Whether any collaboration was established with one of the potential mycobacterial groups in Argentina, INTA-Castelar, the <i>M. bovis</i> French strains to be sent will be so only if a MTA between the two interested parties (Anses-INTA) was signed beforehand and the <i>ad hoc</i> import licence to send them to Argentina was appropriately established.

Please provide more information on Nagoya Protocol Compliance	Concerning the Nagoya Protocol in the French territory, within the Framework of the n° 2016-1087 law of the 8 August 2016 for reconquering biodiversity, nature and landscapes, which is the implementation of Nagoya Protocol, the decree n°2017-848 of the 9 May 2017 fixates the rules to have access to the genetic resources situated in the national territory and to share the advantages resulting in their use. Argentina complies with the Nagoya protocol by the law 2726 of the 26 November 2015.
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8.1.4.5.8 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
ASMOHEJP2022	Annual scientific meeting of One health European joint programme of 2022.	11-13/04/2022	One health EJP
Training on Phd thesis writing « Journée de formation à la rédaction du manuscrit – présentiel »	Training on thesis writing and the organisation of the end of the thesis.	20/04/2022	Doctoral school ABIES - AgroParisTech
ABIES doctoral days 2022	Scientific meeting on “one health” organised by Ciriac’s doctoral school.	21-22/05/2022	Doctoral school ABIES - AgroParisTech
M.bovis congress	International scientific meeting on <i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> .	07-10/06/2022	M. bovis 2022 organising committee

8.1.4.5.9 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>A day in the life of Ciriac Charles</i>		
Date:	09/03/2022		
Place:	https://onehealthjep.eu/a-day-in-the-life-of-ciriac-charles/		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes /		Yes /
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly</i>	Yes
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Numbe		Num
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>Don't know</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	ABIES doctoral days 2022. Oral presentation.		
Date:	21-22/04/2022		
Place:	Paris, France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes /
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	Number		Num
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	More than 100	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	ASMOHEJP 2022. Presentation of one poster.		
Date:	11-12-13/04/2022		
Place:	In live (Orvieto Italy) and in Visio		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes /
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	Number		Num
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	More than 900	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	

General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	ASMOHEJP 2022. Speech event (RoundTable and Three minute session)		
Date:	11-12-13/04/2022		
Place:	In live (Orvieto Italy) and in Visio		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes /
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	Number		Num
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	More than 900	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	M.bovis congress. Presentation of two posters.		
Date:	07-10/06/2022		
Place:	Galway, Ireland		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes /		Yes /
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	Num		Num
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	500	Media	

Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Scientific Happy Hours. Oral presentation.		
Date:	17/06/2022		
Place:	Teems meeting (Maisons-Alfort France)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes /		Yes /
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	Num		Num
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

8.1.4.6 Phd07-R2-ET2.1-MACE

8.1.4.6.1 Summary

A new spatial model has been developed to analyse the geographic spread of CE disease prevalence and risk within a geographic region. With collaborators from Iran, the PhD student has contributed to an analysis of dog faecal sample data to evaluate dog CE reinfection dynamics, the publication is currently in preparation. The PhD student is also exploring further analysis with additional dog faecal sample data from within the city of Kerman for a follow-up publication. The collaboration with colleagues from Italy has also progressed, data on CE samples of sheep, goats, cattle, and water buffalo from southern Italy has been shared. The PhD student has analysed the data using the spatial model to explore the spatial heterogeneity of the disease. The study is currently being written and is planned to be submitted to a collection within frontiers in tropical diseases by 31st of August latest (relates to D-PhD07-6.2).

The elicitation questionnaire was conducted at the 4th ICAHS conference in Copenhagen. The PhD student is currently looking if there is an adequate number of responses to continue with analysis. The questionnaire was conducted using a disease-agnostic scenario, which may have caused some difficulties with questionnaire uptake. To overcome this, we are considering to either expand the audience, or modify the questionnaire to be specific to CE and distribute it across a group of experts

in the field. Interest has been established within the OHEJP consortium and a community of stakeholders in South America (relates to D-PhD07-6.3).

A mathematical model for the transmission of cystic echinococcosis (CE) has been developed and parameterised using sources from the literature. Currently the focus is on fitting the unknown parameters for different scenarios and developing the inclusion of interventions (relates to D-PhD07-6.4).

The project outputs were presented in the form of posters at three conferences so far. The project was also presented at two talks at the OHEJP ASM 2022.

Additionally, an application was sent for a COVID-19 disruption fund from the doctoral college of university of surrey. The PhD project was granted 3 extra months of funding, extending the end of funding for the project from M61 to M64.

8.1.4.6.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

D-PhD07-6.2: Ongoing

Received data from Iran and Italy on CE prevalence across a number of animal species, with more data to be received. Using the spatial model, the PhD student has analysed the heterogeneity of prevalence within the region and the PhD student is leading on the publication of one paper while assisting in another. It is expected to lead on another once more data has been shared.

D-PhD07-6.3: Ongoing

The elicitation questionnaire on stakeholder investment preferences has been conducted among an audience at the 4th ICAHS conference and responses have been collected. The PhD student will proceed with analysis of the current dataset with a possibility to extend the questionnaire to another audience for more data.

D-PhD07-6.4: Ongoing

The transmission model has been developed and parameterised; currently, fitting of the model is in progress. Once model fitting is completed for multiple scenarios, different interventions for CE will be incorporated.

8.1.4.6.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)
	D-PhD07-6.2	Spatial Temporal Model of CE validated in Italy and Iran	M49		M56	All expected data from Italy and some data from Iran has been shared. Outputs are

						<p>expected by M56 as the PhD student is leading the writing on one paper and assisting in another. Once all data is received from Iran the PhD student will begin leading on another paper as well.</p>
	D-PhD07-6.3	Questionnaire to Elicit WTP/WTA of One Health Surveillance Activities	M52		M58	<p>The methodology and structure of the questionnaire has been fully developed. The questionnaire has been conducted within the 4th ICAHS conference. Responses have been captured but yet to be analysed. It is being investigated whether there is enough data to go ahead with analysis. The PhD student has the option to expand the questionnaire to a wider audience and communications has been established to go ahead with this. There is also an option to reconduct the questionnaire using a different scenario more specific to CE.</p>

	D-PhD07-6.4	Final draft of publication with the model and control scenarios	M50		M57	The model transmission has been developed and parameterised. Fitting and incorporating control scenarios in currently in progress
	MACE.Y5.1	Final draft on economic analysis	M60		M63	Refer to D-PhD07-6.4. Delayed due to 3 month extended funding for PhD
	MACE.Y5.2	Final draft on risk preference evaluation	M60		M63	Refer to D-PhD07-6.3. Delayed due to 3 month extended funding for PhD
	MACE.Y5.3	CE model integrating surveillance, control, economic evaluation and risk preference	M60		M63	Refer to D-PhD07-6.4. Delayed due to 3 month extended funding for PhD
	MACE.Y5.4	Final report to stakeholders	M60		M63	Refer to D-PhD07-6.2. Delayed due to 3 month extended funding for PhD

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	MACE.Y5.A	Online polls with stakeholders completed	M53	Yes		The questionnaire was conducted with the 4 th ICAHs conference attendees
	MACE.Y5.B	Online interviews	M50	Yes		Interviews were in-person.

8.1.4.6.4 Publications and additional outputs

N/A

8.1.4.6.5 Remarkable outcomes

The PhD student is engaging with colleagues in Iran and Italy. He is working on a spatial model using data from a survey investigating CE prevalence in dogs (Iran), and sheep, goats, cattle, and water

buffalo (Italy). The output of the model is currently being organised and written up to be published for data from Italy.

8.1.4.6.6 Impact & relevance

In 2022, the project has collaborated within the consortium (mainly between UoS and ISS), stakeholders in South America, Iran and Italy. The PhD student is currently working on a project with colleagues from Kerman University of Medical Sciences (one publication to be submitted, one publication in prep.) and Università degli studi di Napoli Federico II (one publication in preparation). These projects are working on understanding the spread of disease prevalence and infection around different regions through data analysis of surveillance studies. Our presence at the ICAHS conference was very well received, with enhanced visibility for both the MACE project and the OHEJP.

8.1.4.6.7 Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

8.1.4.6.8 Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

The work with the questionnaire was in collaboration with OHEJP WP lead Dr Pikka Jokelainen. Dr Adriano Casulli, who supervised the student, leads the MEmE OHEJP project.

8.1.4.6.9 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
GGA Spanish Stage 3	Spanish Language	29/Sept/2021 – 5/May/2022	University of Surrey - Global graduate award

8.1.4.6.10 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>3MT competition, Roundtable talk, and Poster presentation</i>		
Date:	<i>11 - 13 April 2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Orvieto Italy</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	Yes
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Num ber		Num ber
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Poster presentation and Questionnaire conducting
Date:	3 - 5 May 2022
Place:	Copenhagen Denmark

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	Yes
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Num ber		Num ber
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Poster presentation
Date:	21-25 March 2022
Place:	York England

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No

<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	Yes
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

8.1.4.7 PhD08-R2-ET5.1/4.1/FBZSH3-DESIRE

8.1.4.7.1 Summary

In the first few months of 2022, the PhD student has continued the laboratory analyses of the field samples. Almost 700 animals have been captured, and of multiple tissue samples (e.g. lung, liver, ear, kidney, nasal septum, salivary glands) DNA and/or RNA was extracted. Subsequently, (q)PCR, ELISA or IFA was performed for a variety of zoonotic pathogens.

In March and April, the Short Term Mission (STM) to the Friedrich-Loeffler Institut (FLI) in Germany took place. This STM offered an opportunity to compare and harmonise pathogen detection methods between the RIVM and the FLI, share reference material and learn new detection methods. The STM had been postponed due to the COVID-19 pandemic and that had the advantage that all samples could be tested now. The PhD student went to the FLI for 5 weeks, taking all rat and mouse samples collected during her field work, as well as some historic samples from the RIVM. The samples were tested for *Cowpox virus*, rat *Hepatitis E virus* (rat HEV), *Lymphocytic choriomeningitis virus* (LCMV) and *Streptobacillus moniliformis*. For the *Cowpox virus* testing two different tests were used: qPCR (on DNA extracted from nasal septum samples) and IFA using heart fluid on cowpox-infected cells. Both tests were performed in the BSL3 laboratory, for which the PhD student received additional training. For rat HEV, rat liver samples were tested with both conventional PCR and qPCR. The rat samples were tested for *S. moniliformis* by both qPCR and serology in collaboration with two German partner institutes. The mouse liver samples were tested for LCMV by conventional PCR. All the pathogens that were tested will be included in the paper about zoonotic pathogen carriage in wild rats from urban areas and in additional pathogen-specific papers. Next to the valuable test results, this STM contributed to interesting discussions about rodent borne (zoonotic) pathogen research, increased contact between FLI and RIVM and led to new, extended collaborations in sharing of data and writing of papers between FLI and RIVM.

In April the PhD student gave an oral presentation and 3M thesis pitch at the OHEJP ASM, for which she received the price for best 3M thesis pitch.

After the return from the FLI, the remaining laboratory analyses at the RIVM were performed and a start has been made with the data analyses. Next to the laboratory work, the PhD student continued the literature review on zoonoses of urban wildlife, adding more species to this overview. This overview will aid in prioritising research and funds and should give more insight in ecological mechanisms influencing the wildlife populations and/or the zoonotic pathogens.

Finally, in the first months of 2022, the manuscript about 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing as a surveillance tool for screening for zoonotic bacteria in wild rats was finalized and submitted. It is currently under review.

8.1.4.7.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

The outline of the PhD's project had changed slightly from what was initially planned. Below are the anticipated chapters for her thesis and the progress in these subjects

Overview of zoonotic pathogens from urban wildlife

Of six common urban species (brown rat, wood mouse, squirrel, hedgehog, rabbit, stone marten) a systematic literature search has been performed about the prevalence of zoonotic pathogens in these species in Europe. Currently, the systematic literature search of house mice is being finalized. Combining these results in an overview should aid in prioritising research and funds and should give more insight in ecological mechanisms influencing the wildlife populations and/or the zoonotic pathogens, is expected to be finished in the first half of 2023.

Key result 9M: finalization of the systematic literature review for house mouse

Field work: factors in the urban environment affecting rat populations

The field work that has been performed in 2020 and 2021 has resulted in a large amount of data. The PhD student will analyse the relations between the urban environment and the population size and pathogens separately, beginning with relation with the population size. She has already started this by forming hypotheses and orientation within the dataset. It is expected that before the end of 2022, a manuscript is submitted.

Key result 9M: start of data analysis

Field work: monitoring of pathogens of wild rats in the urban environment

The final analyses of the testing of pathogen are currently rounded up, e.g. sequencing of detected pathogens. The following pathogens have been tested: *rat HEV**, *LCMV**, *Bartonella* spp., *Rickettsia* spp., *Borrelia* spp., *Anaplasma* spp., *Neoehrlichia* spp., *Spiroplasma* spp., *Babesia* spp., *Coxiella burnetii*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Sars-CoV-2*, *Orthohantavirus*, *Salmonella* spp., *Leptospira* spp., ESBL producing *E.coli*, *MRSA*, *Cowpox virus**, *Polyomavirus* and *Streptobacillus moniliformis** (*=tested at FLI). Once the final analyses are done and the study of urban environment and rat populations has been (almost) completed, this part of the data analysis will commence. This will obviously strongly benefit from the analyses that are already performed for the population study (chapter 2). It is expected that the manuscript for this study will be finished end of 2022/first half of 2023.

Key result 9M: finishing all laboratory work

16S rRNA amplicon sequencing as a surveillance tool for screening for zoonotic bacteria in wild rats

This manuscript has been submitted for review.

Key result 9M: manuscript submission

Potential: effects of rat population genetics on pathogen dispersal in cities.

The samples necessary for this study have been collected during the field work and through collaboration with pest controllers. Rats have been selected for this study and DNA has been extracted in the first months of 2022, and the will be send away for performing genetic testing, but whether the

PhD student can still perform the necessary analyses, depends on the progress on the previously mentioned studies.

Key result 9M: Rat selection, DNA extraction, preparation of samples for external testing.

Additionally, the PhD student will be co-author on various papers resulting from the Short Term Mission to the FLI, and on a paper describing rodenticide resistance in the Netherlands (finalizing stage). Also, the mice that have been captured in the field study as bycatch, have been tested for zoonotic pathogens and the PhD student will also be involved in writing up these results.

8.1.4.7.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)
	NEW (instead of D2)	An international, peer reviewed publication about genetic relationship of rat populations in urban areas.	M60		?	Unsure, priority is given to the studies describing relations between urban environment and rat populations and rat zoonotic pathogens.
	D5	An international, peer reviewed publication about the effect of city greening on rat populations and related public health risks.	M45		M60 (study urban environment and rat populations)	Due to additional fieldwork in 2021, this deadline has shifted.
	D3	An international, peer reviewed publication about the pathobiome of brown and black rats in various living environments	M57	M54 (submission)		Submitted for review
	D7	Oral or poster presentation on a One Health conference.	M57	M52 M 54		OHEJP ASM: oral presentation ICUP: poster presentation

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	M3	Visit laboratories of partner institutes WBVR and FLI	M42	Yes (M51)		5 week STM to FLI; Delay due to COVID-19 restrictions)

8.1.4.7.4 Remarkable outcomes

The PhD student, who has gained a lot of experience using rat snap traps by her field work, has been involved in the development of a questionnaire about use of snap traps for pest control. This questionnaire is part of a study from another PhD student on the welfare of animals in pest control. One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 3M Thesis competition winner 2022.

8.1.4.7.5 Impact & relevance

For the virome analysis, analysis of 16S NGS results and specific pathogen testing there is frequent contact with the supervisor and scientists from the WBVR. The STM of the PhD student contributed to new collaborations (both papers and sample sharing) between FLI and RIVM, and collaborating partners institutes in Germany and Lithuania.

The supervisors involved in this PhD meet once every 3 months to discuss the progress of the research. For the analyses of the populations genetic results, we have set up new collaborations with the Wageningen University.

8.1.4.7.6 Interactions with on-going JRP/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

Unfortunately, the grant proposal “Ticks and the city”, in which the PhD student and PI’s were involved, has not been selected for funding.

Collaboration is present with our RIVM colleagues working on AMR: samples that contain MRSA or antibiotic resistant Enterobacteriaceae are further typed together with this group.

Furthermore, we share samples with a PhD student who is based at the Erasmus MC and who is part of the *One Health PACT – Predicting Arboviruses Climate Tipping points* project from the Netherlands Centre for One Health. This PhD student will test the samples for arboviruses that we initially had not included in our study plan, of which our PhD can also use the results. This collaboration therefore is beneficial to both PhD’s.

Another part of the mice samples (bycatch from the field study) will be used for a PhD student from Wageningen University who is looking at (pathogen) community structures of rodents in different landscapes.

Samples collected during field work have been shared with colleagues from the Dutch Pest and Wildlife Expertise Centre (KAD) and the PhD student and PI are co-authors on the resulting manuscript (in preparation).

8.1.4.7.7 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Animal Ethics course	Animal Ethics	1st and 2nd of March 2022	WUR

8.1.4.7.8 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting</i>		
Date:	<i>11-13 April 2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Online/Italy</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
Organisation of a Conference	<i>No</i>	Participation to a Conference	<i>Yes</i>

<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	150	<i>Media</i>	0
<i>Industry</i>	5	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	10		

Name of the activity:	ERRAZE meeting		
Date:	25 th May 2022		
Place:	Wageningen University		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	No
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	Yes
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	100	<i>Media</i>	0
<i>Industry</i>	15	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	15		

Name of the activity:	Netherlands Centre for One Health (NCOH) Annual scientific meeting		
Date:	23 rd June 2022		
Place:	Wageningen		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	80	Media	0
Industry	5	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	10		

Name of the activity:	International conference for Urban pests (ICUP)		
Date:	27-29 June 2022		
Place:	Barcelona, Spain		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories

	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	5
Industry	70	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	10
General Public	20	Other	0
Policy Makers	10		

8.1.4.8 PhD09-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC

8.1.4.8.1 Summary

This project aims to trace the trend of fluoroquinolone (FQ) resistance (FQR) over a 25-year period using UK-wide national surveillance data. Over this period FQR in *Campylobacter* derived from broilers has risen from 44% in 2014 to 59% in 2020 (UK-VARSS Report 2022¹) despite a significant reduction in the use of FQs in agriculture during this period. Due to this, the project aims to determine if FQR confers a fitness advantage in *Campylobacter* in the absence of a specific selective pressure (i.e. FQs). This will be done using both *in vivo* and *in vitro* methods.

The student has been continuing to work at contributing partners ANSES having moved to Ploufragan, France in Sept 2021.

Using the previously analysed dataset, which contains information collected from 1995 to 2020 taken from UK-wide national surveillance surveys, four fluoroquinolone susceptible (FQS) isolates were selected for further study. Two of these isolates were selected to represent clonal complexes identified with high levels of FQR and two were selected to represent clonal complexes found to have low levels of FQR.

Using these isolates, the student has developed FQR via passage in chickens, and treatment of these chickens with enrofloxacin (a veterinary FQ), thereby generating *in vivo* fluoroquinolone resistant mutants. The student is currently working to carry out both *in vivo* and *in vitro* competition assays, using the original wild-type isolates and their FQR mutant counterparts. These experiments will be carried out in a controlled environment in the absence of FQs. *In vivo* competition trials have been carried out on all four isolates and their FQR mutant counterparts.

All four *in vivo* competition experiments have been completed and *in vitro* competition experiments designed. The *in vitro* competition assays will measure competition by mimicking important stages of the production cycle (farming environment, abattoir environment and food matrices).

This project has also generated results from sequence analysis and the student identified associations between MLST from whole genome sequences and FQR. He has also undergone training in species identification, AMR and SNP detection on selected sequences with the aim to carry this out on a larger dataset. The student will identify SNPs within the *Campylobacter* genomes and generate a phylogenetic tree to identify clonal groups associated with FQR or FQS.

The student has presented a poster at the 2022 annual OHEJP scientific meeting, competed in the 3MT competition and took part in the round-table discussion. The student will also present a poster at the medical school post graduate conference with the University of Warwick. The student has also applied to present in the 20th congress of the international society for animal hygiene in October 2022 and for the journées scientifiques et doctorales de l'ANSES (JSDA) 2022.

The results from this project will help fill data gaps and improve understanding of how FQR develops in *Campylobacter* and why it has continued to increase in prevalence despite a reduction in specific

selective pressure through FQ usage. This information will allow policy makers to make better informed decisions to help limit the spread of FQR *Campylobacter*.

References

1. UK-VARSS. Veterinary Antibiotic Resistance and Sales Surveillance Report (UK-VARSS 2019). (2020).

8.1.4.8.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

8.1.4.8.3 Literature review of FQ in *Campylobacter*

The student has completed the literature review on the topic as planned. It consists of three major sections: *Campylobacter*; Fluoroquinolones and Fluoroquinolone resistant *Campylobacter*.

Description of the diversity of FQR and acquisition of resistance variants over time

Data analysis of the APHA dataset has been completed for the full 25-year period. The dataset is comprised of isolates from both carcass and intestinal content samples taken during UK-national surveillance studies. The student has worked to track resistance across variables recorded at the time of surveillance (e.g. season, bird age, abattoir, sampling method and farming method) and across MLST profiles. Further work is planned to carry out SNP analysis to genetic diversity within the dataset and how this relates to FQR.

Report on the relationship between WGS and phenotype

Work has been completed on WGS from isolates from 1995, 2008, and 2020. Using the sequencing information derived from these isolates the student has also determined genotypic resistance profiles for FQ resistance and investigate concordance of these results against FQR phenotypes measured via minimum inhibitory concentration assay. The writing of the report is currently in progress.

Identification of strains for fitness trials

Four key *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates have been selected and utilised for analysis in fitness trials. Four isolates derived from caeca samples taken during 2008 that were susceptible to fluoroquinolones were selected. Each isolate is taken to represent clonal complexes associated with both FQR and FQ susceptibility.

Selection and characterization of isogenic resistant strains

From the four *C. jejuni* strains taken to ANSES, four resistant FQR mutants have been created via FQ treatment of previously inoculated chickens. Resistance status for fluoroquinolones within the mutants and parent strains was confirmed by both MIC and genotype.

In vitro fitness study: competition growth assays and growth kinetics

This work was completed from Mar 2022 to Apr 2022. The student measured the growth kinetics of all four wild-type *Campylobacter* strains and their isogenic fluoroquinolone resistant mutants, both individually and in competition. Measurements were taken at regular intervals over a 24-hour period.

Preliminary results appear to suggest variation in the competitive growth throughout the various MLSTs included in this study.

Work is currently ongoing to process the data provided by these experiments.

In vitro fitness study: comparison of survival on abiotic surfaces and on food matrices (e.g. Chicken exudate model)

This work has been completed with the exception of one strain and its mutant. The student has measured the comparative survival capabilities of all four strains and their isogenic fluoroquinolone

resistant mutants on *Campylobacter faeces*. The work for three of four strains has been completed for survival in a chicken exudate model.

Preliminary results appear to suggest variation in the competitive survival throughout the various MLSTs included in this study.

Due to difficulties extracting one strain from frozen stock and delays in the work due to COVID the student will now complete this final survival model at the APHA.

In vivo study: comparison of colonisation using chicken models

The laboratory work took place from September 2021 to June 2022. During this time, the student has conducted four competition trials using wild-type parent strains directly competing against their FQR mutants in the colonisation of specific pathogen free chickens (n=45). Faecal samples were taken at regular intervals throughout the trials, monitoring both *Campylobacter* levels within the birds and the level of FQR in co-inoculated chickens. On day 35-42, the birds were sacrificed, and caeca samples were analysed.

The results of these experiments are currently being compiled and analysed. Preliminary analysis suggests that for some MLST types but not all of the types, the FQR mutant may be more successful at colonising chickens in the model than the wild-type.

8.1.4.8.4 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)
	D-PhD09-1.1	Completion of 9-month review	M33	M33		
	D-PhD09-1.2	Literature review of FQ in <i>Campylobacter</i>	M37	M38		
	D-PhD09-1.3	PhD Annual review	M38	M38		
	D-PhD09-2.1	Description of the diversity of FQ resistance and acquisition of resistance variants over time.	M41		M60	This report has been delayed due to difficulties in obtaining data
	D-PhD09-2.2	Report on the relationship between WGS and phenotype.	M42		M63	Draft versions of this report are currently in process. Was originally delayed due to supply issues of pipette tips. Due to this, isolates need

						to be phenotyped upon students return to APHA
	D-PhD09-2.3	GWAS studies and identification of strains for fitness trials	M45		M59	No longer applicable previously replaced with "Identification of strains for fitness trials". This change in report topic has led to rescheduling of the deadline.
	D-PhD09-3.1	In vivo selection and characterization of isogenic resistant strains	M50		M62	Report delayed due to difficulties regaining susceptible strain of wt-02 post passage. Further processing of the strain was needed ensure the validity of <i>in vivo</i> experiments.
	D-PhD09-3.2	In vitro fitness study: competition growth assays and growth kinetics	M52		M60	<i>In vitro</i> trials reorganised with <i>in vivo</i> trials to fit scheduling with animal supplies and facilities
	D-PhD09-3.3	In vitro fitness study: comparison of survival on abiotic surfaces and on food matrices (e.g. chicken exudate model)	M54		M60	<i>In vitro</i> trials reorganised with <i>in vivo</i> trials to fit scheduling with animal supplies and facilities. Final experimental work is needed to be completed at the students return to the APHA in M55. This delay was due to the

						student contracting COVID over the Christmas period, therefore preventing his return to France from the UK.
	D-PhD09-3.4	In vivo study: comparison of colonisation using chicken models	M57		M66	All <i>in vivo</i> experiments are now complete, and data is currently being processed. The regaining of wt-02 post passage has a knock-on effect that delayed final experiments.

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	M13	<i>In vitro</i> fitness models	M53	No	M58	<i>In vitro</i> trials reorganised with <i>in vivo</i> trials to fit scheduling with animal supplies and facilities. Final experimental work is needed to be completed at the students return to the APHA in M55. This delay was due to the student contracting COVID over the Christmas period, therefore preventing his return to France from the UK.
	M14	<i>In vivo</i> fitness models	M57	Yes		

8.1.4.8.5 Publications and additional outputs

N/A

8.1.4.8.6 Remarkable outcomes

8.1.4.8.7 Impact & relevance

Fluoroquinolone resistance in *Campylobacter* is a threat, with the World Health Organisation (WHO) naming it on their list of 12 priority pathogen/AMR combinations. The results of this project will help policy makers, the scientific community and the agricultural industry make decisions to prevent or reduce the spread of FQR in *Campylobacter*. The study will interrogate archives of *Campylobacter* from UK research and surveillance activities in broilers from 1995 to 2020 to determine the development and diversity of resistance to FQ over time.

The UDoFRIC project combines the collaborative experience of the APHA, ANSES, and Warwick University. It combines the expertise of microbiologists, epidemiologists, and bioinformatics throughout various institutions in the UK and France. The project is supervised by Dr John Rodgers who leads the National reference lab for *Campylobacter* in animals, Professor Muna Anjum who leads bacterial characterisation workgroup and is the AMR research lead and Dr Manal Abu Oun who is the AMR and virulence characterisation team lead at the Animal and Plant Health agency (APHA). Professor Noel McCarthy is the lead of Evidence in Communicable Disease Epidemiology and Control at Warwick University. The project also includes a year at ANSES under the supervision of Dr Isabelle Kempf who is a researcher microbiologist specialized in AMR; Leading the Mycoplasma Bacteriology Antimicrobial Resistance Unit in ANSES, Ploufragan and Dr Katell Rivoal, who works in the Hygiene and Quality of Poultry and Pork Products research unit and is leading scientific projects on zoonotic pathogens (*Salmonella*, *Listeria*, and *Campylobacter*) in poultry productions.

8.1.4.8.8 Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics

8.1.4.8.9 Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

8.1.4.8.10 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
EURL Campylobacter Proficiency Test 2022	WGS and cluster analysis of Campylobacter	01/06/2022	EURL
OH EJP Annual Scientific Meeting	Scientific Conference	11/04/2022-13/04/2022	OH EJP
Warwick University Medical school Post-graduate symposium	Scientific Conference	22/06/2022	Warwick University

8.1.4.8.11 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	One Health European Joint Project Annual Scientific Meeting – 3 minute thesis, poster presentation and participation at roundtable discussion		
Date:	11-13 Apr 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy (attended virtually)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	

<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>550+</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

8.1.4.9 Phd10-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR

8.1.4.9.1 Summary

A literature review has been written on the role of wild birds in dissemination and persistence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the farm environment. The review includes sections on identifying the current situation regarding AMR in different environments; drivers for AMR; the role of vectors and the environment in persistence and dissemination of AMR; the role of AMR surveillance; and evaluation of different methodologies for identifying AMR, both by phenotype and genotype, in bacteria. The student is updating this as new research is published.

Pig and presumptive gull faecal samples were collected over three time points in October 2017, 2018, and 2019 from a low antimicrobial usage pig farm as part of the APHA's work on the ARDIG project within the One Health European Joint Programme (<https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-ardig/>). In total, 632 *E. coli* were isolated from pig and gull faeces (n=342 and n=290 respectively). *E. coli* ST 744 (31.5%), 10 (14.2%), 88 (10.7%), and 44 (8.4%) were most prevalent, and were also the only ST types present in both gull and pig faeces. Over 44% of pig isolates from non-selective agar harboured 1-12 AMR genes, and 36% of gull isolates harboured up to 15 AMR genes. The majority of ST744s were isolated from ciprofloxacin supplemented plates and harboured multiple AMR genes. The presence of *E. coli* strains of the same ST type in both gull and pig faeces across multiple time points indicates the persistence of antimicrobial resistance in the farm environment and the possible transmission or exchange of multi-drug resistant *E. coli* between these compartments.

Another outdoor pig farm, known to have wild birds persistently present on farm, was recruited for a longitudinal study and visited in September 2021. The student used antibiotic-free and antibiotic-supplemented agar plates to isolate over 1400 isolates from 151 environmental samples collected. A mixture of *Escherichia coli* and Non-*Escherichia coli* were isolated based on their appearance on the chromogenic agar. Biochemical and MALDI-ToF testing has been carried out to speciate all isolates before they were frozen down. A subset of 475 isolates were selected and DNA was extracted and sent for whole genome sequencing. The student has used Kraken to further speciate the isolates and is now carrying out downstream sequencing analysis to determine the AMR gene content of these isolates.

The student attended the OHEJP ASM 2022 meeting in person where they delivered an oral presentation on their PhD, took part in the 3MT competition, and participated in the EJP PhD student round table discussion as part of communicating their research. The student won the prize for the best oral presentation by an early career researcher at the OHEJP ASM 2022. The student has also presented their work at a GW4 AMR Alliance (a collaboration between the University of Bath, the University of Bristol, Cardiff University & the University of Exeter) event and at the University of Exeter College of Medicine and Health Post Graduate Conference. The student has attended workshops run by GW4 AMR Alliance and a symposium on ‘Research and innovation to reduce the burden of antibiotic resistance: strengthening the European action’, in order to further develop their skill set for tasks later on in the project.

8.1.4.9.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

- **Milestone 1 - Collection of microbiological samples for longitudinal study (COMPLETED)**
- Due to the number of samples collected and bacteria isolated from the farm visit in September 2021, the decision has been made to not collect any further samples across other timepoints and instead to do an in-depth cross-sectional study. The student collected 151 samples which resulted in over 1500 bacteria being isolated. A subset of 475 isolates (197 *E. coli* and 278 non-*E. coli*) have been whole genome sequenced and are undergoing downstream analysis of the sequence data using bioinformatic tools.
- **Milestone 2 – Molecular analysis of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial resistance (Due M60)**
- The student has carried out molecular analysis of *E. coli* ST744 isolates from pig and gull isolates collected as part of the APHA’s work on the ARDIG project. This was the most dominant ST type amongst the isolates and so phylogenetic and SNP based analysis was carried out to determine how closely related the strains are across both species and timepoints. Further ST744 isolates from other ARDIG partners and online databases were included in this analysis to further identify how clonal this population is and the likelihood for interspecies transmission between the gulls and the pigs on the APHA farm.
- The student has used Kraken to speciate the 475 isolates collected as part of their cross-sectional study. APHA Seqfinder and abricate are being used to identify the presence of AMR genes in the isolates. This work is still ongoing.
- **Milestone 3 - Characterisation of mobile elements transmitting/proliferating AMR (Due M60)**
- The student has been further characterising a large, multi-drug resistant transposon that has been identified in multiple ST744 isolates from both pig and gull isolates from the APHA ARDIG farm. The student is also including the ST744 isolates from other ARDIG partners and online databases to identify how prevalent this transposon is and how it may be expanding and contracting regarding the AMR genes it carries.
- This work has not been started yet regarding the cross-sectional farm visit isolates as it requires completion of Milestone 2. This work is still ongoing.

8.1.4.9.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo)
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	<i>different from the actual one)</i>		Plan 2021 (month)			<i>reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)</i>
	1	Completion of 9 month review	M57			
	2	Completion of 12 month review	M60			

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	1	Collection of microbiological samples for longitudinal study	M56	Yes		
	2	Molecular analysis of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial resistance	M60			
	3	Characterisation of mobile elements transmitting/proliferating AMR	M60			
	4	Completion of 9 month review	M57	Yes		
	5	Completion of 12 month review	M60			

8.1.4.9.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Use of genomics to explore AMR persistence in an outdoor pig farm with low antimicrobial usage ; doi 10.1099/mgen.0.000782	Yes	Manuscript release date: 28 th March 2022	

8.1.4.9.5 Remarkable outcomes

Student won prize for ‘Best Oral Presentation by an Early Career Researcher’ at OHEJP AGM 2022 in Orvieto, Italy.

8.1.4.9.6 Impact & relevance

The supervisory team brings together leading experts in veterinary, wildlife and environmental AMR, with expertise spanning veterinary and molecular microbiology, bioinformatics, microbial ecology and evolution, as well as wildlife disease.

William Gaze is working with the United Nations Environment Project on AMR in the environment, having recently authored the UNEP Frontiers report on AMR and the environment. He is currently located within two interdisciplinary units, Exeter’s Centre for Environment and Human health, and the Environmental and Sustainability Institute, which is also part of the University of Exeter

Beside his work as a researcher within SVA, Stefan Börjesson is involved in the Swedish AMR monitoring program and is also a senior lecturer in clinical microbiology with an emphasis on AMR in a One-health perspective at Linköping University at the Department of Clinical and Experimental Medicine.

Muna Anjum leads the Bacterial Characterisation Workgroup and is the AMR Research Lead at the APHA working at the interface of molecular and veterinary microbiology, within the One Health remit. As lead for the AMR research, she is also involved in supporting national AMR surveillance activities and APHA’s response to national outbreaks, and identifying new and emerging threats. She is a member of the DEFRA Antimicrobial Resistance Coordination Group, which advises and reviews the DEFRA activities on antimicrobial usage in animals and AMR in microorganisms from feedstuffs, animals and food, the APHA lead for the Defra AMR in the Environment group, and works closely with colleagues in Public Health England in various research projects and national activities.

8.1.4.9.7 Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

8.1.4.9.8 Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

8.1.4.9.9 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Engaging in Professional Development	Workshop	14/06/2022	University of Exeter
Research and innovation to reduce the burden of antibiotic resistance: strengthening the European action	Conference	07/06/2022	UE France 2022
GW4 AMR Alliance Early Career Pathways	Webinar	19/05/2022	GW4 AMR Alliance
GW4 AMR Alliance Lightning Talk and Networking Session	Online networking session	28/02/2022	GW4 AMR Alliance

8.1.4.9.10 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>GW4 AMR Lightning Talk and Networking Event – Networking session with other early career researchers from GW4 institutes</i>		
Date:	<i>28/02/2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Online</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes

<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories

	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	30	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Date:	23/03/2022
Place:	Online

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories

	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	Yes
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories

	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	6	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	40
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP AGM 2022 - 3 minute thesis, oral presentation and participation at roundtable discussion
Date:	11-13/04/2022

Place:	Orvieto, Italy (attended in person)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	?	Media	
Industry	?	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	GW4 AMR Lightning Talk and Networking Event – 3 minute presentation on PhD project and networking sessions		
Date:	27/04/2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number

Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Academic Board Student Networking Conference – Helped to organise and co-chaired the second day		
Date:	23-24/06/2022		
Place:	Online		

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			

Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	TBC	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Exeter University College of Medicine and Health Post Graduate Research Conference – Oral presentation		
Date:	28-29/06/2022		
Place:	University of Exeter, Penryn Campus (attended in person)		

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	

<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>TBC</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

8.1.4.10 Phd11-R1-FBZ4/5- EnvDis

8.1.4.10.1 Summary

A mathematical model was conceived to understand the effect that weather alone has on salmonellosis infections in humans. As a result, this method allows the quantification of the prevalence of salmonellosis for a particular subset of weather conditions, which can be interpreted as the *daily probability of acquiring the disease conditional on the weather variables* (P_{cond}).

A preliminary version of the statistical model object of this PhD project was finalised, and various weather variables were explored. The model was validated by visually comparing the simulations with historical infection data in England and Wales for the years 1989-2016. The weather variables were chosen according to the potential relevance over bacterial growth in the last step of the food chain for human consumption (*i.e.*, from purchase to consumption). These include maximum air temperature, air temperature variation (max-min air temperature), sunshine duration, relative humidity, mean dewpoint, mean cloud cover, and mean air pressure. Daylength was also included to encompass any potential human behavioural component.

Because weather variables have a complex, non-linear and potentially inter-connected association with infection, the effect of three variables were explored in combination. From the selected weather variables, the combinations tested include $T^{\text{max}}\text{-RH-DL}$, $T^{\text{max}}\text{-Dewpoint-air Pressure}$, and $T^{\text{var}}\text{-RH-sunshine}$, with the two first showing best correlation with historical infection data. Further weather combinations and an analysis of the variables alone will follow. As a preliminary conclusion, maximum air temperature, relative humidity and daylength seem to have a more relevant role in driving salmonellosis risk of infection.

It starts with the hypothesis that the effect of weather over salmonellosis is universal and unspecific to the geography. If the hypothesis is correct, and the identified weather variables are the main drivers of salmonellosis, similar results should be drawn when applying the methodology developed in the UK for another country. A short-term mission was carried out in the Netherlands to test such hypothesis. If an agreement is found between the real and simulated cases from epidemiological and meteorological data from the Netherlands using the conditional probability built with British data, this would confirm that the chosen weather variables are sufficient to explain the prevalence of salmonellosis. On the contrary, if an agreement is not found, it would mean that weather alone is not sufficient to estimate the risk of salmonellosis and other factors have an important role in infection (such as human behaviour). Analysis is undergoing and results are expected to be produced soon.

8.1.4.10.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

WP1: To develop a general tool to assess the risk of infectious diseases (in particular, zoonosis) when we have information of relevant environmental factors

WP1-T1

WP1-T1-ST1.2: Validate the model with data from another European country; include animal role in the model from (if) available data

- The collaboration to validate the model built in the UK and applied to Dutch epidemiological and environmental data took place and is currently on progress to be analysed and get some results. By the end of the year there will be specific and publishable results.
- Salmonellosis data in chicken farms have been requested to APHA, but it turned out to be confidential and unable to be shared, so it will not be explored further.
- Yearly census of farm animals (cattle, pigs, chicken, duck, geese, other poultry) from 1999 to 2016 per county were provided by APHA. However, the lack of geographical high resolution makes the spatial analysis limited. Instead, the risk of salmonellosis associated to climate change projections will be explored.

8.1.4.10.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)
	D-PhD11-3.1	Presentation of findings (e.g. conferences, internal school seminars) Y3	M60		M60	Pending to publish all conference posters presented at the end of this year

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	M-PhD11-2	Validate the model with data from another European country	M55	Yes		See STM report (in progress, will be uploaded in Zenodo when completed).

8.1.4.10.4 Remarkable outcomes

The PhD student, took part in a Short-Term mission which will be communicated by the end of the year.

8.1.4.10.5 Impact & relevance

The project involves the University of Surrey, UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) and Zoetis. EnvDis project builds on current work being done at UKHSA by Dr Gillingham, Prof Nichols and Dr Lo Iacono.

Laura's work combines phenomenology of *Salmonella* in England and Wales with, to a certain degree, mechanistic models. The project fits also very well with research interests of Dr Kanellos in Zoetis in understanding better the disease and how to prevent it; and the activities led by Prof Cook in vHive (<https://vhive.buzz/>). By collaborating with the Dutch National Institute for Health and Environment (RIVM), the versatility of the model in understanding and measuring the impact of the environment on infectious diseases in different geographic scenarios is being validated.

8.1.4.10.6 Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

A short-term mission to work together with the OHEJP ADONIS project (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-adonis/>) took place at the RIVM (<https://www.rivm.nl/en>) during the months of April and May.

The purpose of the mission was to establish a close collaboration with the ADONIS OHEJP project to share knowledge and methods, which can be of mutual benefit for research outcomes.

ADONIS and EnvDis are two OHEJP projects with a similar research scope, yet with different approaches, where human salmonellosis is studied with the aim of better understanding the epidemiology of the disease:

ADONIS focuses on explaining the trends in the time-series of salmonellosis' incidence. Their approach is based on the variations of explanatory factors, such as national surveillance systems in humans and poultry, following a longitudinal approach. EnvDis aims to estimate the incidence of salmonellosis conditional to certain environmental exposures. It assumes that this conditional incidence is, in general, not depending on time. In addition, it aims to incorporate mechanistic processes, such as bacterial growth in the food source of human transmission. A key benefit of working closely together is to bring the temporal dimension, typical of timeseries analysis, into the conditional incidence approach. Vice-versa, by applying the conditional incidence approach to different settings we would be able to assess whether the relationship between salmonellosis and exposure is universal. This collaboration enhanced the robustness of the findings, and it will help in overcoming the intrinsic limitations of the different approaches.

8.1.4.10.7 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
German A1 - GGA	Language, personal development and diversification of skills	Weekly Oct- May	University of Surrey
Research assistant collaboration to expand on the experimental side of the thesis	Complementary labwork skills	Oct 21 – Jan 22	University of Surrey/ Physics of Life (PoLNET3)
Centre for One Health Annual Conference 202	Continuous exposure and learning of One health topics and its real world applications	03/11/2021	Ryan Institute for One Health
COHESIVE end symposium	Continuous exposure and learning of mathematical modelling and its real-world applications	8/11/2021-10/11/2021	OHEJP
AcriMo Poem competition	Artistic and creativity booster	25/11/2021	UoS Doctoral College
How can mathematical and statistical models combine with big data to improve our	Continuous exposure and learning of mathematical modelling and its real-world applications	02/02/2022	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)

response to pandemics? Virtual conference			
Beyond Academia opportunities for PGRs	Inspiring experiences from researchers some steps above me.	16/03/2022	UoS Doctoral College
BioRender 101 webinar	Tips and tricks on how to make the most out of a graphic design tool for creating posters and diagrams	30/03/2022	BioRender
London Centre for NTD Research anniversary event	Networking and learning about different projects and presentation tactics.	31/03/2022	London Centre for NTD
Public Engagement Workshop	Communication skills	01/04/2022	University of Surrey - Faculty of engineering and physical sciences
The inaugural UoS Open Research Lecture	Open research training, networking and poster presentation	08/04/2022	University of Surrey – Open Research and Reproducibility Society
Introduction to Git	IT skills	27/05/2022	University of Surrey – Open Research and Reproducibility Society
OHEJP ASM 22	Networking, presentation skills	11-13/04/2022	OHEJP
OHEJP STM	Cultural, personal, academic and methodology exchange	20/04/2022-20/05/2022	OHEJP/RIVM
Research Celebration Event	Interdisciplinary education, light talk	16/06/2022	University of Surrey - Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences
ONE Conference	Networking, poster presentation	21-24/06/2022	European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)
Neglected Tropical Disease (NTD) group meeting – organising committee	Friendly space for collaboration, research updates and ideas exchange. Managerial skills	Biweekly June 21 -July 22	University of Surrey

8.1.4.10.8 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 – poster presentation and three-minute thesis competition</i>		
Date:	<i>11-13/04/2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Orvieto, Italy.</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	<i>No</i>	Participation to a Conference	<i>Yes</i>
Organisation of a Workshop	<i>No</i>	Participation to a Workshop	<i>No</i>
Press release	<i>No</i>	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	<i>No</i>
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	<i>No</i>	Video/Film	<i>No</i>
Exhibition	<i>No</i>	Brokerage Event	<i>No</i>
Flyer	<i>No</i>	Pitch Event	<i>No</i>
Training	<i>No</i>	Trade Fair	<i>No</i>
Social Media	<i>No</i>	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	<i>No</i>

Website	No	Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	150?	Media	
Industry	5	Investors	
Civil Society	0	Customers	
General Public	0	Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Bi-weekly knowledge dissemination evet		
Date:	09/05/2022		
Place:	RIVM		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	No
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website	No	Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

8.1.4.11 Phd12-R2-FBZSH9-AptaTrich

8.1.4.11.1 Summary

Trichinellosis is a zoonotic illness transmitted through the consumption of raw or undercooked meat products infected with the parasitic nematode *Trichinella* spp. Excluding its brief existence as a free-living migratory larva, *Trichinella* spp. resides primarily within the confines of its host's muscle cells. In this study, we employ an innovative and novel larval-based selection method to produce a set of *Trichinella spiralis* specific aptamers for potential therapeutic applications. In addition, biomarkers of

infection are to be identified and targeted to develop a novel aptamer-based tool for accurate and sensitive detection in humans and animals.

A magnetic stirrer method of artificial digestion and microscopy were used for the recovery and quantification of *Trichinella spiralis* muscle larvae (ML) from experimentally infected mice. Aptamers were selected from a synthetic single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) library composed of 1013-1016 random sequences by an iterative in vitro selection process termed Systematic Evolution of Ligands by EXponential enrichment (SELEX). An optimized SELEX method was used to yield aptamers capable of binding to the target of interest. Aptamer selection was monitored using qPCR melting curve analysis to estimate aptamer sequence enrichment. In addition High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS) and bioinformatics analysis by PATTERNITY.seq was used to more accurately monitor sequence evolution.

In addition to the 8-round SELEX experiment conducted and presented in the previous report, a 16-round SELEX experiment was performed using a more optimized protocol. This time, qPCR results displayed a likely increase in sequence enrichment starting at round 12 of SELEX. By round 16, a large enrichment is suggested. With these results, samples were sequenced and analyzed using the bioinformatics software tool PATTERNITY.seq. In both SELEX experiments, which were performed months apart, an identical consensus sequence was identified to have evolved in several sequence families.

In light of these results, we are confident to have selected for aptamers specific for the *Trichinella spiralis* muscle larvae. Fluorescein (FITC) conjugated sequences have been synthesized and are currently being tested for their abilities to bind *Trichinella spiralis* muscle larvae. Furthermore, fixed biotin-labelled aptamer sequences lacking the constant primer binding regions have also been synthesized for future studies relating more to antigen capture as well as confocal imaging using streptavidin-conjugated Phycoerythrin.

8.1.4.11.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

In the past few months, an important agreement in HTS and bioinformatics results was determined, suggesting successful selection of ML-specific sequences. As mentioned previously, a 13 nucleotide long consensus sequence has been identified in aptamer pools from two independent SELEX experiments performed months apart. In light of this, 12 FITC-labelled sequences have been synthesized and are currently being tested for their ability to bind *T. spiralis* muscle larvae.

In the next couple months we expect to successfully identify the optimal aptamer sequences and simultaneously localize the binding by confocal microscopy (Deliverable #4). We also intend on using fragmented biotin-labelled “micro aptamers”, which lack the constant primer binding regions, to confirm our results with streptavidin-conjugated Phycoerythrin.

8.1.4.11.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)
	D-1	<i>T. spiralis</i> are fixed in ethanol		M27		
	D-2	Aptamers set on whole larvae are selected		M48		

	D-3?	Aptamers et on stage specific proteins are selected			M63	Will probably not be achieved
	D-4	<i>T. spiralis</i> super aptamers are identified			M57	
	D-5	Article submitted to peer-review journal			M59	
	D-6	Article on the use of the aptamers-based test submitted			M61	Will probably not be achieved
	D-7	Thesis manuscript is written and thesis defended			M63	No-cost extension was accepted by OHEJP

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	M-6	The test is operational (reproducible, repeatable, sensitive and specific)	?	No	M61	Will probably not be reached
	M-7	The test is able to detect the Three <i>Trichinella</i> species in pig serum	?	No	M63	Will probably not be reached

8.1.4.11.4 Publications and additional outputs

N/A

8.1.4.11.5 Remarkable outcomes

8.1.4.11.6 Impact & relevance

The partners involved in the project offer various elements of expertise to optimally support a PhD student in the development of a new method. The partners come from institutes with a wide interdisciplinary background.

ANSES laboratories conduct their activities in three major areas: animal health and well-being, food safety (chemical and biological) and plant health. The French NRL is also an OIE Collaborating Centre, it is part of the Animal Health Laboratory of Anses, which is internationally renowned and carries out critical missions for France, Europe and World in the field of animal health and public health, food safety, epidemiology. Researchers of the NRL work in close collaboration with medical doctors, veterinarians and give their expertise when outbreaks occur.

The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) is the German national scientific institution in the area of consumer health protection, food safety, authenticity and risk assessment/ risk communication. The NRL for *Trichinella* mainly operates in the field of diagnostics, food safety and risk assessment, but also provide consultant support in human diagnostics.

The Canadian National Reference Centre for Parasitology (NRCP) is located within the Research Institute of the McGill University Health Centre (RI-MUHC) and provides reference serological and molecular diagnostics for parasitic diseases. Investigators at the Centre are active in several areas, including clinical parasitology, parasite diagnostics, parasite epidemiology, vaccine immunology, as well as cold-climate parasitoses and circumpolar health.

The existing close collaboration between the partners, which operate between the medical, veterinary and food science fields, will facilitate the success of the proposed PhD project under a One Health approach.

8.1.4.11.7 Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

8.1.4.11.8 Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

8.1.4.11.9 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Non-Coding Genome 11 th Edition	Genetics	11/05/2022 – 18/05/2022	Institut Curie, Paris, France

8.1.4.11.10 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	Oral Presentation at Journee des Sciences de la Vie et de la Sante a Creteil		
Date:	16 th February, 2022		
Place:	Creteil, Ile-de-France, FRANCE		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	60	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	3 minute thesis presentation OHEJP ASM 2022
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Date:	11 th – 13 th April, 2022		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	100	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Poster Presentation at Non-coding Genome 11 th Edition 2022		
Date:	11 th – 18 th May, 2022		
Place:	Institut Curie, Paris, France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number

<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	50	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

8.1.4.12 PhD13-R2-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR

8.1.4.12.1 Summary

The VIMOGUT project consists of *in vivo* analysis of the microbiome in the caecum of healthy broilers and the set-up of an *in vitro* model to study the transmission dynamics of antimicrobial resistance in caecal microbial communities.

In the first period of 2022, the PhD student has focused on molecular work needed for the completion of the *in vitro* experiments. The *in vitro* chicken caecum model was first tested in 2020 after which further optimisation was necessary. Due to technical difficulties with the current equipment, an updated system has been ordered and is expected to be delivered in Q3 2022. It is expected that, after installation, a minimal set of optimisation is needed to transfer the currently established *in vitro* gut model, to be used with the novel equipment. The new system will consist of 4 parallel bioreactors, allowing for increased efficiency in the running of parallel experiments.

For the *in vivo* component, no further data collection or analysis has been possible due to an extensive Avian Influenza outbreak in the Netherlands. Activities related to *in vivo* studies are currently planned for Q4 2022. If sampling in commercial broiler farms cannot be managed in this timeframe, alternative sampling streams will be sought by sampling at veterinary practices.

8.1.4.12.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

WP1 *In vivo* analysis of the chicken gut microbiome

Deliverable 1

The manuscript submitted for publication in *Animal Microbiome* was revised based on the peer-review report. The revised version of the manuscript was accepted for publication. The published version of the paper was uploaded onto Zenodo.

Milestones 8 – 9

Due to the outbreak of COVID-19, farm sampling was postponed from 2021. The continuous outbreak of Avian Influenza in the Netherlands has hampered collection of novel samples since. A final attempt at collection of caecal samples at broiler farms is currently underway, after which alternative sampling methods will be considered. These alternative sampling streams will potentially include samples from animals at university teaching farms or samples collected from running broiler experiments at one of the collaborating facilities.

WP2: *In vitro* analysis and modulation of the chicken gut microbiome

Milestones 6, 10, 11, 12

Due to technical difficulties with the equipment of the *in vitro* model, a novel supplier has been sought. Additional equipment in which anaerobic conditions can be reached more reliably are expected to be installed in September 2022. Experiments for the colonisation of the *in vitro* model are planned to occur shortly after. The PhD student has supervised a BSc student that performed some experiments in the analysis of previously collected data, giving her opportunity to gain experience in managing and supervising a sub-project.

In anticipation of the plasmid conjugation experiments, the PhD student performed a short-term mission to the laboratory of Luca Guardabassi at the University of Copenhagen in order to learn

molecular cloning techniques. This knowledge will be used in the construction of *E. coli* strains, labelled with fluorescent genes on the chromosome and ESBL plasmid, so-called 'dual labelled strains'.

8.1.4.12.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Over this period, the student has focussed on preparation for the current short-term mission at the University of Copenhagen. The student has performed background work on transformation and molecular cloning techniques with relevant antimicrobial resistance genes. At the University of Copenhagen molecular cloning is being performed using the lambda red recombineering technique. This technique is utilised to introduce various fluorescent markers into the chromosome and ESBL-encoding plasmids of wildtype *E. coli* isolated from Dutch broilers. These fluorescently labelled isolates and plasmids will be used to study the transfer of plasmids in the *in vitro* gut model under baseline conditions, compared to conditions in which antibiotics are present in the model.

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
	D1	Manuscript on preliminary findings for the relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL colonisation.	36	45		Public: zenodo 7057449
	D2	Manuscript on relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL colonisation over several farms.	48		65	Public Due to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 and an extensive non-seasonal Avian Influenza outbreak in the Netherlands no farm sampling has been possible. Alternative sampling is planned in Q4 2022.
	D3	Manuscript describing the results of the results of testing <i>in vitro</i> ESBL <i>E. coli</i> intervention strategies.	60			Public
	D4	Manuscript to describe the host range of ESBL plasmids from <i>E. coli</i> into the <i>in vitro</i> microbiome and strategies to lower plasmid spread.	68			Public

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
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	M1	Molecular technique training and 16S barcode sequencing.	22	Yes		
	M2	Attend course on analysis for 16S barcode sequencing.	24	Yes		
	M3	Visit APHA for training on <i>in vitro</i> chicken gut model.	24	Yes		Training was performed online.
	M4	Perform 16S barcode sequencing on currently collected samples.	27	Yes		
	M5	Perform analysis of initial 16S experiment	30	Yes		
	M6	Perform initial test runs on <i>in vitro</i> gut model to determine CFU for reliable ESBL colonisation.	36	No	58	Due to technical difficulties in the set-up of the model, this will be carried out after installation of new equipment, expected in August 2022.
	M7	Write manuscript on initial results relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL gut colonisation.	36	Yes		
	M8	Perform 16S sequencing and analysis of caecal samples from OH-EJP VIMOGUT.	50	No	62	Farm visits were rescheduled due to COVID-19 and avian influenza.
	M9	Write manuscript on relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL colonisation over several farms.	56	No	65	Farm visits were rescheduled due to COVID-19 and avian influenza.
	M10	Experiments in the <i>in vitro</i> model for ESBL <i>E. coli</i> colonisation intervention strategies.	60			Due to technical difficulties in the set-up of the model, this will be carried out after the installation of new equipment, expected in September 2022.
	M11	Experiments in the <i>in vitro</i> model to test the transfer range of ESBL plasmids within the microbiome.	60			Due to technical difficulties in the set-up of the model, this will be carried out after the installation of new equipment, expected in September 2022.

	M12	Experiments in the <i>in vitro</i> model to test ESBL plasmid conjugation intervention strategies.	64			Due to technical difficulties in the set-up of the model, this will be carried out after the installation of new equipment, expected in September 2022.
	M13	Write the manuscript describing the results of the results of testing <i>in vitro</i> ESBL <i>E. coli</i> intervention strategies.	68			Expected after installation of the new system and collection of data from the <i>in vitro</i> experiments.

8.1.4.12.4 Publications and additional outputs

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Succession in the caecal microbiota of developing broilers colonised by extended-spectrum β -lactamase-producing <i>Escherichia coli</i> https://doi.org/10.1186/s42523-022-00199-4 https://zenodo.org/record/7057449#.YxiUTHZByUk	Yes		Yes € 714.81

8.1.4.12.5 Remarkable outcomes

The research article titled: **Succession in the caecal microbiota of developing broilers colonised by extended-spectrum β -lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli*** was published in the scientific journal *Animal Microbiome* on August 19 2022. In this research article, we assessed the role of ESBL-*E.coli* in the successional dynamics of the caecal microbiota in developing broilers. Our findings suggest that ESBL-*E.coli* is associated with mild but consistent alpha diversity reductions and transient bacterial compositional differences. We also documented the prevalence trend and clonal spread of ESBL-*E. coli* in a broiler farm, and pointed to the farm environment as a potential source for ESBLs.

8.1.4.12.6 Impact and Relevance

While executing the PhD project VIMOGUT, we have opened up significant cooperation channels with other research groups and institutions with similar interests. Namely, microbiota studies and the development and assessment of interventions to prevent and/or reduce the horizontal spread of AMR genes.

Early in 2020, VIMOGUT collaborated with researchers from the Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ in Leipzig, Germany. This collaboration strengthened the microbiota data analysis and generated fruitful ideas and knowledge about the chicken caecal microbiota and the role of resistant

bacteria in the development of the chicken gut microbiota from commercial farms. This work is currently published in the scientific journal *Animal microbiome*.

Moreover, valuable knowledge was exchanged with the Animal Plant Health Agency (APHA) to establish an *in vitro* chicken caecum model capable of reproducing the main physiological conditions to maintain the members of the caecal microbial community.

Other vital collaborations were done with the One Health Antimicrobial Resistant (OHAR) group of the University of Copenhagen via a short term mission (STM). During the STM, the PhD student learned bacterial cloning techniques and developed and strengthened her lab skills to produce dual fluorescently labelled commensal *E.coli*. The dual labelled bacteria is essential to carry out the *in vitro* experiments to study the effect of antibiotics and microbiota interventions in the horizontal spread of Extended Spectrum β -Lactam (ESBL) genes in the *in vitro* cultured chicken microbiota. The output of this collaborative work is expected to be published as a research article in a scientific journal.

8.1.4.12.7 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Reviewing a scientific manuscript	Communication	17/02/22	GSS-WUR
Poster and pitching	Communication	10/03/22	Loop Genomics
WEES seminar	Science	16/03/22	WUR
Plasmid evolution and antimicrobial resistance	Science	21-25/03/22	ICTP – International Center for Theoretical Physics
Internship at the One Health Antimicrobial Resistance (OHAR) group -University of Copenhagen	Bacterial cloning	01/05/22	Short Term Mission; OH-EJP
Microbial Ecology course	Microbial Ecology	June 19-24, 2022	PE&RC graduate school
Short Term Mission at the University of Copenhagen	Bacterial cloning - AMR	April 30 - July 09, 2022	OH-EJP

8.1.4.12.8 Impact & relevance

The PhD has carried out her STM at Copenhagen University within the One Health Antimicrobial Resistance (OHAR) group. During these weeks the PhD student worked in a multidisciplinary environment and has performed several experiments for the construction of the fluorescent labelled ESBL-*E.coli* strains. Such strains will be utilised for *in vitro* experiments in the *in vitro* gut model to study the effect of antibiotics and microbiome interventions on ESBL plasmid-transfer to the broiler caecal microbiome.

8.1.4.12.9 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	OH-EJP 3-minute thesis competition at OH-EJP ASM 2022		
Date:	11-04-22		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No

<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	>500	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	Poster presentation at OHEJP ASM 2022		
Date:	11-13/04/22		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	

<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	>500	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	PhD round table OHEJP ASM 2022		
Date:	13/04/22		
Place:	Orvieto, Italy		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			

	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	>500	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OH-EJP side event "Lessons Learnt from a European Multidisciplinary Initiative" ONE2022 Conference		
Date:	June 22 2022		
Place:	Brussels, Belgium		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	Yes
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	>150	Media	>100
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Poster carousel, Microbial ecology course.		
Date:	19-24 June 2022		
Place:	Nunspet, The Netherlands		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes

Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	Yes
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	50	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

8.1.4.13 Phd14-R2-FBZ4-ToxSauQMRA

8.1.4.13.1 Summary

The present research project aims to answer to the scientific question: “What is the attribution of the traditional raw pork products in the human *Toxoplasma* infection? “based on three main areas of study consisting of (i) a thorough investigation of *T.gondii* predilection sites in experimentally infested pig carcasses with two different stages (tissue-cyst versus oocyst) (WP1); (ii) evaluate the impact of the manufacturing process (including different incorporation rates of nitrites and NaCl) and the conservation of dry sausage on the viability of *T. gondii* (WP2); (iii) a quantitative microbiological risk assessment analysis to be conducted for the various raw pork products (dry sausage, dry ham, etc) (WP3). The 3-year project spans over four Annual Periods (Y2-Y5).

8.1.4.13.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

WP1 - Investigation of *T.gondii* predilection sites in pigs experimentally infected with two different stages (tissue-cyst versus oocyst)

WP1-T1: Experimental infection of pigs – **successfully completed during year 3**

WP1-T2: Predilection sites of *T.gondii* in pigs – **successfully completed last year**

WP2 - Assessment of the persistence of *T. gondii* during the production and storage of dry sausages and dry ham

WP2-T1: Manufacture of dry sausages and dry ham – **successfully completed during year 3**

WP2-T2: Assessment of the persistence of viable *T. gondii* in pork delicatessen – **underway/ to be completed by the end of this year**

WP3 - Quantitative microbiological risk assessment

WP3-T1 Review of prevalence of *T. gondii* in various dry pork delicatessen – **successfully completed this year**

WP3-T2 QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections– **started/ to be completed by the end of this year**

The key activities, results, and achievements for the reporting period of January to September of this year are the following:

Key scientific results:

1. Complete assessment of the French and European country specific meat products including their composition and processing steps during production that might influence viability of potential *T. gondii* tissue cysts within.
2. Adjusted and updated database necessary to the development of the up-to-date heating model as a part of the final QMRA model.
3. Meta-analysis of available scientific data on the anatomical distribution within animal tissues of animals experimentally infected with *T. gondii* into the updated database. To be used as a step in the final QMRA model.
4. Meta-analysis and data collection on the dose-response relation for *T. gondii* infections in various animal species. This will serve as a base for the estimation of the dose-response relation in humans within the final QMRA model.
5. Human prevalence and risk factors analysis for further use in the final QMRA model.

Challenges:

1. Non-uniform reporting of results in various publications. Not suitable for use in the QMRA modelling.
2. Time constraints caused by involvement of cooperating partners.

Adaptations:

1. Involvement of under-graduate students for helping us with the digestions and PCRs
2. Additional short term stay at RIVM to speed up the progress on the QMRA modelling task.

8.1.4.13.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

The present research project aims to answer to the scientific question: “What is the attribution of the traditional raw pork products in the human *Toxoplasma* infection? “ based on three main areas of study consisting of (i) a thorough investigation of *T. gondii* predilection sites in experimentally infested pig carcasses with two different stages (tissue-cyst versus oocyst) (WP1); (ii) evaluate the impact of the manufacturing process (including different incorporation rates of nitrites and NaCl) and the conservation of dry sausage on the viability of *T. gondii* (WP2); (iii) a quantitative microbiological risk assessment analysis to be conducted for the various raw pork products (dry sausage, dry ham, etc) (WP3). The 3-year project spans over four Annual Periods (Y2-Y5). The present 9-month report focuses on the progress and activities from WP1 (delayed due to covid 1st and 2nd confinement), WP2 and WP3.

Within the WP1 (Investigation of *T. gondii* predilection sites in experimentally infested pig carcasses with two different stages (tissue-cyst versus oocyst)), the work of WP1-T2 is finished: Predilection sites of *T. gondii* in pigs which has been delayed due to covid 1st and 2nd confinement. Within the WP2 - Assessment of the persistence of *T. gondii* during the production and storage of dry sausages and dry ham, mainly on Task 2 has been worked on: WP2-T2: Assessment of the persistence of *T. gondii* since Task 1: WP2-T1: Manufacture of dry sausages and dry ham has been completed last year.

However, a short summary of WP1-T1 and WP2-T1 is mentioned for a better understanding of the workflow over the last 2 years. All the work has been completed with the help of external partners: Institut du Porc (IFIP) and Université de Champagne-Ardennes (URCA).

For WP1-T1, the main focus was to be able to collect meat massively contaminated with *Toxoplasma gondii*. Therefore an infection with a high dose (1000) of parasites was carried out (strain ME49) in pigs (WP1-T1). These tests were carried out with 2 parasitic forms that may be at the origin of contamination in pigs: the oocyst (ingestion from the environment) and the tissue cyst (ingestion from infested meat). Three pigs were inoculated with oocysts and 3 others with tissue cysts. Serological monitoring of the serum of these pigs was carried out by Modified Agglutination Test (MAT) on a weekly basis until D30, then every 15 days until the end of the protocol (3-4 months/80-90 kg). After euthanasia of the MAT positive pigs, 4 tissues /pig were collected for analysis: heart, breast, shoulder

and ham as tissues used in the manufacture of dry sausage. For each of the anatomical regions studied, the different muscles (4 for breast, 7 for shoulder and 13 for ham) were pooled. Some 40 supplementary muscles per carcass were individually collected, representing the most important anatomical regions. One hind leg was collected for each pig for dry ham production.

Concerning the WP1-T2, the main focus was to identify the predilection sites of *T.gondii* presence in pig tissues. Therefore, mouse bioassays and quantitative PCR was performed on a part (200g) of the pooled sample per region. The remaining parts of the pools were used for industrial (salting, smoking, etc) processing (WP2).

The analysis of tissue samples ([breast, shoulder, ham, heart + 40 supplementary muscles] x 6 pigs) by MC-PCR, delayed by the 1st and the 2nd confinement due to COVID19 sanitary crisis in France, has been completed this year, for both parasitic stages (oocysts and tissue cysts). This involved the digestion, DNA extraction and PCR for each individual tissue sample.

Within the WP2-T1 the manufacture of dry sausages was carried out on a pilot scale by IFIP, according to a protocol representative of those used by a commercial factory. Briefly, after mincing, the muscle pool was divided into seven portions (corresponding to the 7 combinations of nitrites (as sodium NaNO₂ nitrites) and NaCl concentrations that was to be compared: 120 (maximum dose of nitrites mentioned in the Code of Practice), 60 and 0 ppm of nitrites combined with the usual dose of 26 g/kg NaCl or a reduced dose of 20 g/kg NaCl or 0 g/kg NaCl. For each of the tested formulations, 3 dry sausages was collected at different dates (D0, D2, D10, D20, D30 and D50). On each analysis date, IFIP has carried out a physico-chemical monitoring (pH, Aw, weight loss) and a count of the lactic flora from a dry sausage per formulation, in particular to check that the process is running properly. A total of 168 dry sausages was required for this study (3 dry sausages x 7 recipes x 6 analysis dates for *T. gondii* monitoring as well as 1 dry sausage x 7 recipes x 6 analysis dates for physico-chemical and bacteriological analyses).

The dry hams were meant to be sent and manufactured by INRAe Corte (Corsica), using two traditional salting techniques (a long one : 2.5 days/kg and a short one: 1 day/kg). However due to a local strike in the harbour of Marseille, the hams arrived with 10 days of delay, causing the sanitary quality of meat to be questionable in terms of manufacturing. Therefore, a long salting technique has been applied only, with 300g of product that was taken at D30 and D90 due to Covid19 shut-down.

Concerning the WP2-T2 the main focus was the analysis of the dry sausages and ham for the presence of viable *T. gondii* by bioassay in mice that has been performed in the animal facility of URCA. In total 90 mouse bioassays were performed (1 dry sausage x 7 recipes x 6 analysis dates x 2 mice + 2 dry hams x 3 analysis dates) with the last data being collected 6 weeks after the last bioassay was performed. In the same time, the presence of *T. gondii* DNA in the inocula, resulting from the dry sausage digestion, was quantified by URCA using a (conventional) qPCR and by ANSES by MC-qPCR developed by Opsteegh et al., (2010).

Within the WP3 - Quantitative microbiological risk assessment we focused on the WP3-T1 Review of prevalence of *T. gondii* in pigs and pork products and WP3-T2 QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections. During Y4, the main focus was the review of the prevalence data of *T.gondii* in pigs and pork products. Therefore, data from various studies involving long-last processing pork delicatessen (Jambon de Parme; Jambon Serrano, etc) are about to be collated, building on the systematic reviews performed for EFSA and EJP Toxosources. In the same time we initiate the first steps in WP3-T2 QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections by providing the animal *T.gondii* prevalence for the QMRA model that needs to be build.

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include	Deliverable name (Include original name, if	Delivery date stated in	Actual Delivery	If not achieved: Forecast	Comments
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	<i>original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	<i>different from the actual one)</i>	Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Date (month)	achievement date (month)	<i>(Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)</i>
	D-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-WP3.2	Report on relative contribution of different meat products and tissues to human T.gondii infection.	M60	M60		

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	M-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-01	Processing parameters for relevant meat products are provided as input for QMRA.	M55	Yes		Achieved ahead of the schedule in M54.
	M-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-02	Country-specific estimates for prevalence of human T. gondii infection provided as input data for QMRA	M57	No	M57	On time

8.1.4.13.4 Impact & relevance

From the beginning, the PhD project was built as an interdisciplinary project involving partners from the Vet (Anses, RIVM), Med (URCA, RIVM) and industrial (IFIP) area. The topic itself touches all three domains, fitting perfectly into the OneHealth approach. Therefore, the PhD student is working in an inter-disciplinary environment, gathering together vets, researchers, doctors, pharmacists, engineers, technicians with a broad spectrum of activities such as parasitology, food-product manufacture, risk assessment analysis, statistics, epidemiology. Precisely, the experimental infection of pigs has been performed by JRU BIPAR, the sausages were manufactured by Institut du Porc (IFIP), and tested both by JRU BIPAR and URCA. Later on, the results will be interpreted with the help of statisticians (ANSES) and the QMRA model will be run and performed in RIVM. The PhD project and the PhD student are playing perfectly the role of a pivot within this interdisciplinary environment. Without them this part of the research would not have been possible.

8.1.4.13.5 Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

The student has been involved in the EJP JRP Toxosources, as part of the Anses team, participating at the kick-off meeting (3-4.02, Copenhagen, Denmark) and since then participating at all the videoconferences of the various WPs, where Anses is involved in. He took a very active role in the

activities of WP2 (human/animal prevalence review, questionnaires, meat product processing, QMRA model updating, etc), helping the coordinators of this WP during his STSMs in RIVM. In the same time he participated in all the activities of WP3 (T.gondii detection in RTE salads).

Similarly, part of the Anses team, the student is involved in the national research project n° 0917003490 financed by the French Ministry of Agriculture through the France Agri Mer agency with the title: Study of the tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to sausage, gathering the above mentioned partners (Ifip, URCA, Inrae Corte), representing in the same time the fundament/basis of his PhD programme.

8.1.4.13.6 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Animal experimentation training - Designer level	Animal experimentation	21/03/2022 - 01/04/2022	Institut Pasteur, Paris
Cours Français Langue Etrangère niveau Avancé B2/C1	Language	24/01/2022 - 14/03/2022	Maison des Langues, UPEC
DataCamp - courses on R programming	Programming	10/07/2021 - 10/06/2022	Online courses

8.1.4.13.7 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting</i>		
Date:	<i>11/04/2022 – 13/04/2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Orvieto, Italy</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	Yes	Pitch Event	No
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	Yes
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1000	Media	0
Industry	50	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0

Policy Makers	50		
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Name of the activity:	<i>Journée des Sciences de la Vie et de la Santé</i>		
Date:	16/02/2022		
Place:	Créteil, France		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	Yes	<i>Pitch Event</i>	No
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	200	<i>Media</i>	0
<i>Industry</i>	10	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	100	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

8.1.4.14 Phd15-R2-FBZ5-TRACE

8.1.4.14.1 Summary

During the first part of this year the optimisation of sample (pre)processing (enrichment) to make whole genome sequencing was established (WP1).

The producer/supplier of the enrichment product made a change in the product. For this reason, a new HEV-probe enrichment set was used, based on probe capture enrichment. With this new probe set whole-genome sequences could be generated up to a Ct value of 30. It is planned for the second part of this year, to start generating new whole genome sequences.

Because of the delay of WP 1, WP2 (phylogenetics) could not be started, with the analyses of newly produced sequences. However, a method for HEV analyses for time-phylogeny of known sequences from the NCBI was set up. This enables application of this method for sequences generated by the student.

8.1.4.14.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

WP1-T1

WP1-T1-ST1.1 Whole genome sequencing

During the first year of the project work was done to establish a sample (pre)processing (enrichment) to make whole-genome sequencing possible. Different methods were used, and DNA depletion

treatments were explored. mRNA of 18S (host) and 16S (bacterial) origin was successfully removed. HEV whole-genome sequences were successfully generated using the above enrichment methods and specific probes.

The producer/supplier of the enrichment product made a change in the product. For this reason, a test based on the multi-primer sequencing method for HEV was developed. Probably the genome structure of HEV is a little bit complicated therefore this method wasn't successful. In the second part of 2021, a new enrichment method was set up based on the principle of the first original procedure - probe capture enrichment. For this a complete new probe set was developed before the enrichment procedure could be optimised. In the first part of 2022 this was successful and whole genome sequences were generated, of samples of different origin with a Ct value up to Ct30.

WP2-T1

WP2-T1-ST1.1 HEV phylodynamics

Using HEV whole-genome sequence data generated in WP1, a timed-phylogeny of HEV based on core-genome SNP analysis will be constructed. From this analysis, time-points of evolutionary divergence of different HEV types can be inferred. Coupled with the geographic location data of the isolates a spatial dimension will be included to the phylogeny which will inform the geographical origin and spread of HEV types over time. Comparison of sequences over time will also be used to identify sequences that differ between time periods where there was different epidemiology of HEV, giving indications of probably increased colonization success in pigs, increased environmental survival, and/or increased virulence. This work was planned to start at the beginning of 2021, due to the delay of WP1, WP2 could not be started with the analysis of newly produced sequences. However, a method for HEV analysis for timed-phylogeny of known sequences was set up from the NCBI, which can be applied to the method for our generated sequences.

WP3-T1

WP3-T1-ST1.1 Identification of HEV virulence genes and HEV quasispecies

Work on this work package is planned to start in month 54

WP4-T1

WP4-T1-ST1.1 Data analyses and data evaluation

Work on this work package is planned to start in month 54

8.1.4.14.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
	D1	Sample processing protocol for HEV RNA positive target samples of different origin and associated deep sequencing procedure for HEV from such samples	48			At the start of this project 2020, there was a delay due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to the producer/supplier of the enrichment product made a change to the product. And a first attempt to

						develop a new method was unsuccessful. This will be worked on to finish it in month 57
	D2	Report/publication on HEV dynamics including information about the geographical origin of predominant virulent strains and identification of genetic traits changed over time.	48		60	D2 is dependent on D1.
	D3	Identification of virulence genes and elucidation of the relationship between quasispecies and changing virulence of circulating HEV strains	64			D3 is dependent on D1.
	D4	Report explaining HEV strain shifts and HEV disease outcomes related to HEV circulation and HEV variability. Evaluation of results for future anticipation and intervention as possible.	64			D4 is dependent on D1
	D5	Evaluation of results for future anticipation and intervention as possible.	64			D5 is dependent on D1

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	1	Detailed outline PhD plan	24	y		

8.1.4.14.4 Impact & relevance

OHEJP SRA 1 Updated List and Descriptions of Priority Research and Integrative topics: “risk factors and infection dynamics”.

Development and harmonisation of deep sequencing-based methods for detection and tracing of foodborne zoonotic agents and emerging threats have been identified as a main research item within the updated EJP One Health SRA. Data from this project will lead to improved surveillance and more harmonized data analyses on the foodborne zoonosis HEV. This will contribute to broader and flexible actions to detect actual hazards, main reservoirs, trends and routes of transmission as well as common approach and timely analysis and data sharing which will be needed more and more with ongoing globalization

8.1.4.14.5 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	
Date:	
Place:	

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	N	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Y
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	N	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	N
<i>Press release</i>	N	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	N
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	N	<i>Video/Film</i>	N
<i>Exhibition</i>	N	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	N
<i>Flyer</i>	N	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Y
<i>Training</i>	N	<i>Trade Fair</i>	N
<i>Social Media</i>	N	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	N
<i>Website</i>	N	<i>Other</i>	N
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	N		N
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

8.1.4.15 Phd16-R2-FBZ2/AMR6.1-Codes4strains

8.1.4.15.1 Summary

Whole genome sequencing allows the tracking of pathogenic strains and informs infection control, diagnostics, and sometimes treatment strategies. Universal strain nomenclatures are necessary to track strains at a global level, and as they spread between the environment, food, animals, and humans. The core genome Multilocus Sequence Typing (cgMLST) approach is an accurate, reproducible, and portable strain genotyping method that underlies widely used strain nomenclatures, in which groups are generally determined by single-linkage clustering. However, cgMLST groups are unstable due to the possibility of group fusion upon subsequent sampling. Recently, a new coding approach named LIN (Life Identification Number) was introduced by Marakeby et al. (1). It provides a numerical code for each genome based on its similarity (estimated using the Average Nucleotide Identity, ANI) to the closest genome already encoded. As LIN codes are attributed to each genome rather than to groups, they are stable. A common feature of both approaches is that single linkage groups and LINcodes can be defined using several similarity cut-offs, in which case they inherently convey phylogenetic proximity information. cgMLST additionally provides, through the number of allelic mismatches among cgMLST profiles, intuitive human-understandable metrics of differences among strains involved in epidemiological events (e.g., ‘5 cgMLST allele differences’).

The aim of the PhD project is to develop a novel genome-based genotyping approach taking the best of the two above classification approaches, *i.e.*, combining the advantages of cgMLST (discrimination, standardization) with those of the LIN code approach (complete stability). The aim is to develop and explore the strain classification utility of cgMLST-based LIN code (cgLINcodes) systems, where the pairwise distance is based on the number of allelic mismatches, rather than ANI. Also to compare the cgLINcodes approach with other existing classification approaches: the SNP address and multi-level

single-linkage classifications (Multilevel Single Linkage, MLSL). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Kp) and *Escherichia coli* (Ec) are used as two important pathogens to develop and evaluate the approach.

Report on the period of January to September 2022

Before the reporting period, the analyses of cgLINcodes have been consolidated, and their comparison with MLSL. A novel way to define the population structure of bacterial species has been developed, called MSTclust (**D-PhD16-4.3**); the inheritance algorithm has been optimised to provide backwards compatibility of MLSL groups with previous nomenclature identifiers from 7-gene MLST (**D-PhD16-4.4**); the optimal input order for cgLIN encoding has been defined; the ANI metric has been compared with the cgMLST metric (**D-PhD16-4.5**); a method has been devised to identify recombination in cgMLST data (**D-PhD16-4.6**); the MLSL identifiers have been incorporated into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available (**D-PhD16-4.7**); a manuscript has been submitted for publication on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in Kp, with comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications (**D-PhD16-4.2**).

During this reporting period, the cgLIN codes have been incorporated into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available. The cgLIN codes and MLSL identifiers are being integrated into the Pathogenwatch platform, which will allow to extend the dissemination of our approach. In addition, visitors and students will come to the lab to be trained on the different nomenclature approaches. External collaborators have also been contacted to test the approaches on their datasets.

The manuscript on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in Kp with comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications was accepted in *Molecular Biology and Evolution* in June 2022.

References:

1. Marakeby, H. *et al.* A System to Automatically Classify and Name Any Individual Genome-Sequenced Organism Independently of Current Biological Classification and Nomenclature. *PLOS ONE* **9**, e89142 (2014).

8.1.4.15.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

D5.1. Method implemented in partners' laboratories.

Implementation in BIGSdb

The cgLIN codes was implemented into the Institut Pasteur *K. pneumoniae* MLST and whole genome MLST database (<https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>). In BIGSdb version 1.35.0, the new functionalities are: the definition of cgLIN code schemes, the assignment of cgLIN codes, and the nomenclature of cgLIN code prefixes.

The cgMLST profile of all isolates with less than 30 missing cgMLST-629 alleles were assigned to a core genome sequence type (cgST), and these were assigned a cgLIN code. For SL and CG levels, a nomenclature of cgLIN code prefixes was defined. All cgMLST profiles, cgLIN codes and their corresponding classification identifiers were made available for public use. All functionalities were implemented and are available from the website sequence query page (<https://bigsdbs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/administration.html#setting-up-lincode-definitions-for-cgmlst-schemes>).

The original code for assigning cgLIN codes was written in python and is available at this link: <https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/LINcoding>. However, the second version was implemented in perl language in order to be incorporated into BIGSdb. In addition, we have compared the results of two algorithms.

Before the encoding of cgLIN code an order is defined by the Prim's algorithm (see details in **D-PhD16-3.2**).

The orders generated by Prim's algorithm were compared, either from BIGSdb or from the cgLIN script shared above. The results show that the two orders are different. However, whatever the order, the interpretation of the cgLIN codes is identical. Following this observation, it was decided to follow the order initially calculated (in the shared script), which is consistent with all previous results generated and previous reports.

The accuracy of the calculation of the distances between the cgMLST profiles has been highlighted and the accuracy of the cgLIN code thresholds have an impact on the results. Therefore, the chosen solution is to calculate all the distances between the profiles and the thresholds of the cgLIN codes on the same machine and with the same programming language.

Integration into Pathogenwatch

Pathogenwatch provides species and taxonomy prediction for over 60,000 variants of bacteria, viruses, and fungi (<https://pathogen.watch/>). The species *K. pneumoniae* is of particular interest. This platform presents many features such as it provides MLST and cgMLST profiles with available schemes, it predicts resistance genes, virulence loci, capsule and O-antigen biosynthesis loci, and it provides replicon typing.

A collaboration with the platform's team has been created to add our MLSL nomenclature, cgLIN code and cgLIN code prefixes. This integration is in progress.

Collaboration to test our approaches

Visitors and students will come to the lab to be trained on the different nomenclature approaches. External collaborators have also been contacted to test the approaches on their datasets.

D5.2. PhD viva

The writing of the thesis is in progress and below is an abstract of the manuscript.

Infectious diseases are a global public health concern due to antimicrobial resistance, especially in bacteria. The species *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is identified as one of the most threatening bacteria as it is responsible for many resistance-related deaths. *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, which causes diphtheria, is controlled by vaccines but can re-emerge when vaccine coverage is insufficient. It is important to detect and accurately identify resistance genes and emerging strains of these pathogens.

The research carried out in this thesis consists of three related parts.

The first part consists of bioinformatics analyses of antibiotic resistance and it is organised in two chapters. Chapter 1 is the study of the molecular basis of resistance in *C. diphtheriae*. An analysis of the associations between antimicrobial susceptibility phenotypes, diphtheria toxin production and genomic characteristics of the strains was performed. A new penicillin resistance gene was identified in *C. diphtheriae*. Chapter 2 presents the development of a genotyping tool designed specifically for *C. diphtheriae*, for which the links between genotypes and clinical phenotypes are poorly known. This tool consolidates the detection and genotyping of the main virulence factors and resistance genes, and the use of nomenclatures (MLST, MLSL, etc.) from genome assemblies. It also allows the prediction of biovars and the toxicity of the tox gene (which can be sometimes inactivated).

The second part is about the genetic structure of populations and the genomic taxonomy of strains. It is organised in three chapters. Chapter 3 presents a broadly applicable genomic classification and nomenclature approach for bacterial strains, using the *K. pneumoniae* species as a model. This chapter details the design and implementation of a dual barcode system that combines Single Linkage MultiLevel clustering (MLSL) and Life Identification Number (LIN) codes, both based on the same core genome MLST (cgMLST) typing scheme. This innovative taxonomic approach is widely deployable in other bacterial species. Chapter 4 deals with the study of the phylogenetic structure of *C. diphtheriae* and the implementation of a cgMLST system, on the basis of which a genomic taxonomy and

nomenclature of the strains is proposed. Chapter 5 highlights and characterises a new species, previously confused with *C. diphtheriae*.

Finally, the third part consists of the application of the bioinformatics approaches developed above to the analysis of antibiotic resistance and the phylogenetic diversity of strains in several case studies: the diphtheria epidemic in Yemen, a series of human *C. diphtheriae* infections in New Caledonia, and a series of cases (mainly caused by *Corynebacterium ulcerans*) in animals in mainland France.

8.1.4.15.3 Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number (Include original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Include original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Actual Delivery Date (month)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments (Please mention: public or confidential, Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay, other comments)
	D5.1	Method implemented in partners' labs.	M54		M56	Collaboration in progress
	D5.2	PhD viva	M57	M54		

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date stated in Annual Work Plan 2021 (month)	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date (month)	Comments
	D5.1	LINcodes method disseminated	M54	Yes / No	M56	Collaboration in progress
	D5.2	Viva presented	M57	No	M59	

8.1.4.15.4 Publications and additional outputs

In addition to the main project, the student also contributed to side projects. The PhD host lab comprises the National Reference Center for Corynebacteria of the diphtheriae complex (i.e., *C. diphtheriae*, *C. ulcerans* and phylogenetically related species; <https://www.pasteur.fr/fr/sante-publique/CNR/les-cnr/corynebacteries-du-complexe-diphtheriae>). It thereby collected and characterized all potentially toxigenic strains identified in French metropolitan area and overseas territories for the past 11 years. This unique collection of isolates and the associated clinical and epidemiological data has been an essential resource for various related projects.

The student has been interested in and contributed to a few of these projects, including the study of the diversity and evolution of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* and the computational research of antimicrobial resistance. Below is a list of the articles for which the student made contributions:

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
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A dual barcoding approach to bacterial strain nomenclature: Genomic taxonomy of <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> strains. DOI: 10.1101/2021.07.26.453808 Zenodo: peer-reviewed publication soon available	Yes	No	(to be defined)
Genomic epidemiology and strain taxonomy of <i>Corynebacterium diphtheriae</i> . DOI: 10.1128/JCM.01581-21 Zenodo: soon available	Yes	Yes 1670 US dollars 18 November 2021	
Ongoing diphtheria outbreak in Yemen: a cross-sectional and genomic epidemiology study. DOI: 10.1016/S2666-5247(21)00094-X Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/6393150#.YqbZ5XZBwuU	No		4300 EUROS
<i>Corynebacterium rouxii</i> sp. nov., a novel member of the diphtheriae species complex. DOI: 10.1016/j.resmic.2020.02.003 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/6393067#.YqbiCHZBwuU	No	Yes; 12 months 28 February 2020	
Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance in <i>Corynebacterium diphtheriae</i> . DOI: 10.1186/s13073-020-00805-7 Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4576982#.YqbYm3ZBwuU	Yes		3000 EUROS

8.1.4.15.5 Remarkable outcomes

Our publication on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications is available on Molecular Biology and Evolution (<https://academic.oup.com/mbe/advance-article/doi/10.1093/molbev/msac135/6608353?login=true>).

8.1.4.15.6 Impact and Relevance

The project will define, implement, and evaluate a novel bioinformatics strategy to classify and name strains within pathogenic bacteria, from the level of deep subspecific lineages down to shallower levels of diversity that differentiate epidemiological related strains from non-related ones. It will be first tested on Ec and Kp, two important ubiquitous 'One Health' pathogens. The general applicability of the approach means that in the future the classification and nomenclature of strains of other pathogens could benefit from the PhD project outcomes.

By facilitating the intercommunicability on bacterial strains across sectors and countries in the future, the project is highly relevant to multiple topics and objectives of One Health EJP: antibiotic resistance clonal dissemination, emerging pathogens, cross-sector transmission, public health, and basic microbiology integration.

The project will deliver a novel nomenclature system of bacterial pathogens genomes that will be stable by design, unlike existing systems based on SNPs and cgMLST single linkage groupings. This has a far-reaching impact on possibilities to integrate efforts of agencies (e.g., at the international levels, ECDC, EFSA, PulseNet international) to detect, monitor, understand and control the spread of pathogens.

8.1.4.15.7 Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes

The novel method developed during the course of the PhD project will naturally disseminate via the existing networks of collaboration in which the main investigators are involved: Kp networks include MedVetKlebs (just finished JRP), KlebNET, SpARK, kleb-GAP, Nor-Kleb-Net (see MedVetKlebs final report), and KlebNET-GSP (funded by BMGF); and Ec surveillance networks at national and international levels include the French NRC & NRL @Pasteur, ANSES, the ECDC, and PulseNet international.

The novel nomenclature system will be compared with existing nomenclatures (dictionaries of nomenclature correspondence between LIN codes and current SNP/cgMLST nomenclatures for wider communication and backwards-compatibility will be created) and will need in the future to be integrated in existing platforms that provide nomenclatures of bacterial strains (e.g., SnapperDB, EnteroBase, BIGSdb-Oxford and PulseNet international for E. coli). Future interactions with 'dev-op' specialists (application developers) will be established with free software such as EnteroBase, BIGSdb and Innuendo; or commercial software such as BioNumerics or SeqSphere.

Following the writing of the first draft of our publication on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in Kp with comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications, Martin M. C. Maiden and Keith A. Jolley became aware of it and were interested in applying our method on other pathogens of interest to the One Health perspective (e.g., *Campylobacter*) or Clinical/Antimicrobial resistance (e.g., *N. gonorrhoeae*).

8.1.4.15.8 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Communicate effectively in writing	<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applying the principles of effective communication to concrete cases adapted to the needs of doctoral students - Learning how to write a document, in particular an article, adapted to its recipients in order to be read and understood <p>Practicing using the methodology specific to each document and professional writing style</p> <p>Contents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Characteristics of writing in communication and marketing (objectives, targets, messages) - How to select relevant information and give it meaning - How to structure your writing (adapted plans and specific methodologies) - Writing to be read (principles of readability and popularisation of information) - Improving the presentation of your documents (rules of form) 	31/03/2022 and 01/04/2022	Sorbonne Université
Speed up the writing of your thesis	Objectives	11/04/2022	Sorbonne Université

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding the different approaches to the thesis - Managing the organisation of the thesis - Structuring and writing the document clearly <p>Contents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of research work (project management approach) - General approach - Searching for the main theme 		
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8.1.4.15.9 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>"Journées Boris Ephrussi" 2022</i>		
Date:	<i>May 05th -06th 2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Paris</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>100+</i>	<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 – 3M Thesis Competition</i>		
Date:	<i>11-13 April 2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Online</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes</i>

<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	NO	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	NO
<i>Press release</i>	NO	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	NO
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	NO	<i>Video/Film</i>	NO
<i>Exhibition</i>	NO	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	NO
<i>Flyer</i>	NO	<i>Pitch Event</i>	NO
<i>Training</i>	NO	<i>Trade Fair</i>	NO
<i>Social Media</i>	NO	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	NO
<i>Website</i>	NO	<i>Other</i>	NO
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	NO		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	0
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	5	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

8.1.4.16 PhD17_SUSTAIN

8.1.4.16.1 Summary

Research work:

The start of 2022 was used to work on the dissertation and finalise two manuscripts. One manuscript deals with the survey study conducted in 2021 and the other with the interview study conducted in 2020 and 2021 in Italian and Swedish public health, veterinary, food and environment institutes. For the interview study, the remaining interviews were transcribed in early 2022 and subsequently with the analysed.

The manuscripts are currently submitted to two journals.

Conferences:

As an invited speaker, I presented some of my research at the One Health Sweden scientific meeting, which was held from the 29th-30th March. The title of my presentation was “Importance of connecting early and senior project collaborators under the One Health umbrella”. I also participated at a round table discussion about Covid-19 reflections.

I participated online at the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2022 (11th-13th of April) by engaging in the three minute competition, a round table, and presenting a poster at the conference (Lessons Learned from One Health Practices in Sweden and Italy).

From the 21st- 23rd of June, I participated online at the ONE - HEALTH, ENVIRONMENT, SOCIETY conference with a poster presentation titled “One Health knowledge translation among European scientists and policy actors”.

8.1.4.16.2 Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

D7.4, Subtask 7.4.2 & MS100

- Interview study

Institutional analysis of agencies in Sweden and Italy is completed. A closer look on Sweden has already been performed and published (<https://doi.org/10.1177/14034948211024483>). But a combined

analysis of the Swedish and Italian approach, structures and systems will follow (manuscript is submitted).

- Survey study

Analysis completed of survey results that investigated institutionalisation within European countries and Europe as a whole (manuscript is submitted and under review).

Book chapter manuscript that addresses institutionalisation of One Health in relation to AMR (submitted, to be published end 2022).

8.1.4.16.3 Impact & relevance

The PhD project has a unique angle on One Health. It investigates the whole project in terms of One Health integration, implementation and how One Health is put into practice within public health, veterinary, food and environment Institutes. The results of this research can be used by all partners to evaluate and consider their coordination and collaboration efforts. It can be used to enhance disease surveillance nationally and internationally. It produces useful knowledge and examples for institutes on challenges for collaboration and how to overcome those. On a political level, it will provide insight into sharing and translating knowledge between scientists and politicians.

8.1.4.16.4 Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

Name of Training Event	Topic	Dates (DD/MM/YY)	Organising Institute
Course: The good PhD defence - Objectives and Challenges	Professional development seminar	03.06.22	Roskilde University
Internal evaluation of dissertation	Feedback for and evaluation of dissertation (last step before submission)	23.06.22	Roskilde University

8.1.4.16.5 List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>One Health Sweden Scientific Meeting</i>		
Date:	<i>29.-30.03.2022</i>		
Place:	<i>Uppsala, Sweden</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	YES
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number

Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	70	Media	10
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM – 3MT		
Date:	11.04.2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	YES
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	No	Pitch Event	Yes
Training	No	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	No	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	No	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	550+	Media	20
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM – Poster presentation		
Date:	11.-13.04.2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	YES
Organisation of a Workshop	No	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No

<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	OHEJP ASM – Roundtable discussion		
Date:	13.04.2022		
Place:	Online		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

Name of the activity:	ONE – Health, Environment, Society
Date:	21.-23.06.2022
Place:	Online

Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	YES
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	No	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Press release</i>	No	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	No
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	No	<i>Video/Film</i>	No
<i>Exhibition</i>	No	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	No
<i>Flyer</i>	No	<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>	No	<i>Trade Fair</i>	No
<i>Social Media</i>	No	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	No
<i>Website</i>	No	<i>Other</i>	No
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	550+	<i>Media</i>	20
<i>Industry</i>	0	<i>Investors</i>	0
<i>Civil Society</i>	0	<i>Customers</i>	0
<i>General Public</i>	0	<i>Other</i>	0
<i>Policy Makers</i>	0		

8.1.5 Task 6.5: One-Health Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Module

The Continuing Professional Development (CPD) module for 2022 is planned for the 2nd – 4th November 2022 to be held at the Statens Serum Institut (SSI), Copenhagen, hosted by SSI and DTU-Food, Denmark, with the theme: Rapid diagnostics and harmonisation of diagnostic tests.

8.1.6 Task 6.6: Communications workshop and media training

N/A

8.2 Deliverables and Milestones

8.2.1 Deliverables

Del. Rel. No	Deliverable title	Submission
D6.22	4th Periodic Report onPhDs	M51
D6.14	Report n°3 of the annual short term missions completed also uploaded onto the EJP webpage.	M54

8.2.2 Milestones

Mil. Ref.	Milestone title	Expected Delivery/ Achievement Month	Notification
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MS89	Preparation and launching of annual One-Health Summer Schools n°4	M60	Preparation of the SS has been engaged, the 4 th SS will take place in Autumn at UoS
MS95	Preparation of a One Health CPD module and launching of annual course n°4	M59	The 4 th CPD module will be held from 2 nd – 4 th November 2022 at the Statens Serum Institut (SSI), Copenhagen

9 WP7 – Sustainability

9.1 Work carried out to date

9.1.1 Task 7.1: Gathering Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations

This task consists of three main components: i) the evaluation of the results of the SWOT analysis, ii) the completion of the stakeholder mapping and iii) listing a selection of outcomes of the One Health EJP intended to be utilised by stakeholders.

Subtask 7.1.1: Collection and evaluation of the stakeholders need and expectations regarding the One Health EJP. An objective of the One Health EJP was to identify the requirements of the stakeholders to continue the alignment and integration activities set up in the One Health EJP. In addition, it was anticipated that interactions with stakeholders would contribute to the definition of sustainability principles and the development of sustainability strategies. A SWOT analysis of the Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations was conducted at the early stages of the One Health EJP to collect input from the stakeholders (MS97) and provide recommendations for the continuing work during the course of the EJP, as well as to contribute to the development of strategies for the sustainability of the One Health EJP (SRIA, D7.2 and D7.4).

Subtask 7.1.2: Stakeholder mapping. Interactions with the stakeholders is curated by WP5. A description of the stakeholder categories is presented in D5.1. Through the course of the One Health EJP WP5 enlarged the list of participating stakeholders and held One Health EJP Stakeholders' Committee meetings, with WP7 participation. Key activities and documents issued by the stakeholders have been scanned and documented throughout the course of the One Health EJP by WP5. WP7 has used the information in these reports for the preparation of the SRIA and the stakeholders of the One Health EJP will be invited to provide input into the draft SRIA.

Subtask 7.1.3. Analysis of outcomes of the One Health EJP likely to be utilised by stakeholders also beyond the end of the One Health EJP. An objective of the One Health EJP was to ensure that the EJP main scientific outputs, protocols, databases, and other strategic integration activities will be sustainable beyond the lifetime of the project. To address this objective and aiming at delivering a clear legacy the EJP, WP7 worked together with WP1, WP3, WP4 and WP5 in collaboration with the project leaders to produce a list of outcomes resulting from One Health EJP JIP and JRP that will address some of the needs of principal stakeholders, namely, ECDC, EFSA, DG-HEALTH and DG-AGRI. This list of outcomes describes protocols, databases and other tools and solutions expected to contribute to the work of not only the 4 named stakeholders, but also others. Whenever available, links to the source of the outcome is given (D7.1 Analysis of outcomes and uptake of EJP's outputs by stakeholders submitted in M54).

9.1.2 Task 7.2: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 2021-2030

Jointly with WP1, WP2 and WP5 and with the information collected in task 7.1 a European One Health SRIA 2021-2030 will be drafted to describe the societal and scientific needs, and how to develop interdisciplinary and high-quality knowledge to address them. The agenda will also focus on the role and contribution that the One Health EJP will provide in the future challenges dealt with by the coming Horizon Europe partnerships, in particular –but not limited to- the ones on Animal Health & Welfare and on OH-AMR. The SRIA will consider the research activities and gap analysis identified mainly in WP2; this information will be evaluated to consider its relevance within the EU scenario (Horizon Europe, Green Deal, etc.) in the long-term period (up to 2030). Also, the range of funding opportunities and legal forms for sustainability will be explored. The SRIA will take into account the main challenges identified in the original One Health EJP SRA as well as new emerging challenges.

Subtask 7.2.1: Definition of the SRIA in cooperation with WP1, WP2, WP5.

The items identified together with WP2 will be also assessed regarding their relevance for the sustainability of the One Health EJP. Matching of the items with the needs and expectations defined in task 7.1 will be also carried out within this task.

Subtask 7.2.2: Definition of the innovation activities to be included in the agenda, taking into account the SRIA and the results of task 7.1. The integration of the SRIA with the innovation items defined will be carried out.

9.1.3 Task 7.4: Making the bridges between EJP's beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable

In order to support policies that can ensure long-term implementation and integration of the One Health approach in the daily activities of the Med-Vet partners in Europe, an evaluation with the participation of beneficiaries in Sweden and Italy was conducted by assessing drivers and constraints for the successful institutionalisation of trans-sectoral integrative actions in an EU context, i.e. how such activities can become robustly and permanently integrated into the EU socio-political system. A large part of the work was carried out by the PhD project SUSTAIN – ‘Scientific UnderSTanding of the policy process for Transboundary integration And INstitutionalisation of the One Health across EU member States’ (Roskilde University, with assistance from ISS and SVA).

The SUSTAIN project aims to understand the political drivers and constrains for increased institutionalisation of the One Health approach across EU member states. For this, interviews with experts working in Swedish and Italian public health institutes, veterinary institutes, environmental institutes and food institutes were conducted. In Sweden, data gathering was conducted from March to October 2020. In Italy, data was gathered in October 2020 and 2021.

While one article (One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination) is already published investigating the Swedish approach for implementing One Health practices, another article is planned that compares the Swedish and Italian system in relation to the institutionalisation of the One Health approach. The transcription of the interviews will be completed by March 2022 and will be followed by the analysis. The aim is to compare the two cases, Italy and Sweden, to comprehend concrete institutional and political challenges for the One Health approach.

Further, a survey on the governance of One Health was launched in March 2021. The survey was addressed to ministries, EU institutions, international organisations and high level members of staff from public health, veterinary, environment and food agencies. The online survey examined policy networks for One Health by understanding policy- and decision-making processes of One Health. It investigated knowledge translation challenges for turning One Health topics into policy to shed light on opportunities for One Health policy integration. Data gathering was completed in June - July 2021 and followed by analysis.

How the work already published can contribute to D7.4 “Document on institutionalisation of One Health” (M58) and MS 100 Workshop on road map for institutionalisation of One Health (M66)

- “One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination”: The article shows some of the challenges and opportunities for the One Health approach based on a concrete case in Sweden. The case focuses on Swedish public health, veterinary, food and environmental protection agencies, and understanding barriers and opportunities can be beneficial when planning and implementing future One Health activities. While there is potentially the need to adapt and modify some aspects, this study might also shed light on other contexts, such as agencies in other countries that might come across similar challenges.

- “Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach”: The article presents two cases in Italy (occurrence of aflatoxin M1) and Denmark (Danish surveillance for AMR - DANMAP) that highlight opportunities and benefits of engaging the environmental sector and actors for a successful and comprehensive institutionalisation of One Health.

9.2 Deliverables and Milestones

9.2.1 Deliverables

Del. Rel. No	Deliverable title	Submission
D7.1	Analysis of outcomes and uptake of EJP’s outputs by stakeholders	M54

9.2.2 Milestones

Mil. Ref.	Milestone title	Expected Delivery/Achievement Month	Notification
MS98	Analysis of outcomes and uptake of EJP’s outputs by stakeholders	M52	Achieved

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